

Unlocking Bronze Age Combat Sword Experiments and Wear Analysis

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Abstract

Following the ever-increasing interest in prehistoric violence and warfare, my research aims to reconstruct the sword fighting styles of the Middle and Late Bronze Age in Europe (c. 1650-600 BC), with a particular focus on Britain and Italy. The fighting styles are investigated through an innovative combination of combat experiments, partially based on historical sources, and metalwork wear analysis of archaeological swords from both countries. For the experiments, a new methodology had to be developed, allowing me to record and link the marks created through specific actions during live combat. The experiments were successfully carried out over a number of field days, and a reference database of wear marks was created. As for the wear analysis, existing methodologies were developed further, and analysis was carried out on a total of 110 swords from various British and Italian museums. Over 2300 combat-related wear marks could be identified, and the most detailed list of Bronze Age wear marks to date was created. Comparing the experimental and archaeological marks has enabled me to propose original observations regarding fighting practices and swordsmanship in Middle and Late Bronze Age Europe.

For Fionnlagh

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Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1 Researching combat practices in European prehistory

Our understanding and interpretation of prehistoric violence and warfare has undergone a significant transformation over the last two decades. Before the late 1990s, scholars of European prehistory mostly interpreted the prehistoric past as intrinsically peaceful. Although evidence from grave goods and rock art was used to create the notion of a warrior-elite society (e.g. Kristiansen 1984; 1999a; 2002), their associated items such as swords and battle-axes were primarily interpreted as status symbols or indicators of male identity. The practical use of these items was often thought to be largely restricted to choreographed duels between champions (Dolfini et al., in press). As Vandkilde noted, it was a tale of warriors without war (Vandkilde 2013, 38-9). This peaceful interpretation of prehistory by mid-20th-century scholars is likely rooted in the desire for a relief of the violence and brutality experienced during the two world wars (Dolfini et al., in press; Keeley 1996; Vandkilde 2013). During the 1990s, however, a shift in global affairs and the emergence of new violent conflicts all across the world triggered a new consciousness as to the reasons and causes of warfare. In 1996, the publication of Keeley's ground-breaking *War before Civilization* prompted new interpretations of the prehistoric past, and laid the groundwork for an unprecedented amount of debate about conflict and violence (Dolfini et al., in press). Criticising the artificial pacification of the past brought about in the period since the 1950s (Keeley 1996, 18), Keeley uses archaeological and anthropological evidence to demonstrate that warfare and violence were just as prevalent amongst prehistoric societies as they were during the historical periods (ibid., 174).

1.1.1 Bronze Age combat in focus

The development of Bronze Age warfare research as a discipline has undergone rapid development since the publication of Keeley's (1996) monograph. Whilst earlier studies were mostly concerned with presenting the evidence that interpersonal and intergroup violence did, in fact, occur (e.g. Osgood 1998; Carman & Harding 1999; Osgood & Monks 2000; Thorpe 2003; Jockenhövel 2004-5; Guilaine & Zammit 2005), comparatively little attention was paid to the specifics of how combat was conducted during the European Bronze Age. Due to the perhaps dangerous nature of practical combat studies, the majority of interpretations of Bronze Age combat were entirely theoretical. On the one hand, swords were regarded as prestigious, mostly non-functional items that signified rank and wealth. It was argued that

they were at most used for despatching opponents and trophy taking rather than actual fighting (Mercer 2006, 147). In contrast stands the notion of dividing swords into “thrusting” and “slashing” weapons, depending on the shape of the blade (Harding 2007, 108), which had been widely accepted without ever being put to the test. How exactly these thrusting and slashing motions were employed, however, was not discussed. This theoretical interpretation of the practical execution of combat peaked in Harding’s statement that Bronze Age warriors probably just used their weapons in whichever way they saw fit (*ibid.*), without really knowing what to do with them exactly. Clearly, the study of Bronze Age combat called for a more practice-orientated and evidence-based approach. Isolated practical studies, such as John Coles’s experimental shield tests, have been carried out from as early as the 1960s. Coles (1962) pioneered experimental combat archaeology by testing the effectiveness of replica Bronze Age shields in battle. The results of his tests suggested that Bronze Age metal shields were extremely easily penetrated and prone to destruction, and were thus not suitable for combat. Instead, they would only have served as status objects or for display purposes. Although his experiments were conducted with unauthentic replicas made of 0.3 mm thick copper sheet (at the lowest end of the thickness range of actual Bronze Age shields, most of which are around 1 mm thick; Uckelmann 2011, 189), this notion was widely accepted in the academic field until recently. It was not until the beginning of the new millennium, however, that the new approach to Bronze Age warfare research kick-started a series of new scientific approaches, which have enhanced our understanding of how combat was conducted during that period. Generally speaking, there have been two types of approaches: combat experiments with replica weapons, and metalwork wear analysis studies of original Bronze Age objects (see Chapter 3.2 for a detailed discussion of previous studies). Barry Molloy has been at the forefront of experimental combat archaeology for the last decade or so, and his research has produced some invaluable data and results. By putting replica weapons to the test, he was able to demonstrate that Bronze Age swords cannot simply be divided into thrusting or slashing weapons, but instead that they were suitable for both actions, and that copper-alloy shields were in fact suitable for combat (Molloy 2007; 2008; 2009). He further suggested that Bronze Age swords were employed with cut-and-draw motions, slicing along the opponent’s flesh rather than attempting to injure through forceful percussive blows, as the leaf-shaped swelling of the blades supports this technique (Molloy 2007, 92-4). While Molloy’s experiments have yielded interesting results, his approaches are not without problems. For example, his sword tests cannot be regarded as scientific experiments, as they lacked the controlled conditions, repeatability, and independent validation methods inherent in any scientific procedure. Instead, his method and results were based on his experience with

the weapons and what he believed that they were capable of. Additionally, his interpretations were then not justified by comparison with archaeological evidence. Other studies, such as Bridgford's sword research (1997; 2000) and O'Flaherty's halberd tests (2007), fulfil the scientific experimental criteria, but as they were conducted in a laboratory environment, with machines wielding the replicas, they lacked the dynamics of human movement and were not representative of real-life combat. In contrast stand use-wear studies of copper-alloy objects, a discipline that was pioneered by Kienlin & Ottaway (1998), who were the first to adapt a long-standing lithics analysis technique for their research of Bronze Age metal axes. Since then, wear analysis studies of copper-alloy swords and other weapons have been conducted with varying degrees of quality and detail (see Dolfini & Crellin 2016 for review). The number of different approaches to metalwork wear analysis is almost as great as the number of its practitioners. While some approaches are based on macroscopic examination with the naked eye alone (e.g. Kristiansen 2002; O'Flaherty 2007), others use more sophisticated equipment such as high-powered stereo-microscopes (e.g. Dolfini 2011; Horn 2013). What they all have in common is a lack of consistent, accurate, and detailed terminology of wear marks. In fact, many studies summarise a multitude of marks under a single term (e.g. Kienlin & Ottaway 1998; Kristiansen 2002; Higgins 2010; Dolfini 2011). Without defining and recognising each type of mark correctly, however, any interpretation will necessarily be biased. These studies demonstrated that the swords were indeed used, but they only speculated on *how* they were used. Whilst the above-mentioned combat experiments are usually interpreted without reference to metalwork wear analysis, the latter often suffers from a distinct lack of comparison with experimental results. It transpires that, in order to gain a conclusive understanding of Bronze Age combat, it is imperative to develop and combine the two approaches, thus producing evidence through controlled, scientific combat experiments with sophisticated metalwork wear analysis. The newly found evidence must then be interpreted to make informed suggestions about how Bronze Age swords were used in combat, and by whom. Osteological studies of trauma and injuries, representations of conflict and violence in rock-art, and the analysis of violence through historical and ethnographic sources can contribute to the interpretation as corroborating evidence.

1.2 Open problems

Dolfini et al. (in press) have identified three major problems in the study of Bronze Age warfare: its nature; its role in social interactions; and its significance for Bronze Age society as a whole. Firstly, we need to understand what combat and warfare were actually like. How was combat conducted, by whom, and with which weapons? Archaeological evidence for the

types of weapons is plentiful, the reasons why interpersonal violence was conducted has been discussed extensively by others (e.g. Keeley 1996; Osgood 1998; Harding 1999; 2007) and theories about the kind of people who would bear arms have been proposed (e.g. Kristiansen 2002). The understanding of how Bronze Age weapons were actually used, however, is still significantly underdeveloped. Until now, Bronze Age combat practices have been approached as a whole, without consideration for temporal or regional variations. Interpretations based on speculation and “armchair archaeology” are highly problematic, and have produced narratives not supported by any scientific evidence. Previous combat experiments have often been unscientific and experiential, or laboratory based but significantly removed from real-life combat. Existing wear analysis studies of Bronze Age weapons have usually been conducted without experimental reference material. Although these studies have resulted in suggestions of how Bronze Age weapons could have been used, these individual approaches have frequently been carried out in ignorance of each other’s evidence, thus creating an inconclusive narrative of how Bronze Age combat was conducted. Developing and combining the two approaches for the first time will create original scientific data that can be used to interpret how Bronze Age weapons were used, and by whom. These data can further be used to interpret how combat and warfare were manifested in everyday Bronze Age life.

1.2.1 Aims and objectives

In order to address some of the open problems identified above, this thesis aims to understand how Bronze Age combat was conducted based on the scientific analysis of actual Bronze Age swords, corroborated by accurate tests with replica weapons. To overcome the lack of interdisciplinary communication, my research has been built upon a collaborative approach of metalwork wear analysis, scientific combat experiments, evidence from osteological analysis as well as interpretations and theories from the literature. Particular focus has been laid on the role of the sword in combat, and as such the analysis and experiments were conducted with replica and original Middle and Late/Recent Bronze Age swords from Britain and Italy. The experiments endeavour to be informed by an explicit methodology, controllable, and repeatable, thus fulfilling the criteria for a scientific experiment, which has never been done before. Until now, Bronze Age combat has been studied as a whole – nobody has ever researched the existence of regional differences beyond macro-regions such as continental Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean. Yet typological differences between swords (and also analogy with the mediaeval and post-mediaeval period) do suggest that regionally differentiated combat might have developed by the late 2nd millennium BC. A combat style, or fighting style, is the particular way in which an individual, or a group of people, typically

use their weapon, and can be based on their personal experience, any potential training they may have received, and/or the prevalent fighting traditions. My unprecedented approach to the study of Bronze Age sword fighting is comparing the wear marks from British and Italian swords to understand the differences, and similarities, between the combat styles. Understanding exactly how combat was conducted provides the basis for informed interpretations of the combatants and the role of combat and warfare in Bronze Age life. To achieve this, the following aims and objectives have been identified.

1. Understand how Bronze Age sword combat was conducted and identify any specific (regional) combat styles.
 - a. Review osteological evidence to understand the causes of trauma and injuries on Bronze Age victims of violence.
 - b. Conduct scientific combat experiments with replica weapons to create a reference collection of wear marks and gain a better understanding of sword fighting.
 - c. Undertake metalwork wear analysis on original Bronze Age swords from Britain and Italy.
 - d. Compare the data from the wear analysis, combat experiments and osteological evidence to make original interpretations of the ways swords were used in combat, and to identify any specific combat styles.
 - e. Compare the wear analysis data from Britain and Italy to identify regional similarities and differences.
2. Understand the role of combat and warfare in Bronze Age life.
 - a. Combine the newly gathered knowledge about Bronze Age sword fighting with the literature to propose original interpretations about the role of combatants within society.
 - b. Interpret how combat was integrated into everyday life.
 - c. Propose a revised interpretation of social structure and military organisation amongst Bronze Age societies.

The specific methodologies for scientific combat experiments and metalwork wear analysis can be found in Chapters 3.3 and 4.2.

1.3 Outline of the thesis

The following section provides an outline of this thesis from the next chapter.

Chapter 2 starts with an introduction of the different types of weaponry and armour available during the Middle and Late Bronze Age. The next section introduces osteological evidence of

trauma as well as a discussion of the data. Due to the relative scarcity of osteological studies from the period, evidence from the entire Bronze Age has been considered. Archaeological and osteological evidence from the Tollense Valley battlefield is then introduced and discussed. The three types of evidence complement one another, with each contributing to our understanding of Middle to Late Bronze Age warfare and violence in its own way.

Chapter 3 starts with an extensive review of previous combat experiments and metalwork wear analysis, as found in the literature. The review allows me to ascertain the achievements and limitations of previous approaches. Based on this, it was possible to design methodologies for scientific combat experiments, and develop existing metalwork wear analysis approaches. The chapter then introduces the first set of combat experiments, which were part of the wider Bronze Age Combat Project. This is followed by a description of all combat tests involving swords and a summary of the marks thus created. The chapter finishes with the results as well as an evaluation of the experiment.

Chapter 4 introduces a different methodology for combat experiments, based on historical fighting manuals. Following a brief history of European Martial Arts, the chapter then describes each section of the experiment in detail. Following a summary of the marks created during this experiment, the chapter outlines the results and an evaluation of the methodology.

Chapter 5 concerns the metalwork wear analysis of British Bronze Age swords. The chapter starts with a description of the data collection method, as well as an outline of British sword chronologies relevant for the chapter. This is followed by a detailed description of each of the 70 British swords analysed for this thesis, as well as a discussion of their wear marks, in chronological order. The chapter finishes with a statistical analysis of the locations and frequencies of wear marks on the sword sample.

Chapter 6 discusses the wear analysis of 40 Italian Bronze Age swords. Following a description of the data collection method, an introduction to the main archaeological contexts and an outline of the relevant Italian sword chronologies, the chapter provides a detailed description of each sword and their wear marks. This is followed by statistical analysis of the locations and frequencies of the marks.

Chapter 7 uses all the evidence from the osteological analysis, the combat experiments and the wear analysis, as well as information from the literature, to interpret the ways in which Bronze Age swords were used. This is followed by a wider discussion of how it changes previous perceptions of Bronze Age combat and warfare, with a particular focus on the social classification of the combatants as well as the role of combat in everyday life.

Chapter 8 provides a final summary of the results, and highlights the achievements of this research in relation to the aims and objectives identified in this chapter.

Bibliography

The thesis is complemented by three appendices.

Appendix A is a digital appendix containing the database and all micrographs of wear marks taken during the analysis of the original swords from Britain and Italy. Due to the number of images, the appendix is attached on a USB stick. The micrographs are numbered and organised in folders by Sword ID. Each micrograph can be linked to its specific Mark ID through the database.

Appendix B contains the transcript of the interview with Robert Brooks.

Appendix C contains the original German transcription and the English translation of Codex 44.A.8: sword and buckler, which was used as the basis for the experiments in Chapter 4.

Chapter 2. Warfare and violence in the European Bronze Age

2.1 Introduction

Following an introduction to the weaponry available during the Middle and Late European Bronze Age, this chapter provides an overview of the combat-inflicted trauma and injuries of the period as detected through osteological analysis. Due to the relative scarcity of osteological studies of human remains from the period, it was decided to include studies concerning the entire Bronze Age in this section. Special attention is given to the Tollense Valley battlefield in Germany.

2.2 Weaponry

When studying conflict and warfare in the European Bronze Age, one instinctively turns towards the study of weaponry and armour, as these provide the largest and most iconic category of evidence for combat from the time. Following the early use of hunting weapons such as the bow and arrow, as well as daggers and spears in interpersonal violence, the Late Neolithic and Early Bronze Age saw the development of specialised combat-related artefacts, namely halberds and battle-axes. Daggers and rapiers emerged during the Middle Bronze Age. Swords and beaten bronze armour including helmets, corselets and various types of shields, developed during the Late Bronze Age. Whilst wooden clubs would also have been available during the Bronze Age, these rarely survive (Harding 2007, 71). The evolution, development and typology of these artefacts have been studied and discussed at length (see Winiker 2015; Novotna 2014; Laux 2009; Wüstemann 2005; Harding 1995; von Quillfeldt 1995; Kilian-Dirlmeier 1994; Kemenczei 1991; Bader 1991; Burgess & Colquhoun 1988; Burgess & Gerloff 1981; Schauer 1971 and Bianco Peroni 1970 for swords, Davis 2012; 2015; Gedl 2009; Vasic 2015 and Laux 2012 for spears, Uckelmann 2012 for shields, Brandherm 2003 and Harbison 1961 for halberds, Michler 2013; Laux 2000; 2005; Eogan 2000; Paszthory & Mayer 1998; Harbison 1969 and Schmidt & Burgess 1981 for axes). Recent studies have investigated their use through a variety of approaches (see Chapter 3.2). This thesis focusses on the way Bronze Age swords were used in combat, yet it is imperative to see them in the context of the complete range of weapons and armour that would have been used at the time. Swords would have been used along with, and against, other weapons, and one cannot understand Bronze Age fighting styles without considering this. The following section therefore contains a brief introduction to the different weapons available during the Middle and Late Bronze Age.

2.2.1 Swords

Figure 2.1 – Bronze Age *Griffzungenschwert* of type Ewart Park with a leaf-shaped blade. Image courtesy of The Great North Museum: Hancock.

Previous research into violence and combat in the Bronze Age has been distinctly sword-centred (Anderson 2011, 599), and as such swords are probably the most intensely studied Bronze Age weapons to date, yet surprisingly little effort has been made to understand how exactly they were used. The transition from daggers to swords, defined by an overall length of >30 cm for the latter (Molloy 2010, 404), can be placed in central Europe at around 1700 BC (Harding 2007, 71) during the latest stages of the Early Bronze Age, and the development appeared to occur more or less simultaneously all across Central and Western Europe and the Aegean (ibid., 72-4). A detailed narrative of this development is available in Schauer (1971) and Burgess & Gerloff (1981), and would exceed the scope of this thesis. Whilst the overall blade length appears to increase over time, the technological developments from dagger to sword mainly focussed on the construction of the hilt and its hafting methods, as well as the shape of the blade. Particularly the former can be used as a chronological indicator, and as such most typologies are based on the shape and features of the hilt. Whilst the earliest swords terminated in tangs that were pushed into organic handles, these gradually developed into cast full-metal hilts or, most commonly, the *Griffzungenschwerter* (hilt-tongue-swords; Figure 2.1) of the Late Bronze Age (Harding 2007, 75). Whilst traditionally it has been argued that Bronze Age swords were mostly unsuitable for combat, be it because of the “weak” hafting methods of the earlier swords (Osgood 1998, 13), their inability to cut (Barber 2003, 147; Waddell 2000, 185; Harding 2000, 277; Osgood 1998, 13; Ramsey 1995, 59; Burgess & Gerloff 1981) or the relative shortness of their hilts, allegedly making them impossible to hold (Harding 2007, 76), more recent studies have successfully demonstrated their combat potential (e.g. Kristiansen, 2002; Bridgford 1997; 2000; Molloy 2006; 2007; 2008; 2010; Hermann et al. in press; see also Chapter 3.2). Swords have often been described as being the principal fighting weapons of elite warriors and high-ranking members of Bronze Age communities, who would mostly have employed them as symbols of social status (e.g. Harding 2007, 137; Kristiansen 2002, 325). The sheer number of swords in the archaeological record, however, combined with a better understanding of their usage and the discovery of four swords in the context of a “normal” village dwelling at Must Farm (Knight 2017), is shifting our perceptions of swords. They can perhaps be understood as normal, almost everyday items of Bronze Age life, although this is still being debated. By focussing on the

uses of Bronze Age swords, this research contributes to this debate and offers new perspectives into the social landscape of sword usage in the late 2nd and early 1st millennia BC.

2.2.2 Spears

Figure 2.2 – Class V Bronze Age spearhead after Davis (2006) (Anderson 2011, 601). Unscaled image.

Although much more common in the archaeological record than swords (Harding 2007, 77), spearheads have received significantly less interest within the archaeological community. Whilst typological classifications of spearheads date back to as early as the late nineteenth century (Davis 2012, 1), the terminology used to describe different classes of spearheads has been varied and inconsistent in the past, leading to incomparable typologies and sometimes important attribute differences were missed (ibid., 10). Most recently, Richard Davis has summarised and modified existing classifications and created a general typology of British Bronze Age spearheads, categorizing them into 18 major groups with numerous subgroups, based on the shape and properties of the blade and hilt mechanism (ibid., 15; Davis 2015, 22-3). Developing their stone and bone predecessors, Early Bronze Age metal spearheads consisted usually of kite-shaped blades and tangs which were mounted onto wooden shafts. In order to improve the hafting method, the technology to cast early sockets was developed and the tang was omitted. The socket cavity quickly became integrated into the blade and extended into a midrib (Davis 2012, 3). The Middle Bronze Age saw the addition of different

types of single and double loops to the base of the now usually leaf-shaped blade, long sockets, a gradual transition of lozenge-shaped to rounded midribs and an overall increase in length. These loops disappeared again during the Late Bronze Age, and the sockets became shorter whilst the overall length of the spearheads remained (Davis 2015, 20-1). The end of the Late Bronze Age saw the reintroduction of loop-holes, or blade openings, and the development of barbed and channelled blade shapes, before the use of iron demanded new innovations for weapon design and technologies (ibid., 28). Traditionally, spearheads have been interpreted in terms of the length of their blade, and it was suggested that shorter spearheads were mostly used for throwing, and longer ones for thrusting (Harding 2007, 78). Recent studies by Anderson (2011) and Crellin et al. (in prep.), however, dispute this, and now emphasis is put on the importance of spears in combat (see Chapter 3.2; Crellin et al. in prep. and this thesis).

2.2.3 Axes

Figure 2.3 – Replica Bronze Age flat axe hafted on an oak shaft. Made by Neil Burrige (bronze-age-craft.com).

Whilst Bronze Age axes of all varieties are commonly found within the archaeological record, they are seldomly interpreted as “battle-axes” and therefore rarely regarded as weapons rather than tools. Instead, particularly stone battle-axes are commonly referred to as symbolic and non-functional, or status objects (Harding 2007, 78-9). One must consider, however, that interpretation is overly influenced by the perception of previous researchers, who could not imagine those tools to be used in a violent context. The perceived lack of wear on battle-axes is also not direct evidence for their non-functionality, as many combat actions would likely not leave any traces on the axe heads (see Roy in prep. for a detailed discussion of this). Finally, even if bronze axes were primarily designed as tools, they essentially comprised of a

wooden club (Figure 2.3) with an added metal-weight and a sharp cutting edge, and could have been used in a combat situation if necessary.

2.2.4 Shields

Figure 2.4 – Yetholm type copper-alloy shield from the Late Bronze Age (Uckelmann 2011, 193). Image courtesy of the British Museum.

Bronze Age shields have been the subject of archaeological research from as early as the 18th century, as their visual similarity to the equipment of historical militias made them a popular component of collections and exhibitions (Uckelmann 2012, 2). The shields were manufactured from a variety of materials including copper-alloy (Figure 2.4), leather, rawhide and wood, but as these materials were predominantly of organic origin they rarely survive in the archaeological record. As a result, only 86 metal shields, four wooden and one leather shield are known to date from the European Bronze Age (Uckelmann 2012; 2011, 187). Based on Coles's (1962) early experiments, metal shields have traditionally been interpreted as non-functional, purely symbolic status objects. Coles's interpretations were based on replicas made of 0.3 mm thick, modern copper sheet rather than work-hardened copper-alloy, thus biasing his results drastically. Recent work by Molloy (2009), Uckelmann (2011; 2012) and myself (see Chapters 4.3 & 4.4) has shown that these shields were in fact highly functional (Uckelmann 2011; Uckelmann et al. in prep.; Molloy 2009; see Chapter 3.2; 3.4.4; 3.5) if manufactured and used correctly. Research has shown that Bronze Age metal shields were manufactured out of cast copper-alloy discs measuring around 15 cm in diameter. These

discs were subject to numerous cycles of cold-hammering, re-heating, and quenching in cold water to prevent the material from becoming brittle, until a final diameter of around 50-70 cm was achieved. With an average final weight of 1.5 kg, these shields varied in thickness from 0.3 mm to 1.4 mm and were finished with decorative ribs and bosses, as well as a rolled rim (Uckelmann 2011, 189). Recent tests have shown that even extremely thin sections of work-hardened copper-alloy are able to withstand combat impacts effectively (Uckelmann et al. in prep.; see Chapter 3.4.4; 3.5), whilst contextual evidence also allows for ritual or votive interpretations of shields (Uckelmann 2011, 197). For combat scenarios, it has been suggested that shields should not be classified as armour, but rather as defensive weaponry, which can be used for both defence and attack (Molloy 2009, 1056-7; see Chapter 4.3; 4.4).

2.2.5 *Armour*

Figure 2.5 – Late Bronze Age bell helmet from Biecz, Poland (Hencken 1952). Unscaled image courtesy of the British Museum.

Defensive equipment is rare in the archaeological record and includes copper-alloy cuirasses, helmets, greaves (Harding 2007, 79) and elbow protectors (Kristiansen 2002, 327). Depictions of armoured warriors have been found on Sardinia but remain rare (Harding 2007, 80). Little work has been done to assess the functionality of these items in combat. Since most copper-alloy armour was manufactured from sheet bronze, it has traditionally been interpreted as too thin to provide protection (Harding 2007, 120-1), but more recent understanding of the production of Bronze Age sheet metal (Uckelmann 2011) suggests that these items could have provided at least partial protection, as the ancient manufacturing technique produced

extremely durable material. It is likely that most armour at the time was of organic origin which has not survived in the record, or of composite materials (Mödlinger 2018) such as the leather and bronze armour from Pila del Brancon (Harding 2007, 121). Experiments with Egyptian replica armour consisting of bronze, rawhide and a composite of the two have demonstrated that these materials can provide high levels of protection against contemporary weapons (Hulit & Richardson 2007).

2.3 Osteological evidence of violent trauma

In addition to weaponry and armour studies, osteological examinations of Bronze Age skeletons can provide insights into the injuries sustained by individuals from that time period. In combination with knowledge of weaponry and armour, they also have the potential to provide information on how combat was conducted, especially with regards to target areas, what types of trauma were inflicted, and how serious the injuries were. It must be stressed, however, that there are several problems with this method.

Firstly, burial practices varied over time and space: while inhumations were common during the earlier phases of the Bronze Age, cremations became prevalent throughout Europe in the later 2nd millennium BC (Harding 2000, 76). Cremations, although frequently discovered, yield almost no osteological evidence. On the other hand, the few inhumations from the Late Bronze Age are not without their problems, as they must first of all be recognised as such, and secondly be securely dated to the Bronze Age (Osgood 2000, 19). It is not uncommon that skeletons, that were perceived to be of a Bronze Age date, later turned out to be of Roman, Migration Period or even mediaeval origin (Otto et al. 2006, 156).

Secondly, one must bear in mind that not all osteological evidence is the result of violence or combat, and vice versa not all violence leaves osteological evidence (Osgood 2000, 19). Although generic marks that can be securely linked to violent interaction do exist, such as Monteggia (or “parry”) fractures, a broken skull could in many cases be the result of a fall as well as trauma caused by a blow to the head. On the other hand, a violent death can be inflicted by soft tissue wounds, such as a slit throat or stab to the guts, which would both be fatal yet leave no osteological evidence. An example of this is the Iceman, who was most likely killed from an arrowhead that severed an artery without causing damage to the underlying bones (Janko et al. 2012).

Thirdly, osteological evidence must be recognised as such, and be interpreted in the correct way. What few examples from the British Bronze Age there are consist mostly of archaeologists interpreting what they see, without having specialist knowledge of pathology, although recent years have seen an increase in osteological assessments of Bronze Age remains. Specialists of other time periods or European regions use the help of medics and

pathologists, to create accurate reports of the osteological evidence, thus providing much more reliable and extensive information (e.g. Ostendorf Smith 1997; Robb 1997; Frayer 1997).

Nevertheless, there are some informative examples of osteological evidence for violence from the Bronze Age in Britain, Italy (the two areas with which this research is mainly concerned), and mainland Europe, which provide interesting insights into the brutality of conflict during that time. These are reviewed below.

2.3.1 *Britain*

Figure 2.6 – Unscaled drawing of the Stonehenge archer inhumation burial (right) and photograph of an arrowhead embedded in a rib (top left) (Osgood 2000, 20).

One of the earliest osteological examples of violence in the British Bronze Age comes from Stonehenge. In 1978, John Evans investigated part of the site to assess its environmental potential, and discovered a grave that was cut into the upper silts of the circular ditch which is one of the oldest features at Stonehenge. The inhumation consisted of a crouched male, buried on his left side (Figure 2.6), dating to the Beaker culture at c. 2100 BC. A stone wristguard and flint arrowheads suggest that the individual was an archer. Most strikingly, two barbed-and-tanged flint arrowheads were found embedded in his rib and sternum, suggesting that he was killed in a violent encounter (Richards 1991, 65; Osgood 2000, 20).

Figure 2.7 – Female skull from Chamber 3 with a slash lesion to the frontal cranium. Unscaled image (Leach 2006, 287).

Skull 1, from Chamber 3 of Antoft's Windypit in North Yorkshire, is that of an elderly woman who sustained a slash lesion to the frontal bone of the cranium (Figure 2.7). The fracture would likely have been the cause of death. It appears to be the result of a sharp force injury caused by a narrow metal blade, possibly a sword or long-headed spear. There is no bone healing, which indicates that this is a perimortem injury. A radiocarbon date has been obtained, dating the skull to c. 1350 BC (Mödlinger 2011, 165; Thorpe 2006, 156; Leach 2006, 287-90).

Another example of death by arrow comes from Central Grave 203 of Ring Ditch 201 at the Barrow Hills of Radley, Oxfordshire. Here, the skeletal remains of a crouched male, aged 20-30 years, were discovered with a barbed-and-tanged arrowhead next to the spine. Whilst no marks were recorded on the bones, the arrowhead displays a clear impact fracture at its tip. Although the arrowhead could have been deliberately inserted as a grave good, the location next to the spine, and lack of other goods, make this seem unlikely. Furthermore, the fractured tip seems to be the result of a powerful impact, which was likely caused by impacting the vertebrae. It is possible that the arrowhead was the cause of death of the individual. A sample from a femur was taken for radiocarbon analysis, which dates the remains to c. 1762-1511 cal BC (BM-2700; 3360 ± 50 BP; Barclay & Halpin 1998, 136-8).

Figure 2.8 – Skeleton 2 has the fractured tip of a bronze spearhead embedded between two lumbar vertebrae. Unscaled image (Knight et al. 1972, plate IIc).

Figure 2.9 – Iron Age rock carving from Val Camonica, Lombard, Italy. Unscaled image (Knight et al. 1972, 16).

The skeletal remains of two young males were discovered near West Littleton Down, Tormarton, Gloucestershire, in July 1968, and have since become the most famous examples of violence from the British Bronze Age. Initially discovered by the local Knight family, the skeletons were excavated and first published by R.W. Knight, C. Browne and L.V. Grinsell (Knight et al. 1972), and have since been cited in the majority of articles discussing violence in the British Bronze Age (e.g. Osgood 1998; 2000; 2005; 2006; Thorpe 2006; Otto et al. 2006; Heath 2009). The skeletons were buried unceremoniously in a ditch or pit, approximately within one foot of each other. Skeleton 1 has a hole in its pelvis, made by a lozenge-sectioned spearhead which was driven into the body while the victim was falling to the ground, or had already fallen. It is believed that the spear was driven into the victim from the right side. The legs of the skeleton could not be recovered, as they were buried under a spoil heap which could not be removed during the excavation. Skeleton 2 displays wounds of even greater interest: it, too, has a hole in its pelvis created by a spearhead, but this time the

tip of the spear remains *in situ* in the bone, while the socket has fractured off. Green-brown bronze staining has occurred around the hole and spear tip. A second spear tip was found inserted between two lumbar vertebrae in the victim's lower spine (Figure 2.8). Here, too, the socket has fractured off. The location, where the spear tip has pierced the victim's spinal cord, would have caused an immediate and permanent paralysis of the legs. Bronze staining has also occurred in this area. Furthermore, a hole was discovered in the skeleton's skull, which is likely the result of a blow or wound to the head. The authors suggest that the male may have initially been hit on the head, then was pierced twice with the spears while falling to the floor (Knight et al. 1972, 14). A radiocarbon date was obtained for Skeleton 2, dating it to c. 1394-908 cal BC (BM-542; 2927 ± 90 BP). The similarity to the victim of Queensford Farm (see below) was also noted (*ibid.*, 16). The site was revisited by Richard Osgood and a small team of archaeologists in 1999 and 2000, and further excavations were conducted. What is believed to be the poorly preserved remains of at least a further three males were recovered, and although no direct evidence for violent deaths were found on these skeletons, one can assume that their deaths were not necessarily peaceful. It seems likely that the site saw a brutal act of violence in which five young males were murdered and disposed off in a ditch or pit by those who killed them (Osgood 2005; 2006, 335; Heath 2009, 59). A parallel to this violent event can be found in an Iron Age rock carving from Val Camonica in the Italian Alps, depicting two males with spears in a combat situation (Figure 2.9). One male apparently drives his spear through the lower back of his opponent. Next to the victim is a third depiction of a human without legs, possibly representing the paralysis experienced when the spinal cord is severed (Knight et al. 1972, 14).

In 1901, a Bronze Age inhumation was discovered at Queensford Farm in Dorchester, and the first rather brief mention is that of Hewitt (1902), who states: "Last spring, on Queensford Farm, Dorchester, belonging to Mr Richard Hall, a skeleton was dug up with part of a bronze spear broken off in the pelvis, a very fine spear with a beaded midrib; ...". Further information was not published for another 70 years, when it was mentioned by Knight and co-workers that, similar to the Tormarton skeletons, the socket of the spearhead had fractured off when the spear was withdrawn, leaving its broken tip *in situ* in the pelvis (Knight et al. 1972, 16). Later, Ehrenberg identified the remains of the spear tip as a triangular-bladed basal-looped socketed bronze spearhead, which is generally dated to the Penard phase of the British Middle Bronze Age (c. 1275-1140 cal BC; Roberts et al. 2015; Ehrenberg 1977, 37). A radiocarbon date was obtained, dating the skeleton to between c. 1216-976 cal BC (OXA6883; 2900±40 BP), which roughly coincides with the Penard Phase (Osgood 1998, 19).

Research into burnt mounds, a type of feature consisting of shattered stones, charcoal and a trough or basin that is associated with heating water (Barfield & Hodder 1981, 370), has increased over the last 20 or so years. The sites of five burnt mounds were excavated in the East Midlands. Site 1 is located near the River Soar in Birstall, Leicestershire, and consists of a mound and a channel. The mound included material culture typical of Bronze Age burials in the region, such as a shallow, crescent-shaped mound of fire-cracked stone and charcoal, two hearths and a trough. Directly adjacent to the mound, and extending over the palaeochannel, are two parallel rows of oak posts, which are likely the remains of a bridge or jetty spanning the water course. From the channel silts close to the mound an amount of animal bones were recovered, including a decapitated horse skull and remains of cattle and aurochs. The same channel, albeit in a different location, has also revealed the skeletal remains of at least two adult males. One of the skulls displays a series of sharp cut marks on the outside of the posterior of the atlas vertebrae. A lack of newly formed bone tissue suggests that the cuts had not healed, indicating a perimortem trauma and possibly suggesting some form of defleshing or decapitation. Samples for radiocarbon analysis were obtained, which dated the skull to 1040-810 cal BC (OxA-6831; Beamish & Rippers 2000, 37-38).

2.3.2 Italy

Burial evidence from the Italian Bronze Age is rich and varied, comprising of rock-cut tombs, collective burials, single inhumations, cremation burials and mass cemeteries. Detecting the number of individuals who suffered serious or fatal injuries during the Italian Bronze Age is, however, a difficult task, as bone preservation is generally far too poor to allow for deductions. The large amount of cremations from the later Bronze Age complicates things further. Furthermore, the subject of bone analysis and palaeopathology has been extremely uneven and low-frequency amongst Italian scholars (Toms 2000, 104-107), although recent years have seen an increase in osteological studies of Bronze Age human remains in the area. One study by John Robb about violence and gender in early Italy suggests that, of almost 1000 Bronze Age skeletons he looked at, only ten displayed any signs of violent trauma. It must be stressed, however, that many of these skeletons were poorly preserved and incomplete (Robb 1997).

A recent, conclusive osteological study is that of the Olmo di Nogara cemetery near Verona, north-eastern Italy (see Chapter 6.3.1 for a detailed introduction). The cemetery is located c. 30 km south of Verona and dates from the second half of the 16th to the first half of the 12th century BC. To date, the site has revealed 61 cremations and 456 inhumations, many of which included swords and other martial paraphernalia, identifying them as “warrior graves” (Cupitò

et al. 2015, 333; Salzani 2005, 537). Osteological analysis has been carried out on a number of individuals, giving insight into the types of injuries sustained at the time.

The adult male from Grave 87, c. 40 years old, suffered a cut and puncture lesion caused by a metal blade to his eleventh posterior thoracic vertebra. The blade edge transversally cut across the spinous process, a bony projection off the back of the vertebra, at a length of 17 mm and a width of 1 mm. The lesion terminates at the base of the superior articular facet, where the bone was pierced to a diameter of 2.5-3 mm. Judging by the angle of the wound, it seems possible that the blow was struck from behind, left to right. The absence of bone healing suggests a perimortem injury (Canci et al. 2009, 6).

Figure 2.10 – Curved lesion on the scapula recovered from Grave 168. Unscaled image courtesy of M.L. Pulcini.

Grave 168 contained a young adult male, c. 20-25 years old, as well as a dagger of type Monte Castellaccio, which dates this burial to Phase 2 of the Middle Bronze Age (c. 1650-1350/1300 cal BC; Nicolis 2013, 693-4). A modern pit has caused a disturbance to the grave, and almost completely removed the skull. Head injuries can therefore no longer be detected. A lesion that was likely caused by a forceful blow is located on the lateral margin of the left scapula (Figure 2.10). It runs at a transversal angle at a length of 15 mm and width of 1 mm, and was executed from left to right. It is assumed that the male had lifted his left arm, possibly to protect his face, therefore exposing the scapula to the attack (Canci et al. 2009, 6).

The burial of a senior adult male in Grave 207, c. 50 years of age, was slightly disturbed by a modern hole which has affected the right arm and ribs. A single barbed-and-tanged bronze arrowhead has been recovered from the grave. Over the lateral margin of the sixth thoracic vertebra (T6) runs a transversal cut, measuring 14 mm in length and 2.5-3.5 mm in width. The cut is likely the result of a thrust with a sword or a shorter bladed weapon, possibly a spear, which pierced the vertebral body (Canci et al. 2009, 7). It is possible that the single arrowhead had not been inserted as a grave good, but was in fact embedded in the flesh of the individual.

Figure 2.11 – Skull from Grave 405 with two cut lesions.
Uncaled image (Cupitò et al. 2015, 334).

Grave 405 contained a 35-45-year-old adult male. The burial has been looted, but green traces suggest that bronze grave goods, likely weapons, had been present. Two cut wounds to the skull and parietal bone have been identified (Figure 2.11), both of which were inflicted by a metal blade from above. There is no evidence of bone healing (Canci et al. 2009, 7-8; Cupitò et al. 2015, 334).

Figure 2.12 – Lesion on femur shaft of the male recovered from Grave 475.
Unscaled image courtesy of M.L. Pulcini.

The adult male of Grave 475, c. 40 years old, is at 178 cm unusually tall. The accompanying sword of type Sauerbrunn dates the grave to Phase 2 of the Middle Bronze Age (c. 1650-1350/1300 cal BC (Nicolis 2013, 693-4)). Laterally to the diaphysis (shaft) of the left femur, along the fourth distal end, is a rectilinear lesion perpendicular to the major axis of the bone (Figure 2.12). A small section of bone has been cut off at the upper margin. On the bottom edge runs a semi-circular fracture line. Both are undoubtedly the result of a violent impact by a weapon. The trauma was likely inflicted by a blow to a spot just above the knee, executed with considerable force. There is also a pair of small lesions on the posterior of the left ulna, which exhibit the typical features of a parry fracture, caused when the arm is raised to protect the head against an incoming blow (Canci et al. 2009, 7-8). It must be noted, however, that so-called parry fractures can also occur when an individual falls to the ground and uses their hand to absorb the impact.

Figure 2.13 – Type Boiu Ib/Keszthely sword from Grave 54.

The adult male from Grave 54 was buried with a sword of type Boiu Ib/Keszthely (Figure 2.13), dating the grave to Phase 2 of the Middle Bronze Age (c. 1650-1350/1300 cal BC (Nicolis 2013, 693-4)). His skull exhibits one elliptical depression on the left frontal bone, and three lesions on the left posterior parietal bone, which are one circular impression and two

circular punctures that pierce the skull (Canci et al. 2009, 9; Cupitò et al. 2015, 334). The absence of bone healing suggests that the injuries were perimortem.

Figure 2.14 – Skull from Grave 117 with a bone arrowhead embedded in its sphenoidal sinus. Unscaled image (Cupitò et al. 2015, 334).

The adult male from Grave 117, 35-45 years old, was buried without grave goods and is therefore undated. A bone arrowhead with three tangs has penetrated the left eye cavity, and became embedded in the sphenoidal sinus (Figure 2.14). The arrow would have destroyed the eye ball and severely injured the optic nerve and ophthalmic artery. The cause of death was most likely the shock experienced when the arrow penetrated. It appears that the bone arrowhead was especially designed for interpersonal warfare, as the three tangs provided increased penetration power and prevented the projectile from being extracted (Canci et al. 2015, 761; Cupitò et al. 2015, 334-5).

2.3.3 *Continental Europe*

This section introduces osteological studies from other parts of continental Europe. Firstly, osteological evidence from Iberia will be considered, which will be followed by analyses from the Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Croatia, and Slovakia.

There are only a few examples of injuries and death from the Iberian Bronze Age that can be conclusively attributed to violence. There has been an increase in pathological studies and scientific analysis of ancient human remains on the Iberian Peninsula over the last 20 years. Before the turn of the millennium, human remains had often only been studied poorly, if at all, or were simply discarded. Graves were also frequently looted in the past, disturbing and

destroying any remains that might have survived (Monks 2000, 45-6). Nevertheless, there are some examples of recorded osteological evidence for interpersonal violence:

Skeletal remains of a 40-year-old adult male have been discovered at El Puig, Alcoy, Alicante. The male had sustained a curved fracture to the posterior of the head. The shape and appearance of the fracture suggest that it was caused by a sharp implement, such as an axe or a sword. Bone regeneration had started around the wound, indicating that it was not fatal. As regeneration is not complete, however, the male must have died not long after the injury from unknown causes around 1400 BC (ibid.; Mödlinger 2011, 165).

At Carrelasvegas, Palencia, the remains of an individual missing a foot were found dumped into a ditch. The unhealed wound and missing extremity, in combination with the unceremonious burial, suggest that the individual, whose sex remains unknown, may have been involved in a violent encounter during which their foot was severed, and they were subsequently killed and discarded (Monks 2000, 47).

An 18-month-old baby from Elche, Spain, suffered a fatal sword cut to the head c. 1700-1500 BC (Mödlinger 2011, 165).

Although these two examples clearly show that interpersonal violence has occurred and left its marks on human remains, osteological and pathological analysis of Bronze Age finds is missing, and only laymen's interpretations by archaeologists have been made.

A Bronze Age burial mound containing the cremated remains of one individual was excavated at Hoogeloon, Netherlands. A single flint arrowhead was found amongst the remains. The base of the arrowhead has been badly damaged by the firing process, whereas the tip has remained in much better condition. It is likely that the arrowhead was partially embedded in a bone at the time of cremation. This would have caused the base of the arrowhead to be directly exposed to the fire, whilst the tip was protected by the bone it was embedded in. The arrowhead could well have caused the death of the individual, for example by damaging important soft tissue, severing a major blood vessel, or triggering infection (Janssens 1970, 36; Osgood 2000, 20).

The skeletal remains of an adult male, 50 to 60 years old, have been recovered from a burial at Over Vindinge near Svaerborg, Denmark. Embedded in the male's pubis were the remains of a copper-alloy spearhead, 47 mm long and up to 24 mm wide. The positioning of the spear tip suggests that it must have entered the body from behind. Bone healing, i.e. the growth of new bone material around the penetration point, has taken place around, and over, the spearhead, indicating that the injury was not fatal. Instead, the male would have survived for some time with the fractured spearhead deeply embedded in his body. Unfortunately, since

discovery, the skeleton has been lost, making further analysis impossible (Bennike 1985, 109-10; Osgood 2000, 21).

Figure 2.15 – Arrowhead embedded in vertebra from Klings, Germany. Unscaled image (Osgood 2000, 75).

A skeleton of unknown age or gender has been recovered at Klings, Germany. The skeleton was found with a bronze arrowhead embedded in a vertebra (Figure 2.15). Shot into the body from behind, the arrowhead would have caused immediate paralysis of some parts of the body, but it would likely not have been fatal. It is suggested that further flesh wounds must have been inflicted to subsequently kill the victim (Feustel 1958, 8; Osgood 2000, 73). As discussed above, these can easily be fatal without leaving any osteological evidence. It must be noted, though, that the excavation and recording took place in the 1950s, and any faint traces of bone trauma would likely have been overseen, or indeed not been looked for. An arrowhead lodged in a vertebra, however, stands out, and would have attracted the interest of the excavator. This exemplifies the often-biased nature of Bronze Age osteological evidence.

Another skeleton of unspecified age or gender has been excavated at Karlstadt, Germany. This individual suffered what is described as a gruesome arm injury, and was found with an arrowhead protruding from the humerus of the upper arm (Fröhlich 1983, 41; Osgood 2000, 73). Once again, osteological analysis, or even a detailed description of the finding, to determine the extent and severity of the injury, is lacking.

Figure 2.16 – Fracture lesions to the skull of a young girl from Stillfried, Austria. Unscaled image (Osgood 2000, 76).

The skeletal remains of a young female, twelve or 13 years old, have been discovered underneath a late Urnfield rampart at Stillfried, Austria. Four large circular perforations are visible on the girl's skull, as well as a number of smaller puncture wounds (Figure 2.16). It is suggested that the initial blow came from an attacker to her right and struck her at the right brow, resulting in a large puncture wound that was likely fatal. Subsequently, further strikes were aimed at her body, in what can be imagined to be a frenzy. The combination of impression fractures and piercing wounds suggests that possibly a sword was used, piercing the skull at the temple then making use of the pommel to repeatedly fracture the bone. Alternatively, the round fractures could have been caused by a second weapon, such as a club or a mace (Breitinger 1976; Osgood 2000, 75; Mödlinger 2011, 165). It is unlikely, yet not impossible, that the young female would have had the role of a warrior in the presumed conflict that must have taken place. However, her wounds are evidence for ferocious interpersonal violence on some level. Possibilities are that the girl was what is now referred to as a civilian casualty in a conflict between two parties, on the receiving end of domestic violence, or that she was simply the unfortunate victim of a violent raid. The question also

remains why the body was discovered underneath the rampart, and whether the rampart was built as a direct consequence of the conflict that killed the girl.

The Early Bronze Age burial site at Hernádkak in Hungary has revealed numerous inhumation burials. Of particular interest is the skeleton from Grave 122, which had been pierced by a spearhead. The spearhead penetrated the pelvis and remained in the bone when death occurred. There is no description of bone healing occurring around the wound, suggesting either poor recording and a lack of osteological analysis, or, more likely, that the victim was stabbed around the time of death (Bóna 1975, 150; Osgood 2000, 73).

During a series of excavations between 2007 and 2009, the remains of 16 individuals were recovered from three Bronze Age burial sites, namely Crip, Matkovići and Veliki Vanik, in Split, Croatia (Novak et al. 2011, 16). Grave 2 in Burial Mound 3 at Crip is of particular interest. A mature adult male, 35-50 years old, was found to exhibit an ante-mortem parry fracture of the left distal ulna (ibid., 19). This distinct fracture is the result of raising one's arm in front of the head to protect it from the impact of a blow. The fracture is well-healed, indicating that the incident happened a considerable amount of time before the death of the individual (ibid., 24).

Figure 2.17 – A sword was thrust through the skull of Skeleton 600. Unscaled image (Koel 2011, 334).

A total of 267 individuals have been excavated at Jelšovce near Nitra, Slovakia. The burial site comprises inhumations of two different archaeological cultures dating to the Early Bronze Age. One-hundred and seventy-two individuals have been identified as Nitra Culture, and 95 individuals are associated with the Únětice Culture. Human remains were first reported in this area in 1979, and subsequent excavations were undertaken between 1982 and 1987. The skeletal remains were pathologically examined by Katrin Koel to form the data set of her PhD thesis (Koel 2011, 51).

Head trauma was identified on seven Nitra and four Únětice Culture individuals. Amongst the Nitra Culture individuals, six had suffered blunt force trauma, and one had been pierced by an arrowhead. Amongst the individuals is one female, exhibiting a lamellar fracture to the skull. The shape of the female's fracture suggests that it was inflicted with a round, oval stone thrown with a sling, or possibly a mace head.

One male has also suffered a lamellar fracture. The particular shapes of the impression fractures in the male's skull suggest that the wound was inflicted through a forceful impact

with the blunt side of an axe. The locations of the traumas indicate that both male and female were struck from the left, suggesting a right-handed attacker. Neither trauma would have been fatal. There is no further information about the other blunt force traumas or the arrowhead injury. The four Únětice Culture individuals are all male. Of particular interest is Skeleton 600. A sword was thrust through the male's skull, causing a wound of 11 cm length (Figure 2.17). Amazingly, the wound has completely healed from both the outside and inside, indicating that the male survived for a considerable amount of time after the incident. Traces on the inside of the skull suggest that an infection grew in the skull, similar to meningitis. The lack of parrying fractures on the arms suggests that the man was possibly unconscious and did not notice the attack, as he would likely have attempted to move his head or raise his arms to protect himself.

Further parry fractures were identified on the remains of two females and one male. In all cases, the fractures were not fixed with a splint, which prevented the bones from healing properly (Koel 2011, 282).

2.3.4 Summary of osteological evidence

The following table (Table 2.1) provides a summary of all of the osteological evidence discussed in the previous section.

Injury	Bone district	Weapon	Gender	Age	Site	Country	Chronology	Individual
puncture	pelvis	spearhead	male	young	Tormarton	Britain	1394-908 cal BC	Skeleton 1
puncture	pelvis	spearhead	male	young	Tormarton	Britain	1394-908 cal BC	Skeleton 2
puncture	pelvis	spearhead	unknown	unknown	Queensford Farm	Britain	1216-976 cal BC	
puncture	pubis	spearhead	male	50-60 years	Over Vindinge	Denmark	Bronze Age (unspecified)	
puncture	pelvis	spearhead	unknown	unknown	Hernádkak	Hungary	Early Bronze Age	
puncture	spine	spearhead	male	young	Tormarton	Britain	1394-908 cal BC	Skeleton 2
puncture	vertebra	bronze arrowhead	unknown	unknown	Klings	Germany	Bronze Age (unspecified)	
puncture	vertebra	flint arrowhead	male	20-30 years	Central Grave 203, Barrow Hills	Britain	1762-1511 cal BC	
puncture	rib	flint arrowhead	male	unknown	Stonehenge	Britain	2100 BC	Stonehenge Archer
puncture	sternum	flint arrowhead	male	unknown	Stonehenge	Britain	2100 BC	Stonehenge Archer
puncture	eye socket	bone arrowhead	male	35-45 years	Grave 117, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	Middle/Late Bronze Age	
puncture	humerus	arrowhead	unknown	unknown	Karlstadt	Germany	Bronze Age (unspecified)	
puncture	skull	arrowhead	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
puncture	temple	sword	female	12-13 years	Stillfried	Austria	1200-800 BC	
puncture	skull	unknown	male	adult	Grave 54, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
puncture	skull	unknown	male	adult	Grave 54, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
cut lesion	skull	sword	infant	18 months	Elche	Spain	1700-1500 BC	
cut lesion	skull	sword	male	adult	Jelšovce	Slovakia	1870-1730 BC	Skeleton 600
cut lesion	skull, frontal cranium	blade (sword or spear)	female	elderly	Antoft's Windypit, North Yorkshire	Britain	1350 BC	
cut lesion	skull	blade	male	adult	Site 1, Birstall	Britain	1040-810 cal BC	

		(unspecified)						
cut lesion	skull	blade (unspecified)	male	35-45 years	Grave 405, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
cut lesion	skull	blade (unspecified)	male	35-45 years	Grave 405, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
cut lesion	vertebra	blade (unspecified)	male	c. 40 years	Grave 87, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
cut lesion	vertebra	blade (sword or spear)	male	c. 50 years	Grave 207, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
cut lesion	scapula	blade (unspecified)	male	20-25 years	Grave 168, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
cut lesion	femur	blade (sword or spear)	male	c. 40 years	Grave 475, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	sword or club	female	12-13 years	Stillfried	Austria	1200-800 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	sword or club	female	12-13 years	Stillfried	Austria	1200-800 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	sword or club	female	12-13 years	Stillfried	Austria	1200-800 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	sword or club	female	12-13 years	Stillfried	Austria	1200-800 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	round stone	female	adult	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	Skeleton 609
blunt force trauma	skull	axe	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	adult	Grave 54, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	adult	Grave 54, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	adult	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	Skeleton 450
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	

blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	1870-1730 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	1870-1730 BC	
blunt force trauma	skull	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	1870-1730 BC	
parry fracture	forearm	unknown	female	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
parry fracture	forearm	unknown	female	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
parry fracture	forearm	unknown	male	unknown	Jelšovce	Slovakia	2200 BC	
parry fracture	ulna	unknown	male	35-50 years	Grave 2, Crip	Croatia	Bronze Age (unspecified)	
parry fracture	ulna	unknown	male	c. 40 years	Grave 475, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
curved fracture	skull	blade (axe or sword)	male	c. 40 years	El Puig, Alicante	Spain	1400 BC	
fracture	femur	unknown	male	c. 40 years	Grave 475, Olmo di Nogara	Italy	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	
hole	skull	unknown	male	young	Tormarton	Britain	1394-908 cal BC	Skeleton 2
amputation	foot	unknown	unknown	unknown	Carrelasvegas	Spain	Bronze Age (unspecified)	

Table 2.1 – Table summarising all of the osteological evidence discussed in Chapter 2.3 , organised by injury type, affected bone district and inflicting weapon.

2.3.5 Discussion

The evidence presented above represents by no means a conclusive picture of the extent of combat-related injuries from the European Bronze Age. It does, however, show that weapon trauma was more widespread than it was previously assumed, and may affect not just adult males (i.e. the supposed warriors) but also other members of society, including young males and females of all ages. It can be assumed that there is a general underestimation of the amount of combat injuries sustained during the period, that a large portion of injuries did not leave evidence on the skeletal remains, and that the majority of osteological traces have not been recorded (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 350). Furthermore, the drastic increase in cremation burials during the Late Bronze Age prevents us from gaining conclusive osteological data from human remains of that time. Nevertheless, the case studies above reveal some patterns regarding the types of injuries suffered during the Bronze Age. These patterns, and their development, are worth considering, as they can provide an indication of preferred target areas, which in turn can be used to interpret fighting styles of the Bronze Age. There are five punctures of the pelvic bone inflicted by spearheads, some of which remained with the spear tip partially still *in situ*. It appears that the attackers were aiming for the large central mass of the abdomen, an area not protected by ribs or other bones. This is also the height at which an attacker would hold the spear to put his whole body behind the powerful thrust. Although this attack can inflict devastating injuries, it was not always fatal, as proven by the male from Over Vindinge, Denmark, who survived for quite some time with the spear tip embedded in his body. There is also evidence of a spear thrust that struck between two lumbar vertebrae, which are to the posterior of the abdomen, and would likely have been inflicted from behind. Another spear thrust was executed to the neck of one individual, also injuring the spine. It appears as if spear fighters were primarily aiming for large areas of soft tissue not protected by the rib cage. The abdomen and pelvic area also contain large blood vessels, thus making severe life-threatening injuries likely when targeted.

Four out of seven arrowheads had been shot at the victim's centre mass, penetrating the rib, the sternum or the spine (see Table 2.1). Two individuals were shot in the head, one of whom was pierced through the temple, the other through the eye socket. Such precise shots were likely executed from short range. There is also one arrowhead embedded in a humerus, which could have been a deliberate close range shot to render the arm useless.

A total of 16 impression fractures on eleven skulls have been counted (Table 2.1). This number might suggest a dominance of blunt force trauma, but the evidence is likely to be biased on two accounts: firstly, this is the most easily detectable trauma and does not require specialist pathological expertise to be identified; secondly, skulls often exhibit multiple blunt

force traumas, thus reducing the number of victims. Blunt force trauma has not been discovered on any other body parts but the skull, suggesting that the head was deliberately targeted by attackers wielding clubs, maces, and other blunt-force weapons.

There are relatively few combat-related cut marks, but this might be due to the difficulty of identifying them. In one case, the mark is clearly the result of a strike to the knee, an attack often carried out in sword fighting to incapacitate the opponent (Clements 1998, 26). The lesion to the scapula seen in Grave 168 at Olmo, Italy (see Table 2.1), was caused when the defender raised his arm to protect his head, thereby opening up to the attacker who could inflict the injury to the shoulder blade.

Finally, parry fractures seem to be common, and mostly show evidence of healing. Although it is easy to relate this kind of injury to combat, it must be noted that the fracture can also be sustained during a fall, and without further evidence for violence it is almost impossible to differentiate between the two.

2.4 The Tollense Valley battlefield

The Tollense Valley battlefield near Altentreptow in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany, is by far the largest and most important site associated with conflict, violence and warfare in Bronze Age Europe. Having been the focus of excavations and research for over 20 years, the site has yielded invaluable results about prehistoric weaponry, warfare, and traumas experienced by those who participated in the violent encounter.

2.4.1 *Discovery and excavations*

Figure 2.18 – The first find: a flint arrowhead embedded in the humerus of a human being. Unscaled image (Lidke et al. 2015, 338).

The first reports of the discovery of human remains in the valley date to the 1970s, when on occasion partial skeletons would appear during construction or environmental works. As the initial finds were not associated with any chronologically coherent find context, the bones were mostly discarded and little attention was paid to them. During the 1980s and early 1990s, a range of roughly 70 copper-alloy objects were recovered, including items such as arrowheads, spear tips, adzes, knives, a dagger blade, the fragment of a sword, two fibulae, several pins, and one decorated box. Human remains discovered at the time also included numerous skulls, or fragments thereof. It was not until the summer of 1996, however, when voluntary monument conservator Ronald Borgwardt and his father undertook a boat trip on the Tollense River, that several pieces of skeletal remains were discovered in a freshly eroded river bank. Importantly, a human humerus with a retouched flint arrowhead was also retrieved (Figure 2.18). Borgwardt also discovered a thoroughly manufactured wooden club, in appearance similar to a modern baseball bat, in the immediate proximity of the human remains. The flint arrowhead, which could only have originated from the Neolithic or Bronze Age, was the first find suggesting a prehistoric chronology for the objects from the valley. Reports of previously found human remains and copper-alloy objects from the valley were then remembered, and provided the first indication of a possible conflict situation on the site. To evaluate the site, several test pits were excavated in the same year. These revealed a large amount of animal bones, mostly from horses, as well as a well-preserved human *cranium* exhibiting a large peri-mortal depression fracture on the frontal bone. Although this was further indication that a violent conflict had taken place in the past, no further action was taken at this time. In 1999, it was again Borgwardt, who, at the same spot, discovered further human remains and another wooden club, the latter similar in shape to a croquet mallet. While these new discoveries might have confirmed that a violent encounter had taken place near the river, alternative interpretations were also put forward. It was suggested that the finds could be the remains of a burial site that had been destroyed by the river; that a conflict had taken place elsewhere and the victims had been disposed of in the river; or that the human remains were in fact the result of ritual (human) sacrifices, and that their deposition in the river might have been carried out over decades or centuries as part of recurrent ceremonies. In order to address these questions, systematic, large-scale archaeological investigations were conducted from 2009 by the State Office for Culture and the Preservation of Historical Monuments Mecklenburg-Vorpommern and the Department of Prehistoric Studies at the University of Greifswald. In-depth excavations were undertaken at the original find spot, named Weltzin 20, and at several other locations throughout the valley (Figure 2.19). Moreover, underwater archaeologists and volunteer divers were drafted in to conduct thorough searches in the river.

They found numerous human remains that have been washed away, as well as skeletons remaining *in situ* in the river bed. Since 2010, large-scale palaeopathological and osteoarchaeological analyses have been carried out on the skeletal material, while on-site excavations are still ongoing (Jantzen et al. 2011, 417-21; Jantzen & Terberger 2011, 6, 8; Brinker et al. 2013, 146-7; Lidke et al. 2015, 337-8). This research has shed light on the reality of interpersonal violence in Bronze Age Europe.

Figure 2.19 – Map of the Tollense Valley showing the find spot Weltzin 20 and the distribution of human remains in green (Jantzen et al. 2011, 419).

2.4.2 The site and its finds

Figure 2.20 – Two wooden clubs discovered at Weltzin 20. Unscaled image (Lidke et al. 2015, 338).

The river Tollense runs through the morainic landscape of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern at a length of 68 km. Archaeologically significant are c. 3.5 km of river meandering through the Tollense Valley, the course of which has changed little over the last few millennia (Jantzen &

Terberger 2011, 7). At a maximum width of around 400 m, the valley cuts relatively deeply into an otherwise flat landscape. Dredging of the river has caused it to cut deeper into the valley than ever before, and it is believed that the prehistoric stream would have been shallower, wider, and considerably slower. The layer containing human remains and Bronze Age artefacts has been detected along the entire 3.5 km stretch, varying in depth between 1 and 2.5 m. At Weltzin 20, the layer has been excavated in an area of over 350 m², at a length of at least 90 m, in which the remains of at least 70 individuals have been discovered. Radiocarbon dating and dendrochronology have placed the majority of the finds in the 13th century BC, phase Bz D of the Later Bronze Age in Germany (Jantzen & Terberger 2011, 6-7; Jantzen et al. 2011, 425; Lidke et al. 2015, 338).

Perhaps the most extraordinary finds are two wooden clubs, which were recovered from Weltzin 20 (Figure 2.20). Albeit discovered at different times, they were located at a distance of a few metres from each other. Recovered in 1996, the first object is a 73.5 cm long club made of ash wood, closely resembling a modern baseball bat. It is essentially an elongated piece of wood that thickens towards one end. The second club, discovered in 1999, has a length of 62 cm, and is similar in style to a croquet bat. A long, slightly curved handle terminates in a hammer-like head which sits at a 90° angle to the handle. Wooden clubs like these are believed to be the cause of severe blunt force trauma, which can be seen on some of the skulls recovered from this and other Bronze Age sites in Europe (Jantzen et al. 2011, 418; Jantzen & Terberger 2011, 8-9; Brinker et al. 2013, 140-1; Lidke et al. 2015, 338).

2.4.3 *Human remains and evidence for violence*

Figure 2.21 – Blunt force trauma to the forehead. Unscaled image (Jantzen et al. 2011, 422).

Over 20 years have passed since the discovery of the site, and the amount of recovered skeletal remains is steadily increasing. Due to the nature of the interpretation of Tollense Valley as a battlefield, pathological and osteological analysis have become a major part of the study of the site. As time has passed, more and more osteological samples have been analysed, and an increasing amount of evidence of violence has been found. This has led to ever changing interpretations of the data set, and published statements about the extent of violence from the site have changed drastically over the years.

By the time the first article was submitted for publication in 2010, it was estimated that the remains of around 100 individuals had been recovered. Of these, 38 were only represented by skulls or skull fragments. A clear dominance of young and early mature males, between 20 and 40 years old, had been observed, while infants and females were only present in small numbers. The majority of individuals are only represented through partial skeletons, which were often dislocated and retrieved from various find spots throughout the valley. A total of 83 individuals had been analysed by 2010, and lesions had been identified on eight of them. These consist of two blunt-force traumas, five cases in which the lesion was caused by a

projectile point, such as an arrow or spearhead penetrating the bone, and one case in which a fractured femur was possibly caused by a fall (Jantzen et al. 2011, 424-5).

By 2011, the minimum number of individuals (MNI) from the site had slightly increased, and c. 45 of them were then identified as being represented only by a skull or skull remains (Jantzen & Terberger 2011, 9). The paper states that, although eight cases of injuries had been identified, there was no evidence for lesions caused by sharp cutting edges. Furthermore, it is stated that this clearly contradicts the traditional view of the Bronze Age warrior and his sword (*ibid.*, 9-10). Although this is consistent with my personal and others' most recent understandings of Bronze Age combat, in which spears and clubs would have been the preferred weapon of choice (Hermann et al., *in press*), this statement has retrospectively proven to be premature, and was based on an incomplete analysis of the data set (see Chapter 7).

The subsequent publication from 2013 focusses on the original find spot Weltzin 20, as this has to date been the most comprehensively investigated site from Tollense Valley. Based on data from March 2011, a total of 2574 human bones had been recovered from the site, which consist of small amounts of crania, mandibles, skull fragments, some isolated teeth, around 400 long bones and, by far the most common type, 2082 post-cranial skeletal elements. Calculations based on the number of femurs identified amongst the sample, the latest MNI for Weltzin 20 had been determined as being 56 (Brinker et al. 2013, 150-1). This means that roughly half of all individuals identified from Tollense Valley were recovered from this particular spot. Gender diagnostic analysis has revealed a male to female ratio of 22:4, revealing an evidently unusual dominance of males in the sample. The paper also stresses the clear dominance of young adult individuals, both male and female (Brinker et al. 2013, 151-3). By 2013, five cases of combat related peri-mortal trauma had been identified from Weltzin 20, consisting of two cranial fractures induced by blunt force, two piercing lesions caused by projectiles penetrating the bone, and one fractured femur, the result of a high-speed fall from great height (*ibid.*, 153-7). Again, no evidence for cutting edge lesions or sharp force had been detected.

Continuing excavations and an increased focus on pathological and osteological analysis of the bone material had drastically changed the picture by 2015. A total of over 11,000 human bones had been recovered from Tollense Valley by 2014, and around 133 individuals could be identified (MNI). Again, particular interest had been paid to Weltzin 20, from which alone nearly 8500 human bones had been recovered. Not only has Weltzin 20 proven to be an incredibly rich find spot, but the osteological material is also largely intact, and generally in good condition with smooth surfaces, thus providing excellent samples for analysis. The MNI

for Weltzin 20 had increased to 83, represented by left femurs. Instead of eight, now almost 100 unhealed peri-mortem lesions had been identified. The majority of these consist of projectiles penetrating the bone or stabbing wounds, but, for the first time, cutting and slashing injuries could also be proven. Contrary to earlier publications, impression fractures (Figure 2.21) caused by blunt force, such as a strike with a wooden club, have turned out to be of rather infrequent occurrence. While the peri-mortem injuries are clustered around all body regions, the few cases of blunt force trauma are exclusively restricted to the head (Brinker et al. 2018; Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 347-8).

The development of the publications about the skeletal remains from Tollense Valley over the years shows clearly how information, that at one point was regarded as factual, can quickly change. Whilst at first it was believed that combat-related trauma was extremely rare and restricted to blunt force and projectile penetrations, it has taken less than a decade to completely overthrow these statements and reinterpret the site dramatically. The work by Brinker, Jantzen and others has also shown the value of combining traditional archaeological excavations with scientific techniques, such as medical pathological and osteological analysis.

Figure 2.22 – Bronze arrowhead embedded in the occipital bone of a calvarium. Unscaled image (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 348).

Figure 2.23 – Cut marks caused by a blade entering through and being retrieved from the rib cage. Unscaled image (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 349).

To identify and correctly label peri-mortem injuries, a combination of physical examinations, microscopic analysis and radiological procedures have been utilised. To create a comparable data set, and because prehistoric combat injuries are not necessarily published in modern pathological literature, experiments have been carried out. To recreate the marks a bladed

weapon would cause on bone, replica daggers and bow and arrow were used to attack pigs carcasses (Lidke et al. 2014). Previous experiments with Bronze Age arrows (such as Smith et al. 2007; Letournex & Pétilon 2008) were also taken into consideration. Results were then compared to the traces detected on the Tollense Valley remains, to identify which types of weapons were used (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 247). The following section provides a summary of the types of traumas identified, and introduces a number of specific cases to demonstrate the extent of the injuries.

The first category of trauma is represented by arrowheads still embedded in bone. Most famously, the first find from the site, which dates back to 1996, belongs to this category. It is a retouched flint arrowhead embedded in the tubercle of a right humerus, penetrating the bone to a depth of 22 mm. It is suggested that the arrow was shot at high velocity from a short distance while the victim was lying on the floor, or from an elevated attacker (Jantzen et al. 2011, 425; Brinker et al. 2013, 155; Lidke et al. 2015, 338). Another example is that of a bronze arrowhead embedded in the occipital bone of a calvarium (Figure 2.22) recovered from the river bed (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 348). Additionally, small triangular or rhombic impressions on the bone material are evidence for arrow penetration. These marks have been accurately recreated during the experiments. Examples include a left pelvic bone with a rhombic puncture (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 349), and a skull with a small puncture on the right parietal bone, which was likely caused by an arrow that was shot from some distance (Jantzen 2011, 424; Brinker et al. 2013, 153).

The second category consists of single, small cut marks, which are frequently observed on the skeletal material. Some rib bones exhibit two or more cut marks. These are consistent with those recreated during the experiments. One example is the eleventh right rib bone of an adult individual, which exhibits two small, v-shaped cut marks on the caudal margin, close together but at opposing angles (Figure 2.23). Experiments have shown that this was caused by one action: the first mark was likely caused by a dagger penetrating the victim, the second when the blade was retrieved (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 349). Some slash marks are likely the result of violent blows with more substantial bladed weapons, such as swords or axes. An example is a lesion on the left shoulder blade of an adult individual, showing typical characteristics of a sword strike (ibid.). This is comparable to the lesions suffered by the male from Grave 168 at Olmo di Nogara, who also suffered a sword strike to the left scapula (Canci et al. 2009, 6; see above). The characteristics and location of some finer cut marks indicate that they are likely the result of sword or spear thrusts. An infliction by daggers or knives is extremely unlikely in this case, as their blade dimensions would create different marks (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 349).

The third category is blunt force trauma, which occurred infrequently and could only be identified on skulls (Brinker et al. 2018; Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 348).

2.4.4 Discussion

Figure 2.24 - Distribution of peri-mortem trauma, anterior and posterior, as known by 2015. More evidence has since been discovered. Unscaled image (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 349).

Certain distribution patterns of peri-mortem lesions on the body have been identified. Whilst they are present on all areas of the body, 55 % are located on the torso, 31 % on the extremities, and only 14 % on the head. The majority of lesions are on the right half of the body. Roughly two thirds of injuries were inflicted to the front. Half of all lesions caused by arrowheads are located on the ribs or vertebrae. Stab wounds are also predominantly located on the torso. The few blunt force traumas are exclusively located on skulls (Brinker & Orschiedt 2015, 348).

The clustering of arrow wounds on the torso does not come as a surprise, as a body's centre mass provides the greatest target area possible, and would be preferred by marksmen who have to strike their victim from a distance. All vital organs and the spine, as well as several major blood vessels, are located in this part of the body, making it easy to inflict severe injury. More than half of the arrow wounds are located on the back of the body, suggesting that marksmen used the long range of their weapons to remain undetected and attack their enemies from behind, or that the victim was killed while fleeing the scene. Arrows that struck somewhere other than the torso seem to be concentrated on the joints. As in the case of the

1996 humerus, which was presumably shot at from close distance, these wounds could have been inflicted deliberately to render arms or legs incapacitated. Stab wounds are predominantly located on the right side on the front of the body. Assuming a general right-handed dominance of the combatants, it seems likely that the preferred target area would be the side which held the weapon, so that even if an attack did not kill the opponent it would at least weaken that side of their body. Again, stab wounds have been predominantly inflicted to the torso, which provides the biggest and most sensitive target area. Slash wounds are fairly uncommon, and most were inflicted to the extremities, although there is evidence of one slash to the back of the skull, one to the neck and two to the spine just below the rib cage. Cutting has the potential to sever muscle tissue and ligaments better than any other attack, and could have been deliberately aimed at the extremities to handicap the opponent. The high stab-to-cut wound ratio may indicate that preference was given to spears rather than swords, although it must be noted that both weapons can be used for both actions. More brutal slash wounds seem to have been executed mostly to the joints or long bones, as they would have the ability to not only cut the flesh but also fracture the bone. Blunt force traumas inflicted by wooden clubs or stones are exclusively located on the skull, as this provides the most efficient target area for this type of attack. Whilst capable of crushing bone, a blunt strike to the body is unlikely to inflict fatal damage, or, if no bones are broken, injure the victim at all. If the skull is struck, however, it takes relatively little force to inflict a fatal head trauma, or at any rate knock the opponent unconscious. Evidence of other trauma to the skull is limited, as the cranial bones provide excellent protection against stabs or cuts, and such attacks would have to be precisely aimed to the soft tissue or eyes to fatally injure the opponent.

The Tollense Valley battlefield site provides a direct link between osteological evidence for combat trauma and Bronze Age weapons that were found in close proximity to the human remains (Brinker et al. 2018). An extraordinarily high number of individuals, the age and gender bias towards young adult males, the high volume of combat-related trauma and the material culture recovered from the site has provided the basis for numerous theories about what happened at Tollense Valley. The general consensus is that a violent conflict involving an unusually large number of males has occurred, which appears to go beyond any traditional clan warfare or inter-tribal violence. One theory, based on C13-isotope analysis and the typologies of bronze needles, suggests that one party involved in the conflict were an invading population from the south (Jantzen & Terberger 2011, 10).

2.5 Conclusion

Chapter 2 has introduced the weaponry available during the Middle and Late Bronze Age in Europe. This is followed by an overview of the osteological evidence for violent trauma from the European Bronze Age, which was used to identify the types of injuries and target areas prevalent during the period. Special consideration was given to the evidence from the Tollense Valley battlefield in Germany, where directly correlating combat injuries and weapons were discovered side by side. To understand how Bronze Age swords were used in combat, and what marks would be created from clashing contacts with other weapons, the next chapter focusses on combat experiments conducted with replica swords, spears and shields.

Chapter 3. Bronze Age combat – an experimental approach

3.1 Introduction

This chapter commences with a detailed literature review of experimental archaeology and metalwork wear analysis. The review provides the basis for the wear analysis and experimental methodologies used for this research. Following an introduction to the Bronze Age Combat Project, the chapter then describes and discusses the primary data obtained during the experiment in detail.

3.2 Review of experimental archaeology and metalwork wear analysis

3.2.1 Introduction

Almost two decades of research and innovation have finally pushed prehistoric metalwork wear analysis towards becoming a recognised field of archaeological science. Initially inspired by lithic micro-wear studies, the discipline quickly developed its own methodologies, approaches and problems. There is now a large gap between the two disciplines of metalwork and lithic studies, mostly due to the different material properties of the objects studied, and a general lack of communication between the practitioners, and the absence of formal training for metallurgists is now taking its toll. However, some believe that the slightly disorganised initial developmental stage of metalwork wear analysis is now coming to an end, and that its full acceptance as a sophisticated research discipline is imminent (Dolfini & Crellin 2016, 78). The following pages will discuss the issue of definition, provide an introduction to the history of research, a literature review of recent experimental and use-wear studies, and outline the limitations and gaps in the literature to date.

3.2.2 Definition

The discipline has been described with a variety of terms over the years, with use-wear analysis being the most commonly used expression (e.g. Gordon 1985; Kienlin & Ottaway 1998; Kamphaus 2006; Dolfini 2011). It is a term borrowed from microwear studies (Hayden 1979; Odell 2004; Marreiros et al. 2015), and describes the marks caused by use which are visible on the surface and edges of an object. The limitations of the expression become apparent when considering that not all visible marks are linked to usage, but can equally be the result of manufacturing or post-depositional processes (Roberts & Ottaway 2003; Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martín-Lerma 2015). Equally, the terms traceology and functional analysis, both expressions used in lithic wear studies, have its limitations, with the former being generally employed in reference to residue analysis, and the latter implying a wider application of methods including experimental archaeology and artefact classification.

Dolfini & Crellin (2016) propose the term metalwork wear analysis, a newly introduced expression that nevertheless accurately describes the discipline. Whilst being most similar to the now frequently read use-wear analysis, allowing easy recognition by the community, the term does neither suggest that exclusively the marks created by use are investigated, nor does it prioritise any part of the object over another. Furthermore, it communicates the approaches and methods of archaeological wear research whilst explicitly referring to the study of metal objects (Dolfini & Crellin 2016, 79).

For the above-mentioned advantages of the expression, and in order to create consistency within the discipline and spread the word, the term metalwork wear analysis has been adopted for this thesis. The literature review in this section, however, will use the terms published by the individual authors.

3.2.3 History of research

Despite Semenov's early attempt of studying metal tools (Semenov 1964), the discipline of metalwork wear analysis has developed significantly later than its lithic counterpart. The late development has been attributed to the notion that recycling, manipulation, re-sharpening and corrosion would significantly restrict the potential of the discipline (Roberts & Ottaway 2003, 120). Additionally, the long-standing focus on typology in prehistoric metalwork studies has hindered the emergence of a new discipline (Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martín-Lerma 2015, 171). Furthermore, there has been a long-established reluctance to accept violence in prehistory (Keeley 1996), thus preventing researchers from investigating the functionality of weapons and evidence for their use.

Pioneering work on the use of prehistoric and historic copper-alloy objects appears to have been carried out independently by a small number of American and European researchers in the late 1970s, with Kristiansen (1978; 1984; 2002) investigating the functionality of Bronze Age swords, Schauer (1979) analysing wear marks on spears, Penman (1977) assessing the potential of analysing Old Copper culture artefacts, and Gordon (1985) combining metallurgical analysis with microscopy to study indigenous Machu Picchu bronze tools. The studies had a number of limiting factors in common. None of the authors had received any formal training in lithic microwear analysis. The methodologies were rather unsophisticated, and amongst other issues did not include experimental research for reference. Finally, the eclectic approach employed by all authors, who used optical microscopy as part of a wider spectrum of research methods rather than as a specific methodology (Dolfini & Crellin 2016, 79).

It was not until the late 1990s that Kienlin & Ottaway (1998) pioneered a rigorous approach to the study of copper-alloy object wear traces, and the discipline has been developing ever

since. The following section provides a literature review of studies since the late 1990s, beginning with Kienlin & Ottaway's ground-breaking study of prehistoric axe heads, to highlight the different approaches, methodologies, and limitations developed over the last 20 years.

3.2.4 Previous research

Archaeometallurgy was traditionally based on four branches, namely technology, raw material studies, typology, and statistical and contextual studies (Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martín-Lerma 2015, 171). In recent years, however, a great interest in the functionality of prehistoric metal objects has developed, that goes beyond functional presumptions exclusively based on typology. Inspired by a long tradition of lithic use-wear analysis and experimental archaeology, a variety of copper-alloy objects including swords, daggers, axes and halberds have moved into the focus of attention (*ibid.*, 171-2). The authors criticise the inconsistent approaches to both use-wear and experimental studies, with many researchers working on extremely small sample sizes, and others interpreting use-wear without experimental data for reference (*ibid.*, 174-5). The main concern with metal object experiments must always be the raw material, as varying compositions directly affect the presence of use-wear marks. Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martín-Lerma suggest that any future experiments should be conducted with replicas of different raw-materials, post-casting treatments and types of action. Having carried out a number of field tests over the years, the authors have created an ever-expanding table of marks developed during the experiment (*ibid.*, 175). The marks are mostly concerned with working tools, rather than combat interactions. Whilst they cover a large variety of marks caused by working different materials, the definitions of edge deformation, as is of most concern to the study of combat marks, are poorly defined, and terms such as “notch” are used to describe a variety of marks (*ibid.*, 176-84). Prior to recording, the authors suggest that all objects, whether replica or original, should be cleaned. Observations should then be carried out with a microscope (*ibid.*, 185).

The authors provide a valuable insight into the issues with experimental and use-wear studies. Their suggested table of marks is most useful for the study of wear traces on tools. However, in some cases the definitions are too general, i.e. different types of marks are summarised under one term. Furthermore, the table is exclusively based on marks created during the experiments, which are then used to interpret the originals, potentially leading to confirmation bias. Finally, cleaning of originals as described by the authors is almost certainly impossible in any museum I have ever visited, and no further information on the recording process is provided.

Criticising previous theoretical studies of the use and function of flanged axes that emphasised archaeological context and typology, Kienlin & Ottaway (1998) were the first to apply a combined approach of experimental archaeology and wear trace analysis, a technique that was exclusively used on flint, stone and bone tools at the time. The aim of their experiment was to determine whether woodworking activities cause the appearance of distinct wear traces on replica copper and copper-alloy axes. In the next step, a range of flanged axes from south-western German and Swiss museums was examined to establish whether preservation of the cutting edges was sufficient to conduct analysis of the wear traces. Subsequently, casts were taken of both replicas and originals, and microscopic analysis was carried out to determine any correlation between the traces observed (Kienlin & Ottaway 1998, 271).

In accordance with the results from XRF analysis carried out on a range of flanged axes, including that of Ötzi the Iceman, several pure copper and 6 % copper-tin-alloy axes were cast in sand moulds. Half the axes were then work-hardened by cold hammering, whilst the other half were left in the as-cast state. The axes were then polished to remove any traces of the production process. Finally, two types of hafting methods were used. The axes were then used for two different purposes: cutting round wood, and stripping bark. After predefined intervals of woodworking, casts of the cutting edges were taken with dental precision impression material (*ibid.*, 272-3).

Wear trace analysis was then carried out on the replicas and on 61 prehistoric flanged axes, and the results were compared. Following the results from the analysis of the replica axes, the authors were able to identify a range of traces related to the manufacturing process and woodworking activities. The latter include (not further defined) nicks, bluntness of the cutting edge, asymmetry of the blade, and patterns of scratches at different angles protruding from the cutting edge (*ibid.*, 275).

Kienlin & Ottaway were able to demonstrate that the inclined patterns of scratches protruding from the cutting edge were a common occurrence on both experimental and original axes. They are thus evidence that prehistoric axes were used in a similar manner, or for similar activities, as the replicas during the experiment (*ibid.*, 283).

Whilst being able to demonstrate that the traces on copper-alloy axes could be analysed and systematically studied (*ibid.*), there are certain limitations to the experiments, the analytical approach, and the paper itself. Use of sand moulds to cast the axes is problematic, due to the notorious lack of archaeological evidence of such moulds (as the authors themselves note; *ibid.*, 272). The work-hardening process of the cutting edges is not further explained, and there is no information about what materials were used to carry out the procedure (e.g. steel

hammer and anvil), but it is highly likely that these tools would not have been contemporary with the axes. Cold work-hardening also requires annealing and quenching, to realign the molecular lattice structure in order to regain the metal's desired properties, of which there is no mention. Finally, the sharpening process is not explained, but it would have had to be carried out with a contemporary whetstone to produce comparable sharpness. These issues could have had a significant impact on the quality of the replicas. One can argue that if the replicas are not 100 % accurate, the whole outcome of the study will be biased. However, if these issues are considered and accounted for within the study, meaningful results can still be achieved. The paper offers no consideration of this issue though.

The main issue with the paper itself is its inconsistent use of terminology. Especially the term "damage" is used synonymously with numerous other terms (such as use wear, wear traces, bluntness, post-depositional changes), thus confusing the reader. The different types of wear traces are too general, i.e. too many different types of marks are summarised in only a few types of traces. "Bluntness" is frequently referred to, and actually used as the first step of classifying the amount of "damage" on an axe, yet the parameters of bluntness are nowhere explained.

Finally, the traces created during the experiment were used as a basis to identify traces on original axes (*ibid.*, 275). This significantly limits the identification and interpretation of original marks, as the authors would have examined the axes with the expectation to find certain marks. It also increases the likelihood of interpreting potentially unclear traces as definite marks, as humans tend to see what they are looking for, and vice versa previously unknown marks might have been overlooked.

Despite these limitations, Kienlin & Ottaway paved the way for contemporary metalwork wear analysis, and their first steps were crucial for the development of the research method.

Following the pioneering steps of use-wear analysis of copper-alloy objects by Kienlin & Ottaway (1998), Sue Bridgford first applied the technique to swords, and combined her artefact research with experimental archaeology to assess their use in combat situations. She examined a total of 499 swords and sword pieces from the Bronze Age, of types Early, Wilburton, Ewart Park and Late. These types were chosen as they appear to be in approximate chronological succession (Bridgford 2000, 117). It is important to note that Bridgford's aim was to assess whether or not the swords were used in combat, but not how. To achieve this, Bridgford created seven sword samples which were used to recreate marks that would appear during battle. She then arranged these marks in categories and compared the original swords and sword pieces to quantify the extent of similar marks on originals. Although certainly innovative and noble, Bridgford's approach to, and method of, creating reference marks was

unfeasible. Bridgford ordered seven cast copper-alloy sword blade segments, which were then to be work-hardened and sharpened by herself and her team. Using only small sections of blade, instead of whole swords, is bound to yield results not accurately reflecting combat damage (*ibid.*, 93). The first four segments were then, with varying success, work-hardened with a steel hammer and sharpened on an electrically rotating standing sandstone wheel, thus creating a completely different edge and sharpness than would have been achieved with Bronze Age technology. The remaining three segments were work-hardened using a copper hammer, which was subject to extreme distortion but proved to be rather functional. The question, why no bronze hammer was used, remains. Only Segment 5 was manually sharpened using two different kinds of whetstones (*ibid.*, 93-100). Bridgford mentions that the copper hammer proved superior to the steel hammer, while O’Faolain (1997) found stone hammers to be superior to copper in an earlier experiment (Bridgford 2000). Despite this, the inauthentic work-hardening and sharpening left Bridgford with six segments with properties that could not possibly represent those of original Bronze Age swords, and Segment 5, which can be regarded as authentic, but was still only a section of a sword blade. In order to create combat marks, the blade segments were then, two at a time, used in a Monsanto Tensometer Balanced Impact Machine by fixing the segments to wooden cubes that were attached to the machine’s arm and the opposing table. Each segment was used only once, either static (table) or animated (arm), and put into contact with another segment at angles of 45 degrees in two planes (*ibid.*, 103). This repetitive action, and the fact that blade segments strapped to a machine do not account for the various motions a whole sword used by a human swordsman (twisting and turning of the blade, different angles during the point of contact etc.), devised a total of only six different kinds of wear marks, namely bowed, chipped, notched, nicked, scored and torn (*ibid.*, 103-105). Whilst developing a perfectly reproducible laboratory experiment, this approach lacked the dynamics that a human swordsman would introduce to the data.

Kristian Kristiansen has published several articles about Bronze Age swords, warfare and warrior identity (1978; 1984; 1999a; 2002; 2013; 2018). His 2002 article aims to demonstrate the functionality and efficiency of Bronze Age swords through empirical observation, and suggests ways in which these weapons could have been used. It also discusses the issues of ritual depositions and the wider nature of combat.

He starts by disproving the theory that Bronze Age sword handles were too short to be held, hence rendering the weapons unsuitable for combat. Having held several hundred swords, Kristiansen concludes that the shortness of the handle, in combination with the shoulders, effectively locks the hand to the hilt, thus offering great control and handling precision. He

further suggests that a hole, apparently frequently found in the pommel of cast-hilt swords, could have had a leather strap attached to it, allowing more powerful swings and slashing movements whilst preventing the owner from losing their sword. Kristiansen further suggests that, on many occasions, the blade would have been deliberately bent to point at the opponent's heart, a technique allegedly employed by modern sword fighters (Kristiansen 2002, 320). He also suggests that Bronze Age swords are generally capable multi-purpose swords with a dominant function, rather than exclusively suitable for just slashing or thrusting, as would have been the case with rapiers (*ibid.*).

Kristiansen concluded that he had successfully demonstrated that Bronze Age swords were functional (*ibid.*, 323). He further suggested that reoccurring traces are the result of combat. Kristiansen divides the blade into three areas of function, with the section just below the hilt being the "area of defence", the mid-section being the area where "damage from an attack is sustained", and the tip, which is frequently bent or fractured from thrusting (*ibid.*).

From all of this, Kristiansen concludes that flange-hilted swords were the weapons of professional warriors, whilst full-hilted swords belonged to chiefly commanders who would less frequently engage in combat (*ibid.*, 323-5). He supports his theory by saying that the latter blades are generally less damaged than those of flange-hilted swords (*ibid.*, 325). Kristiansen also suggests that for the damage he observed, the Bronze Age swordsmen would have required some sort of training, but as bronze swords would have been too costly to use for such purposes wooden training swords were the norm (*ibid.*, 325-6). In a footnote, he admits that this theory is based on his knowledge of only two wooden swords, but is convinced that others could be found hidden in museums (*ibid.*, 326).

Whilst Kristiansen was able to demonstrate that Bronze Age sword handles were in fact large enough to hold the swords properly, there are certain issues with this paper. From slim evidence he leaps to significant conclusions, such as suggesting that edge damage provides direct evidence for the social role of the sword owner. The issues regarding his interpretation of bent blades as deliberate to point towards the opponent's heart, and the suggestion that bronze swords were too valuable to be used in training and therefore wooden swords were the norm, will be addressed later in this thesis.

Starting with the earliest research for his PhD, Barry Molloy has carried out a number of different combat experiments which he has published partially in several articles (2006; 2007; 2008; 2010; 2011).

In order to determine how the earliest Bronze Age swords could have been used, Molloy (2007) carried out a series of cutting tests to establish their capabilities of penetrating flesh, armour, and flesh-like substances, as well as different ways of utilising the blade. Challenging

the prevalent notion that Middle Bronze Age rapiers could only be used for stabbing (e.g. Ramsey 1995, 59; Waddell 2000, 185; Barber 2003, 147; Harding 2000, 277; Osgood 1998, 13), Molloy set out to demonstrate the versatility and functionality of the weapons, as well as their excellent cutting capabilities (Molloy 2007, 92). Studying a range of rapiers, Molloy observed that, in many cases, distinctly pronounced cutting edges were present along the entire length of the rapier, thus revealing a desire for cutting or slicing motions. The hypothesis was tested on the basis of the principle of penetration by incision and laceration (after Amberger 1999, 94), i.e. drawing the cutting edge along the flesh to create a deep cut. Molloy suggests that such draw-cuts would not have aimed to be immediately fatal, or sever limbs off completely, but to slice through tendons, muscles, and arteries to incapacitate the opponent (*ibid.*, 94-5).

The experiment saw the use of two replica Middle Bronze Age swords against replica body armour, two recently slaughtered pigs, and rolled-up straw mats. Cuts against the pigs' carcasses were executed within half an hour of slaughtering in order to minimise the impact of *rigour mortis* hardening of the soft tissue. Suspended by the hind legs, bungee cords were used to put the forelegs under tension, thus simulating the resistance to movement that a human opponent would display. The straw mats were inspired by traditional Japanese sword testing equipment, consisting of several layers of soaked and rolled up straw mats representing the consistency and resistance of human flesh. Finally, replica armour consisting of leather, glued linen, and a 1.5 mm copper-alloy sheet, was attached to a slightly moving dummy (thus not creating a dead rigid target) on top of a workbench. The replica weapons consisted of a Group IV dagger/short sword (after Burgess & Gerloff 1981, 62-112), created by Andrew Walpole, and a Group II sword (*ibid.*, 19-46) created by Neil Burridge of Bronze Age Craft. On the latter, the cutting edges were work-hardened (Molloy 2007, 96-7).

From the experimental tests, it soon transpired that the short Group IV sword was only of limited capabilities when used for cutting, it being only able to slice through the equivalent of human skin, without damaging the underlying tissue. When thrust or stabbed, however, its penetration capabilities were impressive. The Group II sword, on the other hand, proved extremely capable of cutting and slicing through flesh and soft tissue, both on draw-cuts and forward thrust-cuts. It was not able to cut through the composite armour though (*ibid.*, 98).

Molloy then challenges the notion of large-scale alterations in the way warfare was conducted once Late Bronze Age leaf-shaped swords were introduced. A common issue is the assumption that "poor" MBA swords were replaced with "better" LBA ones (*ibid.*, 102) in a single, society-changing event (*ibid.*, 104). In reality, however, this introduction of different sword types would have occurred over several centuries, and any pre-existing combat styles

and traditions would have adapted over time (*ibid.*). The new sword types were structurally different though, with their cast tangs allowing for a more secure joint between the hilt and the blade, which allowed the introduction of heavier weapons, thus altering the geometry and harmonics of the entire weapon (*ibid.*). The most significant change, however, was the move from straight to leaf-shaped blades. To assess the functionality and difference of their MBA predecessors, two replica LBA swords (Irish Class 4 and Ewart Park) were tested in the same manner as outlined above. These replicas were significantly heavier than the MBA rapiers (750 g and 845 g vs. 250 g and 355 g respectively) and slightly longer, and represent dimensions that occur in the majority of LBA sword types (*ibid.*, 105). The Irish Class 4 sword successfully cut through ten layers of straw mat, the pig's shoulder joint and into its bones and flesh, but failed to cut through the organic armour. When stabbing at the armour, however, the sword penetrated it with ease. Although the sword was incapable of cutting through the armour, its weight meant that a percussive blow could cause injury to the underlying tissue (*ibid.*, 106). The Ewart Park sword proved extremely successful when employed in a cut-draw method, cutting between twelve and 14 layers of the straw mat and deeply into the pig's carcass. Hammer-like percussive blows, however, only managed to dent the mats, suggesting that, if employed in such a manner, the sword could at best have caused fractured bones and bruising in the opponent. Again, thrusts were executed successfully, and the tapered blade tip penetrated the pig and the organic armour with ease (*ibid.*). Molloy concludes that the leaf-shape of the blade significantly improves its cutting capabilities when employed in a draw-cut from the elbow, as the blade slices deeper into the flesh when pulled backwards. He also observes that the thinner blade of the Ewart Park replica cut more efficiently than its slightly thicker counterpart (*ibid.*, 107).

Having carried out extensive analysis on Middle and Late Bronze Age weapons from Ireland, Molloy concludes that the majority of those weapons have been employed in combat (*ibid.*, 98, 107). He fails, however, to provide details of any analysis he has carried out. There is also a lack of mark terminology; Molloy exclusively refers to nicks, which suggests an unsophisticated approach to metalwork wear analysis and a lack of methodology. Nevertheless, he suggests that he has found evidence for sword-on-bone impacts, as well as strikes on the unrolled edge of a metal shield. Neither Middle or Late Bronze Age swords, however, displayed any signs of flat-side-parrying (*ibid.*, 108).

With this paper, Molloy was able to demonstrate that Middle and Late Bronze Age swords were perfectly capable of cutting, and not exclusively used for stabbing. He proposed a number of possible combat actions, including strikes from the shoulder and elbow to inflict slicing cuts, draw-cuts, forward thrust-cuts and thrusts (*ibid.*, 100-1). His analysis, however,

and therefore interpretation of original swords, is unclear, although it was noted that that was not the purpose of his research.

In order to understand the functionalities of Aegean type C and Di swords from the 15th and 14th Centuries BC, Molloy (2008) then aimed to demonstrate the swords' capabilities to cut and thrust, as well as to establish some of the characteristics of contemporary Aegean Bronze Age combat styles (*ibid.*, 116-7).

Molloy's experimental approach combined experiential learning with the physical interpretation of actions, and mainly focused on the actual handling of the swords in order to determine the most effective ways to use them. The author clearly understands the importance of previous knowledge and proficiency in sword fighting, or lack thereof, to study the ways in which such weaponry can be used, and quite rightly states that the experiments and results will be basic (*ibid.*, 117-9).

The two sword types discussed in this paper are similar in appearance, and have in fact repeatedly been summarised under the generic term "rapier" (Drews 1993; Kristiansen & Larsson 2005; Monks 2000), but have significantly differing hilt forms, and in the later period differing lengths. Both types, however, continued to be used simultaneously, and even repeatedly occur within the same burial context, which suggests that the different uses are rooted in the difference of the hilt. Replicas of similar lengths, based on originals from Knossos, were used in order to understand the different performance qualities of the hilt types (Molloy 2008, 120-1). The replicas were produced by Neil Burridge and crafted to the best of his abilities, but a lack of knowledge of the original casting techniques and limited experience in producing those particular objects, resulted in replicas with thicker hilts and harder cutting edges than the originals. However, the author claims they were within the boundaries of the archaeological record, and the variations were insignificant enough not to bias the results of the combat experiments (*ibid.*, 122).

Following a two-year period of repeated training with these and other swords to gather experience and an understanding of practical swordsmanship, the main phase of the experiments saw repeated strikes and cuts against straw mats and pigs' carcasses, both simulating the resistance of human flesh. A number of different grips were tested, and eventually a fingering grip, with the forefinger over the shoulder, wrapped around the ricasso, was favoured (*ibid.*, 122-5).

From the combat experiments the author infers that, when used with the correct amount of controlled force, and in the correct manner, these swords can be used extremely effectively in both cutting and thrusting motions. Too much force, or the wrong motions, however, would rapidly bend or break the blades (*ibid.*, 126).

Whilst Molloy's experiments have certainly been able to demonstrate some capabilities of prehistoric weapons, there are a number of limiting factors in his approach. Even casting the influence of non-genuine replicas aside, Molloy's combat tests lack the repeatability and controlled circumstances of a scientific experiment. There appears to be no predefined protocol of actions with controlled repeats to aggregate the data. On two occasions, one of the swords was bent, and an unspecified quick repair was carried out to bend the weapon back into shape (*ibid.*, 123), thus potentially altering the material properties of the blade and biasing the results. Finally, the interpretations are not justified through comparison to original weapons. Whilst Molloy was certainly capable of carrying out the actions he described successfully, the ability of the swords to be used in such a way alone is not evidence for said motions in the Bronze Age. For example, whilst a rifle could most certainly be used as a club to hit an opponent over the head, this does not mean that the original designer invented it for that purpose. Molloy's experiments have provided valuable information about how these swords could have been used. Now further research is needed to understand how they were actually used in the Bronze Age.

Molloy's research into swordsmanship in the Aegean Bronze Age (2010) may not be geographically relevant, but nevertheless reveals valuable insights into how bronze swords could have been used. From Heinrich Schliemann's (1878) search for Troy, it is now evident that, in general, only few archaeological traces of prehistoric warfare remain. Molloy strives to understand Bronze Age warfare and social dynamics through an approach which he has termed combat archaeology. It consists of experimental archaeology, use-wear, taxonomic, mortuary, and iconographic evidence (Molloy 2010, 403). Aegean swords consist of ten major types, which over time changed their shape from long, thin-bladed weapons in the beginning, to short, wide and leaf-shaped blades towards the end of the Bronze Age. The earliest swords also included a single-edged type, with a curved, cleaver-like blade and hilt tang (*ibid.*, 404). Towards the end of the Bronze Age, the central European type Naue II swords were introduced to the Aegean (*ibid.*, 409). Especially later types developed prominent shoulders.

Whilst iconographic depictions of Aegean warriors were not designed to be an accurate depiction of combat, but rather communicated different perceptions and idealizations of war in Aegean society, they can provide some information about combat and swordsmanship during that period. They frequently depict different scenarios such as group or single combat. The former suggests that in group combat situations, swords were rarely used, and if only as a secondary sidearm, whilst different types of shields and spears, supported by archers, were the primary weapons of choice. Between 1700 to 1400 BC, swords in combat were exclusively

depicted on seal images on the mainland and on Crete, and most frequently depicted two opposing warriors in battle. These seals, however, are not depictions of actual combat but rather manifestations of heroism, and must therefore be treated and interpreted as such (ibid., 409-10). Warrior depictions on surviving ceramics almost always lack an opposing force, and as such, no derivations about group combat encounters can be made. The ceramics do, however, provide information about weaponry, and suggest that different types of shields and short swords were used (ibid., 411).

Whilst over the course of a millennium Early Bronze Age daggers eventually developed into swords, they are only superficially similar, and the latter required the development of a completely new set of skills and combat styles. Creating swords required a much higher level of expertise amongst prehistoric bronze smiths, and their mere existence demonstrates the level of sophistication of bronze age metallurgical technology (ibid., 413). The complexity of using such weapons required an equally sophisticated development of combat styles, which in turn implemented a shift in the resources spent on training by both individuals and communities. Molloy suggests that the invention of the sword, the first tool with just the single purpose of interpersonal combat, is evidence for the establishment of a new warrior identity (ibid., 414). To understand the functionality of Aegean Bronze Age swords, Molloy measured different parameters including length, mass, edge-preparation (through the presence of evidence for cold-working and remaining sharpness), centre of percussion, and use-wear evidence. Based on these factors, he derived how the different sword types could have been used effectively, before conducting field experiments with replica swords to test his hypotheses. The replicas were used against the same straw mats and pigs' carcasses that were used in other experiments (compare Molloy 2007). Molloy suggests that the high-tin content bronze-alloys needed to manufacture swords with long and thin blades would cause them to bend or fracture easily, whilst shortswords lacked the necessary cutting-edge-length to create long draw-cuts. Furthermore, their edges could not be sharpened, or maintained sharpened, to a high degree. As Bronze Age smiths would have been aware of those limitations, it can be suggested that their swords were designed in direct accordance with their intended functions (ibid.). Molloy suggests that long and thin bronze swords would have been most effectively used for penetrations by incision and percussion, whilst the shorter, broader swords were also effective for penetration by incision and laceration (ibid., 415). He then provides a functional hypothesis for each of the ten sword types, with the verdict that the length and shape of the blades were not the most determining factors for the ways a sword could have been used effectively. Instead, the hilt, and therefore the way the sword could be held, as well as the balance, which is directly related to the manoeuvrability of the sword in combat, are crucial

(*ibid.*, 416- 421). Molloy found that placing the index finger above the hilt shoulder provided significantly increased control over the weapon (*ibid.*, 415). He was able to successfully demonstrate that typologically different swords could be used successfully in a number of different ways, and that really the individual technique, rather than the physical properties of the weapons, dictated their functionality. Although he was able to demonstrate that Aegean Bronze Age swords could have been used in the ways he derived from their physical appearance, this does not necessarily mean that they really were. Although Molloy refers to use-wear analysis, he states that all of the Aegean swords he examined were too badly corroded to carry out the analysis (*ibid.*, 414). This also suggests that examinations of edge-hardening or remaining sharpness, both factors that influenced his interpretations, could not have been conducted. His speculations are therefore entirely hypothetical, and not grounded in physical evidence of original swords. Finally, Molloy's tests were designed to confirm his preformed hypotheses, rather than carried out to derive new theories, an approach which should be avoided.

In his 2011 paper, Molloy discusses issues affecting the study of swords, such as generalised terminology and unified broad statements across disciplines, provides an introduction into the life-cycle and uses of Bronze Age swords, and presents the sword in its wider context within society. Molloy suggests that a general concise statement about the capabilities of copper-alloy swords can be made: they were light, short, not particularly flexible, and unable to retain a sharp edge (Molloy 2011, 75). This suggests that they were unlikely to be used for wide, sweeping cuts or heavy cleaving attacks, but instead the preferred fighting technique would utilise tight cutting arcs, drawing motions and thrusts. There are, however, exceptions, such as Atlantic Group III Class Lissane grip-plate swords (*ibid.*). It is then suggested that the majority of marks will be located in the centre of percussion, an area c. two-thirds along the cutting edge towards the tip. Molloy suggests a number of different wear marks, including nicks, v-shaped nicks, notches, burred nicks and notches, rippling, bowing, rolling, and cuts. He suggests that v-shaped nicks are the result of very brief contacts with another blade, burred nicks, notches and u-shaped notches are created by twisting movements of one or both blades upon impact, shallow nocks occur from various different types of impact, and bowing as the result of oblique-angle contacts with a spear shaft or bone. All of these marks were created and recorded during choreographed sparring and cutting experiments, carried out as part of Molloy's doctoral research. Considering the frequent, yet generally not severe amount of marks on original swords, Molloy concludes that Bronze Age sword fighters were aware of the capabilities and limitations of their weaponry and learnt to use them accordingly.

Although Molloy has been able to demonstrate the capabilities of Bronze Age swords on numerous occasions over the years, there appears to be a lack of coordination between his metalwork wear analysis and combat experiments. As his use-wear analysis data remains unpublished, it cannot be fully evaluated, nor can his methodology be assessed, but from the short section in this paper it transpires that the categories of marks are generally too broad and too poorly defined to allow conclusive interpretation. There is also no link between Molloy's interpretation of the use of Bronze Age swords and his analysis of the wear marks on original and experimental weapons. In fact, Molloy appears to have published numerous papers on the use of Bronze Age swords without referring to the use-wear analysis carried out as part of his PhD. Whilst his theories about the use of copper-alloy swords are convincing, and certainly present a way in which the original weapons could have been used, they are not fully grounded in the use-wear analysis of combat marks.

Marianne Mödlinger's research investigates the manufacture, development, and usage of Central European Bronze Age swords through the analysis of 80 specimens from Austria, Hungary, Italy, Slovenia, and the Ukraine. The main focus is laid on understanding the manufacturing process, post-cast treatment and alloy-composition through a combination of scientific methods including x-ray and metallographic analysis (Mödlinger 2011, 153). Alloy-compositional analysis of over 50 swords has revealed that the composition generally ranges between 7 and 13 % tin-content, with the majority of swords containing around 9-11 % tin. No link has been found between the type or chronology of the swords and their individual Sn-contents. It transpires, however, that an increase in tin-content is directly linked to an increase in hardness (*ibid.*, 153-4). X-ray analysis of the swords has revealed a change in casting method over time. Allegedly, the earlier swords were cast from the hilt, resulting in a better-quality cast at the tip and blade, with the majority of the casting faults located in the shoulders and tang. As this has the potential to significantly weaken the hafting of the organic hilt, these swords are interpreted as predominantly stabbing weapons. It is suggested that the linear pressure acting on the hilt when carrying out a thrusting action would have no significant impact on the hafting, whilst the forces acting when carrying out a slashing motion would potentially fracture the hilt. Towards the end of Bz D (c. 1300 BC), however, the technology changed, and the Bronze Age metalworkers began to cast swords from the tip. Whilst this would ensure a good-quality cast hilt, it had the potential to significantly weaken the tip. Type Riegsee swords display evidence for both casting directions, indicating that a transitional change in methodology took place. Occasionally, younger swords display evidence for the earlier casting method, such as one Ha B sword from Austria, which fractured at its weakest point in the hilt, as expected (*ibid.*, 154-6). Evidence for post-casting treatment is rare, as

many surface traces have been eliminated during restoration or post-excavation treatment, but remains of hammering, polishing or sharpening are frequently observed. Despite occasional casting faults, which are obvious to the naked eye, the amount of use-wear suggests that these swords were still used in combat (ibid., 156).

An introduction to Mödlinger's wear analysis methodology and terminology is missing. The limited number of wear marks identified by her is explained by the theory that other bladed weapons were usually parried with the flat of the blade, a shield, or another weapon. Mödlinger also suggests that there is no correlation between the number of wear marks and typology and chronology of the swords. The author herself is surprised to realize that although a large number of their swords had been interpreted as stabbing weapons, based on their type, shape and casting process, the wear marks suggest that they had been used differently (ibid., 164).

Shaun Higgins carried out a micro-wear analysis study on the two remaining fragments of a Middle Bronze Age blade currently stored in the Auckland War Memorial Museum, New Zealand. The analysed fragments consist of a partial hilt with the upper blade attached, and another blade fragment, at a total combined length of 230 mm (Higgins 2010, 194). Both provenance and circumstances of discovery remain unknown, however, the blade is similar to Burgess's type IV blade (Burgess 1968, 4) from Britain and Ireland (Higgins 2010, 196). Lacking the lower section of the blade and tip, the total length of the weapon remains unknown. It is therefore not possible to classify it as either a dirk or a rapier. Working on the assumption that weight distribution determines function, Higgins attempts to understand whether the blade in question was intended for slashing or thrusting, but admits that either could apply (ibid., 197). What then follows is a very detailed description of the recorded marks on both fragments. Using a Dino-Lite Pro AM413T, a total of 64 "points of damage" could be identified. The marks were photographed microscopically, and their location, dimensions, and angle in relation to the cutting edge were recorded. Whilst the detail and precision of recording are commendable, the terminology used to describe the marks is unclear, unexplained and largely influenced by Kristiansen's 2002 *The Tale of the Sword*, in itself not a use-wear study (Higgins 2010, 197-8).

Higgins concludes that the amount of wear suggests combat use, rather than just ceremonial purposes (ibid., 203), and stresses that further experimental combat studies have to be conducted in order to understand exactly how Bronze Age swords could have been used. He further suggests that consistent, repeated use of a blade in the same manner would create a cluster of similar marks on a certain blade section (ibid.). It is then suggested that the majority

of the “damage” is located in the upper part of the blade close to the hilt, as this was considered to be the strongest section of the blade and hence most suitable for parrying (ibid., 204).

Christian Horn has conducted extensive research into the use of Bronze Age swords, spears and halberds (Horn 2013; 2015; 2017a; 2017b, Horn & von Holstein 2017). His use-wear analysis methodology is grounded in his 2013 research, which he conducted to understand the functionality and capabilities of Early Bronze Age weaponry, for which he undertook analysis on a sample of 50 swords and 154 spearheads from Denmark, Sweden, Norway, and Northern Germany. Whilst at that point the study of swords has been consistently popular amongst scholars, spearheads had rarely been the main focus of Bronze Age research, and their interpretation had generally been limited to throwing or thrusting (Horn 2013, 20). As recent studies had suggested more complex fighting styles, Horn set out to investigate if, and how, Early Bronze Age spears were used in combat, and how they related to contemporary sword fighting (ibid., 21). Microscopic and macroscopic analysis was then carried out, and findings were recorded in writing, drawing, and photographically (ibid., 22). In order to qualify the observed wear, the marks were organised in different groups, based on the literature available at the time. The damage was then quantified, and a number between 0 (no damage) and 3 (highly/intensely damaged) was attributed to each category to quantify frequency and intensity (ibid.). Horn then provides a detailed description of each mark type, including photographs. The definitions, however, are generally broad, and combine a number of different shapes under one term (such as sharp, v-shaped impact profiles, grazes impacting at a flat angle, very wide marks caused by axes, which are all summarised under the term “notches” (ibid.)). Furthermore, the numbered quantification of mark intensity and frequency is not further explained. This is especially true with damage intensity, which can only be assumed to refer to the relative depth of marks, and can be the result of a variety of reasons including alloy composition, post-casting treatment, the sword fighter’s individual skills and power, as well as their opponent’s, and the definition of the analyst.

Nevertheless, Horn states that the perceived absence of wear marks must not indicate a pre-depositional absence of wear, as corrosion can easily mask faint evidence of use (ibid., 36). The same analytical approach was executed on the spearheads, and it transpired that only 13 % of specimens displayed no clear sign of wear (ibid., 37). When analysing the swords, it became apparent that 56 % exhibited wear traces, although the analysis on 46 % of swords was blurred by corrosion (ibid., 38-9).

Horn’s interpretation of potential combat styles is based on the assumption that all damage is accidental, as an individual would not risk the integrity of their weapon to avoid being

disadvantaged during a fight (*ibid.*). He then argues that tip damage is attributed to thrusting and stabbing attacks, whilst other damage is the result of cutting motions (*ibid.*, 40). Statistically, a smaller percentage of swords displays wear marks than spearheads, however, this might be due to a different probability of corrosion, which affects the analysis. The smaller size of the spearheads compared to swords, in combination with a higher frequency of wear marks, suggests that the former were more frequently involved in combat (*ibid.*). Horn, however, concludes that both weapons were frequently used in combat, and that the wear marks on spears suggest that these weapons were used in a fencing style similar to sword fighting (*ibid.*, 41). Unfortunately, the research lacks experimental data to qualify the author's theories, but future research could lead to more conclusive results.

Andrea Dolfini's (2011) research aims to assess the function of Chalcolithic copper axes, halberds and daggers from the Italian Copper Age (c. 3600-2200 cal BC). Most importantly, he defined a thorough, replicable analytical protocol for copper-alloy artefact use-wear analysis. Faced with the difficulty of gaining access to Italian museums and the issue of tracing artefacts in the literature, and then finding them in the collections, Dolfini eventually analysed 19 axes, eight daggers, five halberds, and a unique Chalcolithic S-shaped knife in six different museums (Dolfini 2011, 1037-8). He then devised an analytical protocol that was applied to every single artefact in order to record the wear-traces. Following a macroscopic inspection with the naked eye, whilst taking record of dimensions, weight, description and photographs, a microscopic examination through a stereomicroscope with varying light sources was carried out. The traces were then recorded in a database and on a drawing, and micrographs were taken with a mounted camera. Unlike others, who took dental casts of the artefacts which were then later examined in the lab, Dolfini decided to carry out all analysis on originals in the museums to avoid residual marks on the artefacts (*ibid.*, 1042). The traces were classified in accordance with a list of marks developed by the author (*ibid.*, 1038), and interpreted in accordance with experimental data from available reference datasets (*ibid.*, 1042).

Following a detailed description of the interpretation, Dolfini arrives at a number of conclusions. Copper axes could be divided into three main categories based on the amount of wear. Those axes that exhibit any amount of wear appear to have been used as multi-purpose tools, rather than just for one particular function. Early daggers and halberds, however, appear to have primarily been used for functions other than practical use (*ibid.*, 1046-7).

Crucially, Dolfini was able to develop an analytical protocol that can be used to record the wear-marks on virtually any type of copper-alloy artefact. He also understands that interpretation is made difficult by the lack of comparative experimental datasets for certain

artefact types, and it is imperative that further intensive research and experimental work is conducted (ibid., 1047). Unfortunately, the issue of poorly defined mark terminology and its inconsistent use remains. The table listing different the different types of marks (ibid., 1038) lacks detailed descriptions, especially regarding wear traces. Later in the text, nicks are described as “...ranging from tiny, isolated indentures to a series of substantial notches...” (Dolfini 2011, 1043), without providing further information about these marks. The issue with inconsistent terminology is especially present when comparing to other peoples’ datasets in order to interpret the artefacts, as even just a slight discrepancy of terms could severely affect the interpretation. Nevertheless, Dolfini’s systematic approach and analytical protocol are pioneering.

Ronan O’Flaherty has conducted research with the aim to prove the functionality and capabilities of Early Bronze Age halberds, a type of weapon which was previously conceived to be only of symbolic or ceremonial purpose (O’Flaherty 1998; 2002). With over 600 examples known from Ireland, Central Europe, and Iberia, archaeologists have previously presumed that the hafting method would result in too weak a bond to withstand impacts, and the weapons were perceived as too clumsy to be used (O’Flaherty 2007, 423). To test the capabilities and effectiveness of halberds, O’Flaherty designed and constructed a replica which was used in a number of field tests. The replica blade is of type Cotton, the most common Irish type, yet it was not created as a direct copy of an original. Instead, its dimensions were calculated from the analysis of 69 original Cotton type halberd blades. An oak shaft was attached in accordance with the only surviving shafted halberd known, from Carn, County Mayo, Ireland, with its dimensions based on a number of sources including rock-art depictions and metal-shafted halberds (ibid., 423-4). No post-casting treatment such as work-hardening was carried out to avoid the problem of applying the appropriate degree of treatment. It thus concludes that whatever the replica’s performance, the Bronze Age originals would have exceeded it (ibid., 424).

Practical field tests were carried out against sheep heads, which were thought to be most directly comparable to human skulls. To reduce the risk of injury to the participants, and to avoid damaging the halberd by impacting on wood or metal of a hypothesised platform, the skulls were placed in the grass at an abattoir in County Wexford, from which the sheep heads originated. Inspired by rock-art, the halberds were held high above the head, which the author describes as intrinsically comfortable and right (ibid., 425). However, the instability and tendency to swivel when held raised, suggest that it was unlikely that original halberds were used in wide, scything attacks, but rather in short, punching blows (ibid., 426). A number of similar short blows were then executed to a central point between the eyes on each skull.

After an initial natural reluctance of the participants to deliver the blows confidently, the halberd quickly proved extremely effective and durable. A total of 20 heads were pierced successfully, c. half of them on the first attempt, and all others on the second or third strike, whilst no damage whatsoever could be observed on the halberd (*ibid.*). O’Flaherty concludes that the Irish Early Bronze Age halberds were designed as functional weapons, but not all of them would necessarily have been used in combat. As the replica preserved almost perfectly through the tests, he suggests that a lack of marks on originals does therefore not necessarily indicate exclusively non-combat related use (*ibid.*, 428).

In this paper, O’Flaherty hints that wear-patterns have been analysed on halberds (*ibid.*, 426), yet so far, no research has been undertaken into the origin of those patterns. Whilst the author has successfully demonstrated the functionality of halberds as weapons, a possibility that has previously been disregarded by most scholars, his suggestions of how the weapons could have been used are exclusively based on personal interpretation, which also coincidentally left the replica completely unmarked. He infers that it is imperative that further combat tests are conducted, and combined with wear-analysis of originals it might be possible to determine how exactly Early Bronze Age halberds were used in combat.

Developing his previous research into Early Bronze Age halberds, O’Flaherty et al. then set out to investigate the origins of edge damage observed on over 50 % of museum specimens (O’Flaherty et al. 2011). In order to carry out scientific combat experiments, a number of laboratory tests were conducted in the facilities of the School of Electrical, Electronic and Mechanical Engineering at University College Dublin (*ibid.*, 1). Macroscopic examination of 135 museum specimens has revealed that nearly 40 % display some sort of edge damage (*ibid.*, 3). The wear-marks are classified as notches, denting and bowing. Notches are divided into v-shaped and u-shaped. Whilst v-shaped notches are interpreted as direct blade-on-blade contact with other weapons, u-shaped notches could at that point not conclusively be explained (*ibid.*, 4-8).

Having characterised the edge-damage on original halberds, the next step was to recreate the marks during the experiments. Replicas of five Cotton type halberds, one contemporary Lough Ravel type axe, and a contemporary type Corkey dagger were cast out of 2 % arsenic copper by B. Rankin of Irish Arms, and post-casting treatment was carried out by Neil Burridge. A range of real and replica stone axes, as well as a timber shaft, were also included in the experiment. Following an initial work-hardening of one replica, subsequent hardness tests confirmed its concordance with originals, and hence all metal replicas were finished to that standard (*ibid.*, 7-9). The weapons were then set up in the laboratory, with the target fixed in a vice and the attacking weapon in a dropping-device that could be set to various impact

velocities. Initially, the target weapon was fixed statically to the vice, a scenario which could have been similar to intentional destruction but is highly unlikely to have happened in actual combat. The setup was therefore altered to include a foam-cushioned base, which allowed the target to slightly move upon impact (*ibid.*, 10). A number of tests and repetitions were then carried out with different combinations of weapons.

The most striking result from these tests was that both v-shaped and u-shaped notches were created by halberd-on-halberd impacts. Characteristically, the u-shaped notches were created in yielding environments, where the blade edges were moving slightly upon impact, whilst v-shaped notches were found to be the result of more static impacts (*ibid.*, 10-1). The tests were also able to recreate the rebounding double impact that is frequently observed on originals. Both copper and stone axes created wide-mouthed v-shaped notches, which are significantly different in appearance to those created by halberds, while the timber-shaft left no traces at all. None of the tests were able to recreate what O'Flaherty et al. described as denting or bowing (*ibid.*, 11-2).

O'Flaherty's second study provides great insight into the causes of wear-marks on Early Bronze Age halberds. He was able to prove that u-shaped notches (which will be referred to as round notches later in this thesis) are the result of blade-on-blade impacts in a yielding environment, and can be produced in essentially the same manner as v-shaped notches (sharp notches in this thesis). However, there are certain limitations to his research. O'Flaherty's wear mark categories are too general; he describes a variety of marks with only four terms. Conducting an experiment to recreate marks previously identified on originals, however, is the correct approach. The experiments themselves are controlled and repeatable, yet they are by no means an accurate reconstruction of actual combat. Whilst this experiment was able to prove that certain impacts create certain marks, it did not investigate how the weapons were actually used.

Dirk Brandherm (2011) set out to investigate hypothetical ways in which Bronze Age halberds could have been used through the interpretation of different types of use-wear marks on original specimens from the Iberian Peninsula. Brandherm developed an increased interest in wear marks whilst conducting a vast survey of museum specimens to create the typological classification, and understand chronology and distribution, of Iberian halberds (Brandherm 2003; 2004) As typology was the main focus of the analysis at the time, rather than the recording of use-wear, it is likely that especially smaller traces were missed, thus biasing the sample. Nevertheless, use-wear could be detected on about 10 % of the halberds (Brandherm 2011, 23-4). Brandherm states that, despite O'Flaherty's (2007) pioneering experiments into the functionality of halberds, a lot more experimental work must be conducted to understand

their combat function, and that only a combination of systematic wear-analysis studies with comprehensive field experiments will ever allow conclusive interpretation of these weapons (Brandherm 2011, 24-5). He further states that the lack of comparative experimental data imperatively renders any interpretation of the wear-marks provisional. The terminology Brandherm uses is based on Gutiérrez's classifications (Gutiérrez 2002, 262-5; Gutiérrez & Soriano 2008, 440-2); an updated version in English language was published by Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martín-Lerma in 2015. Hilt marks, i.e. the preserved outline of the original wooden shaft, are the most common type of use-wear identified by Brandherm, and play an important role in differentiating between daggers and halberds, and correctly identifying the latter (Brandherm 2011, 25-7). The other mark types identified by Brandherm on Iberian halberds are gaps, notches, bluntness, and asymmetry. Gaps are defined as marks "...where metal has been broken or torn from the edge." (ibid., 27), whilst notches are defined as anything that gives the impression that it has been caused by contact with a hard edge (ibid.). Bluntness, in itself self-explanatory, i.e. the loss of sharpness on a cutting edge, was infrequently observed on the sample. Asymmetry of the blade could be the result of deliberate blade design or frequent re-sharpening, and one must differentiate between the two causes (ibid., 28).

Following a detailed description of the use-wear observed on eleven halberds, Brandherm addresses two main questions in his conclusion. By investigating patterns of pre-depositional use-wear, it transpires that the inner edge was subject to a significantly larger amount of wear, and that in comparison the marks on the outer edge are distinctly different. Those latter marks are interpreted as the result of parrying, potentially of sword attacks (ibid., 34). On the inner edge, the marks tend to cluster towards the hafting point (ibid., 35). Interpreting these patterns, Brandherm suggests that the clusters of marks could be the direct result of a particular combat style (ibid.).

Brandherm's understanding that one must interpret patterns of marks rather than individual wear-traces, in order to understand the ways Bronze Age weapons were used, is commendable. He successfully recorded and interpreted data on a number of halberds, leading to a convincing, yet completely hypothetical theory. However, there are three issues with this study. Firstly, the recording of use-wear was inconsistent, with potentially large amounts of data missing, and not done to microscopic level. This is understandable, as the main focus of the research at the time was typology, but interpreting data on the basis of a biased data set is highly problematic. Secondly, the terminology developed by Gutiérrez is imprecise. Her definitions are extremely vague and do not describe individual mark shapes. Thirdly, the lack of comparative experimental data makes any interpretation hypothetical. Brandherm is fully aware of the first and third issues, and tries to compensate for these as much as possible.

Renewed analysis of the halberds, combined with experimental research and better mark classifications, could lead to conclusive evidence for the uses of Bronze Age halberds.

To assess their significance for ritual activity and combat, Christian Horn has analysed 13 of the 23 known Bronze Age halberds from Denmark (Horn 2014; 2017b, 515), using the same use-wear analysis methodology as previously described (see Horn 2013). Following a detailed description of the wear on each halberd, Horn derives that the majority of the halberds he observed display traces of forceful impacts, regardless of their context or chronology. He further concludes that the notches he frequently observed are most likely the result of combat encounters with other bladed weapons, rather than caused by impacts with bone or flesh, suggesting that Scandinavian halberds were not predominantly used for animal sacrifice. Statistical analysis of the wear traces reveals that the proximal and middle third of halberd blades sustain the most damage, and are thus primarily used to strike the target, whilst the frontal third and tip display comparatively little damage. Combining the latter two, however, adds up to over a third of the marks, which in turn amounts to an equal distribution of marks along the blade, thus revealing the bias of Horn's particular statistical approach. An edge-wise comparison reveals that the lower cutting edge displays only marginally more wear than the upper edge. Combining the two, it transpires that the upper proximal third displays the most amount of wear (Horn 2017b, 526). Despite a lack of direct evidence, comparison to Irish and Central German specimens and rock-art depictions suggests that Scandinavian halberds were carried one or two-handed, in an axe-like fashion. As the comparatively large amount of wear in the upper proximal third contradicts this, it can be suggested that this damage was sustained through defensive motions. Although Horn has argued that preservation of the weapon would have been of utmost importance (Horn 2013), he suggests that fighters potentially preferred to risk damage to their weapon rather than damage to themselves, and that the marks in the upper proximal third could be the result of frequent last-resort efforts to save their lives (Horn 2017b, 528). Horn further argues that the use-wear supports the "hooking" technique proposed by Brandherm (2003, 387-399), but suggests that the small amount of wear in the lower proximal third indicates that the technique would not have been deployed routinely (Horn 2017b, 528). Frequently observed direct tip pressure suggests that stabbing would also have occurred. Horn concludes that halberds could have been used with a variety of attacks and defences, including slicing, piercing, stabbing, and hooking. Using halberds effectively would likely have required some degree of training. He also suggests that the shaft could have played an important part for defence (*ibid.*).

Christian Horn was able to create interesting hypotheses about the ways Scandinavian halberds could have been used. His statistical analysis has shown that both cutting edges were

used to a similar extent. He proposes that the frequently observed notches argue against a predominantly sacrificial use. Furthermore, the cluster of wear marks in the lower proximal third supports the theory of “hooking” the opponent. However, the same limitations of Horn’s use-wear analysis methodology (see Horn 2013) remain. The sample of eleven halberds is also considerably small and does not allow for comprehensive interpretation. There is no link to data from experimental combat to support his theories, and as such any interpretation is hypothetical. Finally, although Horn suggests that the shaft could have been used defensively, using the shaft for attacking is not considered.

Inspired by John Coles’s 1960s attempt at experimental shield combat, the recent years have seen some research into the manufacture and use of Bronze Age shields.

Barry Molloy (2009) set out to test the widely accepted theory that Bronze Age copper-alloy shields were highly unfunctional in combat, whilst leather and wooden shields were functional, as suggested by Coles (1962). Working on the premise that a strictly functional differentiation is unsuitable for the interpretation of objects, Molloy suggests that shields, or indeed any other object, could have diverse functions at different stages during their life-cycle, and as such a shield could be a defensive weapon, a status symbol, and a ritual offering (Molloy 2009, 1052). Emphasis is also laid on the fact that, in combat, shields are pieces of defensive weaponry, rather than armour, and require a degree of training and experience to be used effectively, for both defence and attacks (*ibid.*, 1056-7).

Four replica shields were created for the experiments: one leather shield based on the original found in Cloonbrin, Ireland, which at a thickness of 3.5-4 mm was slightly thinner than the original 4.5 mm; and three metal shields. Molloy realized that the replica metal shields John Coles used in his experiments were too thin, at only 0.3 mm thickness, and hence produced his replicas out of 0.9 mm pre-fabricated copper sheet. As tin-bronze was unavailable to the author at the time, this was believed to be a mechanically similar alternative. One shield was also equipped with a rolled rim and inlaid metal wire for added strength (*ibid.*, 1058-60).

The shields were then held stationary, and a number of attacks were executed on target with replica copper-alloy swords, spears and flint and bronze arrows. All swords withstood the attacks without severe damage or being rendered unfunctional. The leather shield suffered several grazes and nicks, a 57 mm long incision when the rim was struck, and punctures caused by stabbing attacks. All three metal shields withstood the attacks successfully and were generally only grazed, buckled or slightly bent. The wired rim proved invaluable, as it prevented the sword from cutting into the rim (*ibid.*).

The paper played an important part in demonstrating the combat functionality of Bronze Age metal shields, and successfully disproved the incorrect, yet widely accepted theory developed

by John Coles. Molloy also understands the importance of appreciating shields, and other objects, in different ways, without restricting the interpretation to one particular function. There are, however, certain limitations to the research that cannot be ignored. No information is given on the production of the leather shield, and its material and manufacturing process, especially in relation to the original from Cloonbrin, remain unknown. The 0.9 mm pure copper sheet used to produce the metal shields is as unauthentic as it can be, and the material properties of such a shield will be significantly different to genuine copper-alloys from the Bronze Age. We now know that the originals were made by numerous cycles of hammering and annealing cast high-tin bronze (Uckelmann 2011, 189; 2012), and as such prove much stronger and resistant than any modern fabricated copper-alloy sheet metal. Again, Molloy's experiments seem to lack the controlled environment and reproducibility scientific experiments require. Mentioning a use-wear study of the Cloonbrin shield (Molloy 2009, 1059), he gives no information about the type of analysis carried out, or the results.

Despite these limitations, Molloy's research played a significant part in the reinterpretation of Bronze Age shields, and he has been an inspiration for further research such as the Bronze Age Combat Project. Now further research into how exactly those shields would have been used needs to be carried out.

Marion Uckelmann recorded and collated European Bronze Age shields as part of her doctoral research (Uckelmann 2012), before focussing on their manufacture and use. Having analysed all 86 European metal shields known from the Middle and Late Bronze Age, she worked in collaboration with traditional bronzesmith Neil Burridge to understand the genuine manufacturing process of Bronze Age shield. Metallography has suggested that sheet bronze was created by hammering out a thick cast metal disc until the desired surface area or material thickness was achieved. In order to avoid the brittleness of hammered bronze, the metal would have to be annealed frequently, after each hammering phase. It was estimated that, in order to produce a 60 cm diameter sheet, a 20 cm cast disc would require 200 hammering and annealing phases. Several shields display the signs of this hammering process (Uckelmann 2011, 189). The majority of these shields feature a rolled rim, occasionally comprising a metal wire for additional strength. In most cases, a grip consisting of rolled metal or a massive metal strap was attached with rivets. There is also frequent evidence for loops or tabs, used to attach a piece of string to carry the shield on one's back (*ibid.*).

Uckelmann claims that, on the whole, few traces of use-wear have been identified. There is some evidence that suggests contacts with spear and swords, however, the marks are only interpreted visually, without comparison to experimental data (*ibid.*, 193-4).

The author concludes the article by suggesting that experimental research into the use and use-wear of shields needs to be carried out (*ibid.*, 195). These tests have now been carried out as part of the same wider project as my research, and will be referred to later in this chapter.

As research into Bronze Age weaponry had previously been dominated by the sword, Kate Anderson (2011) set out to investigate the ways in which Late Bronze Age spearheads in Britain could have been used. Use-wear analysis was carried out on 40 % of a total of 220 Late Bronze Age spearheads discovered in northern Britain. Apart from Molloy (2006) who suggested a short spear shaft similar to that of the Zulu *assegai*, most authors had previously interpreted spears simply as thrusting and throwing weapons, without basing their assumption on physical evidence (Anderson 2011, 599). As only six European Late Bronze Age spear shafts are known, all of which exceed 143 cm in length, this does not preclude the existence of shorter specimens. The 89 spearheads included in Anderson's study were examined for the six types of cutting edge wear marks described by Bridgford (2000), which were identified on 31 % of the specimens. Evidence for work-hardening of the cutting edges was discovered on 58 % of the spearheads, whilst only 19 % displayed any form of tip damage. A set of experiments with two different aims was designed. The first aim was to throw and thrust replica spears onto leather and metal shields to assess whether this would result in tip damage. If tip damage was created, this would in turn mean that the lack of tip damage on the original spearheads implies that these weapons were not predominantly thrown and thrust. As the edge damage observed on original spearheads was comparable to that recorded on swords by Bridgford, the second aim was to assess the methods of spear use by employing them in a sword-like manner, hafted onto a short shaft and wielded with one hand (Anderson 2011, 600). Based on originals discovered in Scotland and Ireland, a number of replica spearheads, a replica sword, a metal and a leather shield were manufactured to use in the experiment. The long leaf-shaped replica spearheads were modelled on the most commonly found spearhead in northern Britain, Class V (Coles 1959-60). Each 190 g heavy spearhead consisted of a 90 % Cu, 9 % Sn, and 1 % Pb alloy and was cast in a sand mould. The edges were work hardened and annealed twice. Ash shafts of two different lengths, 150 cm for throwing and 78 cm for slashing, were used. The spearheads were wedged on and secured with a small tack. After the experiment, 13 randomly selected spearheads were taken for hardness testing. The results revealed that the modern replicas were, despite the work hardening, slightly softer than comparable originals, suggesting that there is a discrepancy between ancient and modern manufacturing techniques, and that the replicas would be more prone to sustaining damage (Anderson 2011, 601-2). Working on the hypothesis that the type of damage sustained is linked to different factors including the type of strike, the angle, the mode of defence, and the

defending material, the experiment combined these factors into 30 different combat actions. Each action was twice repeated. A freshly slaughtered pig was also used to simulate human flesh, and strikes with the sword and the spears were executed to its shoulders, throat, legs and body (ibid., 603). During the experiment, it quickly transpired that through percussion alone a spear strike could not cause damage effectively. Used in a “whipping” or draw-cut motion, however, the spears were able to create deep, cleaving incisions in the pig’s carcass with ease (ibid.). Percussive strikes also significantly increased the risk of damaging the spear, and five shafts were fractured in this way during the experiment. Anderson also discovered an additional wear mark, termed “flattening”, which was created when the cutting edge of a spearhead struck a blunt metal object. Only two out of thirty strikes involving throwing or thrusting created tip damage, thus suggesting that the absence of tip damage on originals does not indicate that spears were not used in such ways (ibid., 604). The experiments confirmed that spears could be used effectively in a sword-like manner, at least when mounted on the short shaft. Longer shafts proved to be too unwieldy in close-quarter combat, tangling in the opponent’s legs and arms, requiring constant shifting of both hands and creating a significant risk to fellow combatants (ibid., 605). Comparing patterns of wear marks identified on originals with those created during the experiment, there appears to be a distinct discrepancy between the two, and three of the seven types of wear marks were not recreated at all (ibid., 606). It also transpired that, in most cases, the type and angle of movement had no effect on the damage. Instead, the material of the defending object seemed to be decisive (ibid., 605-6).

Anderson successfully recreated some of the wear marks discovered on original spearheads, which closely resemble those discovered on swords from the same period. She demonstrated that short-shafted spears could be used in a sword-like manner, as suggested by Molloy (2006), and that these weapons were most effective when executing “whipping” draw-cut motions. As her use-wear analysis methodology was based on that by Bridgford (2000), it has the same issue with broad wear mark definition as discussed earlier in this chapter. In fact, Anderson herself discovered a new type of wear which she termed “flattening”. Analysis of the replica spearheads has shown that there is a discrepancy between ancient and modern manufacturing techniques, resulting in softer cutting edges and potentially inauthentic replicas. No information about the manufacturing of the sword or shields is given. Based on Uckelmann (2011), it can be assumed that the metal shield, responsible for a significant amount of wear on the spearheads, was unauthentic, thus biasing the results and interpretation. As only some of the wear marks identified on original spearheads could be

recreated, further tests should be conducted to gain a fuller understanding of how these weapons could have been used.

Christian Horn (2015) analysed the use-wear on 63 Swedish Period I spearheads, to assess whether they were used as weapons and to understand how combat and warfare contributed to “change” in the Scandinavian Bronze Age. Bearing in mind a potentially biased archaeological record through varying burial practices, the spear seems to be the prevalent weapon of the Scandinavian Bronze Age, and thus demands a re-evaluation of its uses, challenging more traditional views of spears as hunting tools (Mercer 2006, 131), which could only be used for throwing and thrusting (Osgood 1998, 91; Osgood & Monks 2000, 22) and were deemed inappropriate for combat (Harding 2007, 76). Following his previously described use-wear analysis methodology (Horn 2013), Horn determined that 87 % of the analysed spearheads display use-wear. Whilst notches and nicks in the cutting edges were the most frequently observed damage, 41 % of the spearheads also displayed blow marks on the body of the spearhead. Horn suggests that this damage was the result of the spears being used in a fencing style (Horn 2015, 203-4). Tip pressure occurred on 30 % of the examined spearheads, although this figure may be biased, as 41 % have a fractured tip thus preventing analysis. Evidence for repair, mostly grinding, was found on 79 % of the specimens (*ibid.*, 204), although it must be said that Horn’s definition of repair marks is extremely vague, and especially grinding could also be a result of the manufacturing process. From all this, Horn concludes that spears were employed in combat and were generally used on more than one occasion. Bronze Age spearfighters would have combined slashing and thrusting attacks, and potentially used their spears in a sword-like manner (*ibid.*). Following a discussion about ornamentation on different spearheads, Horn proposes that there could have been a gradual change in fighting techniques towards a fencing style as the Bronze Age progressed, which homogeneously occurred in a wider geographic area and was used for swords and spears. Despite primarily being used as functional weapons, an increase in ornamentation might suggest that the meaning of spears also increased over time (*ibid.*, 210). Casting the problematics of Horn’s use-wear analysis methodology aside (see Horn 2013), this research lacks comparable experimental data, and as such, any interpretation of the wear marks is completely hypothetical. Horn’s final interpretation of the shift in fighting styles is based on a marginal difference in the amount of tip damage observed on two different types of spearheads (Horn 2015, 204). This hypothesis is based on a marginal difference observed on a very small number of spearheads and must therefore be seen sceptically.

Criticising that previous use-wear studies of copper-alloy objects had not taken the material properties of the metal into account, Horn and von Holstein (2017) set out to investigate the influence of the copper-alloy on the creation and preservation of wear marks. They further argue that a lack of visible wear marks cannot be used to interpret the analysed object as purely ceremonial (ibid., 90). Discussing three major factors, namely the consequences of plastic deformation, repair and corrosion, the authors demonstrate how consideration of the copper-alloy properties could change previous interpretations of wear marks. Following a discussion of the creation of v-notches, and how one impact can lead to a variety of related types of damage, the authors argue that theories about the overall usage of weapons are biased by fractured specimens. An example of this are spears and swords from Period I of the Nordic Bronze Age, of which 50-74 % fractured and could have displayed combat marks on the missing pieces (ibid., 92-3). Repairing of copper-alloy weapons causes a change in the mechanical properties of the affected area, thus creating reduced mark shapes when new damage occurs. Furthermore, ancient repairs were designed to remove the wear traces, thus complicating analysis by modern researchers (ibid., 93-4). The level of corrosion on a copper-alloy object is influenced by a variety of factors, including the soil composition, climate, vegetation, and human activity, and varies significantly, often very locally. No direct link between the rate of corrosion and any particular factor of soil composition could be found (ibid., 95). Corrosion also frequently affects different parts of an object unequally, and likely occurs in thin sections of the metal, such as the cutting edges. The level of corrosion on each object must therefore be assessed individually, and adjustments have to be made when interpreting them as part of a range of objects (ibid., 96, 98). Horn and von Holstein have provided an insight into the influence the mechanical properties of copper-alloy objects can have on their interpretation. Most crucially, researchers have to consider how fractured and incomplete specimens as well as corrosion alter their understanding of the object.

3.2.5 Achievements and limitations of previous research

The review of recent experimental and metalwork analysis literature demonstrates the achievements of other authors' research. Kienlin & Ottaway (1998) were the first to employ use-wear analysis on copper-alloy objects, thus pioneering an entirely new approach to the study of prehistoric metalwork. They combined wear analysis with experimental archaeology to justify their results. Following their lead, other authors have developed and published different approaches to metalwork wear analysis (e.g. Bridgford 2000; Higgins 2010; Anderson 2011; Brandherm 2011; Dolfini 2011; Mödinger 2011; O'Flaherty 2007; O'Flaherty et al. 2011; Horn 2013) and mark terminologies (Bridgford 2000; Higgins 2010; Anderson 2011; Brandherm 2011; Dolfini 2011; Molloy 2011; O'Flaherty 2007; O'Flaherty

et al. 2011; Horn 2013). O’Flaherty et al. (2011) have demonstrated that different types of marks can sometimes be created by the same action. Experiential and experimental approaches have yielded insightful results. Kristiansen (2002) was able to demonstrate that the short handle and shoulders of Bronze Age swords could be held and controlled, contrary to the common belief that these swords were unsuitable for combat. A draw-cut motion, in which the cutting edge of a blade is pulled along the opponent’s flesh to create a deep incision, has proven to be very effective with swords and rapiers (Molloy 2007; 2008; 2010) as well as short-shafted spears wielded in a sword-like manner (Anderson 2011). Bronze Age halberds have proven to be functional weapons (O’Flaherty 2007; O’Flaherty et al. 2011), which, amongst other techniques, could have been used to “hook” the opponent (Brandherm 2003; Horn 2013). Due to the high risk of sustaining damage to copper-alloy weapons, it has been suggested that material preservation would have been of utmost importance, and that most combat related wear marks are either accidental or the result of a desperate effort to save one’s life (Horn 2013).

From the review it also transpires, however, that many research approaches show clear limitations. In order to advance our knowledge and conduct conclusive research, it is imperative to identify these limitations and act accordingly to overcome these. The following paragraphs will outline the major gaps in the literature.

As Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martin-Lerma state, the quality of many experimental studies is notoriously poor (Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martin-Lerma 2015, 174-5). Replicas used in the tests are frequently not genuine, with differing alloy composition and varying degrees of post-casting treatment (e.g. Molloy 2008; 2009). In some cases, the field tests are not to experimental standards, and do not follow methodical approaches (e.g. Kristiansen 2002; Molloy 2008; O’Flaherty 2007). Those tests that can be regarded as experimental are generally lab-based, and are totally removed from real-life situations (e.g. Bridgford 2000; Molloy 2007; 2008; O’Flaherty 2007; O’Flaherty et al. 2011).

Likewise, the approaches to metalwork wear analysis are diverse and consistently poor. Recording is carried out to varying degrees of detail, and often objects are only examined with the naked eye (e.g. Kristiansen 2002; O’Flaherty 2007; O’Flaherty et al. 2011; Brandherm 2011). The main issue, however, lies with inconsistent and imprecise terminology for wear marks. In many cases, the descriptions of individual marks are too broad, summarising a variety of shapes and sizes under one term (e.g. Kienlin & Ottaway 1998; Bridgford 2000; Kristiansen 2002; Higgins 2010; Molloy 2011; Mödlinger 2011; O’Flaherty et al. 2011; Brandherm 2011; Dolfini 2011; Horn 2013; Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martin-Lerma 2015). Without precise definition of each and every type of mark, recognition and

interpretation will necessarily be biased. If retrospectively it transpires that different types of marks are caused by essentially the same action (compare O'Flaherty et al. 2011), these can be summarised in the aftermath, but research should never commence from the conclusion.

Finally, in most cases, the use of weaponry has been interpreted based solely on the results of either experimental archaeology or metalwork wear analysis, without consideration of the other. However, in order to gain conclusive evidence about the ways prehistoric weapons were used, controlled methodical experiments have to be combined with sophisticated metalwork wear analysis, as will be described in the next section.

3.3 Methodology

Considering the limitations of previous experimental approaches and metalwork wear analysis, it was decided to create a new methodology, develop both research approaches and employ them in combination in order to understand how Bronze Age sword fighting was conducted. It was deemed important to develop a methodology that can be employed to analyse a variety of prehistoric weapons and is not just restricted to the study of swords, in order to make the study replicable and relevant to the entire field.

3.3.1 *Metalwork wear analysis*

The two main criticisms of previous metalwork wear analysis approaches are a) the recording methodology, or in some cases the lack thereof, and b) the poor detail and inconsistency of wear mark terminology. Additionally, mark terminology should derive from analysis of original artefacts, rather than be based on the results of an experiment, as the latter could lead to confirmation bias (“seeing what you want to see”) when interpreting the finds. In turn, interpretation that is solely based on experimental data, and not confirmed through analysis of originals, is also problematic, as the results can only ever be hypothetical.

Lab-based metalwork wear analysis should be carried out following the guidelines published by Dolfini (2011, 1042) and consist of the following:

1. Objects are to be photographed, measured, weighed and described.
2. A visual examination with the naked eye is to be carried out, and all macroscopically visible traces must be recorded. The level of visibility and corrosion must also be assessed, which varies in accordance with the aim of the analysis, and ultimately remains subjective.
3. Microscopic examination at various degrees of magnification must then be carried out on the relevant sections of the object. Varying light sources should be employed to make marks visible. Especially side lighting can be useful to detect faint traces.
4. A mounted camera is then used to take high-resolution micrographs of all traces, and their precise location and classification is recorded on a data sheet and sketched on a drawing. These are then cross-referenced with unique ID numbers.

As no universally accepted terminology exists for metalwork wear marks, the terms and definitions used for the project are based on my own analysis of 110 Bronze Age swords (described in detail in Chapters 5 and 6 in this thesis) and the literature. To prevent misinterpretation, it was deemed imperative to describe each type of mark individually, rather than summarising different shapes under one general term. It must be said that the following list is comprehensive, yet by no means complete, as analysis of a single new sword might unveil previously undescribed mark types. The list has also been developed based on sword

analysis, and although certain marks will most definitely be represented on other artefact types, there will be a lack of relation to other objects such as spears or axes. A preliminary list of wear marks is currently being published (Hermann et al. in press), which has been updated for the purpose of this research.

Mark	Description	Literature	Image
Wear Marks			
Sharp Notch	V-shaped mark in the cutting edge of a weapon. Consists of two flanks and a cusp.	Similar to v-notches in Horn (2013, 22), O'Flaherty et al. (2011, 43) and Molloy (2011, 76).	
Round Notch	U-shaped mark in the cutting edge of a weapon.	Similar to u-shaped notch (Horn 2011, 76).	
Wide-Angled Notch	V-shaped mark with a cusp angle greater than 90°.	Similar to "wide v-notch" (O'Flaherty et al. 2011, 9).	
Toothed Notch	Notch-type mark with a characteristic metal thorn protruding from the cusp.	These marks have never been described in the literature before.	

<p>Double Notch</p>	<p>W-shaped mark similar to toothed notch but with a wider profile.</p>	<p>As above.</p>	
<p>Straight Graze</p>	<p>Similar to sharp notch but with one straight flank noticeably longer than the other.</p>	<p>Separated from the notches identified by authors such as Molloy, Horn and O'Flaherty, as their profiles are different, and so is the nature of the impact that created them.</p>	
<p>Curved Graze</p>	<p>Graze but with curved flanks.</p>	<p>As above.</p>	
<p>Elongated Graze</p>	<p>Shallow graze with one considerably elongated flank.</p>	<p>As above.</p>	
<p>Irregular Graze</p>	<p>Graze with irregular flanks.</p>	<p>As above.</p>	

Indentation	Mark with long, shallow, rounded impact profile.	Similar to "shallow indentation" (Horn 2013, 32), "bowed" (Bridgford 2000, 105),	
Rectangular Indentation	Similar to indentation but with a rectangular or trapezoidal impact profile.	These marks have never been described in the literature before.	
Flattening	A very slight compression of the cutting edge.	As above.	
Micronotching	Tiny marks created during secondary rebounding impacts. Considerably smaller than normal marks and difficult to detect.	Similar to "double-impact marks" in O'Flaherty et al. (2011, 49).	
Blow Mark	Impact marks of various shapes on the flat side of the blade.	Similar to Horn (2013, 22).	
Striation	Scratched impact mark on the flat side of the blade.	Similar to Horn (2013, 22).	

<p>Compression Curling</p>	<p>Material displacement where the cutting edge is compressed and curls over.</p>	<p>Similar to Horn (2013, 22).</p>	
<p>Bulge</p>	<p>Material displacement where the cutting edge is physically pushed sideways to form a bulge.</p>	<p>Similar to Horn (2013, 22).</p>	
<p>Rippling</p>	<p>Material compressed to such an extent that ripples are formed.</p>	<p>Similar to Horn (2013, 22).</p>	
<p>Fissure</p>	<p>A tear in the material caused by excess stress on the metal.</p>	<p>Similar to Horn (2013, 22).</p>	
<p>Fracture</p>	<p>Material failure where part of the weapon has broken off.</p>	<p>Similar to Horn (2013, 32).</p>	
<p>Tip Pressure</p>	<p>Deformation of the tip of a weapon due to intense impact pressure.</p>	<p>After Horn (2013, 22), Molloy (2007) and Uckelmann (2012, 194).</p>	

Bending	A large-scale plastic deformation affecting part or the whole length of a weapon along its lateral axis.	Similar to Horn (2013, 32).	No image available.
Twisting	Plastic deformation along the longitudinal axis of a weapon.	Similar to Horn (2013, 32).	No image available.

Manufacturing Marks		
Grinding and polishing marks to clean the surface of the weapon following casting	Patterns of striations on the body of the sword.	After Horn (2013, 33-34).
Sharpening marks	Patterns of striations on the blade edge.	After Horn (2013, 33-34).
Hammering marks	Patterns of depressions – the exact shape depends on the hammerhead and force used, but they are most frequently elongated.	After Horn (2013, 34).
Post-depositional Marks		
Marks cutting through the patina	Striations through the patina or alteration/corrosion products covering the object.	After Horn (2013, 33-34).

Table 3.1 – Metalwork wear analysis marks as observed on original Bronze Age swords from Britain and Italy.

The terminology used to describe swords is largely based on Burgess & Colquhoun (1988, 3), but has been slightly expanded for this research. Coin terminology has been introduced to describe the two different flat sides of the sword; the flat with the accession number painted on is referred to as *obverse*, the other side as *reverse*. The cutting edges are referred to as *left* and *right* in relation to the obverse with the blade tip pointing downwards (see Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 – Sword terminology, expanded and updated after Burgess & Colquhoun (1988, 3).

3.3.2 *Combat experiments*

As discussed earlier in this chapter, two contrasting combat experiment approaches were previously employed: field tests and laboratory tests. The latter offer the distinct advantage of a controlled environment, in which all factors contributing to wear formation can be monitored, recorded, and understood. The drawback is that the complexity of human behaviour cannot be reproduced adequately by a rig or robotic device. In contrast, the former provide us with an opportunity to experiment with objects in seemingly ‘authentic’ conditions, but control of wear formation processes can be poor. Problematically, ‘authentic’ combat tests need to be grounded in a predetermined body of knowledge regarding use of the weapons, which is normally provided by personal experience of the researcher, or mediaeval combat manuals. Experimental combat field tests can be designed with different research methodologies, each with their own strengths and weaknesses. Experiential experiments, consisting of actual continuous periods of fighting, such as those carried out by Anderson (2011) and Molloy (2004; 2006; 2007; 2008), are very much experienced-based and body-centred. The latter, in particular, produce results based on the researcher’s experiences and personal feelings about how the weapons were used correctly. Valuable insights into the capabilities of prehistoric weapons can be drawn from this, however, these types of field tests lack the control and recordability of other experimental methodologies. Understanding which wear marks are related to which specific actions is almost impossible when fighting is conducted for an extended period (Crellin et al., in press). The interpretation of original swords based on experience alone, rather than through comparison with evidential wear marks, is therefore always purely hypothetical. Alternatively, tests can be designed based on historical fighting manuscripts, and information from these can be used as an analogy to interpret the use of prehistoric weapons, even without experimental testing (e.g. Heath 2009; Mödlinger 2011). However, not only are historical sources often cryptic, partial, and open to innumerable interpretative problems; they also discuss historically contingent combat styles, which cannot be projected back into the prehistoric past uncritically. Bronze Age copper-alloy weapons have entirely different material properties to their mediaeval iron predecessors, and as such likely behave differently under stress, thus implementing different use. The same issues with reproducibility and recording of the wear marks created during a continuous fighting sequence remain. Studying and practicing different historical fighting styles, however, equips the researcher with a portfolio of combat knowledge, and as such enables them to design better experiments. Bearing the already known capabilities and limitations of prehistoric weapons in mind, historic fighting manuals can be adapted to explore and develop new areas of combat research. For optimal control, recordability, and reproducibility, combat

experiments can be conducted split into individual, single actions. After each action the weapons can then be examined, and any wear marks can be recorded, thus creating a direct link between action and mark. The drawbacks with the method are that the initial decision as to which actions will be carried out is also based on either personal experience or historical manuscript, and that individual actions are not representative of actual combat, thus lacking some of the dynamics of real fighting. To limit the distortions caused by either type of test, it was decided to undertake two separate weapon experiments. In the first, continuous combat sequences were broken down into discrete actions to be recorded individually. In the second, the project strove to recreate a realistic Bronze Age sword fight based on the combat techniques described in a historical European fighting manual from the Middle Ages, broken down into its individual plays. This approach combines the benefit of fully recordable, if rather crude, weapon tests with embodied experiments, in which the mechanical properties of the weapons can meaningfully be understood in relation to the biomechanical properties of the combatants. In order to be as scientifically reproducible as possible, the field tests must follow a strict experimental protocol, which must be predefined, but can be altered accordingly during the experiment to accommodate varying circumstances and developments on the day. Experiments should be designed with the aim to reproduce the marks found on original artefacts. Prior to the experiment, all tested equipment must be thoroughly examined for previous wear traces and recorded as original condition. The experiment itself must be divided into individually identifiable sections, either single actions or sequences, after each of which the equipment must be thoroughly examined and any traces of wear recorded with as much accuracy as the conditions allow, and always noted in relation to the sequence numbering. Macroscopic photography, drawings, measuring mark distance from the tip, and note taking have shown to be most effective. After the experiment, the artefacts must then be taken to the lab and full metalwork wear analysis should be carried out. The marks must be termed in relation to those identified on comparable originals.

When using replica artefacts, these should be manufactured to the highest authenticity possible. This requires an in-depth understanding of the original material, especially concerning alloy composition and manufacturing process. As some degree of deviation from the original pieces is inevitable, even if only caused by the inconsistency of prehistoric metalwork, this must be accounted for in the final interpretation of the data. Finally, the data created during the experiments should be cross-referenced with metalwork wear analysis of originals to interpret the way prehistoric weapons were used.

The sword tests carried out for this research were conducted as part of the wider Bronze Age Combat Project, which was launched in 2013 in order to explore late 2nd millennium BC

fighting styles in Europe. It investigates uses of Bronze Age swords, shields and spears based on an innovative combination of wear analysis and tests with replica weapons. The project aims to understand how prehistoric bronze weapons were used, in what kind of combat situations, and with what weapon strikes and bodily engagements. One of its main objectives is to explore the possibility of linking distinctive combat marks with specific uses of the weapons, including strikes, parries, stabs, and throws. The project unfolded following three main steps. Firstly, rigorous field experiments were designed, in which the replica weapons could be tested against other weapons, replica shields made of leather, bronze and wood, and static targets. Secondly, the wear marks generated in the tests were examined microscopically, catalogued based on a coherent nomenclature, and recorded both graphically and photographically. Thirdly, archaeological weapons from various museums in the United Kingdom were examined for wear marks, paying special attention to those matching the experimental marks. My research solely focusses on the tests carried out with swords, but as they were used against a variety of other weapons reference to these will also be made. The first experiment consisting of discrete, individually recordable combat actions is described in the remainder of this chapter. Chapter 4 discusses the actualistic experiments of the second tests.

3.4 Experiment

3.4.1 *The Bronze Age Combat Project*

Figure 3.2 – First field tests in 2013 at Bede’s World, Jarrow. From left to right: Rachel Crellin, Andrea Dolfini, Raphael Hermann and Jon Allison.

Extensive field tests had to be conducted to deliver conclusive data for this experiment. Due to funding issues, the extensive amount of data following each experiment, and continuously developing ideas for further experiments, the tests were staggered over five years. After initial planning and organisation, the first three days of field experiments were carried out at Bede’s World, Jarrow, in the summer of 2013, with the following participants: Dr Andrea Dolfini (project leader), Raphael Hermann (experienced fencer and sword fighter), Jon Allison (former soldier trained in tactical small group combat), Rachel Crellin (in charge of on-site recording), Dave Horan (in charge of on-site filming and photography), Dr Thea Ravasi (logistics and IT) and Dr Kate Anderson (expert on Bronze Age spear combat). On two days, the researchers were also joined by media teams who filmed and interviewed various participants.

August 2014 saw the introduction of Dr Benjamin Roberts of Durham University, Dr Marion Uckelmann (renowned expert for Bronze Age shields), and Dr Quanyu Wang (archaeometallurgist at the British Museum), who joined the project and provided a replica rapier and copper-alloy shield which were also tested at Bede’s World.

The third set of field experiments was conducted in July 2016, this time at Durham Botanical Gardens as Bede's World had been forced to close. A replica wooden shield, provided by Dr Marion Uckelmann, was the focus of attention on the day, and was tested against a variety of contemporary weapons.

A vast variety of actions were undertaken with swords, spears, and shields, but only the marks created on swords (alas in combat against all other weapons) are discussed in this thesis.

The kit

Five swords, four spears, and four shields were used in the combat tests, based on extant British and continental templates. With exception of the wooden shield, they were all manufactured by Neil Burrige (www.bronze-age-craft.com) using traditional casting and working methods. To avoid discrepancies in the test results, all metal weapons were cast with the same 12 % tin-bronze alloy (compare Gutiérrez-Sáez & Soriano-Llopis 2008). This alloy composition sits near the upper end of the spectrum documented for British Late Bronze Age swords (Northover 1988, 133); it was chosen as it improves the fluidity of the cast, and reduces the risk of potentially dangerous casting defects developing within the objects. The swords were cast in heated two-piece sand moulds from the hilt, resulting in a better and stronger cast in the blade and tip of the sword, but potentially weakening the hilt (compare Mödlinger 2011, 154-5). A single sequence of work-hardening with a bronze hammer and anvil was then applied to the cutting edges, and they were sharpened to a razor finish. Finally, oak hilt plates and pommels were added to four swords, while the fifth had the hilt and pommel cast in solid bronze.

Figure 3.3 – SW1 type Wilburton replica sword. Image by RJ Crellin.

SW1 is a Wilburton type sword. Swords of this kind mark the first stage of the British Late Bronze Age (Wilburton Phase, c. 1150-975 BC); they are found all over Britain with a special concentration in the South-West (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 40ff).

Length: 562 mm. Weight: 511.5 g.

Figure 3.4 – SW2 type Ewart Park replica sword. Image by RJ Crellin.

SW2 is a Ewart Park sword. These swords are found in great numbers throughout the British Isles and are dated to the later part of the Late Bronze Age (Ewart Park Period, c. 925-800 BC) (ibid., 55ff.).

Length: 658 mm. Weight: 701.4 g.

Figure 3.5 – SW3 type Carp's Tongue replica sword. Image by RJ Crellin.

SW3 is a Carp's Tongue sword, a type mostly found along the Atlantic façade, particularly in Brittany and South-East England; they are generally dated to the later part of the Late Bronze Age (Ha B2/B3 and Bronze Final III, c. 950-800 BC) (ibid., 108-11).

Length: 745 mm. Weight: 761.5 g.

Figure 3.6 – SW4 Kemenczei type S *Vollgriffschwert* replica sword. Image by RJ Crellin.

SW4 is a European continental sword, a *Vollgriffschwert* belonging to Kemenczei's type S. These swords are mostly found in Hungary and are dated to the Ha A1 period (c. 1200-1000 BC) (after Kemenczei 1991, 47).

Length: 595 mm. Weight: 938.2 g.

Figure 3.7 – SW5 rapier replica, bent by experiments. Image by RJ Crellin.

SW5 is a Middle Bronze Age Group IV rapier replica dating to c. 1300-1150 BC (after Burgess & Gerloff 1981, 62ff.). Although this weapon originates from an earlier part of the Bronze Age, the slightly different blade shape was deemed as too insignificant to bias the results.

Length: 658 mm. Weight: 565 g.

The spearheads belong to Group 11 in Davis's (2015) catalogue of British Late Bronze Age spearheads. Davis terms this group "generic", as these spearheads are the most numerous during the Late Bronze Age. They are a development of the basal-looped spearheads, where the loops are lost and replaced with two peg holes in the socket (Davis 2015, 42).

Both types of spearhead were mounted on seasoned ash shafts of c. 110 cm and c. 180 cm in length. Ash is the most common species of wood found in the shafts of prehistoric spearheads from Britain (Davis 2006, 95). Discussing the results of the various spear tests conducted would lie beyond the scope of my research, but reference will be made when swords and spears were employed against each other.

Figure 3.8 – SP1 and SP2 spearhead replicas. Image by RJ Crellin.

SP1 and SP2 are replicas of short Group 11C "leaf-shaped blade" spearheads, dating from 1200-800 BC (ibid., 43).

Figure 3.9 – SP3 and SP4 spearhead replicas. Image by RJ Crellin.

SP3 and SP4 are replicas of long Group 11A "flame-shaped blade" spearheads, dating from 1300-1000/900 BC (ibid., 44).

Four different shields were also used in the experiments, made of leather, wood, and copper-alloy. Again, discussing the shield tests at length would go beyond the scope of my research, but reference will be made where needed.

Figure 3.10 – Cloonbrin type leather shield replica. Image by RJ Crellin.

The two leather shields are replicas of the only surviving leather shield, of type Herzsprung, from Cloonbrin, Co. Longford, Ireland, which was dated to 1134-971 cal. BC (Uckelmann 2012, no. 85). They were each created out of one piece of vegetable-tanned leather hide, first shrunk in hot water, then beaten into a wooden mould, dried and eventually coated in beeswax. For additional strength, a leather boss was sewn onto one of the shields (see Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.11 – Replica bronze shield (front and back) after types Athenry-Eynsham and Nipperwiese. Image by RJ Crellin.

A copper-alloy shield, based on specimens of types Athenry-Eynsham and Nipperwiese, dating to c. 1300-1000 BC (Uckelmann 2012, no. 24), was also created. Consisting of 12 % tin bronze, the shield was hammered out from a 22.7 cm diameter and 2.3 cm thick cast blank disc. This blank was worked on in 54 cycles of hammering, annealing at 600 °C, and quenching in water. Each cycle took one to one-and-a-half hours to complete. The final sheet measured c. 37.6 cm in diameter and was left in the annealed state, with a thickness range between 0.8-1.2 mm, and a final weight of 1200 g. To form the rim, the edge of the disc was hammered over a bronze edge to bend it, and a 3.2 mm bronze wire (commercial bronze wire, 5 % tin) was inserted. A wooden former and a further 20 annealing phases were necessary to create the rim ribs, small bosses and central boss. A final thorough phase of annealing and quenching took place before the tubular handle was riveted onto the back (Figure 3.11). This was the first time a replica shield was made from an authentic, hammered-out blank, rather than modern bronze sheet.

Figure 3.12 – Wooden alder shield based on Cloonlara specimen.
Image by RJ Crellin.

Jake Newman, a Durham University archaeology student and skilled woodworker, carved a wooden shield (Figure 3.12) out of seasoned alder imported from Germany using traditional Bronze Age copper-alloy tools. The shield is based on the Cloonlara specimen from Ireland, dating to 1633-1164 cal BC (Uckelmann 2012, no. 83).

Considering that the team was to conduct live combat experiments with potentially life-threatening sharp weaponry, the initial wide-ranging experimental protocol was designed to fulfil our experimental needs before having an extensive consultation with a health and safety

professional. The aim was to make the desired experiments safe, rather than design safe experiments. Due to the risk of serious bodily injury to the combatants, however, full Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) had to be worn for all combat actions. This consisted of thick protective gambesons, steel-clad gauntlets covering the hands and forearms, and

Figure 3.13 – Practising combat actions with wooden training swords wearing full PPE.

fencing masks and/or safety goggles. Prior to each action, the weapons were checked for damage that could result in unexpected behaviour during combat. Following the protocol, each action was thoroughly discussed until both combatants were completely aware of what was about to happen. The actions were then practised with wooden swords and mimed with the replicas (Figure 3.13). All observers and recorders had to maintain a minimum safety distance to avoid injury from any unexpected circumstances, such as splintering or broken weapons.

Based on my personal experience in historical sword fighting and sports fencing, an extensive experimental protocol was created based on a number of strikes and parries. The research design was predicated on the belief that, during combat, weapons of different kinds would have encountered each other. Therefore, we tested sword against sword, sword against spear (including the shaft), and sword against shield. To allow for chronological consistency, tests were solely carried out with weapons that would have been in use at the same time. The sword-against-sword and spear actions comprised four strikes and six parries each (Table 3.2).

Strikes	
Leg strike	The attacker swings the weapon with its tip facing downwards in a low-angled arc to strike the other weapon near the defender’s legs, in the region of the knee area. The attack is parried with the defending sword pointing downwards at an angle.
Hip strike	The attacker swings the weapon horizontally in an arc to strike the defender’s weapon near the hip. The defending sword is held almost vertically, pointing upwards in front of the hip. To counter the height of the blow the defender has to crouch slightly.
Shoulder strike	The attacker swings the weapon in a diagonal arc from above to strike the defender’s weapon near the shoulder or neck. The defender holds the weapon diagonally in front of the body, slightly raised towards the shoulder, with the tip pointing upwards towards the shoulder opposite the sword hand, to cover the upper body.

Strikes	
Head strike	An overhead strike, coming straight down onto the defender's weapon in the head area. The defending sword is held horizontally above the defender's head.

Parries	
Static edge parry	The defending weapon is held in place to block the attacker's strike with the cutting edge.
Static flat parry	The defending weapon is held in place to block the attacker's strike with the flat of the blade.
Kinetic edge parry	The defending weapon is moving away from the defender's body, forcefully meeting the incoming strike with the cutting edge.
Kinetic flat parry	The defending weapon is moving away from the defender's body, forcefully meeting the incoming strike with the flat of the blade.
Dynamic edge parry	A kinetic parry carried out with so much force and momentum that it catches the attacking blade on the cutting edge and knocks it off its course. This parry may be best described as a weapon attack met by another weapon attack.
Dynamic flat parry	As per above but the parry is executed with the flat of the blade.

Table 3.2 – Strikes and parries tested within the Bronze Age Combat Project.

Due to the health and safety hazards associated with using a shield defensively against a full force attack, the above-mentioned protocol had to be modified. The risk of a person holding the shield was as deemed too high, and instead the shield target had to be mounted in front of hay bales or on wooden posts. Different strikes and slashing attacks were then executed to the front and the rim of the shield. Horizontal thrusts were also aimed to hit the shield boss and front to test penetration.

Although a great deal of research and preparation was carried out prior to designing the protocol, it soon transpired that the reality of the field experiment was slightly different to what we expected. The replica weapons were subject to much more substantial damage than expected. Dynamic parries frequently slightly bent the weapons, in one case to such an extent that the sword was rendered useless and unsafe to be used again. The large amount of damage prevented us from conducting as many strikes and repetitions as originally planned. Whilst it would occasionally have been possible to bend the swords back into their original shape, this would not only have had the potential to significantly alter their physical properties, thus biasing the comparability and repeatability of the experiment, but it would also have created an additional, uncalculatable risk to the combatants.

All experiments comprised static, kinetic, and dynamic parries (see Table 3.2) in order to replicate a range of potential situations that could create the wear marks observed on prehistoric swords. Static experiments might at first seem to be unhelpful as it is unlikely that, in a real combat situation, the defender would hold their weapon statically and allow it to be struck. However, these tests enabled effective examination and interpretation of weapon

damage based on objective experimental evidence. They also allowed me to compare our tests to the literature (compare Bridgford 2000; Molloy 2007; O’Flaherty et al. 2011). The dynamic tests conducted relate most clearly to what was considered to be a true combat situation, in which both combatants are engaging in full-force interpersonal violence and are actively using their weapons for attacking and defending. Separating out static, kinetic, and dynamic tests allowed me to examine the linkage between different marks and the conditions in which they were generated, and to test the conclusions arrived at by other researchers in a non-laboratory environment.

Working strike by strike and parry by parry, each action was individually filmed and photographed, and all marks thus generated were recorded photographically, with the location and shape of each mark being also noted and labelled. This allowed me to build direct linkages between specific combat moves and specific marks. It soon became apparent, however, that the protocol we as a team had originally devised was extremely ambitious, and in addition to the unforeseen severe damage inflicted on the weapons the recording turned out to be vastly time-consuming. We thus cut down on the number of repetitions in order to carry out a sufficient amount of tests on all weapons. The ultimate aim was to create a wide range of reference marks that can be used to interpret the marks found on original Bronze Age weapons. Although only a fraction of the original experimental protocol was carried out, the original numbering was retained during the recording and in this thesis.

3.4.2 *Sword vs. sword*

A total of 15 sword vs. sword actions were carried out by Jon, Andrea and myself. Despite me being left-handed, for reasons of consistency all strikes were carried out with the sword held in the right hand. For chronological consistency, only contemporary weapons were used against each other, i.e. SW1 vs SW4 and SW2 vs SW3.

1. Sword vs. sword attack, leg strike, full force, SW1 vs. SW4

1a. left, edge parry, static – SW1 attack, SW4 defend (Figure 3.14)

Figure 3.14 – 1a. leg strike with static edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.15 – 1a. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force. Sharp notch, 163 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.16 – 1a. SW4 defend, edge parry, static. Sharp notch, 186 mm from the tip.

1a. was a full force leg strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a static edge parry (Figure 3.14). Sharp notches were caused in both swords. The sharp notch in the attacking sword is directed downwards due to the sword tip facing downwards when catching the defending sword in an upward circular motion. There is some micronotching and material deformation in immediate proximity to the mark (Figure 3.15).

The sharp notch in the defending sword is rectangular to the cutting edge, but the material deformation visible on the left of the notch in the photograph indicates slight upwards directionality towards the hilt (Figure 3.16).

1c. left, edge parry, kinetic – SW1 attack, SW4 defend (Figure 3.17)

Figure 3.17 – 1c. leg strike with kinetic edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.18 – 1c. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force. Round notch, 206 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.19 – 1c. SW4 defend, edge parry, kinetic. Curved grazes, 333 mm from the tip.

1c. was a full force leg strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a kinetic edge parry (Figure 3.17). Rebounding caused a primary mark and secondary micronotching on both swords.

The initial impact caused a downwards directed round notch in the attacking sword. A micronotch further towards the hilt was then created by the rebound. Some material displacement has taken place at the borders of the round notch (Figure 3.18).

The defending sword displays two curved grazes in immediate proximity to each other, directed downwards towards the tip. This direction is caused as both swords were swung in an

upward arching motion. The initial impact mark penetrates clearly through the bevel line into the flat of the blade, whilst the secondary mark is much shallower (Figure 3.19).

1e. left, edge parry, dynamic – SW1 attack, SW4 defend (Figure 3.20)

Figure 3.20 – 1e. leg strike with dynamic edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.21 – 1e. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force. Curved graze, 123 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.22 – 1e. SW4 defend, edge parry, dynamic. Sharp notch, 204 mm from the tip.

1e. was a full force leg strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a dynamic edge parry (Figure 3.20). Executed with a force that is essentially that of two attacking strikes, a single mark was created on each sword.

The downward curved graze in the attacking sword is long and fairly deep, almost reaching the bevel line. A forceful countermovement of the defending sword lengthened the mark and gave it its shallow grazed appearance. The surface immediately surrounding the graze is disturbed due to the scraping contact with the defending cutting edge (Figure 3.21).

A deep sharp notch penetrating the width of the bevel line was created in the defending blade. Rectangular to the cutting edge, this mark does not display any directionality. Material

displacement bending the metal around the sharp notch is visible in both directions (Figure 3.22).

When both swords are connecting with what are essentially two attacking strikes, it appears that the swords move too fast to allow for a second rebounding contact. Instead, the dispelling energy causes the defending sword to graze along the attacking cutting edge, thus creating a long and deep graze.

1g. left, flat parry, static – SW1 attack, SW4 defend (Figure 3.23)

Figure 3.23 – 1g. leg strike with static flat parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.24 – 1g. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force. Indentation, 245-9 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.25 – 1g. SW4 defend, flat parry, static. Material displacement and striations, 315 mm from the tip.

1g. was a full force leg strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a static flat parry (Figure 3.23). In this case, the attacking sword struck the defending blade at a shallow angle on the cutting edge.

Upon first impact, the attacking sword SW1 struck SW4 on the flat of the blade near the cutting edge. The impact caused deep striations and material displacement on the blade and cutting edge of SW4. It appears as if the most force struck SW4 directly on the cutting edge, thus creating a fissure in the edge (Figure 3.25).

The initial shallow-angled impact caused an indentation on the cutting edge of the attacking sword. Two further, much shallower indentations, found in immediate proximity of the mark, were created when the cutting edge made contact with the rest of the blade flat of SW4 (Figure 3.24).

In this case, the defending sword failed to parry the attacking strike just with the flat of its blade. Instead, the sword must have been held with a slight rotation along the longitudinal axis, resulting in a parry with both the flat side and the cutting edge.

1i. left, flat parry, kinetic – SW1 attack, SW4 defend (Figure 3.26)

Figure 3.26 – 1i. leg strike with kinetic flat parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.27 – 1i. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force. Round notch, 76 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.28 – 1i. SW4 defend, flat parry, kinetic. Blow mark and striations, 146-54 mm from the tip.

1i. was a full force leg strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a kinetic flat parry (Figure 3.26). The attacking sword struck the defending on the central ridge and scraped upwards along the flat of the blade towards the hilt.

The prominent midrib on SW4 caused a round notch rectangular to the cutting edge on SW1. Compressed material on the right boundary of the mark indicates its directionality (Figure 3.27). Further towards the tip, the cutting edge of SW1 is slightly flattened.

A deep blow mark was created on the midrib of the defending sword. Several deep striations extend in a pattern from the blow mark on the flat of the blade towards one cutting edge (Figure 3.28).

The striations near the midrib on SW4 are likely the cause of the slight flattening on SW1. However, this flattening was only discovered upon microscopic analysis of SW1 in the lab, and could also have been caused by poor handling, moving, and storing of the sword.

1k. left, flat parry, dynamic – SW1 attack, SW4 defend (Figure 3.29)

Figure 3.29 – 1k. leg strike with flat parry causing SW4 to bend. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.30 – 1k. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force. Indentation, 236-40 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.31 – 1k. SW4 defend, flat parry, dynamic. Striations, 325 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.32 – Bending of SW4 after 1k.

1k. was a full force leg strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a dynamic flat parry (Figure 3.29). The extreme force behind what were essentially two attacking strikes caused the defending sword to bend, and rendered it unsuitable for further combat without repair.

The attacking sword struck SW4 on the midrib and proceeded to scrape along the flat of the blade. A long and deep striation, created by the initial impact on the flat of SW4, is followed by a pattern of broad striations which are extremely close together (Figure 3.31). These indicate the considerable force that acted on this narrow part of the blade of SW4 during the

time of contact. The fairly elastic copper-alloy composition reacted by giving in to the impact, resulting in the sword to be significantly bent (Figure 3.32).

The central ridge of SW4 created a small indentation and material displacement on the cutting edge of SW1. Slight flattening of the cutting edge can be found next to the mark further towards the hilt (Figure 3.30).

SW4 became unsuitable for further experiments after it was bent. For safety reasons, it was decided not to use this sword any further. An attempt to manually bend the sword back into shape was abandoned as the impact would have changed the material properties of the sword, thus making it impossible to predict how the sword would react to further forceful impacts, and potentially biasing the results. It is presumed that annealing, the process of reheating and cooling the metal to allow the molecular lattice to settle again, is needed to repair this sword. The little impact this action had on the cutting edge of SW1 proves the importance of work hardening the cutting edges.

At this point, it must also be said that I experienced great pain in the wrist upon every parry with the flat of the blade, despite wearing wrist supporting gauntlets. Consequently, it was decided to alter the experimental protocol and abandon further flat parries, to prevent both the destruction of further swords and injury to the wrists of the combatants.

3. Sword vs. sword attack, shoulder strike, full force, SW2 vs. SW3

3b. right, edge parry, static – SW2 attack, SW3 defend (Figure 3.33)

Figure 3.33 – 3b. shoulder strike with static edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.34 – 3b. SW2 attack, right, shoulder strike. Sharp notch, full force, 301 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.35 – 3b. SW3 defend, edge parry, static. Curved graze, 178 mm from the tip.

3b. was a full force shoulder strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a static edge parry (Figure 3.33).

A deep sharp notch with directionality towards the hilt was created on the attacking sword. Compressed swelling of the cusp and rippling has taken place around the mark. A number of small fissures are visible in the cusp (Figure 3.34).

A curved graze with directionality towards the hilt was created in the cutting edge of the defending sword. The attacking sword cut into the edge of SW3, scraping and deforming the material. As a result, material deformation in the form of a compressed swelling was created towards the upper left boundary of the mark (Figure 3.35).

This particular action yielded unexpected results. Instead of creating a mark directed towards the tip in the attacking sword, as was expected from the particular motion of the attack, the sharp notch is facing the opposite direction. On the defending sword, the mark is in the shape of a curved graze, suggesting that the sword was in motion rather than static. Speaking to the combatants, it transpired that a twisting motion in the attacker's wrist likely took place, causing SW2 to scoop this graze into the defending sword.

3d. right, edge parry, kinetic – SW2 attack, SW3 defend (Figure 3.36)

Figure 3.36 – 3d. shoulder strike with kinetic edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.37 – 3d. SW2 attack, right, shoulder strike full force. Sharp notch, primary mark 241 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.39 – SW3 defend, edge parry, kinetic. Round notch, 223 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.38 – 3d. SW2 attack, right, shoulder strike full force. Primary mark (right) and secondary micronotch (left) 246 mm from the tip.

3d. was a full force shoulder strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a kinetic edge parry (Figure 3.36). The force of the kinetic parry caused a rebound, creating a further clash with lower force resulting in a secondary mark.

A deep sharp notch directed towards the tip was created in the attacking sword. The impact caused material displacement in the forms of compression and rippling. Furthermore, a number of small fissures formed around the cusp of the notch (Figure 3.37). The rebound created a single micronotch 5 mm further towards the hilt. Some material displacement has taken place around its boundaries (Figure 3.38).

The round notch in the defending blade is also directed towards the tip and penetrates the bevel line. Its directionality was caused by the slight upward motion of the kinetic parry, as well as the slight angle at which the sword was held from the body. Some compression has taken place towards the right boundary of the notch. A small amount of copper-alloy chipped off near the cusp (Figure 3.39). Some evidence of micronotching was found in close proximity to the mark, but it was no longer possible to determine its exact origin.

3f. right, edge parry, dynamic – SW2 attack, SW3 defend (Figure 3.40)

Figure 3.40 – 3f. shoulder strike with dynamic edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.41 – 3f. SW2 attack, right, shoulder strike full force. Sharp notch, 296 mm from the tip (mark in red rectangle).

Figure 3.42 – 3f. SW3 defend, edge parry, dynamic. Curved graze, 153 mm from the tip.

3f. was a full force shoulder strikes executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a dynamic edge parry (Figure 3.40). Despite this action essentially being two attacking motions, only one mark was created on each sword. The directly adjoining mark stems from 36b., and its proximity is purely coincidental.

A sharp notch, almost rectangular to the cutting edge but with slight directionality towards the tip, was created in the cutting edge of SW2. Material displacement has taken place around the mark; the copper-alloy has curled to either side of the cutting edge (Figure 3.41).

A curved graze with directionality towards the hilt was created in the cutting edge of the defending sword. This directionality was caused by the downwards arching motion of the

dynamic parry. Some compression and swelling have occurred on the left boundary of the mark. A striation protruding from the cusp towards the hilt indicates that the sword was slightly twisted along the longitudinal axis upon impact (Figure 3.42). That twisting likely caused the curling observed on the attacking sword.

36. Sword vs. sword attack, shoulder strike, full force, SW3 vs. SW2 (Figure 3.43)

36a. left, edge parry, static – SW3 attack, SW2 defend

Figure 3.43 – 36a. shoulder strike with static edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.44 – 36a. SW3 attack, right, shoulder strike full force. Rectangular indentation, 282 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.45 – 36a. SW2 defend, edge parry, static. Sharp notch, 373 mm from the tip.

36a. was a full force shoulder strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a static edge parry (Figure 3.43).

A rectangular indentation was created in the attacking cutting edge of SW3. Rippling has occurred around the mark. The micronotching to the left of the indentation cannot be attributed to the action of 36a. with certainty (Figure 3.44).

The sharp notch in the defending sword penetrates deeply through the bevel line into the flat of the blade, and is directed towards the hilt. Plastic deformation of the material has occurred on the left boundary of the mark, which further caused a fissure (Figure 3.45). The curling was likely caused by a twisting motion along the lateral axis of either sword during impact.

36b. left, edge parry, kinetic – SW3 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.46)

Figure 3.46 – 36b. shoulder strike with kinetic edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.47 – 36b. SW3 attack, right, shoulder strike, full force. Round notch, 195 mm from the tip, and micronotch. Figure 3.48 – 36b. SW2 defend, edge parry, kinetic. Sharp notch, 298 mm from the tip.

36b. was a full force shoulder strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a kinetic edge parry (Figure 3.46). Deep marks were created in both cutting edges upon initial impact. Micronotching was created during the rebound.

The initial impact created a round notch with directionality towards the tip in the attacking cutting edge. Material displacement occurred around the notch. The copper-alloy was compressed, and swelled to a thick rippled ring around the notch. It appears as if the attacking sword made impact at a slightly twisted angle along the longitudinal axis, as the round notch penetrates the metal deeper on the left. Rebounding caused a micronotch approximately 3 mm further towards the tip (Figure 3.47).

A sharp notch directed towards the hilt was created in the defending sword. This directionality was expected from a kinetic parry executed upwards and away from the defender. A small fissure protrudes from the cusp. Both flanks of the mark are curled towards either side of the cutting edge, indicating that twisting of either sword occurred during the impact. The severe curling between this mark and that of 3f. is likely the result of two impacts in close proximity. Rebounding has created a single micronotch approximately 3 mm further towards the tip (Figure 3.48).

36c. left, edge parry, dynamic – SW3 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.49)

Figure 3.49 – 36c. shoulder strike with dynamic edge parry. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.50 – 36c. SW3 attack, right, shoulder strike, full force. Curved graze, 119 mm from the tip.

Figure 3.51 – 36c. SW2 defend, edge parry, dynamic. Sharp notch, 170 mm from the tip.

36c. was a full force shoulder strike executed on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left with a dynamic edge parry (Figure 3.49). During what were essentially two attacking strikes, only one mark was created on each sword. The considerable force of the impact, however, caused a number of fissures in the cutting edge of the defending sword.

A curved graze with directionality towards the tip was created on the cutting edge of the attacking sword. Compression occurred around the mark and formed a swollen rim. The striations visible below the mark (Figure 3.50) cannot be attributed to the action, and their origin remains unknown.

A narrow sharp notch was created in the cutting edge of the defending sword. The mark penetrates the cutting edge at a right angle. In this case, the force of the two clashing blades generated several fissures around the mark. Material displacement has also taken place. One flank is slightly curled. Compressed metal forms swollen ripples around the notch (Figure 3.51).

3.4.3 *Sword vs. spear*

A total of 13 spear vs. sword attacks were carried out, consisting of short spearhead on long shaft and long spearhead on short shaft vs. contemporary swords. Whilst the original protocol scheduled tests with all combinations, the sheer number of actions quickly turned out as too time-consuming, and as such the decision was made to only execute the following motions. Notably, only the marks created on the swords are included in this section. The marks created on spearheads will be the subject of a publication by Rachel Crellin and co-workers, which is currently in preparation.

27. Sword vs. short spearhead on long shaft, leg strike, full force

27a. left, edge parry, static – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.52)

Figure 3.52 – 27a. sword vs. static short spearhead edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.53 – 27a. SW1 attack, left, leg strike, full force against static edge parry. Sharp notch, 158 mm from the tip, and micronotching (right).

27a. was a full force leg strike executed with SW1 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SP2 with a static edge parry (Figure 3.52). The initial impact resulted in a sharp notch in the cutting edge of SW1. A small fissure protrudes from the cusp. Further towards the tip of the sword, a series of micronotches can be found (Figure 3.53). These were created when the blade rebound and scraped along the cutting edge of SP2, on which a similar pattern was discovered.

The weight of the spear tip, combined with the length and lightness of the wooden shaft, is responsible for the rebound during this static parry. Although the tip was forced downwards during the initial impact, the defender's wrist naturally twitches to maintain the position of the spear, which causes the weapons to connect repeatedly.

27c. left, edge parry, kinetic – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.54)

Figure 3.54 – 27c. sword vs. kinetic short spearhead edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.55 – 27c. SW1 attack, left, leg strike, full force against kinetic edge parry. Sharp notch, 120 mm from the tip.

27c. was a full force leg strike executed with SW1 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SP2 with a kinetic edge parry (Figure 3.54). A sharp notch directed towards the tip of the sword was created in the cutting edge of SW1. Material displacement has taken place on the right flank of the notch, where the metal has formed compressed ripples (Figure 3.55).

The kinetic movement in both weapons prevented the two blades to connect again. The weight distribution of SP2 allowed the sword to deflect the spear with ease.

27d. right, edge parry, dynamic – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.56)

Figure 3.56 – 27d. sword vs. dynamic short spearhead socket. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.57 – 27d. SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force against kinetic edge parry. Flattening, 91-98 mm from the tip.

27d. was a full force leg strike executed with SW1 on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left by SP2 with a kinetic edge parry (Figure 3.56). In this case, the defender failed to parry the attack with the cutting edge of SP2. Instead, the strike was defended with the rounded socket of the spearhead. The impact created a very shallow flattening on the cutting edge of SW1 (Figure 3.57).

The impact on the spear, only 3 mm from the edge of the socket, fractured the shaft. As a result, the binding became so loose that the spearhead had to be remounted onto a different shaft.

27e. left, central ridge parry, static – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.58)

Figure 3.58 – 27e. sword vs. static short spearhead central ridge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.59 – 27e. SW1 attack, left, leg strike, full force against static central ridge parry. Indentation, 177-86 mm from the tip.

27e. was a full force leg strike executed with SW1 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SP2 with a static central ridge parry (Figure 3.58). A 9 mm long indentation, with a profile reflecting the roundness of the central ridge of the spearhead, was created on the cutting edge of SW1. The indentation is extremely even so that no directionality can be determined. A pattern of small striations erupts from the indentation at a right angle (Figure 3.59). Two marks in immediate proximity to each other were recorded on the spearhead. It appears that the sword connected twice with the exact same section of the blade. The force of the rebound caused a slight twist of the sword along its longitudinal axis.

27g. left, central ridge parry, kinetic – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.60)

Figure 3.60 – 27g. sword vs. kinetic short spearhead central ridge.
Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.61 – 27g. SW1 attack, left, leg strike, full force
against kinetic central ridge parry. Indentation,
129-39 mm from the tip.

27g. was a full force leg strike executed with SW1 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SP2 with a kinetic central ridge parry (Figure 3.60). An indentation was created in the cutting edge of SW1. The steeper curvature towards hilt-end of the indentation suggests directionality towards the hilt. This is supported by a pattern of short striations erupting from the bottom of the indentation angled towards the hilt. Material was displaced and compressed, flattening and widening the indentation (Figure 3.61).

The combined force of the sword strike and the kinetic parry caused the shaft of SP2 to fracture.

27h. right, central ridge parry, dynamic – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.62)

Figure 3.62 – 27h. sword vs. dynamic short spearhead central ridge. Image by RJ Crellin.

27h. was a full force leg strike executed with SW1 on the right-hand side of the attacker, defended on the left by SP2 with a dynamic central ridge parry (Figure 3.62). Although the field recordings clearly state that damage was caused to the spearhead, no marks could be found on the sword. The action was therefore repeated.

27h.2 – right, central ridge parry, dynamic – SW1 attack, SP2 defend (Figure 3.63)

Figure 3.63 27h.2 sword vs. dynamic short spearhead central ridge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.64 – 27h.2 SW1 attack, right, leg strike, full force against dynamic central ridge parry. Indentation, 110-18 mm from the tip.

Repeat (Figure 3.63) of 27h. In this case, an indentation was created in the cutting edge of SW1. The metal was compressed and displaced into a swollen rim and slight rippling. A pattern of short striations has also formed on the indentation (Figure 3.64).

The force of the two weapons in motion caused a deep blow mark on the central ridge of the spearhead, extending into, and damaging, the cutting edge.

31. Long spearhead on short shaft vs. sword, leg strike, full force

31a. left, edge parry, static – SP4 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.65)

Figure 3.65 – 31a. long spearhead vs. static sword edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.66 – 31a. SW2 defend, left, edge parry, static. Sharp notch, 167 mm from the tip.

31a. was a full force leg strike executed with SP4 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SW2 with a static edge parry (Figure 3.65). The wedge-like cutting edge of the spearhead cut into the sword at a right angle, thus creating a deep sharp notch which penetrates the bevel line. Several fissures were torn into the metal around the mark. Both flanks and the material around the fissures have curled. The metal at the cusp is compressed and swollen (Figure 3.66).

31c. left, edge parry, kinetic – SP4 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.67)

Figure 3.67 – 31c. long spearhead vs. kinetic sword edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.68 – 31c. SW2 defend, left, edge parry, kinetic. Sharp notch, 100 mm from the tip.

31c. was a full force leg strike executed with SP4 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SW2 with a kinetic edge parry (Figure 3.67). The cutting edge of the spear cut deeply into the sword at a right angle. The increased force of the kinetic parry produced a much cleaner profiled sharp notch. Some curling occurred on the right flank of the mark. Material displacement is visible on the left flank (Figure 3.68).

31e. left, edge parry, dynamic – SP4 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.69)

Figure 3.69 – 31e. long spearhead socket vs. dynamic sword edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.70 – 31e. SW2 defend, left, edge parry, dynamic. Indentation, 31-48 mm from the tip.

31e. was a full force leg strike executed with SP4 on the left-hand side of the attacker, defended on the right by SW2 with a dynamic edge parry (Figure 3.69). Because of the relative shortness of the spearhead, the attacker failed to connect with the sword properly. Instead, the spear connected with the rounded socket. A long indentation was created on the cutting edge of the sword. Material displacement in the form of flattening and compression of the cutting edge took place. The metal was forced to either side of the indentation (Figure 3.70). Striations were created on the socket of the spearhead.

The decision to repeat the action was made.

31e.2 – left, edge parry, dynamic – SP4 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.71)

Figure 3.71 – 31e.2 long spearhead socket vs. dynamic sword edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.72 – 31e.2 SW2 defend, left, edge parry, dynamic. Indentation, 13-31 mm from the tip.

31e.2 was the second attempt to parry SP4 with SW2 in a dynamic motion (Figure 3.71). Once again, the attacker failed to hit the sword with the cutting edge of SP4. Instead, the sword connected with the rounded socket of the spearhead again. Almost the same spot on the cutting edge of the sword was struck as in 31e., extending the indentation further towards the tip (Figure 3.72). Coincidentally, it was also almost the same section of the socket of SP4 that was struck.

Once again it was decided to repeat the actions.

31e.3 – left, edge parry, dynamic – SP4 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.73)

Figure 3.73 – 31e.3 long spearhead vs. dynamic sword edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.74 – 31e.3 SW2 defend, left, edge parry, dynamic. Wide-angled notch, 214 mm from the tip.

This time the attacker succeeded in striking the sword with the cutting edge of SP4 (Figure 3.73). The wide-angled cutting edge of the spear tore a wide-angled notch which penetrated the bevel line into SW2. A fissure was torn into the left flank of the mark, somewhat distorting the appearance of the mark. This distortion could be misinterpreted as a straight graze. The metal around the notch was compressed and ripples formed, especially around the cusp.

The impact force of the dynamic parry caused numerous micronotches in the spearhead. This appeared unusual to the team, and it was decided to carry out the action once more.

31e.4 – left, edge parry, dynamic – SP4 attack, SW2 defend (Figure 3.75)

Figure 3.75 – 31e.4 long spearhead vs. dynamic sword edge. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.76 – 31e.4 SW2 defend, left, edge parry, dynamic. Wide-angled notch, 273 mm from the tip.

31e.4 was the final attempt to parry SP4 with SW2 with a dynamic motion (Figure 3.75). It was carried out mostly for the benefit of producing comparable data on the spearhead, as the number of marks created during 31e.3 struck the team as unusually high.

Again, a wide-angled notch was torn into the cutting edge of SW2. The metal around the mark was compressed and turned into numerous ripples. A small number of fissures can be seen around the cusp of the notch. The flanks of the notch appear very rounded and smooth. They are both slightly curved outwards (Figure 3.76). Again, the spearhead was subject to numerous micronotches.

3.4.4 *Sword vs. shield*

A variety of sword strikes and thrusts were carried out against the leather, wood, and bronze shields. For health and safety reasons the shields were mostly mounted onto a dummy, a fence, or against hay bales.

Sword vs. leather shield

6. Sword vs. leather shield attack, hip strike, full force

6c. left, kinetic x 3 – SW2 attack

This hip strike across the face of the shield was carried out three times. Although each strike was executed with full force, the sword was not able to penetrate the shield. Deep striations were left on the surface of the shield. Residue of the shield leather was found on the cutting edge of SW2, but no visible damage could be recorded on the sword. The residue was easily removed with a cloth.

8. Sword vs. leather shield attack, slashing strike to the shield edge, full force, shield mounted on dummy

Initially, the shield would have been held by the defender, as the team assumed that penetration would, if anything, be minimal. Fortunately, however, a last-minute decision to mount the shield on a dummy was made. As it later appeared, this action could have caused serious injury to the defender.

8c. slash and draw – SW2 attack (Figure 3.77)

Figure 3.77 – 8c. Jon Allison executing a slashing shoulder strike towards the rim of the leather shield. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.78 – Deep tear into the leather shield as the result of 8c. Image by RJ Crellin.

This slashing strike on shoulder height was executed on the right-hand side of the attacker. Unexpectedly, SW2 easily penetrated the rim of the shield and tore deeply into the leather (Figure 3.78).

8d. repeat of 8c. – SW2 attack

The second strike, executed in the same fashion, missed the rim of the shield and merely scratched over the boss of the shield, leaving deep striations in the leather. Again, no damage to the sword could be recorded.

9. Sword vs. target leather shield attack (to the middle of the shield), thrust, full force

These were carried out by different persons with different levels of height, weight, and body strength. The following thrusts were carried out:

9a. static thrust – SW1 Jon (Figure 3.79)

9b. repeat 9a – SW2 Jon

9c. kinetic thrust – SW1 Raphael

9d. repeat 9c – SW2 Raphael (Figure 3.80)

9e. static thrust – SW3 Jon

9f. kinetic thrust – SW3 Raphael (Figure 3.81)

9g. static thrust – SW1 Rachel

9h. static thrust – SW2 Rachel

9i. static thrust – SW3 Rachel

9j. kinetic thrust – SW1 Rachel

9k. kinetic thrust – SW2 Rachel

9l. kinetic thrust – SW3 Rachel

Figure 3.79 – 9a. static thrust into leather shield with SW1. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.80 – 9d. kinetic thrust into leather shield with SW2. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.81 – 9f. kinetic thrust into leather shield with SW3 (top) and penetration (bottom). Image by RJ Crellin.

Both static and kinetic thrusts easily pierced the leather shields. None of the thrusts, however, created any wear marks on the swords.

Sword vs. bronze shield

101. Sword vs. bronze shield, glancing blow, full force, shield held by defender

101a. static defence – SW5 attack (Figure 3.82)

Figure 3.82 – 101a. Jon executing a glancing blow to the static bronze shield. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.83 – 101a. glancing blow to the face of the static bronze shield. Flattening, 110-30 mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

101a. was a glancing blow executed to the face of the statically held bronze shield. The impact caused a 20 mm long flattening on the cutting edge of SW5 (Figure 3.83), whilst the shield suffered merely a 50 mm long striation.

101b. kinetic defence – SW5 attack

Figure 3.84 – 101b.i glancing blow to the face of the kinetic bronze shield. Flattening, 130-4 mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.86 – 101b.ii Flattening, 230-8mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.85 – 101b.iii Flattening, 231-65mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

101b. was a glancing blow (i.e. a slash across the flat of the shield, mimicking the defence against a slashing strike), executed to the face of the bronze shield, defended with a kinetic movement of the shield. Three marks were created through contact with the surface of the shield. 101b.i is a short flattening created through contact with the shield boss (Figure 3.84). Flattenings ii and iii are the results of impacts on the shield ribs (Figure 3.86 & Figure 3.85). The shield suffered minor striation marks in three corresponding areas on the boss and ribs.

104. Sword vs. mounted target shield, thrust, full force

For health and safety reasons, the shield was mounted onto hay bales for all thrusting tests, as it was feared that the relative thinness of the copper-alloy would let the sword penetrate the shield with ease.

104a. right, static defence, static thrust – SW5 attack (Figure 3.87)

Figure 3.87 – 104a. static thrust executed to the static bronze shield mounted on hay bales. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.88 – Bronze shield boss with a hole from the manufacturing process. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.89 – 104a. static thrust to static target shield. Tip pressure. Image by RJ Crellin.

104a. was a static thrust executed to the face of the bronze shield mounted on hay bales. The thrust was aimed at the thinnest part of the boss, where the manufacturing process had left a hole in the metal (Figure 3.88). It was struck just to the top left of the hole. The impact caused a small amount of tip pressure on SW5 (Figure 3.89), as well as a slight bend to the first 140 mm from the tip. Against expectations, the bronze shield withstood the impact extremely effectively, and it was not possible to penetrate the metal.

104b. right, static defence, kinetic thrust – SW5 attack

Figure 3.90 – 104b. kinetic thrust to mounted target shield. Tip pressure. Image by RJ Crellin.

104b. was a kinetic thrust to the face of the mounted bronze shield. The tip of SW5 made contact just below the boss and was deflected to scrape along the surface of the shield. Again, the shield withstood the impact and suffered merely striation marks. The sword experienced exacerbated tip pressure and a distinct bend to the first 180 mm from the tip.

Having seen how effectively the bronze shield withstood different sword impacts, it was decided to abandon further sword vs. bronze shield tests in order to prevent further damage to the sword.

Sword vs. wooden shield

For health and safety reasons, and because of the uncertainty of how the material would behave under pressure, the wooden shield was mounted on two wooden poles for all experiments (Figure 3.91).

Figure 3.91 – Mounted wooden shield at Durham Botanical Gardens.
Image by RJ Crellin.

201. Sword vs. wooden shield attack

201a. glancing blow to the face of the wooden shield – SW5 attack (Figure 3.92)

Figure 3.92 – 201a. glancing blow to the face of the wooden shield. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.93 – Struck rim after 201a. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.94 – 201a. glancing blow to the face of the wooden shield, right, full force. Flattening, 63 mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

201a. was a glancing blow to the face of the wooden shield, executed with full force on the right-hand side (Figure 3.92). As SW5 had a slight bent to the blade from a previous experiment, my aim was completely off, and I was unable to glance the sword off the flat of the shield and instead struck the rim (Figure 3.93). A 14 mm long flattening was caused near the tip of SW5 (Figure 3.94). It was decided to repeat the action.

201b. repeat

Figure 3.95 – 201b. glancing blow to the face of the wooden shield, right, full force. Irregular graze, 143 mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

201b. repeated the action of 201a. Again, I was unable to glance along the face of the wooden shield and instead struck the rim. An irregular graze was created in the cutting edge of SW5. As it was feared that too many repetitions might damage the sword, it was decided to proceed with the protocol.

203. Sword vs. wooden target shield attack

203a. slashing strike against the rim, left, full force – SW5 attack (Figure 3.96)

Figure 3.96 – Executing 203a. towards the shield rim. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.97 – Deep incision into the wooden shield after 203a. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.98 – Fissure in the cutting edge of SW5 after 203a., 200 mm from the tip. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 3.99 – Severe bend to SW5 after 203a. Image by RJ Crellin.

203a. was a full force shoulder strike with SW5 executed to the rim of the wooden shield. The sword was severely bent on a length of 20 cm from the tip (Figure 3.99). A fissure, where the metal was torn apart from the impact, was also created (Figure 3.98). The shield suffered a deep gash into its rim.

Due to the heavy damage SW5 sustained during this attack, it was decided to discontinue the experiment at this point.

3.4.5 Summary of marks

The following table (Table 3.3) provides a summary of all marks and strikes executed during this experiment.

Test ref	Attack					Defence				
	Weapon	Strike	Mark	Micronotch	Note	Weapon	Strike	Mark	Micronotch	Note
1a.	SW1	leg strike	sharp notch	no		SW4	static edge	sharp notch	yes	
1c.	SW1	leg strike	round notch	yes		SW4	kinetic edge	curved graze	yes	
1e.	SW1	leg strike	curved graze	no		SW4	dynamic edge	sharp notch	no	
1g.	SW1	leg strike	indentation	yes		SW4	static flat	striations	no	
1i.	SW1	leg strike	round notch	yes		SW4	kinetic flat	blow mark	no	striations from blow mark
1k.	SW1	leg strike	indentation	yes	very small	SW4	dynamic flat	striations	no	bent!
3b.	SW2	shoulder strike	sharp notch	no		SW3	static edge	curved graze	no	
3d.	SW2	shoulder strike	sharp notch	yes		SW3	kinetic edge	round notch	no	
3f.	SW2	shoulder strike	sharp notch	no		SW3	dynamic edge	curved graze	no	
36a.	SW3	shoulder strike	rectangular indentation	no		SW2	static edge	sharp notch	no	
36b.	SW3	shoulder strike	round notch	yes		SW2	kinetic edge	sharp notch	yes	
36c.	SW3	shoulder strike	curved graze	no		SW2	dynamic edge	sharp notch	no	
27a.	SW1	leg strike	sharp notch	yes		SP2	static edge			
27c.	SW1	leg strike	sharp notch	no		SP2	kinetic edge			
27d.	SW1	leg strike	flattening	no		SP2	dynamic socket			fractured shaft
27e.	SW1	leg strike	indentation	no		SP2	static ridge			
27g.	SW1	leg strike	indentation	no		SP2	kinetic ridge			fractured shaft
27h.2	SW1	leg strike	indentation	no		SP2	dynamic ridge			
31a.	SP4	leg strike				SW2	static edge	sharp notch	no	

31c.	SP4	leg strike			SW2	kinetic edge	sharp notch	no
31e.	SP4	leg strike		connected with socket	SW2	dynamic edge	indentation	no
31e.2	SP4	leg strike		connected with socket	SW2	dynamic edge	indentation	no
31e.3	SP4	leg strike			SW2	dynamic edge	wide-angled notch	no
31e.4	SP4	leg strike			SW2	dynamic edge	wide-angled notch	no
6c. x 3	SW2	hip strike	none		LS	kinetic face	striations	
8c.	SW2	draw cut	none		LS	static edge	incision	
8d.	SW2	draw cut	none		LS	static face	striations	missed rim and hit face instead
9a.-l.	SW1-3	thrusts	none		LS	static face	pierced	
101a.	SW5	glancing blow	flattening		BS	static face	striations	
101b.	SW5	glancing blow	flattening x 3		BS	kinetic face	striations	
104a.	SW5	static thrust	tip pressure	slight bend	BS	static face		
104b.	SW5	kinetic thrust	tip pressure	heavy bend	BS	static face		
201a.	SW5	glancing blow	flattening		WS	static rim		
201b.	SW5	glancing blow	irregular graze		WS	static rim		
203a.	SW5	slash	bend	also fissure	WS	static rim		

Table 3.3 – Summary of the sword marks created during the experiments.

3.5 Results

The combat experiments were extremely successful in creating a reference database of marks, some of which can conclusively be attributed to certain actions. This section provides a summary of what we have learnt from the experiment.

Figure 3.100 – Flowchart displaying the various ways in which sharp notches were created during the experiment.

The most commonly occurring marks were sharp notches, which were created through attacking and defensive motions against swords and spears (Figure 3.100). Sharp notches can be the result of leg and shoulder strikes, as well as static, kinetic, and dynamic edge parries. They also occurred when leg strikes were defended with the cutting edge of a spear, and when the static and kinetic edge parries were executed with the sword.

Figure 3.101 – Flowchart displaying the various ways in which round notches were created during the experiment.

Round notches occurred less frequently than sharp notches, and were only created in four cases of sword vs. sword combat. They can be attributed to both leg and shoulder strikes, but only one to kinetic edge parries (Figure 3.101). No round notches were created in sword vs. spear combat.

Figure 3.102 – Flowchart displaying the various ways in which curved grazes were created during the experiment.

Five curved grazes were created during the experiment, both on attacking and defending swords (Figure 3.102). The attacking leg and shoulder strikes were both met with dynamic edge parries (see Table 3.3)

Figure 3.103 – Flowchart displaying the various ways in which indentations were created during the experiment.

Indentations are almost exclusively the result of sword vs. spear combat. It proved extremely difficult to strike or parry the opponent’s sword with the cutting edge of the spearheads, even when a conscious effort was made. Instead, the affected area was almost always the central ridge or the socket. The three attacking leg strikes were all defended with the ridge of the spearhead. When the sword was used to defend against the spear, the four indentations were created when it failed to strike the spearhead’s cutting edge and instead connected with its socket (Figure 3.103). These marks are commonly found on originals (see Chapters 5 and 6). The only indentation created during sword vs. sword combat (see Chapter 3.4.2 1k.) was the result of contact with a very prominent midrib during a dynamic flat parry (see below), and is in itself very small. Indentations are therefore not indicative of sword vs. sword combat.

Figure 3.104 – Flowchart displaying the creation of wide-angled notches during the experiment.

Wide-angled notches were exclusively created when the sword connected with the cutting-edge of a spearhead (Figure 3.104), and are indicative of sword vs. spear combat.

One rectangular indentation was created as the result of a sword vs. sword shoulder strike, defended with a static edge parry. A single blow mark was created when a kinetic flat parry was used to defend a leg strike. Perhaps most ground-breaking is the result of 1k., where the dynamic flat parry caused the defending sword to bend significantly. A distinct pattern of striations was also created on the flat of the blade. This suggests that flat parries, as were frequently performed during the mediaeval period (Clements 1998, 19) and was suggested by Mödlinger (2011), were never carried out deliberately as the risk of sustaining serious damage to the sword was significant. Instead, it can be suggested that such actions were deliberately avoided at all costs, and only carried out as an ultimate last resort to save one’s life, or else the bending was created as intentional damage during deliberate destruction.

Micronotching occurred most frequently on the attacking sword. However, despite immediate recording in the field, it was occasionally difficult to determine the connection between a mark and micronotching with certainty. This demonstrates that any such interpretations on originals must be made with extreme caution.

Although in many cases the attacking and defending mark are significantly different, no marks are exclusively attack or defence related.

Using swords against the leather shield has produced three interesting results. Firstly, no marks whatsoever were created on the swords, making interpretation of this sort of encounter extremely difficult, and always hypothetical. Secondly, the swords proved extremely effective when the leather shield was held statically, piercing and slashing it with ease. This leads to the third point, which suggests that leather shields can be used extremely effectively when employed dynamically, i.e. with movements to catch and deflect the opponent's weapon, rather than providing a static barrier.

Both bronze and wooden shields could be used effectively as barriers and dynamically, and no sword was able to penetrate either of them. However, the added increased weight makes both shields more difficult to manoeuvre, especially for a prolonged period of time. The sword used against the wooden shield was slightly bent from a previous experiment, and it quickly transpired that precise strikes are impossible with such a weapon. Instead, I struck the shield in a completely unexpected location. Rather than overly affecting the shields, the contacts had at times devastating effects on the sword, bending the tip and entire sections of the blade until SW5 became unusable. Ultimately, the aim was always to go around the opponent's shield rather than strike it, but to avoid damage to his weapon, a Bronze Age swordsman would have had to employ certain techniques against such defensive weapons.

No patterns regarding the position of marks along the cutting edges could be detected. Both offensive and defensive actions produced impacts along the entire lengths of the cutting edges, and no section was distinctly related to either attacks or parries.

3.6 Evaluation

Whilst this experiment was successful in recreating some distinctive evidence for the creation of certain marks, it is important to reflect and evaluate the positives and negatives of this approach.

The tests successfully created marks as found on original swords. As the experiment was broken down into individual, controlled combat scenes, it was possible to link certain actions and weapons combinations to individual mark types.

Utilising an extensive protocol and combining different weapons has moved this experiment from previous sword-centric research conducted by others to the next level. This allows us to investigate how swords could have been used in combination with other weapons, their individual strengths and weaknesses, and provides a generally more realistic interpretation of prehistoric combat. Including static parries in the protocol also allows bridging the gap between exclusive combat marks and those created during the deliberate destruction of swords.

Four main limitations could be identified for this experimental approach. The first relates to the replica weapons. Using a number of typologically different weapons was introduced in order to give the tests a broader scope, without realising that this could potentially limit comparability between different tests. Whilst it could be argued that it would have been preferential to use only one or two sword types, it must be remembered that the basic form of the sword has a much greater effect on its functionality and the way it was used than any modern typological differences. Sword types aside, there was a basic issue with the quality of replicas employed during the test. The marks created during the experiment were all extremely deep and well-pronounced, much more so than the prehistoric originals (see Chapters 5 and 6). Following the experiments, samples were taken of all weapons and full metallographic analysis was carried out by Quanyu Wang. The results show that there is no significant difference in hardness between the edge and the inner part of the blade (Wang, in prep.), thus indicating that a single cycle of work-hardening does not produce an authentic cutting edge. Whilst the marks only differ in size, and not form, this does not bias the overall results of the experiment. Future replica swords, however, should be manufactured to a higher standard.

The second weakness relates to the fundamental idea of conducting experiments to leave marks on a weapon. True combat is fluid and dynamic, rather than static and broken into individual actions, and the ultimate goal is to strike the opponent, not their weapon. Due to the significant risk of damage to copper-alloy weapons, material preservation would, in fact, have been of utmost importance, and clashing contacts would largely have been avoided. When those contacts did happen, however, they were predominantly accidental or carried out as a last resort to save one's life. Only in specific cases would contact deliberately have been made (see Chapter 4). The experiment actually failed to create any marks related to striking the opponent's body and armour. However, for the purpose of this project, the methodological approach was very successful, as it allows to create the first ever reference collection to investigate original marks on Bronze Age swords. It must be noted, though, that the ways in

which marks were created in this experiment are by no means conclusive, and there is a vast variety of ways in which the weapons could have been used.

Choosing to carry out the experiments in the field rather than a laboratory, as this provided both space and the flexibility needed to conduct the experiments safe and proper, as well as what was felt to be an appropriate background to the topic, the problem with in-field recording became apparent immediately. The open environment made recording difficult at times (wind, storm, bright sunlight, holes in the ground etc.), and the lack of immediate microscopic analysis proved problematic. Especially in cases when newly created marks interfered with those of previous actions, evidence was lost or potentially altered. Future experiments should be conducted in a spacious indoor space, in combination with a (temporary) laboratory to carry out immediate microscopic analysis (Crellin et al., in press).

Finally, conducting comprehensive combat tests, as suggested by Brandherm (2011, 24), is vastly time and money consuming. The Bronze Age Combat Project can be considered as extensive, with nearly 150 weapons tests involving equipment costs of over £3000, six field days and several hundred hours of post-experimental analysis, and yet it appears that we have only just started to scratch the surface. This is partially due to the significant damage the replicas sustain, as well as the fact that a lack of comparable data by other researchers has forced me to essentially start from scratch. Once a suitable reference database is in place, however, it should be possible to make faster and better progress.

3.7 Conclusion

The review of previous experimental and wear analysis studies has provided the basis for the methodologies developed for this research. This has allowed me to conduct a number of very successful scientific field experiments. These experiments have produced a reference database for sword wear marks, which can be used to interpret original Bronze Age swords. Amongst the most conclusive results is the bend and striation pattern resulting from the flat parry (0). Evaluating the experiments has highlighted some limitations of the methodology, such as the static combat broken into individual actions. To counter this, a different, more realistic experimental methodology had to be developed, which will be the focus of the next chapter.

Chapter 4. Actualistic combat experiments

4.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces an experimental methodology different to the one in the previous chapter. It also discusses Historical European Martial Arts, and how these help us to understand prehistoric combat. A detailed description of the experiments carried out in accordance with this new methodology is followed by results and evaluation sections.

4.2 Methodology

4.2.1 Introduction

The second set of combat tests was designed to be more realistic than the somewhat “robotic” individual actions of the first experiment. Unlike Molloy (2004; 2006; 2007; 2008) and Anderson (2011), whose experiments and interpretations were mostly based on the experiential exploration of actions (Molloy 2008, 118), thus determining the capabilities of weapons rather than proving what they were used for, one of the aims of this experiment was to combine controlled realistic combat with precision recording and metalwork wear analysis in order to create a link between specific actions and their marks. Perhaps the best term to describe this approach is “actualistic” as coined by Molloy (2008) and Outram (2008). The term is defined as “...exploring practical activities” (Molloy 2008, 119) through conducting “real life” scenarios with authentic materials in a range of environmental conditions to “investigate activities that *might* have happened in the past using methods and material that would actually have been available” (Outram 2008, 2), thus bridging the gap between laboratory-based experiments (e.g. Bridgford 2000; O’Flaherty et al. 2011) and the aforementioned experiential tests. The second aim was to test the hypothesis that historical combat manuscripts can be used to interpret Bronze Age sword fighting, provided that the capabilities and physical properties of the prehistoric weapons are taken into account. Due to the difficulties in identifying the best manuscripts and interpreting the historical texts correctly, it was decided to collaborate with Historical European Martial Arts (HEMA) expert, internationally renowned fencing instructor, and former president of the British Federation for Historical Swordplay, Robert Brooks. With his assistance, the experiment was then designed on the basis of several short plays with a small number of sword contacts each. Although this may not be fully representative of the duration of an entire prehistoric fight, the plays consist of realistic, fluid combat actions, whilst allowing to record and cross-reference the created wear marks with individual moves. Collaborating with HEMA practitioners without an archaeological background has the added benefit of introducing different mindsets

and ideas, thus allowing interpretation of prehistoric weapons in different ways than academic researchers might reach.

4.2.2 A brief history of HEMA

Historical European Martial Arts is an inclusive term used by modern martial artists and researchers who study and practise the fighting manuscripts of the mediaeval and renaissance period from Europe. The trend developed independently in various locations throughout Britain, Europe, and the USA in the early 1990s (Craddock 2016; Winter 2011). In particular the movement at Napier University, Edinburgh, where the sports fencing society worked in collaboration with the academic environment to research and reconstruct historical fencing methods, was pioneering. Robert Brooks, himself a student of journalism at Napier at the time, was heavily involved, initially in setting up the Dawn Duellist Society, and later in establishing the British Federation for Historical Swordplay, a governing body that was founded in 1997 and of which he was elected president in 2013 (Brooks 2015). Although there was initially only very limited contact between HEMA groups around the world, the university environment and its exchange of international students provided the background for a spread of HEMA into different countries through the return of foreign students back to their home countries. The emergence of the internet during the late 1990s suddenly allowed contact and exchange between groups who were previously completely unaware of each other (Craddock 2016). It also provided the basis for increased publicity and accessibility for those interested, and the field has been growing ever since. In more recent years, popular TV series such as *Game of Thrones* have led to a massive increase in participants, and European Martial Arts schools such as Brooks's *Hotspur School of Defence* count more than 70 members at any given time, with a 40 % female member rate (Brooks 2018). Members typically come from a diverse range of backgrounds and interests, thus allowing for open-minded and inclusive discussions and interpretations. The HEMA community now mainly consists of two sections: those that primarily practice HEMA as a sport for recreational purposes and to enter tournaments, and those that focus on the discovery, study, and interpretation of historical manuscripts. For the former, there are now frequently held major tournaments that regularly get over 150 participants. The latter have sparked an academic interest in the subject, and previous, uninformed presumptions about historical combat now have to be reviewed (ibid.). A quarter of a century after its embryonic development, the HEMA community has connected and developed to such an extent that official recognition as a sport is being sought. The digital exchange of those studying the historical fighting manuals individually has revealed that, in most cases, the scholars come to very similar conclusions of how these manuscripts should be interpreted, thus creating a credible basis that can be introduced to academic research.

4.2.3 *Combat experiments*

To conduct meaningful combat tests, it was imperative to choose the most informative historical martial arts manuscript, whilst considering the material properties, dimensions, and capabilities of the Bronze Age replica weapons. Having discussed these issues with Brooks, it was decided to follow his suggestion to design the experiment based on the *Commentary by Andre Lignitzer on Sword and Buckler* from folios 80r-80v, Codex 44.A.8, by Peter von Danzig from 1452 (Farrell 2012). The development and evolution of historical fighting manuals has been discussed by others at length (Clements 1997; 1998; Anglo 2000; Forgeng & Kiermayer 2007; Jaquet & Walczak 2014), and it is not the purpose of this research to discuss it comprehensively, thus only a brief summary on the historical context of Lignitzer's Codex 44.A.8 and other manuscripts will be given. The social divide between the literate classes, typically monks or merchants, and the military classes, i.e. those who would practice swordsmanship and fight on a regular basis, has led to a relatively late development of written fighting manuals. As such, the earliest manuscript known today is the German *Walpurgis Fechtbuch* aka *Royal Armouries MS I.33* aka *The Anonymous Tower Fechtbuch*, dating from the late 1200s or early 1300s (Clements, 1988, 12; Forgeng 2004).

Figure 4.1 – List of masters in the Lichtenauer tradition from Paulus Kal's 1470 *Fechtbuch*, Folio 2r. Master Andre Lignitzer is highlighted.

For over a century, subsequent publications remain scarce and isolated, with no perceptible lineage. It was not until 1389, when Johannes Lichtenauer's *Fechtbuch* marked the birth of a comprehensive tradition of German martial artists who followed and developed his teachings. The tradition established complex hierarchical systems of masters and students, and produced publications by numerous authors including the well-known German master fencer Hans Talhoffer (ibid., 13). Lichtenauer, who was considered the grandmaster of German fencing tradition, co-authored with Paulus Kal his 1470 *Fechtbuch*, which contains a list of the 17 masters of the Fellowship of Lichtenauer. This list includes Andre Lignitzer (Figure 4.1), thus placing him in direct connection to the Lichtenauer tradition. Little is known about Lignitzer's life, though he is mentioned, or his work has been included, in a number of manuscripts including Codex 44.A.8, Codex I.6.4.3, MS KK5126, MS M.I.29, MS Dresden C.487, and

Codex 10825/10826 (Jaquet & Walczak 2014). His contribution to the sword and buckler (a small, round combat shield) in Codex 44.A.8 consists of six different plays (Appendix C), of which the first five were deemed appropriate for the experiment. Designing the tests on the basis of sword and buckler fighting is rooted in the relative shortness of Bronze Age swords, which makes it imperative to fight in close proximity. Contrary to a more traditional image of mediaeval sword fighting, where the combatants face each other from a comfortable distance and merely exchange strikes that are warded off with the shield as described in MS I.33, the lack of blade length in bronze swords would not allow for that type of combat. Lignitzer's manuscript was chosen as it is short, yet comprehensive, and there is comparable data from other sources allowing correct interpretation. His sword and buckler plays bring the fight to the correct measure, and includes, strikes, thrusts, and slices, all of which bronze swords are capable of. Furthermore, his manuscript works on the principle of *versetzen* (displacement) rather than parries, which prevents undue stress on the material that could render a bronze sword useless (see Chapter 3.4.2). Not only does *versetzen* displace the attack and provide control of the opponent's weapon, it also primes the blade in an offensive position so that one can immediately counter the opponent's attack with a thrust or slice of their own (Brooks 2018). Attack and defence eventually become interchangeable. Furthermore, his manuscript uses the shield to protect the sword hand. Considering the lack of crossguards on Bronze Age swords, which leaves the sword hand effectively unprotected, this application for increased protection seems plausible (*ibid.*, 8). Use of the shield extends beyond the mere protection of the hand though, and it is frequently used offensively to strike, block or detain the opponent in a position from where they can no longer fight. Finally, Lignitzer has also written about the longsword and wrestling, suggesting that he was knowledgeable about various strands of armed combat, thus making him a credible source. The sixth play focusses on disarming the opponent without clashing sword contacts. As this would not have produced any data on the blades it was not included in the experiment.

4.3 Experiment

4.3.1 Introduction

Following an initial discussion about the practicalities of conducting an actualistic combat experiment based on historical sources with Andrea Dolfini and Robert Brooks, I joined Brooks's *Hotspur School of Defence* (HSD) for a one-year training and familiarisation period. During this period, I studied historic combat in general, with a particular focus on the *Messer*, a mediaeval short sword similar in dimensions to Bronze Age swords, to gain an insight into how combat was conducted with such weapons. Starting with basic movements to get a feeling for this type of combat, I eventually studied Lignitzer's Sword and Buckler from

Codex 44.A.8, with the intention to carry out the experimental combat myself. Due to an injury I sustained unrelated to the training, however, I was eventually not able to carry out the combat myself, and instead recruited Andrew Milburn, a high-ranking student and instructor within HSD, to take my place and conduct the fighting with Robert Brooks. One day of experiments was planned to take place in February 2017. Because of the adverse weather conditions an indoor location had to be found, which proved difficult due to the limited number of available locations in Newcastle, the high rental rates the few available locations wanted to charge, as well as the unusual nature of the research which seemed to appall some of the landlords. Eventually, a local church hall could be hired for a reasonable amount of money, and as such the day of experiments was conducted at St. Luke's Church, Newcastle, near the university. I was joined by Robert Brooks and Andrew Milburn, who would conduct the sword fighting on the day, Andrea Dolfini acting as supervisor and first aider, Rachel Crellin, who recorded and photographed the combat, and Marion Uckelmann and Quanyu Wang, who were involved in the first set of experiments.

Figure 4.2 – SW6 Ewart Park replica obverse (top) and reverse prior to the experiment.

Figure 4.3 – SW7 Ewart Park replica obverse (top) and reverse prior to the experiment.

The two swords used in this experiment are both replicas of type Ewart Park (Figure 4.2 & Figure 4.3). This type of sword is very commonly found in the British Isles and dates to the

later part of the Late Bronze Age (Ewart Park Period, c. 925-800 BC; Burgess and Colquhoun 1988, 55ff.).

SW6 (Figure 4.2) length: 696 mm. Weight: 753.0 g

SW7 (Figure 4.3) length: 695 mm. Weight: 752.1 g

Both swords were cast by Neil Burrige with twelve-percent tin-bronze. The edges were subject to a single cycle of work hardening, and sharpened to a razor finish.

Figure 4.4 – Cloonbrin type leather shield replica. Image by RJ Crellin.

The same two Cloonbrin type leather shield replicas (Figure 4.4) from the previous tests were used for this experiment (see Chapter 3.4).

Figure 4.5 – Recording setup: Andrew Milburn and Robert Brooks in front of the video camera.

Figure 4.6 – Andrew Milburn and Robert Brooks practising with blunt weapons.

The experiment was broken down into five individual plays as described by Lignitzer. Each play was practised extensively with blunt training weapons (Figure 4.6) before it was conducted with the sharpened replica swords. Following each play, the replicas were taken to a side room, and all marks created were immediately recorded on paper and photographed. Videos and photographs of the combat sequences were taken with a SONY Cyber-shot DSCH300B Bridge Camera (Figure 4.5) and Olympus Stylus Touch, respectively. Personal

protective equipment (PPE) was worn for all live experiments, consisting of fencing masks, thick, padded gambesons, and arm guards.

The five plays are discussed below. Each play starts with the English translation of the manuscript taken from Farrell (2012). Every action is then described in detail, and followed by a description of how the related marks were produced.

4.3.2 301. First play

“The first play with the buckler from the Oberhaw (over strike / strike from above). Mark when you drive the Oberhaw to the man: with the pommel go inwards, your sword close to the buckler and your thumb, and thrust in from beneath to his face. Wind against his sword and then go with a snap over and around.” (Farrell 2012, 3).

Figure 4.7 – 301. Both combatants commence from the same starting position.

Figure 4.8 – 301a. Oberhaw resulting in a clashing contact at chest height.

Figure 4.9 – 301b. the attacker winds and pushes their sword upwards.

Figure 4.10 – Final stab to the face of the first play.

The first play consists of two sword contacts. Both combatants commence with the shield covering their forward extended arm and the sword resting on their shoulder (Figure 4.7). They each execute an *Oberhaw* (vertical strike from above), resulting in a clashing contact (301a.) at chest height (Figure 4.8). The attacker then twists their sword 180° and pushes upwards (301b.), thus temporarily controlling the defender's sword (Figure 4.9). To regain control, the defender pushes the attacker's sword to the side. In response, the attacker twirls their sword forwards and concludes with a stab to the face (Figure 4.10).

301a. first play, *Oberhaw*, *Oberhaw* – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.8)

Figure 4.11 301a. SW6 attack, *Oberhaw*. Curved graze, 273 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.12 – 301a. SW7 defend, *Oberhaw*. Round notch, 401 mm from the tip.

The first clashing contact of 301. resulted in a single combat mark on each sword. SW6 struck the defending SW7 with the mid-section of its forward cutting edge, thus creating a curved graze (Figure 4.11). A round notch was created in the upper section of the defending SW7 (Figure 4.12). Both marks are the result of an *Oberhaw*, thus demonstrating that different marks can be created by essentially the same action.

301b. first play, right, twist and push – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.9)

Figure 4.13 – 301b. SW6 attack, twist and push, three micronotches, 324-8 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.14 – 301b. SW7 defend, no action, micronotch, 462 mm from the tip.

The second contact of 301. consisted of the attacking SW6 twisting along its longitudinal axis whilst pushing upwards, scraping along the cutting edge of the defending SW7. Three micronotches were created in the forward cutting edge of SW6 (Figure 4.13). The defending sword was held static and did not carry out an action as it was being controlled by the attacking weapon. A single micronotch was created in the cutting edge of SW7 (Figure 4.14). Despite the scraping action no striations could be detected. Afterwards, Robert, the attacker, said that contrary to his expectations, there was a great level of friction between the weapons, and he felt that his sword almost “stuck” to Andrew’s weapon. Historical iron weapons tend

to have less friction than their bronze predecessors, which allows the blades to glide along each other thus providing less grip. This highlights the copper-alloy's capability of binding (binding is the deliberate pressing of the sword blade upon the opponent's blade, thus creating an almost sticky contact between the two weapons which allows to control the opponent's blade) and controlling.

The last two actions created no marks.

4.3.3 302. Second play

“From the Underhaw (under strike/strike from below), when he strikes from above. Wind against him to your left side, [with his sword] against your shield. Thus you stand in two shields. So wind to the right side opening and strike in at the mouth. See if he deals with this by raising his shield, and if so then take the left leg. This works on both sides.” (Farrell 2012, 3).

Figure 4.15 – 302. The defender starts with the sword on their shoulder for an *Oberhaw*, the attacker with their sword low next to the leg for an *Underhaw*. Both shields are extended forwards.

Figure 4.16 – 302a. *Oberhaw* and *Underhaw* twisting motion resulting in a

clashing contact at head level.

Figure 4.17 – 302b. The attacker twists their sword in preparation for a slash at the defender's face.

Figure 4.18 – Final move of the second play. The attacker slashes at the defender's face.

The second play consists of two clashing sword contacts. At first, the attacker and defender start from different positions (Figure 4.15). The defender commences with an *Oberhaw* from their shoulder, whilst the attacker responds with an *Underhaw* (upward strike from below), twisting into the defender's sword at head height (Figure 4.16). From this, the attacker twists their sword (Figure 4.17) then slashes at the defender's face (Figure 4.18). Should the defender raise their shield, the manuscript suggests striking at their leg. As neither action would have resulted in a sword contact, it was decided not to execute them.

302a. second play, *Underhaw and twist, Oberhaw* – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.15)

Figure 4.19 – 302a. SW6 attack, *Underhaw and twist*. Bulge, 327 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.20 – 302a. SW7 defend, *Oberhaw*. Bulge, 297 mm from the tip.

For the first contact of the second play, the attacking SW6 executed an *Underhaw* to meet SW7's *Oberhaw* at head height (Figure 4.16). In order to make contact with the forward cutting edge, SW6 was twisted upon impact, with the combatant's palm facing upwards, thus allowing greater control of both weapons. A bulge was created through the twisting motion in the mid-section of the cutting edge on both swords (Figure 4.19 and Figure 4.20).

302b. second play, twist – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.17)

Figure 4.21 – 302b.1 SW6 attack, twist. Striations, 358-70 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.23 – 302b. SW7 defend, no action. Bulge, 317 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.22 – 302b.2 SW6 attack, twist. Striations, 393-406 mm from the tip.

Following the initial contact, the attacker then twisted SW6 180° along the longitudinal axis to the left whilst maintaining constant contact with the defending SW7 (Figure 4.17). This twisting bound the swords together, thus allowing the attacker to control the defender’s sword whilst setting up the succeeding slash to the face. Whilst twisting, the attacking sword SW6 scraped along the cutting edge of SW7, and two sets of striations were created on the flat side of SW6 (Figure 4.21 & Figure 4.22). On the defending sword, the twisting caused the creation of a bulge in the mid-section of the cutting edge (Figure 4.23). As with the first play, both combatants felt that the properties of the copper-alloy swords made them outstandingly capable of twisting and binding motions, even more so than historical iron swords.

4.3.4 303. *Third play*

“From the buckler, from the Wechelhaw (changing strike), sweep from the left side. From your buckler sweep clearly above with your sword then cut into his head from the left side; wind [to the] opening and thrust into his mouth. If he lifts with the shield and with the sword and defends against this then cut with the long edge in at his right leg. This works on both sides.” (Farrell 2012, 3).

Figure 4.24 – 303. Both combatants start with the shield extended and the sword on their shoulder.

Figure 4.25 – The attacker is executing a *Wechelhaw* to counter the defender's *Oberhaw*.

Figure 4.26 – 303a. Head-level edge contact following the *Wechelhaw*.

Figure 4.27 – 303b. The attacker twists his sword. Note the inverted hand.

Figure 4.28 – 303c. Following a twirl, the attacker strikes at the defender's head who uses their sword to bind the incoming weapon.

Figure 4.29 – Final position of the third play. Note the downwards pointing sword of the defender from 303c.

For the third play, both combatants commence from the same starting position, with the shield arm extended and their swords resting on their shoulders (Figure 4.24). The attacker then carries out a *Wechelhaw* (changing strike), by moving their sword over to the left side of the body and conducting an upwards slash towards the defender's face. This is met by an *Oberhaw* from the defender (Figure 4.25), resulting in the first edge contact (303a.) of the third play (Figure 4.26). In an attempt to cut forwards into the defender's face, the attacker then twists their sword (note the inverted hand in Figure 4.27). To counter this, the defender pushes their sword upwards, and uses the friction between the two weapons to push the attacker's blade to the left (Figure 4.27). Having their sword back on the right side, the attacker then twirls it and executes a downward slash to the defender's skull. This is met with a binding parry which allows for the attacker's blade to be deflected once more (Figure 4.28). The play finishes with a thrust to the defender's belly (Figure 4.29) without sword contact.

303a. third play, *Wechelhaw*, *Oberhaw* – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.25)

Figure 4.30 – 303a. SW6 attack, *Wechelhaw*. Round notch (right) and rebound mark, 339 mm and 349 mm, respectively, from the tip.

Figure 4.31 – 303a. SW7 defend, *Oberhaw*. Curved graze, 225 mm from the tip.

Both swords were in motion during the first contact of the third play and clashed as the result of an upwards slash by the attacker and a downwards strike by the defender. Subsequently, a deep round notch and a small rebound mark (Figure 4.30) were created in the forward cutting edge of the attacking SW6. The high velocity impact further caused a curved graze (Figure 4.31) in the cutting edge of SW7.

303b. third play, twist, push – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.27)

Figure 4.32 -303b. SW6 attack, twist. Flattening, 265 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.33 – 303b. SW7 defend, push. Striation, 293-301 mm from the tip.

Attempting to strike the defender in the face, the attacker twists their sword 180° along the longitudinal axis and pushes forward. To stop this, the defender pushes their sword handle up and left, using the friction between the swords to control the attacker's weapon, before pushing the latter to the side. This caused SW6 to scrape along the flat side of SW7. The combined actions resulted in a flattening on the cutting edge of the attacking sword (Figure 4.32). A deep striation was created in the flat side of SW7 (Figure 4.33). The impact on the defending sword also caused the blade to bend slightly.

As discussed in Chapter 3, the flat side contact caused the blade to bend slightly. This bend, however, was deemed not significant, and the experiment was continued.

303c. third play, *Oberhaw*, binding – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.28)

Figure 4.34 – 303c. SW6 attack, *Oberhaw*. Striations, 286-99 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.35 – 303c. SW7 defend, binding. Bulge, 297 mm from the tip.

The final contact of the third play consisted of a downwards strike towards the defender's skull, whose sword bound and deflected the incoming weapon. SW6 was hereby impacted on the flat side of the blade, and a scratched striation pattern was created (Figure 4.34). The binding and deflecting caused a small bulge in the cutting edge of SW7 (Figure 4.35), created when the blade was slightly twisted to push SW6 to one side.

4.3.5 304. *Fourth play*

“From the *Mittelhaw* (middle strike) make the *Twer* (cross strike) to both sides and the *Schaitlär* (skull strike) with the long edge, then make a thrust in underneath.” (Farrell 2012, 3).

Figure 4.36 – 304. Both combatants start with their shield extended and the swords on their shoulder. The attacker carries out a swinging strike with the back cutting edge towards the defender's face.

Figure 4.37 – 304a. The attacker's strike is stopped with a dynamic edge parry.

Figure 4.38 – The attacker carries out a cross strike to attack from the other side.

Figure 4.39 – 304b. The defender twists their sword to parry and control the incoming attack.

Figure 4.40 – 304c. The attacker changes direction again to strike at the defender's head.

Figure 4.41 – The fourth play finished with a thrust to the defender's body.

Both combatants commence the fourth play from the same starting position, with their shields extended and the swords resting on their shoulders (Figure 4.36). To set up the *Twer* (cross strike), the attacker carries out a scything strike with the back cutting edge to the right of the defender's head. This is met by a dynamic edge parry in front of the defender's face (Figure 4.37). From this position, the attacker snaps his wrist to carry out a cross strike to attack from the opposite side (Figure 4.38). In defence, the opponent twists their sword upon impact, thus binding and controlling the attacker's weapon momentarily (Figure 4.39). To break the bind, the attacker pulls their sword backwards, changes direction again and strikes at the defender's skull from the right (Figure 4.40). The attacking sword is bound and deflected away to the left

of the defender (Figure 4.40). Finally, the attacker uses their shield to control the opponent's weapons, and thrusts at the defender's open body (Figure 4.41).

304a. fourth play, scything strike, dynamic parry – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.37)

Figure 4.42 – 304a. SW6 attack, scything strike with back cutting edge. Curved graze, 213 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.43 – 304a. SW7 defend, dynamic parry. Sharp notch and rebound mark, 337 mm from the tip.

The first contact of the fourth play was the result of a scything strike, executed with the back cutting edge of SW6, defended with a dynamic edge parry. A small curved graze was created in the back cutting edge of SW6 (Figure 4.42). In the defending sword SW7, a sharp notch and a shallow rebound mark were created (Figure 4.43). Both marks indicate the high-velocity with which the swords clashed.

304b. fourth play, cross strike, twist and bind – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.39)

Figure 4.44 – 304b. SW6 attack, cross strike. Bulge, 361 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.45 – 304b. SW7 defend, twist and bind. Curved graze, 392 mm from the tip.

In order to strike the defender's head from the left, the attacker snaps his wrist and conducts a strike from the opposite side with the forward cutting edge. Upon impact, the defender twists and binds their blade to control the attacking weapons. This action caused a bulge in the cutting edge of SW6 (Figure 4.44). A curved graze was created in the cutting edge of the defending SW7 (Figure 4.45).

304c. fourth play, vertical skull strike, binding – SW6 attack, SW7 defend (Figure 4.40)

Figure 4.46 – 304c. SW6 attack, vertical skull strike. Curved graze, 476 mm from the tip.

Figure 4.47 – 304c. SW7 defend, binding. Shallow bulge, 199 mm from the tip.

Pulling away from the previous bind, the attacker stretches their arm to execute a vertical downwards strike to the skull of the opponent. This strike is caught and bound by the defender's sword, and eventually deflected to the side. Having to stretch to reach the defender's head, a curved graze was created close to the hilt on the cutting edge of SW6 (Figure 4.46). The binding caused a shallow bulge in the defending SW7 (Figure 4.47).

The grazes and bulges created in this play are the result of high-velocity swinging impacts and binding and twisting motions, respectively.

4.3.6 305. Fifth play

“From the *Sturzhaw* (plunging strike) make as if to go to [his] left side over his shield with a thrust then with the point change under and thrust swiftly inside his shield. Wind immediately to your left side and if he defends against this then take his right leg with your long edge.” (Farrell 2012, 3).

Figure 4.48 – 305. Both combatants start from the same position. The attacker prepares for a *Sturzhaw*, the defender for an *Oberhaw*.

Figure 4.49 – The attacker carries out a backhand thrust to the defender’s face, which is intercepted by the flat of the defender’s blade.

Figure 4.50 – 305a. Unintentional flat parry intercepting a thrust to the face.

Figure 4.51 – Final position of the fifth play.

Both combatants commence the fifth play from the same position, with their shield arm extended and the sword resting on their shoulder (Figure 4.48). The attacker prepares for a plunging strike from the left by inverting their sword and dropping the tip, allowing them to stab at the defender's face, while the defender prepares for an *Oberhaw* (Figure 4.49).

Contact is made when the cutting edge of the attacker's blade is intercepted by the flat of the defender's, thus deflecting the latter's sword to the side (Figure 4.50). The attacker then uses their shield to control the defender's weapons, and thrusts into the defender's face from the right (Figure 4.51). This play was carried out twice, as no marks were created on either sword the first time. The following mark (305a.) was created during the repeat.

305a. fifth play repeat, backhand thrust to the face, unintentional flat parry – SW6 attack, SW 7 defend (Figure 4.50)

Figure 4.52 – 305a. SW7 defend, impact on the flat of the blade. Striations, 209-240.

The only blade contact of the fifth play occurs when the backhand thrust of the attacker is intercepted by the flat of the defender's blade. Although contact was made during the first attempt of this play, no wear marks were created. During the repeat, the only marks created were a set of striations on the flat of the defending SW7 (Figure 4.52). No marks were created on the attacking sword SW6. Despite the impact on SW7, the sword was not noticeably bent.

4.3.7 Summary of marks

The following table (Table 4.1) provides a summary of all marks created during the actualistic experiments.

Test ref	Attack				Defence			
	Weapon	Strike	Mark	Micronotch	Weapon	Strike	Mark	Micronotch
301a.	SW6	<i>Oberhaw</i>	curved graze	no	SW7	<i>Oberhaw</i>	round notch	no
301b.	SW6	twist and push	three micronotches	no	SW7	no action	micronotch	no
302a.	SW6	<i>Underhaw</i> and twist	bulge	no	SW7	<i>Oberhaw</i>	bulge	no
302b.	SW6	twist and bind	striations	no	SW7	no action	bulge	no
303a.	SW6	<i>Wechelhaw</i>	round notch	yes	SW7	<i>Oberhaw</i>	curved graze	no
303b.	SW6	twist	flattening	no	SW7	push	striation	no
303c.	SW6	<i>Oberhaw</i>	striations	no	SW7	binding	bulge	no
304a.	SW6	scything strike	curved graze	no	SW7	dynamic edge	sharp notch	yes
304b.	SW6	cross strike	bulge	no	SW7	twist and bind	curved graze	no
304b.	SW6	vertical skull strike	curved graze	no	SW7	binding	bulge	no
305a.	SW6	backhand thrust	no mark	no	SW7	impact on flat	striations	no

Table 4.1 – Summary of the sword marks created during the actualistic experiments discussed in this chapter.

4.4 Results

The actualistic experiments successfully recreated further marks for the reference database, some of which can conclusively be attributed to certain combat actions. Furthermore, the methodology allowed for detailed recording of actual combat. Although the swords are referred to as “attacking” and “defending”, in reality all actions were essentially offensive. It quickly became apparent that, in real combat, attacking and defending motions become interchangeable.

Figure 4.53 – Locations of marks created on SW6 during the actualistic experiments.

Figure 4.54 – Locations of marks created on SW7 during the actualistic experiments.

During the experiment, both swords were held in the same way for each play, resulting in clear edge dominance on both swords (Figure 4.53; Figure 4.54).

Figure 4.55 – Traditional grip (left) and a grip with the thumb on the flat of the blade. The latter allows for quick changes of direction.

The swords were held in both a traditional grip and with the thumb on the flat of the blade (Figure 4.55), depending on action. The latter completely changes the balance of the sword, and allows for extremely fast changes of direction as well as greater control during horizontal strikes. A disadvantage of this grip, however, is that the maximum amount of force one can put into an attack decreases.

Figure 4.56 – Flowchart displaying how bulges were created actively and passively during the actualistic experiments.

Bulges were the most commonly created mark, and in all six cases is their formation related to twisting and/or binding movements (Figure 4.56). Half of these were created actively, i.e. in the sword that was carrying out a twist or a bind (302a.; 303c.; 304b.). The other half were created passively, i.e. the bulge was created in the sword that was being controlled by the opponent’s blade (304b.; 302a.; 302b.). Bulges have exclusively been reproduced through twisting and/or binding, a technique that requires training and practice, and are thus indicative of such motions in both attacking and defending swords.

Figure 4.57 – Flowchart displaying how curved grazes were created actively and passively during the actualistic experiments

The second most commonly created marks were curved grazes (Figure 4.57). Scything strikes (304a.), vertical skull strikes (304b.), and *Oberhaws* (301a.; 303a.) all created curved grazes. In all four active cases the sword was met by an equally fast-moving opposing blade. The passive creation was the result of the opposing blade carrying out a cross strike, which was countered by twisting and binding to control the other weapon, thus creating a bulge and a curved graze (304b.).

Figure 4.58 – Flowchart displaying how striations were created actively and passively during the actualistic experiments.

Striations were most commonly created passively as the result of another weapon impacting on the flat of the blade. In those cases, the striations were caused by binding (303c.), twisting (303b.), and a backhand thrust connecting with the flat (305a.). Only in one case was the striation caused actively, when the sword was used to twist and bind the opponent’s weapon, thus scraping along the cutting edge of their blade (302b.).

Two round notches were created during an *Oberhaw* (301a.) and a *Wechelhaw* (303a.). In both cases, a curved graze was created in the other blade. One sharp notch was created when a dynamic edge parry was carried out (304a.). Again, the opposing weapon sustained a curved graze. One case of flattening of the cutting edge could be recorded, created as the result of a twisting action against a pushing blade (303b.). Finally, a twisting and pushing action against a static blade created three micronotches and one micronotch, respectively (301b.).

The experimental methodology proved feasible, and allowed me to conduct detailed wear analysis whilst carrying out real-life combat. Valuable results were obtained from the actualistic experiments. It was shown that grazes are most often related to impacts created when both blades clash at high speed. Twisting and binding motions could be carried out very successfully, and the material properties of the copper-alloy work in favour of such actions. Whilst not all binds or twists created a single type of mark, it has conclusively been demonstrated that bulges are always the result of binding and twisting motions, either actively or passively. Finally, a distinct distribution of marks was created. By holding the sword in a certain way every single time, the vast majority of marks were created on the forward cutting edge, thus displaying edge dominance (Figure 4.53 & Figure 4.54). All marks were created in the middle and upper third of the swords, whilst the lower third and tips remained unscathed. As in the previous experiments (see Chapter 3.5), no relationship between blade section and offensive or defensive motions could be detected.

From an experiential point of view, the swords proved capable of being used according to mediaeval fighting style when used within the known limitations. The swords were just as capable of striking, slicing, and thrusting as their mediaeval iron successors. Placing the

thumb on the flat of the blade just above the shoulders has proven to be extremely effective, and it allows for a completely different control of the weapon than a more basic grip on the hilt. Carrying out binding and twisting motions proved extremely effective with the replica swords. It felt as if the copper-alloy was physically glued to the opponent's sword, making it easy to control the opponent's sword. The short blades and balance of the Ewart Park swords allowed for quick changes of direction, allowing for both forward and backhand strikes to be carried out with ease. Deliberately seeking blade contact with the opponent's blade in order to control their weapon and prime your own for the next attack, rather than accidental damage as suggested by Horn (2013), could explain the amount of wear marks observed on original Bronze Age swords.

4.5 Evaluation

Although this experiment was successful in conducting and recording actualistic combat experiments based on historical manuscripts, a critical reflection of the tests reveals the positives and negatives of the approach.

The methodology successfully allowed for the recording of "real-life" combat, albeit broken into sections, which could be cross-referenced with the marks that were created during the fight. Those marks have expanded the reference database, and previously unexplained marks such as bulges could be created. The tests have also changed my understanding of how marks can be created, and that they are not necessarily the result of accidental damage.

With the exception of bulges, all of the marks created during this actualistic experiment resemble the marks created during the first set of combat tests. As the strikes carried out in this set of experiment are essentially the same actions as the sword strikes in Chapter 3, albeit termed differently in accordance with the historical manuscript, the fact that the same types of marks were created highlights the repeatability of the experiment. Bulges, however, were only created as a result of *versetzen* (displacement), a technique that was not employed during the first tests.

As the production of the swords used for this experiment was commissioned before Wang's (in prep.) metallurgical study of the previous test weapons was conducted, the same issues with material authenticity and workmanship as outlined in the previous chapter (see Chapter 3.6) remain.

For a number of reasons, it was not possible to test the swords against other weapons during this set of experiments. First of all, the methodology of recording fluid combat had never been tested, and as such it was uncertain as to what extent it would be successful. It was therefore

decided to start with a small, manageable number of tests and weapons. Secondly, the replica weapons were expensive and only two swords could be afforded. Subsequently, the shields from the first experiments were repaired and used for this set of tests. Thirdly, this experiment was based on historical combat manuals, and it took a year of training before I felt confident enough to understand and conduct the swordplay. Introducing other weapons would have required the study of further manuscripts and would have gone beyond the scope of this research. For future tests, this problem could be compensated for by expanding the collaboration with HEMA experts, with the researcher solely focussing on understanding the combat without actually training and conducting it.

The sword plays conducted during the experiment are only a fraction of what is available in historical sources, and it is by no means certain that prehistoric combat was conducted in this way. However, from an experiential point of view, the replica swords proved extremely capable of the actions, and good data was created on the swords. Although the experiments cannot prove that prehistoric combat was definitely conducted in such ways, these actions *could* have been carried out.

4.6 Conclusion

The methodology developed for the experiment discussed in this chapter proved feasible and successful. Basing combat actions on suitable historical manuscripts, it was possible to conduct real combat, broken into sequences, whilst still being able to record and match individual wear marks with their corresponding actions. Besides recreating edge dominance and previously unexplained marks such as bulges, this experiment has shown that combat wear marks are likely the result of deliberate contact with the opponent's blade, and that changing the way the sword is held provides different control of the weapon. The replica marks created during the experiments discussed in this, and the previous chapter can now be used as a reference collection to interpret the wear on original Bronze Age swords. In order to derive exactly how these swords were used, the next chapter discusses the wear on 70 original specimens from the British Bronze Age.

Chapter 5. Wear analysis of British swords

5.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the chronologies and archaeological contexts of the 70 British swords analysed for this research, before describing the specimens and their wear in detail. These swords are interpreted in relation to the reference marks created during the experiments discussed in Chapters 3 and 4. The individual discussion of each sword is followed by statistical analysis of the entire sample.

5.2 Method

Research trips to five English museums were undertaken to analyse and record a total of 70 British Middle and Late Bronze Age swords. Initially, I had planned to exclusively analyse swords of type Ewart Park. However, it soon transpired that it would be impossible to access a large enough number of well-preserved Ewart Park swords to collect a meaningful data set. Instead, it was agreed to extend the focus to any contemporary leaf-shaped copper-alloy swords, as although typologically different, the functional elements (i.e. the shape of the blade) remained the same. Also, many aspects of modern typology, such as minimal deviations in the hilt form or the number of rivet holes in a specific section of the blade, would have had negligible influence on the functionality of the sword, and most likely remained completely irrelevant to, and likely unnoticed by, the Bronze Age user.

In May 2015, permission was granted to carry out two research visits to the British Museum to analyse a total of 20 swords. Whilst struggling with very limited access hours and constant supervision, it was possible to carry out the analysis successfully, and valuable data could be gained. To boost the data set, permission was granted by the Museum of London to analyse 25 swords from the collections in July 2017. The curatorial team could not have been more cooperative and supportive, and the analysis was successfully carried out within four days. In an attempt to further increase the data set, and cut down on travelling costs, two local museums were approached after locating relevant swords in the literature. Access to two swords in the Alnwick Castle collection was granted, and a day trip was undertaken to analyse them. However, once there, the enthusiastic curator presented me with several other boxes containing around 20 swords. A second research visit was agreed, and in the end a total of seven swords could be analysed in Alnwick. The second local museum was the Preston Park Museum & Grounds in Stockton-on-Tees. After originally requesting access to three swords, it soon became apparent that one of the swords was blatantly a fake, modern copy of a Bronze Age sword. Thus, only two swords were analysed. To further increase the data set, it was decided to also include the data of 17 swords, which I had analysed for my Master's thesis in

2014 (Hermann 2014). Eight of those swords are in the possession of the Great North Museum: Hancock in Newcastle, and were analysed in the Wolfson Archaeology Laboratory on campus. For the remaining nine swords, permission was granted by the Yorkshire Museum of Archaeology to analyse them during a series of day trips to York in July 2014. Having conducted several further combat experiments and an extensive amount of analysis since writing the MA thesis, my terminology, interpretations and theories have developed significantly. Thus, the MA data has been completely reworked, updated, and reinterpreted for the purpose of this research.

The data was collected in accordance with the wear analysis technique outlined in Chapter 3. Two types of setups were used, depending on circumstances. In the cases of the Yorkshire Museum of Archaeology, the Alnwick Castle Museum, and Preston Park Museum & Grounds, where only a small number of swords were analysed during individual day trips, a lightweight, handheld DinoLite digital microscope and DinoCapture software were used to collect the images. Knowing that a large amount of data would have to be collected over several days at the British Museum and the Museum of London, I decided to bring a GX-Cam 9 mounted on an optical stereo microscope, with GX Capture software to capture high-resolution micrographs. The same microscope was also used in the Wolfson Archaeology Laboratory, where it is usually permanently set up. Whilst the DinoLite is an affordable, compact, and easily transported device that takes acceptable micrographs, its limitations mean that it is not adequate to record large amounts of data. Being a handheld microscope, the DinoLite requires an extremely steady hand to take a picture in focus, which significantly slows down the recording process. Furthermore, the setup of the microscope does not allow to take clear images with a variety of magnifications. Instead, the magnification dial only serves to bring the picture into one focus.

Figure 5.1 - Low-quality image taken with the DinoLite (left) compared to high-quality photograph with GX-CAM9.

The quality and resolution of the pictures is also not comparable to those taken with the GX-Cam 9 (Figure 5.1). Although analysis can be carried out to the same accuracy, albeit with lower quality micrographs, the process is too time consuming to analyse a large number of swords. This explains my choice of recording devices, which were selected in accordance with the specific circumstances of each recording session.

An Access database (see Appendix A) was used to record type, size, and location of each mark. The locations are referred to as obverse (the side with the accession number painted on) or reverse, left or right cutting edge (when held with the tip downwards), and distance from the tip. Consequently, over 1600 wear marks and numerous patterns could be identified. The following pages provide an insight into the archaeological contexts, or lack thereof of the swords analysed, and an introduction to the main chronological phases of the later British Bronze Age, followed by descriptions of the swords and their marks, as well as an analysis of the patterns and possible interpretations. All swords have been divided into categories, first chronologically, then by the number of marks detected on the cutting edges.

5.3 Archaeological contexts/provenance

Figure 5.2 – Map of the British Isles showing the provenance of the British swords described in this chapter.

The majority of swords described in this chapter are single finds, often from water-logged contexts, with little or no contextual information. In the cases in which further information could be retrieved from the literature, this is included in the individual sword descriptions in section 5.5. As some swords were recovered from the same location, the map (Figure 5.2) displays occasional tight clusters of provenance markers.

5.4 Sword chronologies

5.4.1 Table

The following table provides the relative and absolute chronologies of all British sword types examined as part of this research. Whilst the relative chronologies were taken from the relevant sections in Burgess & Colquhoun 1988 *The Swords of Britain*, the absolute chronologies were determined through cross-reference with the synchronized version of the relevant chronological systems for Western Europe (Roberts et al. 2015, 18-9 fig. 2.1). Whilst an effort was made to express the relevant chronologies using the system developed by Needham (1996), the swords belonging to types Ballintober, Wilburton Variant A, Holme Pierrepont and Gündlingen could only be dated by direct comparison to their continental equivalents (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 22, 43); hence Central European chronology after Reinecke (1965) had to be included. Types Wilburton, Ewart Park and Gündlingen are divided into several subcategories. For type Wilburton, it was possible to determine absolute chronologies for each subtype in accordance with their individual relative chronologies outlined in Burgess & Colquhoun (1988, 43, 48, 50-2). Due to a chronic lack of reliable associated finds (*ibid.*, 71-2, 83-4, 101-2), or contradictory evidence (*ibid.*, 74), individual relative chronologies could not be determined for the Ewart Park and Gündlingen subtypes. Instead, they have been dated to their respective metalworking phases. For the purpose of this research, where the chronology is merely used as a tool to organize the data, this is entirely sufficient. Any possible deviations at the scale of a few decades are negligible.

Sword ID (Acc. No.)	Type	Relative Chronology	Absolute Chronology	Reference
2 (WG.1250), 49 (ACAT 236), 58 (YORYM1948.1308), 61 (YORYM1948.1303)	Ballintober	Bz D/ Ha A1	1325-1140 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 22
25 (B.25), 33 (O.1368), 37 (O.1332)	Limehouse	Penard Phase	1275-1140 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 34
56 (YORYM1948.1300)	Clewer	Later Penard Phase	1200-1140 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 32
30 (49.107/812)	Teddington	Penard-Wilburton transition	1200-1100 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 39
28 (O.1356)	Wilburton, Variant F	Early Wilburton Phase	1150-1100 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 50-1
23 (O.1364), 35 (O.1359), 41 (O.1337)	Wilburton, Variant C	Final Wilburton Phase	1025-975 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 48

11 (WG.1268), 59 (YORYM1966.1)	Wilburton, Variant G	Final Wilburton Phase	1025-975 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 52
3 (OA.124), 22 (O.1367), 36 (O.1361), 39 (O.1341), 44 (O.1358)	Wilburton, Variant A	Ha B1	1025-925 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 43
19 (1858,1115.1)	Ewart Park, Caledonian Step 1	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 101-2
47 (ACAT 234)	Ewart Park, Caledonian Unclassified	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 101-2
16 (1878,1101.203)	Ewart Park, Eastern Step 1	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 83-4
17 (1892,1104.4)	Ewart Park, Eastern Step 2	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 83-4
13 (1892,1104.3)	Ewart Park, Eastern Step 3	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 83-4
52 (ACAT 228), 55 (YORYM1948.1161)	Ewart Park, Northern Step 1	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 101-2
18 (1858,1115.2), 46 (ACAT 230), 63 (YORYM1948.1245), 66 (NEWMA1932.21), 67 (NEWMA1932.20)	Ewart Park, Northern Step 2	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 101-2
6 (1951,1007.1), 15 (1911,1021.6), 57 (YORYM1948.1148), 65 (NEWMA1814.22.1), 68 (NEWMA1814.22.2), 69 (NEWMA1932.22), 70 (NEWMA1923.9)	Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 101-2
12 (1863,0122.115), 40 (O.1371), 45 (O.1346), 48 (ACAT 390), 50 (STCMG:1925.SB24.012), 51 (STCMG:1925.SB24.014), 53 (ACAT 387), 62 (YORYM1948.1162)	Ewart Park, unprovenanced	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 55-106
21 (28.181/1), 24 (57), 31 (49.107/118)	Ewart Park, South-Eastern Step 2	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 71
32 (A.27190), 38 (A.16956), 43 (28.137/1)	Ewart Park, South-Eastern Step 3	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 72

5 (WG.1244), 7 (WG.1246), 29 (O.1355), 34 (O.1354)	Ewart Park, South-Eastern Step 4	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 74
4 (WG.1241)	Ewart Park, Western Step 2	Ewart Park Phase	925-800 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 88
1 (1850,1226.1), 20 (1864,0903.5)	Holme Pierrepont	Ha C	800-600 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 113-4
9 (1857,0920.1), 27 (O.1357)	Gündlingen, Variant B	Ha C	800-600 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 116
8 (1863,0122.119), 10 (WG.2271), 60 (YORYM1948.1301), 64 (NEWMA1886.33)	Gündlingen, Variant C	Ha C	800-600 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 116
14 (WG.1238)	Gündlingen, Variant D	Ha C	800-600 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 116
71 (NEWMA1929.67)	Gündlingen, Unclassified	Ha C	800-600 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 116
26 (O.1379), 42 (O.1342)	Gündlingen, unprovenanced	Ha C	800-600 cal BC	Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 116

Table 5.1 – Relative and absolute chronologies of all British sword types examined.

5.4.2 Chronological Phases

Table 5.1 suggests that the British swords examined for this research can be organized into four general chronological phases, namely Penard (1275-1140 cal BC), Wilburton (1150-975 cal BC), Ewart Park (925-800 cal BC), and Hallstatt C (800-600 cal BC; after Roberts et al. 2015; Needham 1996; Reinecke 1965).

This thesis utilizes the standard terminology for British Bronze Age chronology as it is now widely accepted amongst scholars, which divides the period into phases based on metalworking traditions. The terminology is fundamentally based on the period system developed by Hawkes (1960), which was modified and completed by several authors (e.g. Britton 1963; Burgess 1968a; 1968b; 1974; Coles 1959-60; 1963-4; 1968-9; Eogan 1964) to include said phases. With advances in technology and an increasing amount of C14-dates, the most recent absolute chronologies for each phase were developed by Needham (1996) and Roberts et al. (2015). Whilst this system has an obvious issue with regional variations (Burgess 1974), or potentially long life-cycles of individual swords, which were cast during a certain period, then passed on as heirlooms over many generations, in this case the chronology is merely used to organise the data set.

In some cases, Reinecke's (1902; 1965) chronological system had to be used. The conceptualisation of Hallstatt C as part of the Bronze to Iron Age transition period, and how

our understanding of Hallstatt C has changed since Reinecke, should therefore briefly be introduced. Particularly as the term “Hallstatt” is more conventionally associated with the continental Iron Age. In order to create a chronological system for later prehistory in central Europe, and in response to Montelius’s division of the northern Bronze Age into six sub-periods (I-VI; Montelius 1885), Reinecke developed a multi-phase system for the central European Bronze Age (*Bronzezeit* BzA-D; Reinecke 1902; 1911a-c) and Iron Age (Hallstatt A-D (1911d-h) and Latène A-D (1911i-l). As absolute dating methods had not yet been invented at this stage, his relative chronology and the absolute dates he assigned to each phase were based on cross-referencing artefacts with historically-dated objects from southern Europe (Gerloff 2007, 118). Despite the overwhelming presence of copper-alloy artefacts during what is now perceived to be the Late Bronze Age, Reinecke assigned this period to the earliest Iron Age, as some copper-alloy objects comprised iron components. He further cross-dated the Urnfield period (Hallstatt A and B) with the “pre-Etruscan” Iron Age from Italy, as they shared similar forms of pottery, metal types and funerary traditions (ibid., 120). Reinecke’s assignment of a period so rich in copper-alloy objects to the Iron Age, however, caused great controversy amongst other scholars, and his system was only partially adopted throughout Europe. Advances in the typology and dating of copper-alloy artefacts, as well as the inconsistency of Reinecke’s terminology, as “Hallstatt” was intrinsically associated with the purely Iron Age concept of the Celts, inspired Childe to rename Hallstatt A and B into BzE and F (Childe 1948, 180), thus ultimately assigning these periods to the end of the Bronze Age. This concept was accepted by other scholars such as Hawkes (1948). Cross-referencing Reinecke’s chronology with the British system of metalworking stages as introduced by Burgess (1974) and developed by Needham (1996), has linked Hallstatt C with the Llyn Fwar Phase, both of which are characterised by their assemblages of both copper-alloy and iron artefacts, thus identifying the period as a transitional phase between the Final Bronze Age and the Earliest Iron Age (Roberts et al. 2015, 19; O’Connor 2007, 64, 71, 74; 1980, 271).

The following pages provide a brief introduction to the wider contexts of the four British metalworking phases from this chapter.

Penard Phase

The Penard Phase, named after the Welsh Penard Hoard (Crawford & Wheeler 1920-1, 138), is closely linked to the rise of the Urnfield traditions of Central Europe, which, although originating on the continent, had a significant impact on the material culture of the British Isles. Whilst the number of early Urnfield imports remains small, the arrival of stimuli from the continent resulted in an explosion of experimental metalwork amongst British smiths. As

a result, many traditional artefact types, such as Group D palstave axes, notched-butt dirks and rapiers, and certain spearheads, were developed, and completely original types were created. It is important to note that the distribution of Urnfield artefacts is concentrated around the South-English Thames Valley, South Wales and Ireland, creating an unusual link between southern Britain and the latter, whilst the northern parts of England and Scotland remain relatively untouched. Generally, Urnfield material does not occur in isolation, but mixed in with local artefact types. There is also a strong link to materials found in Brittany, and especially Ballintober type swords appear on both sides of the Channel (Burgess 1974, 205-7).

Wilburton Phase

Once the Wilburton Phase arose, the noticeable Urnfield impact of the earlier Penard Phase soon ceased to exist, along with its unusual England-Ireland connection, whilst cross-Channel links to Brittany remained persistently strong. The phase saw the introduction of a new lead-bronze alloy, designed to increase viscosity and improve the casting properties of the metal, as well as a new industrialised repertoire of artefacts. For the first, time leaf-shaped swords, pegged spearheads and socketed axes were produced in large quantities in Britain. Similar artefacts were created across the Channel, yet with different emphasis on certain properties of the artefacts. Geographically, Wilburton material is most common in the southern and middle parts of England, whilst being practically absent from the highland areas of Wales, Northern England and Scotland. The contemporary presence of earlier artefact types and copper-alloys in these areas suggests that those materials were still present, and highlights the issue of regional variations within the system (Burgess 1974, 207-9).

Ewart Park Phase

This latest phase of the Late Bronze Age saw an “industrial revolution” spreading through the British Isles, ending the southern monopoly and drastically increasing the amount of copper-alloy artefacts produced and deposited. The material culture began to display diverse cultural influences from the Mediterranean, Atlantic, Late Urnfield, and Northern Europe, suggesting cultural links and connections with the rest of mainland Europe, whilst retaining its original insular characteristics. Not only did the quantity of metal artefacts increase to an industrial level, the amount of hoards and water-logged depositions also dramatically grew. It has been suggested that the rise of the Hallstatt culture on the continent, and deteriorating climate on the British Isles, resulted in a period of unrest and uncertainty, despite the significant technological developments of the time. Whilst there are certain aspects of metallurgy, such as Ewart Park swords that are uniform throughout the British Isles, there are clear differences

between the regional industries, which include different production technologies and methods as well as regional products, which are directly related to the relative proximity and availability of raw materials. Interestingly, whilst the Ewart Park material culture displays clear signs of Hallstatt influence, there is very little evidence of imported Hallstatt artefacts in Britain (Burgess 1974, 209-14).

Llyn Fawr Phase (Hallstatt C)

The Llyn Fawr Phase, named after a hoard discovered in Llyn Fawr, South Wales, between 1909-13, was the final metalworking stage of the British Bronze Age, which spread over two centuries during the transition between Bronze and Iron Age. Whilst iron objects gradually found their way into the record, copper-alloy artefacts, and especially swords, continued to be produced. It has been suggested that changes in deposition practices were linked to a reduced supply of metal artefacts from the continent (O'Connor 2007, 74).

5.5 Swords descriptions and figures

The following pages provide detailed descriptions of each British sword analysed for this research, their recorded wear marks and possible interpretations. Where available, the compositional data of the alloys has been included. The swords are organised in four chronological categories, and within each category by the number of marks recorded per sword. Visibility of marks has also been included, with “1” being excellent visibility (where a full assessment of the sword was possible), “2” being poor visibility (where only partial analysis could be carried out), and “3” being extremely poor visibility (where the majority of the blade could not be examined).

5.5.1 Penard Phase

Sword ID 49 – ACAT 236 (Figure 5.3)

Figure 5.3 – Sword ID 49 obverse. Image courtesy of Eve Recherchon.

3	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Irregular Graze
Left	1	n/a	n/a
Right	n/a	1	1
Visibility	1		

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ballintober, Chelsea Variant, was a single find discovered near a gasometer in Bath, Somerset, possibly deposited in a stone coffin (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 22 No. 46). The sword is covered in patchy white, brown, green, and grey patina. There are four rivets *in situ* in the broad hilt tang. The shoulders are short and rounded. Ricassi, bevel lines or midrib are not present. The total length of this sword is 446 mm.

Only three wear marks could be identified on this sword, one on the left and two on the right cutting edge. The indentation on the left is located in the mid-section of the blade, whereas the two marks on the right are located in close proximity to each other close to the hilt.

Although the three marks appear to be the result of clashing impacts with other weapons, the locations of the marks suggest that they could have been caused in a non-combat scenario. The close proximity of the two marks on the right could be the result of a twice repeated action, such as hacking another object. If the sword was indeed recovered from a coffin, the marks could have been produced during a ritual or ceremony related to the deposition.

Sword ID 61 – YORYM1948.1303 (Figure 5.4)

Figure 5.4 – Sword ID 61 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

6	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	n/a	n/a	1	n/a	1
Right	1	1	n/a	2	n/a
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ballintober was recovered from the River Thames in Hammersmith, London (Burgess and & Colquhoun 1988, 20 No. 27). The sword is covered in smooth green patina, which was partly removed. There are four drilled rivet holes in the tongue, with one rivet remaining *in situ*. Short curved shoulders, slightly curved ricassi and a midrib are present. The total length of this sword is 428 mm.

A total of six wear marks could be identified on this sword, two on the left and four on the right cutting edge. Both marks on the left edge are located in close proximity to each other in the upper half of the blade. Three marks on the left edge are close to the tip, the fourth is in the mid-section of the blade.

This sword displays the signs of at least one combat encounter with another bladed weapon. The bulge (Figure 5.5) suggests that binding and twisting motions existed in the present combat styles (see Chapter 4.4).

Figure 5.5 – Mark ID 1467, bulge, left cutting edge, 335 mm from the tip of Sword ID 61.

Sword ID 58 – YORYM1948.1308 (Figure 5.6)

Figure 5.6 – Sword ID 58 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

9	Indentation	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Bulge
Left	n/a	2	n/a	3	1
Right	1	n/a	1	n/a	1
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ballintober, Chelsea Variant, was recovered from an unspecified location in the River Thames (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 23 No. 53). The sword is completely covered in smooth brown patina. There are four bi-conically drilled rivet holes in the tongue. The hilt has very short, curved shoulders. Long, slightly curved ricassi and bevel lines are present. A midrib swelling can only be found in the upper fifth of the blade. Total length of this sword is 475 mm.

A total of nine wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with six on the left and three on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are curved grazes. Two bulges (Figure 5.7 & Figure 5.8) and tip pressure are present. The majority of marks are located in the lower third of the blade, close to the tip.

This sword shows the signs of at least one combat encounter. The marks suggest that high- and low-velocity cuts and slashes as well as binding and twisting motions were likely part of the individual's combat style (see Chapters 3.5 & 4.4).

Figure 5.7 – Mark ID 1368, bulge, right cutting edge, 124-7 mm from the tip of Sword ID 58.

Figure 5.8 – Mark ID 1374, bulge, left cutting edge, 91 mm from the tip of Sword ID 58.

Sword ID 33 – MOL O.1368 (Figure 5.9)

Figure 5.9 – Sword ID 33 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

12	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze
Left	2	1	2	n/a	1	1
Right	2	n/a	2	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	3					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Limehouse was recovered from the River Thames opposite the Feathers Public House in Wandsworth, London, in 1863 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 33 No. 95). The sword is covered in rough dark, black, brown and grey patina. There are patches of corrosion on the entire sword, especially along the cutting edges. Visibility=3 made the analysis almost impossible. There are ten bi-conically shaped drilled rivet holes (Figure 5.10): four in the tongue and three in each shoulder. The hilt has curved shoulders and curved ricassi. Bevel lines are only faint. The tip is slightly bent at 63 mm. Total length of this sword is 716 mm.

Despite the poor visibility, twelve prominent macroscopic wear marks could be identified, seven on the left and five on the right, including various indentations, notches, and grazes. It is likely that there would have been further, less pronounced wear marks on the blade, made undetectable by the corrosion. Tip pressure has occurred (Figure 5.11).

The poor state of the sword prevents a full interpretation of the sword, as it must be assumed that other wear marks may have been lost. It can be suggested, however, that the sword was used in at least one combat encounter against another bladed weapon.

Figure 5.10 – Drilled rivet holes in the hilt of Sword ID 33. Figure 5.11 – Mark ID 806, tip pressure on Sword ID 33.

Sword ID 2 – BM WG.1250 (Figure 5.12)

Figure 5.12 – Sword ID 2 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 4 No. 23).

14	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Compression Curling	Bulge	Rebound
Left	2	1	n/a	1	n/a	n/a	3	1
Right	3	n/a	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	2							

This slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park was recovered from the River Thames in Twickenham, Greater London (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 19 No. 23; Rowland 1976, 426 No. 1975) (NB the accession number WG1250 is listed twice in Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, for number 23, p.19 and for number 283, p. 71. The sword is in fact the one described on p. 19). The sword is complete with a fractured hilt and remains at a length of 547 mm. Three rivets remain *in situ*, the hilt has fractured at a fourth rivet hole and the rivet is missing. All four rivet holes are arranged in a rectangle in the tongue of the hilt. The shoulders are short and straight whereas the ricassi are unusually long (40 mm). Faint bevel lines are present. The sword is completely covered in rusty, slightly rough, brown and black patina. Due to a large amount of corrosion on the cutting edges (Visibility=2) only the bigger marks could be recorded.

Despite the corrosion, a total of 14 wear marks could be identified, eight on the left and six on the right cutting edge. All marks recorded on this sword are located in the lower two thirds of

Figure 5.13 – Mark ID 35, curved graze, left cutting edge, 65-72 mm from the tip of Sword ID 2.

the blade and consist of an array of indentations, notches, grazes (Figure 5.13), and bulges.

Due to the corrosion it was impossible to carry out a full analysis of the sword, and further marks most likely remain undetectable. Despite that, the sword appears to have been used in combat, displaying sign of high-velocity clashing impacts (i.e. grazes) and binding and twisting (i.e. bulges) motions (see Chapters 3.5 & 4.4).

Sword ID 37 – MOL O.1332 (Figure 5.14)

Figure 5.14 – Sword ID 37 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

15	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Irregular Graze	Compression Curling	Bulge
Left	4	1	1	n/a	1	n/a	3
Right	n/a	n/a	1	1	1	1	1
Visibility	1						

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
17.90	0.44	0.29	0.56	n/a	0.23	n/a	0.12	n/a	n/a	0.013

Table 5.2 – Sword ID 37 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 142).

The three pieces of this extremely elaborate leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Limehouse were recovered from the River Thames at Strand on the Green, Chiswick, Middlesex, in 1862 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 34 No. 100). With a total length of 687 mm, the sword fractured at 186 mm and 417 mm from the tip. There are signs of bending at both fracture points. The sword is completely covered in an even, smooth dark grey patina. There is one elongated rivet hole in the tongue, and two drilled rivet holes in each shoulder (Figure 5.15). A third rivet hole was attempted in each shoulder but remains unfinished. One rivet remains *in situ* on the left. The shoulders and ricassi are curved. Broad bevel lines and a midrib are present. There is some decoration on the blade.

A total of 15 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with ten on the left and five on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are bulges (Figure 5.16) and indentations. All but two marks on the left cutting edge are located within the upper half of the blade.

The edge dominance may suggest that the sword had a single owner who consistently held it in the same manner. Binding and twisting motions were prevalent in the combat style. The deliberate bending and fracturing of the blade could have been carried out as part of a ritual prior to deposition in the river.

Figure 5.15 – Drilled rivet hole and one rivet *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 37.

Figure 5.16 – Mark ID 860, bulge, left cutting edge, 272 mm from the tip of Sword ID 37.

Sword ID 25 – MOL B.25 (Figure 5.17)

Figure 5.17 – Sword ID 25 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 16 No. 96).

73	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Rebound
Left	n/a	15	20	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Right	1	17	10	1	2	5	1	1
Visibility	1							

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Limehouse was discovered in 1852, 28 mm below gravel in blue clay in the River Thames at Kingston on Thames, Surrey (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 33 No. 96). There are nine cast rivet holes (Figure 5.18) in the hilt, three in each shoulder and three in the tongue. The shoulders and ricassi are slightly curved. Bevel lines and a slight midrib in the upper half of the blade are present. The sword is in good condition and completely covered in smooth black patina. Total length of this sword is 541 mm.

A total of 73 wear marks could be identified on this sword, evenly distributed with 35 on the left and 38 on the right. The most common marks are sharp notches and round notches (Figure 5.20 & Figure 5.19), which add up to 85 % of the marks on this sword. There is only one indentation and few grazes. The marks are very evenly distributed along the lengths of both cutting edges.

Assuming that round notches and sharp notches are created through similar, controlled motions (compare O’Flaherty et al. 2011, 11), the large number of these marks and even distribution may suggest that this sword was perhaps used as a training weapon rather than in extensive actual combat. The latter would likely create a larger variety of marks, and, if executed by a skilled swordsman, a more distinct clustering and pattern along the cutting edges. Instead it appears as if the sword was used numerous times, with varying degrees of success, to practice certain strikes and motions.

Figure 5.18 – Cast rivet holes in the hilt of Sword ID 25.

Figure 5.20 – Mark ID 633, round notch, left cutting edge, 218 mm from the tip of Sword ID 25.

Figure 5.19 – Cluster of marks in immediate proximity to each other. Sharp notch (Mark ID 626), round notch Mark ID 627), sharp notch (Mark ID 628), 273-7 mm from the tip of Sword ID 25.

Sword ID 56 – YORYM1948.1300 (Figure 5.21)

Figure 5.21 – Sword ID 56 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

84	Indentation	Round Notch	Sharp Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Flattening	Rebound
Left	6	19	5	n/a	5	3	5	1	1
Right	5	15	5	1	1	5	6	n/a	1
Visibility	1								

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Clewer was recovered from the River Thames in 1899 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 32 No. 93). The sword is completely covered in dark brown and black patina. Small corrosion holes and casting faults can be found all over the sword. There are five cast rivet holes in each shoulder, and one elongated rivet slot in the tongue. Long, slightly curved shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines and a midrib are present. Total length of this sword is 785 mm.

A total of 84 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 45 on the left and 39 on the right cutting edge. By far the most common marks are round notches (Figure 5.22). The marks are evenly distributed along the entire lengths of both cutting edges.

The large amount of wear marks suggests extensive use against a variety of other weapons. However, the number of marks appears too large to be solely the result of combat. Instead, it seems likely that the marks could have been created in a training scenario, where the same actions were repeated multiple times without concern of damaging the sword. Interestingly, no bulges were detected, which, with regards to such a large amount of marks, suggests that binding and twisting was not part of the combat style.

Figure 5.22 – Mark ID 1220, round notch, right cutting edge, 601 mm from the tip of Sword ID 56.

5.5.2 Wilburton Phase

Sword ID 23 – MOL O.1364 (Figure 5.23)

Figure 5.23 – Sword ID 23 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

3	Indentation	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	n/a	1	1
Right	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1		

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
6.93	0.38	0.44	4.40	0.08	0.37	Tr	0.12	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table 5.3 – Sword ID 23 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 143).

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant C, was recovered from the River Thames in Twickenham, Middlesex, during dredging works in 1882 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 47 No. 201). There is a wide, elongated rivet hole in each shoulder, and a further two in the tongue. The hilt has rounded shoulders and curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in fairly smooth brown patina. Segregation holes and corrosion are present on the majority of the blade, yet visibility is acceptable. Total length of the sword is 660 mm.

Only three wear marks could be identified on this sword, two on the left and one on the right cutting edge. The bulge (Figure 5.24) and indentation (Figure 5.25) are both located in the upper mid-section of the blade, the irregular graze slightly further towards the tip.

It appears as if this sword was used in only one very brief combat encounter. The bulge indicates a binding and twisting motion (see Chapter 4.4). The indentation suggests use of the sword against a spear (see Chapter 3.4.3). It is possible that the marks were created in one single sequence immediately prior to deposition in the river.

Figure 5.24 – Mark ID 588, bulge, left cutting edge, 445 mm from the tip of Sword ID 23.

Figure 5.25 – Mark ID 591, indentation, right cutting edge, 331-9 mm from the tip of Sword ID 23.

Sword ID 41 – MOL O.1337 (Figure 5.26)

Figure 5.26 – Sword ID 41 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

4	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Curved Graze
Left	1	1	n/a
Right	1	n/a	1
Visibility	1		

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
9.17	0.45	0.53	9.90	0.01	0.17	Tr	0.09	0.03	n/a	n/a

Table 5.4 – Sword ID 41 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 143).

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant C, was recovered from the River Thames in 1861, near the Ship Public House in Grove Park, Middlesex (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 47 No. 194). The tongue has fractured off at the rivet hole closest to the blade. There is one rivet hole in the right shoulder, and one rivet *in situ* in the left (Figure 5.27). The shoulders and ricassi are curved. Slight bevel lines and a midrib are present. The sword is covered in smooth but patchy brown, bronze, white, and black patina. There is a lot of surface oxidation on the reverse side near the tip. Total length of this sword is 583 mm.

A total of four wear marks could be identified on this sword, two on each cutting edge. The sharp notch (Figure 5.28) and indentation on the left cutting edge are located in close proximity to each other in the midsection of the blade. Both marks on the right are located slightly further towards the hilt.

This sword displays the marks of a very limited amount of combat. It appears as if the hilt was deliberately removed, rather than accidentally fractured off, which could have been carried out to render the weapon useless prior to deposition in the river.

Figure 5.27 – Rivet *in situ* in the left shoulder of Sword ID 41.

Figure 5.28 – Mark ID 944, sharp notch, left cutting edge, 191-7 mm from the tip of Sword ID 41.

Sword ID 44 – MOL O.1358 (Figure 5.29)

Figure 5.29 – Sword ID 44 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

6	Indentation	Round Notch	Bulge	Saw-Tooth Pattern
Left	n/a	n/a	1	1
Right	2	1	1	n/a
Visibility	1			

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant A, was discovered in the River Thames off Old England above the Great Western Dock in Brentford, Middlesex, in 1864, and in association with Sword IDs 29 and 34 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 41 No. 146). It is covered in slightly rough brown patina and corrosion. The upper quarter of the blade is particularly badly corroded, however, visibility remained adequate to carry out the analysis. There are two rivet holes in each shoulder, with one rivet remaining *in situ*. The tongue has fractured. Straight shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines and a slight midrib are present. Total length of this sword is 463 mm.

A total of five wear marks could be identified on this sword, one on the left and four on the right cutting edge. All marks on the right cutting edge are located within 50 mm of the tip. The bulge on the left cutting edge is also located in the lower quarter of the blade. There is an unusual saw-tooth pattern (Figure 5.30) near the tip of the left cutting edge, 39 mm in length, which appears to be the result of an intentional disfiguration of the blade.

The small amount of wear marks suggests that the sword was used in at least one combat encounter. It can be suggested that the sword was owned by a skilled swordsman, trained in a combat style including binding and twisting motions. The saw-tooth pattern and fractured tongue are likely the result of intentional disfiguration and destruction of the sword prior to deposition, and is reflected in the two associated swords.

Figure 5.30 – Mark ID 967, saw-tooth pattern, left cutting edge, 43-82 mm from the tip of Sword ID 44.

Sword ID 35 – MOL O.1359 (Figure 5.31)

Figure 5.31 – Sword ID 35 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

8	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Irregular Graze	Fissure
Left	n/a	1	2	1	n/a
Right	2	1	n/a	n/a	1
Visibility	1				

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
10.36	1.14	1.35	2.60	0.03	0.29	Tr	0.27	0.03	0.04	n/a

Table 5.5 – Sword ID 35 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 143).

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant C, was recovered from the River Thames at Sion Reach, Isleworth, Middlesex, in 1865 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 47 No. 197). At a total length of 575, mm the sword is significantly bent twice, first in the lower quarter at 170 mm from the tip, then bent the other way at c. 80 mm from the tip. There is one elongated rivet hole in the tongue, and one in each shoulder (Figure 5.32). The hilt has curved shoulders and curved ricassi. This sword is stored unsecured in a box with three other swords, allowing them to clash every time the box is moved. There are a number of extremely small microscopic marks, which most likely stem from this process. These marks have not been recorded.

A total of seven combat-related wear marks could be identified on this sword, four on the left and three on the right cutting edge. There is a fissure (Figure 5.34) protruding at a right angle to the cutting edge into the blade at 170 mm. A pattern of two round notches in immediate proximity to each other (Figure 5.33) was recorded on the left cutting edge. The marks on the right are located closely to the tip.

The marks suggest that this sword was used in at least one combat situation and experienced clashing contacts with other bladed weapons. Both bends appear to be the result of a deliberate destruction of the sword. The fissure was recorded at the same location as the bend closest to the hilt. It is likely a direct result of the material strain imposed by the bending process.

Figure 5.32 – Elongated rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 35.

Figure 5.34 – Mark ID 837, fissure, right cutting edge, 170 mm from the tip of Sword ID 35.

Figure 5.33 – Pattern of two round notches in immediate proximity to each other (Mark IDs 828-9), left cutting edge, 190-1 mm from the tip of Sword ID 35.

Sword ID 28 – MOL O.1356 (Figure 5.35)

Figure 5.35 – Sword ID 28 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

9	Indentation	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Bulge
Left	1	2	n/a	n/a	n/a	1
Right	n/a	n/a	1	2	1	1
Visibility	1					

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
12.03	0.60	0.45	1.00	0.05	0.18	0.06	0.18	Tr	Tr	n/a

Table 5.6 – Sword ID 28 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 144).

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant F, was recovered from the River Thames at Old England above Great Western Dock in Brentford, Middlesex,

in 1864 (Burgess and Colquhoun 1988, 50 No. 220). There are two elongated rivet holes in the tongue, and two drilled rivet holes in each shoulder, with three rivets remaining *in situ* (Figure 5.36). The shoulders and ricassi are slightly curved. Faint bevel lines are present. The sword is slightly corroded and covered in patchy brown and black patina. Total length of this sword is 555 mm. The lower half of the blade is bent.

A total of nine wear marks could be identified on this sword, four on the left and five on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are various grazes (Figure 5.37). There is no indicator for the cause of bending. There appears to be a clustering of marks in the lower quarter of the blade. The marks are very subtle and shallow.

This sword seems to have experienced a certain amount of clashing and binding contacts. The clustering of marks in the lowest quarter suggests that the length of the sword was used to increase the fighter's reach. The bending could be caused deliberately as part of the deposition process.

Figure 5.36 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 28.

Figure 5.37 – Mark ID 732, curved graze, right cutting edge, 437 mm from the tip of Sword ID 28.

Sword ID 22 – MOL O.1367 (Figure 5.38)

Figure 5.38 – Sword ID 22 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	4	1	n/a	1	1
Right	n/a	1	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1				

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
8.35	2.23	2.20	3.00	0.10	0.41	0.02	0.52	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table 5.7 – Sword ID 22 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 143).

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant A, was recovered from the River Thames, 55 m above Feathers Public House, off Putney Hill, in 1863 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 41 No. 143). The sword has one elongated rivet slot in the tongue with a rivet remaining *in situ*. Each shoulder has one bi-conical, drilled rivet hole. The rivet in the right shoulder remains *in situ* (Figure 5.39). Round shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in smooth brown and white patina. There is little macroscopic wear on the cutting edges. The blade is slightly bent in two places. Total length of this sword is 596 mm.

A total of nine wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with seven on the left and two on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. On the left, the marks are all clustered within the lower third of the blade. The

Figure 5.39 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 22.

two marks on the right are located in the mid-section of the cutting edge.

The marks suggest that this sword was used in at least one combat situation. A similar pattern of edge dominance was created during the actualistic experiments (see Chapter 4.4). One can therefore suggest that the sword was used during at least one high-velocity encounter without binding and twisting motions.

Sword ID 36 – MOL O.1361 (Figure 5.40)

Figure 5.40 – Sword ID 36 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 26 No. 150).

11	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Irregular Graze	Compression Curling	Blow Mark	Bulge
Left	2	1	1	1	n/a	1	n/a
Right	1	n/a	1	1	1	n/a	1
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant A, is of unknown provenance (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 41 No. 150) and has a total length of 617 mm. The sword is completely covered in slightly rough, dark and light grey patina. There is a rivet slot with one rivet *in situ* in the tongue, and a large drilled rivet hole in each shoulder (Figure 5.41). The hilt has straight shoulders and curved ricassi. Bevel lines are not present. The lowest quarter of the blade is ever so slightly bent.

A total of eleven wear marks could be identified on this sword, six on the left and five on the right cutting edge. The marks are spread very evenly along the entire length of both cutting edges. No patterns could be identified. The tip is intact and displays long striations (Figure 5.42), likely caused by grinding and/or sharpening.

This sword displays the signs of at least one combat interaction. However, the lack of patterns and general scattering of marks suggests that the fighter was perhaps not trained in a certain combat style. The indentations and compression curling indicate combat against weapons with blunt sections (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.41 – Drilled rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 36.

Figure 5.42 – Tip with striations of Sword ID 36.

Sword ID 11 – BM WG.1268 (Figure 5.43)

Figure 5.43 – Sword ID 11 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 36 No. 228).

15	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	2	1	3	1	1	n/a
Right	1	n/a	3	n/a	1	2
Visibility	1					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant G, was recovered from the River Thames in Isleworth, Middlesex. Its two pieces were discovered on separate occasions in 1886 and 1887, and were later found to match (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 51 No. 228). At a total length of 595 mm, the sword fractured at 334 mm, and the lower half of the blade is bent at 120 mm (Figure 5.43). The sword is in fairly poor condition and covered in patchy, corroded patina of varying colours and textures. While the surfaces are generally too corroded to identify any marks, the cutting edges are fairly well preserved. The sword has straight shoulders, curved ricassi and the remnants of bevel lines. There are three elongated irregular rivet holes, one in the tongue and one in each shoulder (Figure 5.44).

A total of 15 wear marks could be identified on this sword, eight on the left and seven on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches. Two bulges are also present. The tip has experienced severe pressure and is flattened (Figure 5.46). A scratched striation pattern can be detected protruding from the left cutting edge into the flat of the blade, just before the point of bending (Figure 5.45).

This sword displays all the marks of live action combat against other bladed weapons. The indentations, various notches and grazes indicate the use against potentially a variety of weapons, including spears and swords. Binding and twisting motions, causing the bulges, indicate that a distinct combat style was executed. The striation pattern and bending resemble the result of a flat parry, where the impacting sword has scratched along the flat of the blade and caused the sword to bend (see Chapter 3.4.2, 3.5).

Figure 5.44 – Irregular rivet hole in the left shoulder of Sword ID 11.

Figure 5.46 – Mark ID 222, tip pressure on Sword ID 11.

Figure 5.45 – Mark ID 219, striation pattern on the flat side of the blade, 110-23 mm from the tip of Sword ID 11.

Sword ID 30 – MOL 49.107/812 (Figure 5.47)

Figure 5.47 – Sword ID 30 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

16	Indentation	Round Notch	Compression Curling	Curved Graze	Fissure	Bulge
Left	5	n/a	1	1	n/a	3
Right	n/a	1	n/a	1	1	3
Visibility	1					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Teddington was recovered from an unknown location in the River Thames (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 39 No. 136). The top of the hilt has fractured at the rivet hole closest to the blade. There are two cast rivet holes in each straight shoulder (Figure 5.48). Curved ricassi and bevel lines are present. There is a slight

twisting along the longitudinal axis of the blade. It is completely covered in a golden, bronzy patina. Total length of this sword is 510 mm.

A total of 16 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying slight edge dominance with ten on the left and six on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are bulges (Figure 5.49) and indentations. On the left cutting edge, the marks are fairly evenly distributed along the entire length of the blade. There are no marks within 108 mm of the tip on the right edge.

The slight edge dominance suggests that the sword was repeatedly held in the same way, possibly by a single owner (see Chapter 4.4). There is sufficient evidence to suggest that the sword was used in combat. The high number of bulges indicate that binding and twisting motions took place.

Figure 5.48 – Cast rivet hole in the left shoulder of Sword ID 30.

Figure 5.49 – Mark ID 764, bulge, right cutting edge, 308 mm from the tip of Sword ID 30.

Sword ID 39 – MOL 1341 (Figure 5.50)

Figure 5.50 – Sword ID 39 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

21	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge	Rebound
Left	4	n/a	1	1	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	3
Right	2	1	1	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	1	n/a
Visibility	1									

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
6.79	0.30	0.28	3.10	0.03	0.12	0.04	0.05	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table 5.8 – Sword ID 39 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 143).

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant A, is of unknown provenance (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 41 No. 145). The sword is covered in smooth brown and white patina. A modern attempt at cleaning has been made on a section of the reverse. There is one rivet hole at either end of a rivet slot in the tongue, and one rivet hole in each shoulder. Two rivets remain *in situ*, one in the tongue and one in the left shoulder (Figure 5.51). The hilt has straight shoulders and curved ricassi. There is a slight bend in the upper half of the blade. Total length of this sword is 629 mm.

A total of 21 wear marks could be identified on this sword, twelve on the left (three of which are rebound marks) and nine on the right cutting edge. Displaying ten different types of wear,

Figure 5.51 – Rivet *in situ* in the left shoulder of Sword ID 39.

the most common marks are indentations. On both sides, the marks are spread fairly evenly along the cutting edges.

This sword displays clear signs of combat use, most likely on more than one occasion and against a variety of blunt and bladed weapons. However, no patterns could be identified, and no conclusion about a possible combat style could be drawn.

Sword ID 59 – YORYM1966.1 (Figure 5.52)

Figure 5.52 – Sword ID 59 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

27	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Flattening	Bulge	Rebound
Left	5	n/a	n/a	n/a	2	n/a	3	n/a
Right	9	2	2	1	n/a	1	n/a	2
Visibility	1							

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant G, was discovered as a single find near Whenby, Yorkshire, in 1945 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 51 No. 224). The sword is covered in rusty brown patina. There are three elongated rivet slots in the hilt, one in the tongue with one rivet *in situ*, and one in each shoulder. The straight shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines and a midrib are present. There is a distinct bend to the blade at 320 mm from the tip (Figure 5.54). Total length of this sword is 536 mm.

A total of 27 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with ten on the left and 17 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. Although the marks are spread along the entire lengths of both cutting edges, the majority of marks are located in the lower third of the blade. There is a striation pattern on the flat of the blade between 295-303 mm from the tip (Figure 5.53).

Figure 5.53 – Mark ID 1411, striation pattern on the flat of the blade, 295-303 mm from the tip of Sword ID 59.

The edge dominance suggests a single owner. A combination of indentations and various grazes and notches suggests clashing contacts with different types of weapons. Binding and twisting motions are evident through the bulges. The bend and striation pattern mentioned above is near identical with that created during the first experiments (see Chapter 3.4.2) and were caused by a flat parry. Whilst the sword owner was clearly trained in a specific combat style, they must have found themselves under severe pressure to protect their own life.

Figure 5.54 – Sword ID 59 bend. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

Sword ID 3 – BM OA.124 (Figure 5.55)

Figure 5.55 – Sword ID 3 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 26 No. 152).

35	Indentation	Round Notch	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Straight Graze	Bulge	Rebound
Left	4	2	1	2	4	2	4	3	2	1
Right	5	3	2	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1									

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Wilburton, Variant A, was recovered from the River Thames in Twickenham, Greater London, in 1858 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 41 No. 152). Nearly a complete sword, the hilt has fractured at the central rivet hole closest to the blade. A cast rivet hole is located in each straight shoulder (Figure 5.56). The ricassi are curved. Bevel lines are present. There are two noticeable bends in the blade, one directly below the hilt, and a second bend in the opposite direction just above the fractured tip. No striations associated with the bends could be detected. The entire sword is covered in dark, patchy patina and slight corrosion. However, Visibility=1 on the cutting edges allows full analysis of the sword. The total length of this sword is 595 mm.

A total of 35 wear marks could be identified, displaying clear edge dominance with 25 on the left and ten on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations, various notches and grazes. Two bulges are also present. The marks are evenly spread along both cutting edges, but none are located closer than 80 mm to the tip.

Figure 5.56 – Cast rivet hole in the left shoulder of Sword ID 3.

The large amount of wear marks and clear edge dominance suggest skilled use in probably more than one combat situations. Absence of striations near the bends and the fractured tip suggest a deliberate destruction of the blade prior to deposition (compare the ritual treatment of swords of the Pila del Brancon hoard, Chapter 6.3.2).

5.5.3 Ewart Park Phase

Sword ID 69 – NEWMA1932.22 (Figure 5.57)

Figure 5.57 – Sword ID 69. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

0	Indentation
Left	n/a
Right	n/a
Visibility	3

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified, was discovered as part of the Medomsley Hoard whilst ploughing on Low Farm near Ebchester, County Durham, in 1855. It was discovered in association with a plain bronze ring (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 97 No. 544; Burgess 1968a, fig. 20,2). The sword was discovered fractured into two pieces. Since then, a wedge for metallographic analysis was removed from the fracture, and the two pieces were glued together. Today the sword remains in two pieces with glue remains at the fracture. Neither the wedge nor the results of the analysis are available. Covered in black and brown patina, the sword is severely corroded, and visibility is poor. Part of the tongue has fractured at a rivet hole close to the hilt plate. The latter consists of straight shoulders, curved ricassi, one rivet hole in the right shoulder, and a fractured rivet hole and left shoulder. Faint bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 548 mm.

Potentially because of the poor visibility, no wear marks could be identified on this sword. A lump of metal was molten into a large hole in the left cutting edge (Figure 5.58). The origin of the hole remains unknown, but could have been the result of a casting flaw. Hammering marks are visible on the prehistoric filling. There is a deep striation on the flat of the blade (Figure 5.59) resembling a chisel mark.

Due to the poor visibility it remains uncertain whether this sword was used in combat or not. As it was discovered in association with a hoard, it can be suggested that the sword was deliberately destroyed as part of the deposition process. The striation could be the result of a first, unsuccessful attempt to achieve the fracture.

Figure 5.58 – Mark ID 1737, filling, left cutting edge, 241 mm from the tip of Sword ID 69.

Figure 5.59 – Mark ID 1735, striation, right cutting edge, 189 mm from the tip of Sword ID 69.

Sword ID 15 – BM 1911,1021.6 (Figure 5.60)

Figure 5.60 – Sword ID 15 reverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

0	Combat marks
Left	n/a
Right	n/a
Visibility	1

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
8.40	0.38	0.48	6.50	n/a	0.18	<0.006	0.21	n/a	n/a	0.0067

Table 5.9 – Sword ID 15 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 146).

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern unclassified, was found as part of a hoard on the floor of Heathery Burn Cage, County Durham, in 1863. Associated finds include thirteen Yorkshire socketed axes, eight socketed spearheads and several sword fragments (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 96 No. 528). The tongue of the hilt has fractured at the last rivet holes closest to the blade. There is one rivet hole in each shoulder, and attempts to drill a second rivet hole in each shoulder have been made (Figure 5.61). The shoulders are straight and merge into straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is completely covered in smooth green patina and in excellent condition. Total length of this sword is 515 mm.

There are only two marks recordable on the entire blade, none of which are combat related: one striation pattern resembling sharpening marks (Figure 5.62) on the left cutting edge, and one single deep striation (Figure 5.63) protruding from the right ricasso notch into the flat of the blade. Both striations are lying underneath the patina.

This sword has never been used in live combat. It is possible that it was specifically produced with the intention of burying it as part of a hoard. The striation (Figure 5.63) could be the result of holding the sword to brake or bend it prior to deposition.

Figure 5.61 – (Semi-) drilled rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 15.

Figure 5.63 – Mark ID 320, striation, right cutting edge, 445-53 mm from the tip of Sword ID 15.

Figure 5.62 – Mark ID 319, sharpening marks, left cutting edge, 241 mm from the tip of Sword ID 15.

Sword ID 31 – MOL 49.107/118 (Figure 5.64)

Figure 5.64 – Sword ID 31 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 43 No. 272).

2	Bulge
Left	n/a
Right	2
Visibility	1

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 2, was recovered from an unknown location in the River Thames (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 70 No. 272).

The sword is completely covered in smooth brown and grey patina. There are four crudely drilled rivet holes in this otherwise elaborate sword, two in the tongue and one in each shoulder (Figure 5.65). The hilt has straight shoulders and curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 608 mm.

Only two wear marks could be identified, both of which are bulges (Figure 5.67 & Figure 5.66) located in the upper half on the right cutting edge, spaced 50 mm from each other.

The crudely drilled rivet holes stand in contrast to the otherwise elaborate appearance of the weapon. It seems as if as little effort as possible was put into drilling the holes, which are crucial for the hafting of the hilt plate but remain unseen. This may indicate that the sword was not made with the intention of using it as a weapon, but rather as an object for display or non-combat ritual. The bulges, however, must have been created by a binding and twisting action against another bladed weapon.

Figure 5.65 – Crudely drilled rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 31.

Figure 5.67 – Mark ID 769, bulge, right cutting edge, 326 mm from the tip of Sword ID 31.

Figure 5.66 – Mark ID 770, bulge, right cutting edge, 395 mm from the tip of Sword ID 31.

Sword ID 29 – MOL O.1355 (Figure 5.68)

Figure 5.68 – Sword ID 29 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

5	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Bulge	Rebound
Left	n/a	n/a	1	1	n/a
Right	1	1	n/a	n/a	1
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 4, was recovered from the River Thames above the Great Western Dock in Brentford, Middlesex, in 1864. It was found at the same location and within a week of Sword IDs 34 and 44 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 73 No, 313; Cowen 1967, 450 No. 7; Cowen 1952, 145 Pl. 17,2). The sword has a fractured tip and a bend in the lower half. There are two rivets *in situ* in the tongue, and two rivet holes in each shoulder, each with a rivet *in situ* (Figure 5.69). A seventh rivet hole was drilled into the terminal, at which it has fractured. The sword is completely covered in smooth green and brown patina. Total length of this sword is 556 mm.

Only five wear marks could be identified on this sword, two on the left and three on the right, one of which is the rebound mark of the round notch. These two marks are located very closely to the tip and were likely created during an attack. The bulge at 375 mm from the tip (Figure 5.70) was potentially caused by a binding action of an opposing weapon.

This sword has had limited combat interactions with another bladed weapon, potentially just one sword in one encounter. The fracture and bend could have been deliberate destruction carried out as part of a ritual prior to deposition in the river. It is highly likely that the associated swords were deposited at the same time.

Figure 5.69 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 29.

Figure 5.70 – Mark ID 736, bulge, left cutting edge, 375 mm from the tip of Sword ID 29.

Sword ID 6 – BM 1951,1007.1 (Figure 5.71)

Figure 5.71 – Sword ID 6 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 82 No. 548).

5	Indentation	Toothed Notch	Bulge
Left	3	1	1
Right	n/a	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1		

This leaf-shaped copper alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified, was recovered as a single find from a depth of 180 cm in the Lewis Burn, during gravel removal at the North Tyne intersection, Kielder Forest, Northumberland (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 97 No. 548). The sword is almost complete with a fractured hilt, and completely covered in smooth black patina. Two bi-conical rivet holes (Figure 5.72) have been drilled into each slightly curved shoulder. The tongue has fractured off at the fifth rivet hole. Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. Total length of this sword is 537 mm.

A total of five wear marks could be identified on this sword, all of which are located on the left cutting edge. The marks consist of three indentations, a very distinct toothed notch (Figure 5.73) and a bulge and are spread evenly along the length of the blade.

The types of wear marks indicate that a limited amount of combat use has likely taken place; the bulge must have been created during a binding and twisting motion against another bladed weapon (see Chapter 4.4). There is also an extremely clear edge dominance, with all marks exclusively on one cutting edge. The five marks could have been created during one very short, intense fight, after which the sword was no longer used and deposited in the river.

Figure 5.72 – Drilled rivet hole in the left shoulder of Sword ID 6.

Figure 5.73 – Mark ID 162, toothed notch, left cutting edge, 178 mm from the tip of Sword ID 6.

Sword ID 7 – BM WG1246 (Figure 5.74)

Figure 5.74 – Sword ID 7 reverse, photograph courtesy of British Museum.

5	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation
Left	2	1
Right	2	n/a
Visibility	1	

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 4, was a single find recovered from the River Thames at the mouth of the River Wandle, Wandsworth, London, in 1894 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 73 No. 318; Cowen 1967, 449 No. 3,1; Cowen 1952, 145 pls. 17,4, 18,3). The sword is completely intact and covered in smooth, slightly rusty brown patina. There is a total of seven elaborately cast rivet holes: one in each shoulder (Figure 5.75), one in each corner at the transition between tongue and shoulders, two in the tongue and one in the terminal. Straight shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 632 mm.

A total of five wear marks could be identified, three on the left and two on the right cutting edge. There are four indentations and one rectangular indentation. The two indentations on the left (Figure 5.76) are located in immediate proximity to each other towards the upper end of the cutting edge. Both indentations on the right are also located closely to each other.

This beautiful sword must have been produced by a very skilled craftsman, and was finished to a high standard. Perhaps that is also the reason why the wear marks do not necessarily indicate combat use. The close proximity of both sets of indentations, as well as their similar respective shapes, suggest that the sword was used to hit an object twice in sequence, on two occasions. It is possible that the sword was mostly a decorative item, and that the marks are the result of a very deliberate use of the weapon.

Figure 5.75 – Cast rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 7.

Figure 5.76 – Mark IDs 164-5, two indentations in immediate proximity to each other, left cutting edge, 492-6 mm from the tip of Sword ID 7.

Sword ID 46 – ACAT 230 (Figure 5.77)

Figure 5.77 – Sword ID 46 obverse. Image courtesy of Eve Recherchon.

5	Indentation	Wide-Angled Notch
Left	3	n/a
Right	1	1
Visibility	2	

The three parts of this leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 2, were discovered by a young boy and girl under a rock on Simonside near Tosson, Northumberland, in 1868, in association with two lead sword pommels, a sword fragment, and three copper-alloy rings (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 92 No, 492). At a total length of 515 mm, the sword consists of two blade fragments and a pommel made of lead-alloy (Figure 5.78). The blade fractured at 91 mm above the tip. There are two rivet holes in the tongue and one in each shoulder. Three rivets remain *in situ*. The hilt has straight, narrow shoulders and straight ricassi. Unfortunately, the three parts of the sword have been stored in separate boxes and under different conditions, which has resulted in heavy corrosion on the upper blade fragment. It was therefore not possible to carry out full analysis.

Only five wear marks could be identified on the lower 91 mm of the sword, three on the left and two on the right cutting edge. The most common marks here are indentations.

Figure 5.78 – Lead-alloy pommel associated with Sword ID 46.

Due to the heavy corrosion, and a subsequent lack of analysis, interpretation of this sword proves difficult. The marks on the lowest fragment suggest that the sword was most likely used in combat situations. A lead-alloy pommel is extremely unusual, and this sword may have been part of a unique set of prototypes. Due to the heaviness of the pommel, the balance point of the sword is moved further towards the hilt. It also increases the overall weight of the sword.

Sword ID 70 – NEWMA1923.9 (Figure 5.79)

Figure 5.79 – Sword ID 70 obverse. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

8	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Blow Mark
Left	n/a	2	1	1
Right	1	1	n/a	2
Visibility	1			

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified, was found in the River Tyne between Kings Meadow Island and the High Level Bridge in Newcastle, Tyne and Wear (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 97 No. 549). It is covered in smooth black and brown patina, which was partially removed on the hilt and top of the blade. The hilt is poorly cast and incomplete, with a fractured terminus and partially fractured shoulders and rivet holes. Short, straight ricassi and bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 544 mm.

A total of eight wear marks could be identified on this sword, four on each cutting edge. All marks are located within 81 mm of the tip. There are several patterns of hammering marks on the bevel lines (Figure 5.81). Slight tip pressure has occurred (Figure 5.80).

This weapon appears to have been used in a limited amount of combat situations. The exclusive location of marks near the tip may suggest that forwards thrusting motions were part of the fighting style.

Figure 5.80 – Slight tip pressure on Sword ID 70.

Figure 5.81 – Hammering marks on Sword ID 70.

Sword ID 52 – ACAT 228 (Figure 5.82)

Figure 5.82 – Sword ID 52 reverse. Image courtesy of Eve Recherchon.

8	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze
Left	2	2	1	n/a	1
Right	n/a	1	n/a	1	n/a
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 1, was discovered as a single find near a prehistoric enclosure on Amerside Law Farm near Chatton, Northumberland (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 125 No. 780). The sword has been cleaned since its discovery, but remains in good condition and is now covered in gold and black patina. Corrosion holes occur throughout on the sword. There is one drilled rivet hole in each straight shoulder. Three irregularly drilled rivet holes are in the tongue. The ricassi are slightly curved. Total length of this sword is 654 mm.

A total of eight wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with six on the left and two on the right cutting edge. There are no marks in the lower third of the blade. Slight tip pressure has occurred (Figure 5.83).

This sword appears to have been used in at least one combat encounter against another bladed weapon. The clear edge dominance suggests a single owner. Various notches and grazes suggest clashing and hacking impacts of different velocities (see Chapters 3.5 & 4.4).

Figure 5.83 – Slight tip pressure on Sword ID 52.

Sword ID 55 – YORYM1948.1161 (Figure 5.84)

Figure 5.84 – Sword ID 55 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

9	Indentation	Round Notch	Bulge
Left	1	n/a	3
Right	1	2	2
Visibility	1		

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 1, was discovered as a single find in an unspecified location in Sawdon, Yorkshire (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 89 No. 460). The sword is completely covered in smooth green and brown patina. The hilt is intact and includes a cast tongue and terminal. There are two drilled rivet holes in the tongue, and one in each shoulder (Figure 5.85). The shoulders and ricassi are slightly curved. A slight midrib is present in the upper quarter of the blade. Total length of this sword is 581 mm.

A total of nine wear marks could be identified on this sword, four on the left and five on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are bulges. All but one mark are located in the lower half of the blade. Tip pressure has occurred (Figure 5.86).

This sword displays the signs of at least one combat encounter against another bladed weapon. The indentations likely stem from contacts with a rounded section of another weapon, such as a spear shaft (see Chapter 3.4.3). Binding and twisting motions occurred, as is evident through the five bulges, and were likely an integral part of the particular combat style (see Chapter 4.4). The tip pressure was likely the result of stabbing.

Figure 5.85 – Drilled rivet hole in the left shoulder of Sword ID 55.

Figure 5.86 – Tip pressure on Sword ID 55.

Sword ID 34 – MOL O.1354 (Figure 5.87)

Figure 5.87 – Sword ID 34 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

11	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Compression Curling	Bulge
Left	1	3	1	1	n/a	2
Right	1	n/a	n/a	n/a	1	1
Visibility	1					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 4, was recovered from the River Thames off Old England above Great Western Docks in 1864, in association with Sword IDs 29 and 44 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 73 No. 308; Cowen 1967, 449 No. 3,4; Cowen 1952, 145 Pl. 17,5). The sword is completely covered in smooth, light brown and grey patina. There are four cast rivet holes, two in the tongue and one in each shoulder. Two rivets remain *in situ* (Figure 5.88). The hilt has slightly curved shoulders and curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The lower quarter of the blade is slightly bent, and the tip has fractured off (Figure 5.89). This sword has a total length of 553 mm.

A total of eleven wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with eight on the left and three on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are bulges and sharp notches. All marks are located in the lower third of the blade, within 175 mm of the tip.

The edge dominance suggests a single owner, who used the sword in at least one combat situation against other bladed weapons. Binding and twisting motions have taken place (see Chapter 4.4). The clustering of marks towards the tip suggests that the combat style utilised the length and the swelling of the sword, which in turn suggests that the owner was a skilled fighter who had been trained in the combat style.

Figure 5.88 – Cast rivet in the right shoulder of Sword ID 34.

Figure 5.89 – Fractured tip on Sword ID 34.

Sword ID 62 – YORYM 1948.1162 (Figure 5.90)

Figure 5.90 – Sword ID 62 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

11	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Elongated Graze	Blow Mark
Left	2	1	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1
Right	n/a	2	1	1	1	1	1
Visibility	1						

This lozenge-shaped copper-alloy sword is of unknown type or provenance. It was not possible to find this sword in the literature. Typologically, it is most similar to Ewart Park sword of the Northern Step variety, with a flanged tongue and terminal and a diamond-shaped hilt plate (after Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 66-7). The blade, however, is different to any other sword type described in the typology. Instead of straight cutting edges tapering towards a pointy tip, or four curved sections swelling to the typical leaf-shape in the lower third of the blade, this sword has four straight sections of near equal length creating a lozenge shape. The sword is covered in smooth brown and black patina. Modern grinding has partially removed the patina on the reverse. There are two cast rivet holes in the tongue, and one in each shoulder. Bevel lines are visible on both cutting edges, but they are more prominent on the obverse than on the reverse, as if unfinished on that side. Hammering marks (Figure 5.91), most likely from the manufacturing process, are visible along those bevel lines. The tip has fractured (Figure 5.92). Total length of this sword is 578 mm.

A total of eleven wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying slight edge dominance with four on the left and seven on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are sharp notches. On the left, the marks are distributed evenly along the entire length of the cutting edge. The four marks on the right are in the lower third of the blade towards the tip.

This sword displays the signs of combat against at least one other bladed weapon. The unusual shape of the blade, and its uniqueness in the record, suggest that the sword could have been a prototype, or experiment, which was tested, then quickly abandoned after a short trial period during which the marks were created.

Figure 5.91 – Mark ID 1474, hammering marks, 190-225 mm from the tip of Sword ID 62.

Figure 5.92 – Fractured tip on Sword ID 62.

Sword ID 43 – MOL 28.137/1 (Figure 5.93)

Figure 5.93 – Sword ID 43 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

12	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch
Left	2	2	3
Right	n/a	3	1
Visibility	1		

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 3, was recovered from the River Thames under unknown circumstances (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 72 No. 303). The sword is completely covered in smooth brown patina. There are eight drilled rivet holes (Figure 5.94), two in the tongue and three in each shoulder. The hilt has straight shoulders and straight ricassi. Bevel lines are not present, a midrib only in the upper half of the blade. The entire blade is covered in ancient striation marks. Total length of this sword is 563 mm.

A total of eleven wear marks could be identified on this sword, seven on the left and four on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are sharp notches and round notches (Figure 5.95). On the left, the marks are evenly distributed along the entire length of the cutting edge. The marks on the right are located more towards the lower half of the blade.

This sword displays the sign of limited combat use on at least one occasion. The sharp and round notches in combination with a lack of grazes may suggest that the sword was predominantly used in low-velocity motions (see Chapter 3.5). The striations along the blade appear to be the result of very rough ancient grinding. It is possible that these stem from the

manufacturing process, while the next step of polishing the blade was left out. One could suggest that this sword was predominantly used for training purposes, repeatedly carrying out the same hacking motions. The inexpert finish might indicate that the sword was not publicly carried or displayed.

Figure 5.94 – Drilled rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 43.

Figure 5.95 – Mark ID 953, bulge, left cutting edge, 429 mm from the tip of Sword ID 43.

Sword ID 13 – BM 1892,1104.3 (Figure 5.96)

Figure 5.96 – Sword ID 13 obverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

12	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Toothed Notch	Elongated Graze	Straight Graze	Bulge	Rebound
Left	2	2	1	n/a	n/a	n/a	1
Right	n/a	2	n/a	1	1	2	n/a
Visibility	1						

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
12.60	0.11	0.11	3.40	n/a	0.062	0.075	0.033	n/a	n/a	<0.005

Table 5.10 – Sword ID 13 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 145).

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Eastern Step 3, was found as part of a small hoard at Marston St. Lawrence, Northamptonshire, in 1872 (Burgess and Colquhoun 1988, 81 No. 393). Amongst four (fragmented) spearheads, two rings and two pieces of scrap metal, the hoard also contained Sword ID 17. At a total length of 629 mm, the sword has fractured into two parts at 351 mm from the tip, and is heavily bent. Nine bi-conical rivet holes were drilled into the hilt, three in the tongue and three in each shoulder (Figure 5.97). They are not uniform and vary slightly in size and shape. Straight shoulders merge into straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in smooth brown and green

patina. There are few, but very prominent, wear marks, concentrated exclusively on the tip end of the two parts.

A total of twelve wear marks could be identified on this sword, six on either side. There is a pattern of five extremely pronounced marks on the left cutting edge, which due to their size and clustered location appear to be the result of intentional deformation of the blade. The other seven marks are much smaller in size and resemble combat marks found on other contemporary swords. Two bulges (Figure 5.98) indicate that binding and twisting motions took place (see Chapter 4.4).

It can be suggested that this sword was used in at least one combat encounter, resulting in the seven combat related wear marks. The sword then displays the signs of deliberate destruction. Deformation of the cutting edges and the breaking in half would have rendered the sword useless, whilst still preserving its intrinsic identity as a sword (see Sestieri et al. 2013).

Figure 5.97 – Drilled rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 13.

Figure 5.98 – Mark ID 287, bulge, right cutting edge, 152 mm from the tip of Sword ID 13.

Sword ID 63 – YORYM1948.1245 (Figure 5.99)

Figure 5.99 – Sword ID 63 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

12	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Fissure
Left	n/a	3	n/a	4	1	1
Right	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	3					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 2, was discovered as a single find in Leven, Yorkshire (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 94 No. 503). Covered in green, brown and black patina and corrosion, the cutting edges are in particularly poor condition.

There are two cast rivet holes in the tongue and two in each shoulder. The hilt has slightly curved shoulders and straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The tip has fractured (Figure 5.100). Total length of this sword is 542 mm.

Due to the heavy corrosion of the cutting edges, only the twelve most prominent wear marks could be identified. It is therefore unlikely that all marks were recorded. There are nine marks on the left, and three marks on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are straight grazes.

Despite the corrosion, this sword displays the marks of heavy combat. The marks are very deep and pronounced, and may suggest that considerable force and speed was used during the fight (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.100 – Fractured tip on Sword ID 63.

Sword ID 4 – BM WG.1241 (Figure 5.101)

Figure 5.101 – Sword ID 4 reverse, photograph courtesy of British Museum.

13	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	n/a	1	1	2
Right	1	1	2	n/a	1	1	n/a	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1								

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Western Step 2, was discovered as a single find at Broadway Tower in Broadway, Hereford, Worcestershire (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 85 No. 432; Evans 1881, 280). In the hilt, the bi-conical shape of the rivet holes indicates that they were drilled. There are three rivet holes in the tongue in linear alignment. Initially, a further six rivet holes were planned, three in each shoulder, but

only two have been completed and remain with rivets *in situ* (Figure 5.102). The sword has straight shoulders, curved ricassi and bevel lines. It is mostly covered in smooth light and dark brown patina, with an area of green patina near the tip on the reverse. There is a slight bend to the blade at 241 mm from the fractured tip (Figure 5.103). A hairline fissure runs across the outside of the bend, across the width of the blade. The sword has a total length of 634 mm.

A total of 13 combat marks could be identified on this sword, seven on the left and six on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are notches and grazes. Two bulges and two indentations are also present. Spread fairly evenly on the left cutting edges, the marks on the right are clustered within 210 mm in the lower two fifths of the blade. No marks are located further than 353 mm from the tip.

The unfinished rivet holes, potentially causing a weaker hafting of the organic hilt covers, and therefore potentially causing an increased risk to the fighter, might suggest that the sword was not intended for use in warfare. However, a limited amount of combat, involving high-velocity blade contacts and binding and twisting motions, evidently took place (see Chapters 3.5 & 4.4).

Figure 5.102 – Unfinished drilled rivet holes (left) and finished rivet hole (right). Note the bi-conical shape indicating drilling from both sides in the shoulders of Sword ID 4.

Figure 5.103 – Fractured tip on Sword ID 4.

Sword ID 50 –STCMG:1925.SB24.012 (Figure 5.104)

Figure 5.104 – Sword ID 50 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 91 No. 616).

14	Indentation	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze
Left	n/a	3	2	2
Right	2	1	3	1
Visibility	1			

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park is of unknown provenance. It was bought by Preston Park Museum in 1919 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 105 No. 616). The sword is completely covered in patchy black and golden patina. There are three drilled rivet holes in the tongue and three in each shoulder. The hilt has straight shoulders and rounded ricassi. An attempt to create bevel lines was made on the upper part of the blade. Total length of this sword is 665 mm.

A total of 14 wear marks could be identified on this sword, seven on each cutting edge. The marks on the left are evenly spread along the entire length of the cutting edge. On the right, the marks are clustered in the lower third of the blade, though no closer than 92 mm to the tip. The most common marks are various grazes (Figure 5.105).

This sword displays the marks of clashing contacts with other bladed weapons. The clustering of the marks near the leaf-swelling suggests that this feature of the sword was utilised in the combat style. Due to the high number of grazes, it can be suggested that the combat style was focussing on high-velocity slashing motions (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.105 – Mark ID 1079, curved graze, right cutting edge, 181 mm from the tip of Sword ID 50.

Sword ID 38 – MOL A.16956 and A.17103 (Figure 5.106)

Figure 5.106 – Sword ID 38 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

14	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Bulge
Left	7	1	1	1	1
Right	2	n/a	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 3, was recovered complete from the River Thames in Datchet, Berkshire (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 72 No. 296). There are three rivets *in situ*, one in the tongue (Figure 5.107) and one in each shoulder. The hilt has straight shoulders and slightly curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. There is no midrib. The sword is covered in rough green patina and corrosion, with occasional spots of accumulated oxidation. Originally measuring 551 mm in length, a modern saw was used to cut the sword in two at 294 mm from the tip. Burgess & Colquhoun (*ibid.*) list the sword as one piece, and in their drawing the two pieces are attached to each other. Sometime after 1988 the connection was broken again, and the fragments are now stored separately.

A total of 14 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with eleven on the left and three on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. All marks are located in the lower half of the blade.

The clear edge dominance suggests a single owner with a preferred manner of holding the sword (see Chapter 4). Due to the clustering of marks in the lower half of the blade, it seems like the combat style utilised the swelling of the blade. The large amount of indentations suggests use against a weapon with blunt sections such as a spear (see Chapter 3.4.3).

Figure 5.107 – Rivet *in situ* in the tongue of Sword ID 38.

Sword ID 19 – BM 1858,1115.1 (Figure 5.108)

Figure 5.108 – Sword ID 19 obverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

14	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	3	1	1	n/a	1
Right	2	2	2	2	n/a
Visibility	2				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Caledonian Step 1, was found as part of the same hoard as Sword ID 18, at Ythsie Farm, Parish of Tarves, Aberdeen (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 99 No. 575). There is one elongated rivet slot in the tongue and one cast oval rivet hole in each shoulder (Figure 5.109). The shoulders are straight and turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in patchy brown patina. Visibility=2 is poor due to high corrosion of the cutting edges. A modern attempt of polishing has been made on the midrib. Total length of this sword is 636 mm.

Despite the corrosion, a total of 14 pronounced marks could be identified on this sword, evenly divided with seven on each cutting edge. The marks on the left cutting edge are spread along its entire length, whereas on the opposite side the marks are concentrated in the lower half of the blade. The most common marks are various notches (Figure 5.110) and indentations.

The recorded marks suggest that the sword was used in combat against other bladed weapons, and against weapons with round sockets or shafts. As only parts of the blade could be examined, no interpretations of combat styles can be put forward.

Figure 5.109 – Cast rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 19.

Figure 5.110 – Mark ID 520, sharp notch, right cutting edge, 213 mm from the tip of Sword ID 19.

Sword ID 68 – NEWMA1814.22.2 (Figure 5.111)

Figure 5.111 – Sword ID 68 obverse. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

14	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Irregular Graze	Bulge	Fissure
Left	1	2	n/a	n/a	1	n/a	2	1
Right	n/a	n/a	3	1	2	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	3							

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified, was discovered forced vertically into the ground at Ewart Park, Northumberland, in association with Sword IDs 65 and 67, in 1814 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 96 No. 531). The tongue has completely fractured off, leaving the hilt plate with four rivets *in situ* and two fractured rivet holes. Straight shoulders, curved ricassi and bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in smooth brown and black patina. Parts of the upper half have been treated, possibly acid etched, removing the patina and damaging the cutting edges. Consequently, only partial analysis could be carried out. The tip is flattened (Figure 5.112).

A total of 14 wear marks could be identified in the visible area of the cutting edges, seven on each side. The marks are evenly spread along the cutting edges. There is a cluster of two bulges, which are located in close proximity to each other on the left cutting edge near the tip. Due to the poor visibility, it is not possible to meaningfully interpret this sword. However, the available data suggests that the sword was used in combat situations on at least one occasion. The two bulges are evidence of binding and twisting motions (see Chapter 4.4). Their clustering can be interpreted as the result of deliberate training and practice in that technique, and could be part of the particular fighting style used by the bearer.

Figure 5.112 – Tip pressure on Sword ID 68.

Sword ID 48 – ACAT 390 (Figure 5.113)

Figure 5.113 – Sword ID 48 obverse. Image courtesy of Eve Recherchon.

18	Indentation	Bulge
Left	6	n/a
Right	7	5
Visibility	1	

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park is of unknown provenance. It was not possible to find the sword in the literature. The sword is completely covered in rough black patina. A modern attempt at polishing was made on the midrib. There are three cast rivet holes in each straight shoulder. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in segregation holes throughout. As the tongue has fractured off, the remaining total length of this sword is 475 mm. Fractured in two, the blade fragments have been reattached with modern glue.

A total of 18 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with six on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge. The marks consist exclusively of indentations (Figure 5.114) and bulges (Figure 5.115). On both sides, the marks are located in the lower half of the blade. Ten marks are located within 100 mm of the tip.

This sword displays an interesting combination of marks. The indentations are indicative of contacts with rounded parts of weapons, such as spear shaft or sockets (see Chapter 3.4.3). On the other hand, the bulges are most likely the result of binding and twisting contacts with bladed weapons (see Chapter 4.4). The combination of the two, and the lack of any other marks suggesting contacts with blades, indicates that the sword was used against spears with long spearheads, with cutting edges of sufficient lengths to bind and twist. A short spear-shaft with a long spearhead, used in a wielding manner, could have caused these marks.

Figure 5.114 – Mark ID 1050, indentation, right cutting edge, 28-34 mm from the tip of Sword ID 48.

Figure 5.115 – Mark ID 1057, bulge, right cutting edge, 171-21 mm from the tip of Sword ID 48.

Sword ID 47 – ACAT 234 (Figure 5.116)

Figure 5.116 – Sword ID 47 obverse. Image courtesy of Eve Recherchon.

19	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze
Left	n/a	3	n/a	1	1
Right	4	3	3	n/a	4
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Caledonian unclassified, is a single find, which was discovered in a railway cutting in Yorkshire (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 101 No. 595). The sword was cast in one piece, including the solid cast hilt. With a total length of 730 mm, and a width of up to 67 mm, the sword is also extremely long and wide. The shoulders are slightly curved, the ricassi are straight. Bevel lines are present and prominent. A midrib is visible. There are numerous segregation holes on the sword, especially in the upper part of the blade.

A total of nineteen wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with five on the left and 14 on the right cutting edge. There are no marks within 191 mm of the blade. On the left cutting edge, the five marks are located in the midsection of the blade. The marks on the right edge are located in the mid- and upper section. There are no distinct patterns or clusters. The most common marks are sharp notches. Tip pressure has occurred (Figure 5.117).

The sheer size and appearance of the sword would have made it stand out. Although the marks suggest that clashing contacts with other bladed weapons took place, the sword's size

Figure 5.117 – Tip pressure on Sword ID 47.

and proportions make it clumsy and unwieldy. It is possible that the sword was specially made for ritualistic purposes, during which the marks were created. One cannot help but draw comparison to the German *Richtschwert*, a special Late Mediaeval sword used by executioners to decapitate their victims. Such swords were regarded as dishonest, and their use in normal combat was prohibited (Sieverling 2015, 74).

Sword ID 53 – ACAT 387 (Figure 5.118)

Figure 5.118 – Sword ID 53 obverse. Image courtesy of Eve Recherchon.

21	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Elongated Graze	Rebound
Left	5	2	1	1	n/a
Right	1	1	3	n/a	7
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park (according to Burgess & Colquhoun’s typology, 1988, 66-8), was discovered in association with four other swords in a tumulus in the county of Tyrone, Ireland, in 1831 (Alnwick Castle museum internal catalogue). It was not possible to find this sword in the literature. At a length of 665 mm, it is completely covered in smooth brown patina. There are two elongated rivet holes in the tongue, which appear to be the result of drilling two overlapping holes next to each other. One further rivet hole was drilled into each shoulder. The hilt has straight shoulders and straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. There are several striation patterns on the flat sides of the blade (Figure 5.119). A poor attempt at modern cleaning has been made on one section of the blade.

A total of 21 marks could be identified on this sword, nine on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge, of which seven were caused by rebounding. These rebound marks are most likely directly connected to two round and one sharp notch in the lower third of the blade (Figure 5.120; see Chapter 3.4.5). Otherwise, the most common marks are indentations. The marks on the left cutting edge are located in the middle and upper-section of the blade.

It can be suggested that this sword was likely used in more than one combat encounter, potentially against a variety of weapons. The marks in the middle and upper section of the blade could be the result of a fighting style utilising draw-cuts, as suggested by Molloy (2007, 100; 2011, 75).

Figure 5.119 – Striation pattern on the flat of Sword ID 53.

Figure 5.120 – Mark IDs 1151 (round notch) and 1152 (rebound mark), right cutting edge, 267-71 mm and 264 mm from the tip of Sword ID 53 respectively.

Sword ID 24 – MOL 57 (Figure 5.121)

Figure 5.121 – Sword ID 24 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

22	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Compression Curling	Bulge	Rebound
Left	n/a	1	1	n/a	n/a	1	4	4	2
Right	5	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1								

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 2, was recovered from the River Thames at Victoria Embankment, Holborn, London (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 71 No. 282). There are two rivet holes in each shoulder, and two in the tongue. The right shoulder has fractured at the outermost rivet hole (Figure 5.122). Fissures protrude from one of the rivet holes in the tongue. Curved shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is completely covered in smooth brown and gold patina. Total length of this sword is 556 mm. The tip has fractured off.

A total of 22 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 13 on the left and nine on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations and compression curling (Figure 5.123). Furthermore, there are various notches, grazes, and four bulges. Over 50 % of the marks are located in the lower third of the blade. There are two bulges close to the tip, and two bulges in the upper third of the blade.

This sword shows distinct signs of combat use, probably on more than one occasion. The indentations suggest use against weapons with rounded, blunt sections, such as spears (see

Chapter 3.4.3). Notches and grazes suggest that low- and high-velocity impacts with other bladed weapons took place (see Chapter 3.5). The bulges are the result of binding and twisting motions (see Chapter 4.4).

Figure 5.122 – Fractured right shoulder and rivet hole of Sword ID 24.

Figure 5.123 – Mark ID 600, compression curling, left cutting edge, 90-5 mm from the tip of Sword ID 24.

Sword ID 17 – BM 1892,1104.4 (Figure 5.124)

Figure 5.124 – Sword ID 17 obverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

22	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Toothed Notch	Curved Graze	Compression Curling	Rebound
Left	6	n/a	1	n/a	n/a	1	2
Right	3	1	3	1	3	n/a	1
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Eastern Step 2, was found as part of a hoard in Marston St. Lawrence, Northamptonshire, in 1872, in association with Sword ID 13 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 80 No. 389). At a total length of 584 mm, the sword has been deliberately bent and fractured twice, at 106 mm and 358 mm from the tip. There are three drilled rivet holes in the tongue and in each shoulder. The two outer rivets in each shoulder remain *in situ*, and the middle rivet hole was not completely drilled through in both cases (Figure 5.125). Straight shoulders merge into slightly curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. Generally in good condition, the sword is covered in multi-coloured patchy patina, ranging from gold to black, brown, green and grey.

A total of 22 wear marks could be identified on this sword, ten on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. Several notches, including one toothed notch (Figure 5.126), and grazes are also present. The marks are fairly evenly

distributed along the lengths of both cutting edges, although there are no marks within 150 mm from the tip on either side of the blade.

The presence of combat-related wear marks suggests that this sword has been used in fighting scenarios. A large number of indentations, notches and grazes suggests that the sword clashed at low and high speeds with other bladed weapons and rounded shafts or sockets (see Chapter 3.5). Although there does not appear to be any intentional deformation of the cutting edges, the bending and breaking indicates a deliberately destructive treatment of the sword (similar to that at Pila del Brancon, see Chapter 6.3.2 and Sestieri et al. 2013).

Figure 5.125 – (Semi-) drilled rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 17.

Figure 5.126 – Mark ID 459, toothed notch, right cutting edge, 397 mm from the tip of Sword ID 17.

Sword ID 32 – MOL A.27190 (Figure 5.127)

Figure 5.127 – Sword ID 32 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

25	Indentation	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Compression Curling	Irregular Graze
Left	10	1	1	1	1	n/a	1
Right	6	n/a	2	n/a	n/a	1	1
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 3, was recovered from the River Thames at Strand on the Green, Chiswick, Middlesex (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 72 No. 302). The sword is covered in dark brown and black patina, and corrosion. One side is particularly badly corroded. Visibility on the cutting edges, however, remained good enough to carry out full analysis. There are two rivets *in situ* in the tongue, and one in each

shoulder (Figure 5.128). The hilt has straight shoulders and straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 572 mm.

A total of 25 wear marks could be identified, 15 on the left and ten on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. On the left, the marks are all located in the upper two thirds of the blade, with no mark closer than 201 mm to the tip. The marks on the right cutting edge are located in the lower two thirds, with some in very close proximity to the tip, suggesting that in this case the cutting edge with the fewer marks was predominantly used for attacking.

The high number of indentations indicates the use against rounded or blunt parts of weapons such as spears. Grazes and notches suggest the use against other bladed weapons (see Chapter 3.5). It seems likely that the sword was used against more than one opponent with a variety of weapons. Given the edge dominance, it can be suggested that the left cutting edge was forward facing. The high number of marks on the right cutting edge, in turn, suggests that the fighting style included backhanded action (see Chapter 4.3).

Figure 5.128 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 32.

Sword ID 40 – MOL O.1371 (Figure 5.129)

Figure 5.129 – Sword ID 40 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

29	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Fissure
Left	7	2	1	n/a	1	n/a	1	n/a
Right	12	n/a	1	1	n/a	2	n/a	1
Visibility	1							

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park is of unknown provenance (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 106 No. 625). Originally measuring a total length of 587 mm, the blade has fractured at 290 mm from the tip. The sword is covered in rough green and brown patina. There are two cast rivet holes in the tongue, and one in each shoulder (Figure 5.130). The hilt has slightly curved shoulders and straight ricassi. Bevel lines are not present, a midrib only in the upper part of the blade. There is a high number of segregation holes on the sword, and some corrosion along the cutting edges. All but two marks are located in the lower half of the blade. The tip has fractured off (Figure 5.131).

A total of 29 wear marks were identified on this sword, twelve on the left and 17 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations.

The large amount of corrosion holes indicates a poor alloy or poor casting. Nevertheless, this sword displays signs of intense combat, which occurred most likely on more than one occasion. The indentations suggest use against weapons with blunt sections such as spears. Notches and grazes suggest clashing contacts with other bladed weapons (see Chapter 3.5). The clustering of marks in the lower half of the blade indicates that the distinct leaf-shape and the length of the sword were utilised.

Figure 5.130 – Cast rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 40.

Figure 5.131 – Fractured tip of Sword ID 40.

Sword ID 21 – MOL 28.181/1 (Figure 5.132)

Figure 5.132 – Sword ID 21 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

36	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Double Notch	Curved Graze	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Rebound
Left	3	2	7	1	n/a	4	1	2	3
Right	3	2	3	n/a	2	1	1	1	n/a
Visibility	1								

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-eastern Step 2, was recovered from the River Thames at Teddington Lock, Middlesex (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 70-1 No. 281; Lawrence 1929, 76). There are three rivet holes in the tongue, with two rivets remaining *in situ*, and two rivet holes in each shoulder (Figure 5.133). The bi-conical shape of the rivet holes indicates that they were drilled. Straight shoulders turn into straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The midrib is broad and flat. A straight fracture just below the hilt was repaired. The sword is completely covered in green and brown patina. Slight corrosion has taken place on the entire sword and the cutting edges. However, visibility is adequate, so full analysis could be carried out. Total length of this sword is 575 mm.

A total of 36 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 21 on the left and 15 on the right cutting edge, consisting of a variety of indentations, notches, and grazes. The most common marks are round notches. Although spread along the entire lengths of both cutting edges, the marks seem to cluster between 300-400 mm from the tip, with 50 % of the marks located in this blade section.

This sword displays the signs of extensive use in combat use, which potentially took place on more than one occasion. The variety of marks suggests that the sword was used against different types of blunt and bladed weapons.

Figure 5.133 – Drilled rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 21.

Sword ID 18 – BM 1858,1115.2 (Figure 5.134)

Figure 5.134 – Sword ID 18 obverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

38	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Toothed Notch	Bulge
Left	4	1	n/a	1	n/a	3	1	3	2	1	n/a
Right	4	2	1	1	1	4	5	3	n/a	n/a	1
Visibility	2										

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 2, was found as part of a hoard on Ythsie Farm, Parish of Tarves, Aberdeen, in association with Sword ID 19. Only part of the hoard was presented to the British Museum by the Earl of Aberdeen, and several other associated artefacts are now lost (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 92 No. 490; Coles 1959-60, 82, 97f; Henderson 1937-8, 173; Black 1893, 349f; Evans 1881, 290; Kimble 1863, 161f). There are two rivet holes in each shoulder, and two in the tongue. Three rivets remain *in situ* (Figure 5.135). The cast hilt has straight shoulders and short, straight ricassi, which develop into bevel lines. The sword is covered in heavily corroded, patchy dark patina. In places, the cutting edges are too corroded for analysis, so only the most prominent marks have been recorded. The tip has experienced pressure and is flattened. Total length of this sword is 585 mm.

Despite the poor visibility, a total of 38 marks could be recorded on this sword, 16 on the left and 22 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations, various notches and grazes. One bulge could also be recorded (Figure 5.136). The marks are fairly evenly distributed along the entire lengths of both cutting edges.

The high number of at least 38 wear marks indicates that the sword was likely used in combat. *Circa* two thirds of the marks consist of various grazes and notches, likely caused from clashing contacts with another bladed weapon. The indentations are likely the result of contacts with the rounded areas of weapons such as spear shafts (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.135 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 18.

Figure 5.136 – Mark ID 487, bulge, right cutting edge, 39 mm from the tip of Sword ID 18.

Sword ID 66 – NEWMA1932.21 (Figure 5.137)

Figure 5.137 – Sword ID 66 obverse. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

3	Indentation	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	12	5	3	1	n/a	1
Right	11	2	n/a	1	1	1
Visibility	1					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 2, was discovered on East Hill, 750 m west of Percy's Cross, in Brandon, near Wooler, Northumberland, in 1857 in association with another sword (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 91 No. 473; Cowen 1933, 185ff). The sword is covered in patchy dark patina, which is largely missing on the obverse, and corrosion. Visibility on the cutting edge was adequate though, so full analysis could be carried out. Both ancient and modern striations, below and through the patina, respectively, can be found on the reverse. There are two rivet holes in the tongue and one in each shoulder (Figure 5.138). Bevel lines and a slight midrib are present. The tip has fractured off (Figure 5.139). Total remaining length is 600 mm.

A total of 37 wear marks could be identified, 21 on the left and 16 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations, which add up to 61 % of the marks. On both sides, the marks are evenly distributed along the entire length of the cutting edges.

The identified marks suggest that the sword was extensively used in combat situations. There are exact matches with those marks created during experiments, suggesting that the sword

repeatedly clashed against spear shafts or other rounded, blunt sections of a weapon (see Chapter 3.4.3).

Figure 5.138 – Cast rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 66.

Figure 5.139 – Fractured tip of Sword ID 66.

Sword ID 45 – MOL O.1346 (Figure 5.140)

Figure 5.140 – Sword ID 45 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

39	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	5	1	8	1	1	1	4
Right	7	1	6	n/a	2	n/a	2
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park is of unknown provenance (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 106 No. 638) and has a fractured hilt. The sword is completely covered in slightly corroded green and brown patina. There is one cast rivet hole in each straight shoulder (Figure 5.141). The ricassi are curved. Bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 524 mm. There is a slight bend to the entire blade.

A total of 39 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 21 on the left and 18 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches and indentations. There are also a variety of other notches and grazes. Despite a fairly even spread along most of the cutting edges, the majority of marks are located within the lowest quarter, within 120 mm of the tip. There are several small clusters of marks in immediate proximity to each other (Figure 5.142). This sword displays the signs of intense combat use, against almost certainly more than one opponent. Indentations, notches, and grazes suggest combat against a variety of weapons,

including swords and spears (see Chapter 3.5). The different clusters of marks suggest that the fighter was trained in a combat style, and was repeatedly using the same sections of the blade for the same motions. One can suggest that this particular combat style included slashes, cuts and hacks, with varying degrees of force and velocity. The complete lack of bulges suggests that neither the fighter nor their opponent carried out binding and twisting motions to control the other's weapon. Due to the high number of other marks on this sword, one could suggest that the fighter was not trained in that technique, or that it was not part of their particular combat style.

Figure 5.141 – Cast rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 45.

Figure 5.142 – Cluster of marks, left cutting edge, 87-94 mm from the tip of Sword ID 45

Sword ID 51 – STCMG:1925.SB24.014 (Figure 5.143)

Figure 5.143 – Sword ID 51 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 96 No. 643).

42	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Flattening	Bulge	Rebound
Left	3	3	6	1	n/a	5	n/a	n/a	2	n/a
Right	5	4	4	2	2	n/a	1	3	n/a	1
Visibility	2									

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park is of unknown provenance. It was most likely bought by the museum in 1919, at the same Edinburgh sale as Sword ID 50 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 106-7 No. 643). The sword has fractured in two pieces, and the joins have been tampered with in modern times and no longer fit. It was also subject to heavy polishing around the fracture, and analysis was not possible there. The remaining sword is covered in messy brown and black patina. There are two rivet holes in the tongue, and two in

each shoulder. One rivet, closest to the terminal, remains *in situ*. The straight shoulders are distorted, and the terminal has been filed off. Curved ricassi are present. Total length of this sword is 508 mm.

Despite the heavy polishing of some sections of the sword, a total of 42 wear marks could be identified, 20 on the left and 22 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches and indentations. Three double notches are also present (Figure 5.144). There is a great variety of marks occurring in small numbers. On both sides, the marks are distributed evenly along the cutting edges.

This sword appears to have been subject to extensive combat use. There is so much damage to the cutting edges that no distinctive patterns or clusters could be identified. The combination of indentations, various notches and various grazes, suggests low- and high-speed impacts against other bladed and blunt weapons (see Chapters 3.5 & 4.4). Most likely a combination of hacks, slashes, cuts, and binding and twisting motions were used.

Figure 5.144 – Mark ID 1096, double notch, left cutting edge, 78 mm from the tip of Sword ID 51.

Sword ID 12 – BM 1863,0122.115 (Figure 5.145)

Figure 5.145 – Sword ID 12 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 92 No. 622).

44	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Rebound
Left	1	2	9	3	1	1	4
Right	10	5	3	n/a	2	1	2
Visibility	1						

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park is of unknown provenance. A modern saw was used to cut this sword into two halves. The pieces were then glued back together. Despite including the cut on their drawing, Burgess and Colquhoun (1988, 105, No. 622) fail to mention this in their description. There are eight drilled rivet holes in the hilt, three in the tongue, three in the right and two in the left shoulder. An attempt to drill a third rivet hole in the left shoulder was not completed (Figure 5.146). Straight shoulders merge into straight ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in rough blackish patina. The surface is covered in segregation holes. Some sections of the blade are corroded. Total length of this sword is 521 mm.

A total of 44 wear marks could be identified on this sword, evenly spread along both cutting edges with 21 on the left and 23 on the right. The most common marks are round notches (Figure 5.148) and indentations. The tip has been subjected to pressure and is slightly flattened (Figure 5.147).

This sword bears all the signs of heavy combat use. It shows clear evidence of being used against weapons with both cutting edges and blunt, round parts, such as spears (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.146 – Drilled and unfinished rivet hole in the left shoulder of Sword ID 12.

Figure 5.148 – Mark IDs 248-9, round notch and rebound, left cutting edge, 60-1 mm from the tip of Sword ID 12.

Figure 5.147 – Tip pressure on Sword ID 12.

Sword ID 57 – YORYM1948.1168 (Figure 5.149)

Figure 5.149 – Sword ID 57 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

47	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Flattening	Rebound
Left	4	2	2	3	2	1	1	2	7
Right	10	5	6	2	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1								

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified, was discovered under unknown circumstances near Holderness, Yorkshire, sometime before 1875 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 95 No. 520). The sword is completely covered in dark brown patina, and has fractured in four places. The lowest fracture, c. 101 mm from the tip, is

completely straight and appears to be a modern machine cut. A wedge, possibly for metallographic analysis, has been taken out. The fracture was then re-joined by melting copper-alloy into, and onto, the fracture. At 153 mm from the tip, the second fracture is much more uneven and was crudely repaired by brazing copper-alloy onto the line of breakage. The third (Figure 5.150) and fourth fractures, 241 mm and 347 mm from the tip, respectively, are similarly uneven and were crudely brazed. There are traces of heavy grinding over all four fractures, where the copper-alloy bubbles used for brazing were ground down to create a smooth surface. The rest of the sword is also largely covered in striation patterns of various directions (Figure 5.152). Corrosion holes occur frequently on the blade. The hilt consists of straight shoulders, straight ricassi, and a fractured tongue. There are two drilled rivet holes in each shoulder (Figure 5.152 – One of several striation patterns that occur frequently on the flat of the blade of Sword ID 57.) and one rivet hole in the remainder of the tongue. A third rivet hole was attempted in each shoulder. Total length of this sword is 498 mm.

A total of 47 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 24 on the left and 23 on the right cutting edge. All seven rebound marks are located close to the tip on the left cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. The marks are distributed along the entire lengths of both cutting edges. Severe tip pressure has ground the tip into a round shape. There are several small clusters of two or three marks in close proximity to each other.

This sword displays the signs of extensive combat against a variety of weapons. Such a high amount of marks suggests that the sword was used in more than one combat situation. The small clusters of marks suggest that the sword was used by a trained sword fighter who repeatedly carried out the same motions.

Figure 5.150 – Crudely repaired fracture at 241 mm from the tip of Sword ID 57.

Figure 5.152 – One of several striation patterns that occur frequently on the flat of the blade of Sword ID 57.

Figure 5.151 – Drilled rivet holes in the shoulders of Sword ID 57.

Sword ID 5 – BM WG.1244 (Figure 5.153)

Figure 5.153 – Sword ID 5 obverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

	Inden- tation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Wide- Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elon- gated Graze	Irre- gular Graze	Compres- sion Curling	Bulge	Rebound
Left	7	7	n/a	1	n/a	n/a	1	1	2	2	3	4
Right	7	6	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	1	n/a	n/a	3	n/a
Visibility	1											

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, South-Eastern Step 4, was recovered from the River Thames in Chiswick, Middlesex (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 73 No. 315; Cowen 1967, 449 No. 3,2; Cowen 1952, 145 pl. 17,1). The intact hilt has four rivet holes, two in the tongue and one in each shoulder. Rivets remain *in situ* in each hole (Figure 5.154). Straight shoulders merge into slightly curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The entire sword is covered in smooth, fairly even brown patina. Total length of the sword is 645 mm.

A total of 48 combat related marks could be identified on this sword, 28 on the left and 20 on the right cutting edge. Because of the large overall number of marks this difference cannot be interpreted as clear edge dominance. The most common marks are indentations and various notches. Only a small number of grazes are present. Six bulges could also be identified. Furthermore, there are two striation patterns on the obverse flat of the blade (Figure 5.155). The marks are evenly distributed along the entire length of both cutting edges.

The extremely large amount of wear marks indicates extensive use in combat situations. However, the absence of distinct clusters of marks, and the even spread along both cutting

edges, suggests that the swordsman may not have been a particularly skilled fighter at the time the sword was used. Combining the two, it is possible to interpret this sword as having been used in training, creating a high number of marks whilst practising the combat style. The striation patterns, which were likely created by another bladed weapon scraping along the flat of the blade, are indicative of binding and twisting motions, and feeling and controlling of the opponent's blade (see Chapter 4.3.1).

Figure 5.154 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 5.

Figure 5.155 – Mark ID 110, striation pattern, left bevel line, 390-403 mm from the tip of Sword ID 5.

Sword ID 67 – NEWMA1932.20 (Figure 5.156)

Figure 5.156 – Sword ID 67 obverse. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

59	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Rebound
Left	4	11	7	n/a	1	4	1
Right	10	4	6	3	1	3	4
Visibility	1						

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Step 2, was found forced vertically into the ground, in association with Sword IDs 65 and 68 at Ewart Park, Northumberland, in 1814. The flat sides of the blade appear to have been cleaned, so the patina is mostly lost (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 92 No. 486), but the cutting edges have remained in their original condition. There are two drilled rivet holes in the tongue, and two in each shoulder (Figure 5.157). Straight shoulders, straight ricassi and bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 644 mm.

A total of 59 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 28 on the left and 31 on the right, five of which are rebound marks. The most common marks are sharp notches and indentations. On the right side, the marks are evenly spread along the entire length of the

cutting edge. The marks on the left, however, are exclusively located in the lower half of the sword. More than half of these are located within 100 mm of the tip. Slight tip pressure has occurred (Figure 5.158).

This sword displays the signs of extensive combat against other weapons. The marks suggest that combat was conducted against a variety of weapons including spears and swords (see Chapter 3.5). A complete lack of marks in the upper half of the left cutting edge, combined with the large number of marks in that section on the right cutting edge, suggests that the sword was always held in the same way.

Figure 5.157 – Drilled rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 67.

Figure 5.158 – Tip pressure on Sword ID 67.

Sword ID 65 – NEWMA1814.22.1 (Figure 5.159)

Figure 5.159 – Sword ID 65 obverse. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

68	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Rebound
Left	4	8	7	n/a	4	n/a	n/a	1	2
Right	5	11	19	1	2	2	2	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1								

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Northern Unclassified, was discovered when a grassy hill at Ewart Park, Northumberland, was ploughed for the first time, in 1814. It was found in association with Sword IDs 67 and 68, all of which had been forced vertically into the ground (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 97 No. 542; Cowen 1933, 185ff; Evans 1881, 285). The sword is covered in smooth grey and black patina. Tongue and terminal have fractured off at the rivet hole closest to the blade. There is one rivet hole in each

shoulder. It appears as if there was a further rivet hole, located centrally in the hilt plate, which was filled in an attempt to thicken the hilt (Figure 5.160). The hilt plate consists of straight shoulders and slightly curved ricassi. Bevel lines and a midrib are present. Total length of this sword is 577 mm.

A total of 68 wear marks could be identified, displaying clear edge dominance with 26 on the left and 42 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches and sharp notches. On the right, the marks are distributed along most of the cutting edge, not quite reaching the top end near the hilt. The marks on the left are exclusively located in the lower half of the blade. There are numerous clusters of two or three marks appearing in very close proximity to each other (Figure 5.161).

This sword displays extensive signs of use; however, one can argue that they were not necessarily created in combat. The frequent clusters of marks, likely the result of the same action repeated over and over again, and the known weakness of the hilt could suggest that the sword was mostly used in a training scenario. Altering the hilt by filling in the rivet could have been necessary because of a severe casting fault, which in turn could have caused the fracture of the tongue.

Figure 5.160 – Filled rivet hole in the hilt of Sword ID 67. Figure 5.161 – Cluster of marks, right cutting edge, 358-64 mm from the tip of Sword ID 67.

Sword ID 16 – BM 1878,1101.203 (Figure 5.162)

Figure 5.162 – Sword ID 16 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 57 No. 378).

	Inden- tation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Toothed Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregu- lar Graze	Compres- sion Curling	Rebound
Left	11	4	19	1	1	5	5	4	n/a	11
Right	9	9	26	n/a	n/a	1	n/a	1	1	4
Visibility	1									

Sn	As	Sb	Pb	Co	Ni	Fe	Ag	Au	Zn	Bi
6.70	0.16	1.10	2.21	n/a	0.48	0.037	0.24	n/a	n/a	0.02

Table 5.11 – Sword ID 16 alloy composition (Northover 1988, 145)

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Ewart Park, Eastern Step 1, was recovered from Fulbourne Common, Cambridgeshire (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 79 No. 378; Evans 1881, 279), in association with another Ewart Park type sword (*ibid.*, 80 No. 388). Having a total length of 573 mm, a modern saw was used to cut the sword into four pieces, at 128 mm, 236 mm, and 379 mm from the tip. The pieces were then glued back together. Burgess & Colquhoun fail to mention this in their description, despite including the cuts in their drawing. The sword is completely covered in rough, dark brown patina. There are large amounts of corrosion and segregation holes. The tongue of the hilt has one long elongated rivet slot. Two drilled rivet holes can be found in each shoulder, one of which was not completely drilled through (Figure 5.163). Straight shoulders merge into curved ricassi and bevel lines.

A total of 112 combat-related wear marks could be identified on this sword, 61 on the left and 51 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches and indentations. Various grazes, numerous rebound marks and a toothed notch (Figure 5.164) are also present. The marks are distributed evenly along the cutting edges.

In combination with their distribution along the entire cutting edges, and the absence of any visible patterns, this extremely high number of wear marks could suggest that the sword was not only used in actual combat, but potentially as a training weapon of one, or several, (novice) swordsmen.

Figure 5.163 – Drilled and unfinished rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 16.

Figure 5.164 – Mark ID 364, toothed notch, left cutting edge, 182 mm from the tip of Sword ID 16.

5.5.4 Hallstatt C

Sword ID 42 – MOL O.1342 (Figure 5.165)

Figure 5.165 – Sword ID 42 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

0	Combat Mark
Left	n/a
Right	n/a
Visibility	1

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen is of unknown provenance, and has a fractured hilt and tip (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 119 No. 731; Cowen 1967, 443 No. 186). It is completely covered in smooth and rough black, brown and white patina. Some surface corrosion and corrosion holes are present. The remaining right shoulder is straight, as are the ricassi. There are three small rivet holes in each shoulder. The right shoulder has two rivets remaining *in situ* (Figure 5.166), the left shoulder has fractured (Figure 5.167). There is a slight bend to the entire sword, which increases towards the tip. Total remaining length is 603 mm.

No wear marks could be identified on this sword.

The complete lack of wear marks is evidence that the sword was most likely not used in combat against other weapons. It is likely that the fractured tip and hilt, as well as the bend to the sword, could be the result of an intentional destruction prior to the deposition of the sword.

Figure 5.166 – Right shoulder with one cast rivet hole and a rivet *in situ* on Sword ID 42. Figure 5.167 – Fractured left shoulder on Sword ID 42.

Sword ID 10 – BM WG.2271 (Figure 5.168)

Figure 5.168 – Sword ID 10 reverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

4	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	n/a	1	1
Right	2	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1		

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant C, was recovered from the River Tyne below Newcastle, Tyne and Wear, and is in excellent condition (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 118 No, 715; Cowen 1967, 445 No. 199; Evans 1881, 281 fig. 344). It has been subject to modern polishing on the flat of the blade, and it seems as if a lacquer was applied to preserve the shine. Luckily, the bevel lines and cutting edges were not touched, and so full analysis could be carried out. The original smooth black patina has been preserved on the hilt. There are eight cast rivet holes in the hilt, one in the terminal, three in the tongue, and two in each shoulder (Figure 5.169). The rivet holes are not uniform but differ slightly in shape and size. Straight shoulder on the hilt merge into curved ricassi. Prominent bevel lines are present. Total length of the sword is 694 mm.

Only four wear marks could be identified on this sword, two on each cutting edge. The marks on the right cutting edge are on either end of the blade. On the left, the marks are in close proximity to the each other in the upper third of the blade.

Although the recorded marks suggest that the sword was used in a clashing contact with at least one other bladed weapon, the small number of marks does not suggest extensive combat. However, it is possible that it was used in at least one, very short encounter, before the sword was no longer used. The cluster of marks on the left could be the result of a repeated action.

Figure 5.169 – Cast rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 10.

Sword ID 9 – BM 1857,0920.1 (Figure 5.170)

Figure 5.170 – Sword ID 9 drawing (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, Plate 103 No. 710).

6	Indentation	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch
Left	n/a	1	1
Right	2	2	n/a
Visibility	1		

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant B, was recovered from the River Thames near Battersea, London. There are seven rivet holes in the hilt, one in the terminal, two in the tongue and two in each shoulder. All but one shoulder rivets remain *in situ* (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 117 No. 710; Cowen 1967, 442 No. 171). Towards the outer rivet hole, the left shoulder has fractured and twisted (Figure 5.171). The sword has straight shoulders, curved ricassi and prominent bevel lines. It is mostly covered in smooth black patina. Modern polishing has removed the patina on c. one quarter of the blade on both obverse and reverse. Segregation holes and corrosion occur towards the tip. Total length of this sword is 725 mm.

A total of six microscopic wear marks could be identified, two on the left and four on the right cutting edges, consisting of notches and indentations. On the left, the marks are located towards the top of the blade. The marks on the right are all clustered in the lower third.

This sword is one of the longest of type Gündlingen described in Burgess and Colquhoun (1988), and would have been impressive due to its sheer size and shape. It was elaborately cast, yet not to the highest standard as the segregation holes towards the lower part of the blade indicate. The marks resemble the shapes of those created in combat, however they are much smaller than usual. This could be the result of a particular alloy composition (see Gutiérrez Sáez & Lerma 2015), extreme work-hardening, or very low-velocity impacts. Both shapes and clustering of the marks, however, indicate that a certain level of combat must have taken place. Due to the size and appearance of the blade, it is possible that the sword was mostly intended for display purposes, but was used at least once in a combat scenario.

Figure 5.171 – Fractured left shoulder with one rivet in situ on Sword ID 9.

Sword ID 27 – MOL O.1357 (Figure 5.172)

Figure 5.172 – Sword ID 27 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

9	Indentation	Round Notch	Curved Graze
Left	n/a	n/a	n/a
Right	5	1	3
Visibility	1		

These are the two fragments of one complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant B, dredged from the River Thames near the Iron Church in Brentford, Middlesex, in 1864 (Burgess and Colquhoun 1988, 117 No. 709). At a total length of

726 mm, the blade has been bent and fractured at 518 mm. A second bending was attempted at roughly 37 mm, just above the tip. The bending caused fissures across the blade (Figure 5.173), but failed to fracture it. Except for the area surrounding the bend the sword is covered in grey and black patina. A modern attempt at cleaning was carried out around the tip. There are seven cast rivet holes in the hilt, two in each shoulder (Figure 5.174), two in the tongue, and one in the terminal. The shoulders are straight and merge into slightly curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. With the exception of the bend and the fracture, the only detectable wear marks are located on one cutting edge just below the hilt.

A total of nine wear marks could be identified on this sword, all of which are clustered within 40 mm of each other towards the top of the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations.

This sword does not appear to have been used in combat. Instead, it appears to have been subject to ritual destruction (compare the ritual destruction at Pila del Brancon, Chapter 6.3.2 and Sestieri et al. 2013). The fairly elaborate sword was deliberately bent twice. It is possible that two fractures were intended, but only one was achieved. Instead of a destruction of the cutting edges of this weapon, it is possible that the sword was in fact used to hack or saw through other objects. Either way, the partial deformation preserved the general integrity of the sword, whilst the bending and fracturing ensured that the weapon was rendered useless. The subsequent deposition in the water is also comparable to Pila del Brancon.

Figure 5.173 – Fissures c. 37 mm from the tip of Sword ID 27.

Figure 5.174 –Cast rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 27.

Sword ID 20 – BM 1864,0903.5 (Figure 5.175)

Figure 5.175 – Sword ID 20 reverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

9	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze
Left	1	2	2	3
Right	n/a	1	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1			

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Holme Pierrepont was a single find recovered from the River Thames at an unknown location (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 113 No. 698; Cowen 1967, 443 No. 185; Cowen 1967, 443 No. 185). The sword is in excellent condition and completely covered in smooth, shiny, gold-brown patina. A total of eight rivet holes are present in the hilt, two in the tongue and three in each shoulder (Figure 5.176). The straight shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. Total length of this sword is 637 mm.

A total of nine wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with eight on the left and one on the right cutting edge. All marks on the left edge are clustered within 74 mm of each other in the bottom third of the blade. The sharp notch on the right cutting edge is located further towards the hilt in the mid-section of the blade.

The clear edge dominance and clustering of the marks suggest that the sword was used by a single owner, trained in a combat style that utilises the leaf-swelling of their weapon to repeatedly strike the opponent with the same section of the blade. One can suggest that the marks were created during one combat encounter, potentially with multiple opponents, carrying different types of weapons such as spears and swords (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.176 – Cast rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 20.

Sword ID 26 – MOL O.1379 and 49.107/815 (Figure 5.177)

Figure 5.177 – Sword ID 26 obverse. Image courtesy of the Museum of London.

13	Indentation	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Bulge	Rebound
Left	3	n/a	1	1	1	2
Right	1	1	n/a	3	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1					

These are the two fragments of one complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen (after Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 114-121) of unknown provenance. The different accession numbers suggest that the parts were acquired on two different occasions, and were later found to belong to the same sword. With a total length of 675 mm, the sword has fractured at 406 mm from the tip. It is covered in patchy green, brown and black patina. Some areas are corroded. Three rivets in the tongue and two in the right shoulder (Figure 5.178) remain *in situ*. Two cast rivet holes are present in the left shoulder (Figure 5.179), and one in the terminal. The hilt has straight shoulders and curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. A total of 13 wear marks could be identified on this sword, eight on the left and five on the right cutting edge. The marks are all located in the lowest quarter of the blade, within 133 mm of the tip.

The indentations, notches and grazes suggest clashing impacts with bladed and blunt weapons (see Chapter 3.5). These could have happened against more than one opponent. The bulge indicates that a binding and twisting motion took place (see Chapter 4.4). The overall length, and the clustering of marks towards the tip, suggest that a fighting style that utilises the length of the sword to extend the reach and create an extended personal safety zone was executed.

Figure 5.178 – Two rivets *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 26.

Figure 5.179 – Two cast rivet holes in the right shoulder of Sword ID 26.

Sword ID 1 - BM 1850,1226.1 (Figure 5.180)

Figure 5.180 – Sword ID 1 obverse. Image courtesy of British Museum.

23	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Flattening	Bulge	Blow Mark
Left	2	n/a	1	n/a	1	2	1
Right	2	1	n/a	1	3	n/a	9
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Holme-Pierrepont was recovered from the River Thames during dredging operations near Battersea Bridge, Greater London (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 113 No. 697; Cowen 1967, 442 No. 173). The sword is completely covered in smooth, dark brown patina. Otherwise complete, a fraction of the terminus has been removed with a modern saw (Figure 5.181), possibly for scientific analysis. The sample, however, is no longer available. Five of the six rivets remain *in situ* in the hilt. Both shoulders and ricassi are slightly curved. Prominent bevel lines and a slight midrib swelling in the upper third of the blade are present. The sword measures a total length of 630 mm.

A total of 23 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with seven on the left and 16 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are blow marks on the bevel lines (Figure 5.182), which all occur on the obverse side of the blade. In addition to the right edge dominance, there is also a distinct clustering of marks within 277 mm of the tip on this side. The marks on the left are evenly spread along the entire length of the cutting edge.

Both the clear edge dominance and the clustering of marks in the lower third of the blade on the dominant cutting edge indicate that this sword was used by a skilled swordsman trained in a sophisticated combat style, utilising the length and leaf-shape of the sword for attacking. The bulges indicate that binding and twisting motions took place (see Chapter 4.4). However, the exact cause of the blow marks is yet unknown, so no further interpretations regarding the opposing weaponry can be made.

Figure 5.181 – Modern cut to the terminus of Sword ID 1. Figure 5.182 – Mark IDs 24-6, blow marks on the bevel line of the right cutting edge, 241-5 mm from the tip of Sword ID 1.

Sword ID 71 – NEWMA 1929.67 (Figure 5.183)

Figure 5.183 – Sword ID 71 obverse. Image from www.thecuttingedge-gnm.com.

	Indentation	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Compression Curling
Left	1	5	n/a	2	1
Right	6	7	1	1	1
Visibility	1				

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Unclassified, was recovered from the River Tyne in Newcastle, Tyne and Wear (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 119 No. 729). It is completely covered in smooth black patina. A significant amount of repair work was carried out. Typically for type Gündlingen, the sword would originally have had at least two rivet holes in each shoulder and the tongue. The tongue eventually fractured at the rivet hole closest to the blade; the shoulders were deformed. At least one former rivet hole was closed with a filling (Figure 5.185). The original rivet holes were cast. At a later stage, at least two new rivet holes were drilled (Figure 5.187). The slightly bi-conical profiles suggest drilling from both sides due to the thickness of the material. With a new handle hafted, one shoulder was subject to a further fracture. What remains are straight ricassi and bevel lines. There is a distinct bend to the blade (Figure 5.184). Total length of this sword is 601 mm.

A total of 25 combat-related wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with nine on the left and 16 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches. On the left cutting edge, there are no marks in the upper quarter of the blade closest to the hilt. The marks on the right are evenly distributed along the length of the cutting edge. There are several small clusters of marks. Sharpening striations are common

along both cutting edges. A pattern of scratched striations is visible on the flat of the blade near the bend (Figure 5.186). On the other side, there is a fissure in the mid-section of the flat of the blade (Figure 5.188).

This sword displays the marks of combat, which most likely occurred on more than one occasion. The sword was repeatedly repaired, suggesting the high value of the item to its owner. It was likely used against a variety of weapons including spears and other swords. The striation pattern and bend are identical to that created by the flat parry during the experiment (see Chapter 3.4.2). One can therefore suggest that the sword was used in the same manner, and subsequently became useless. The bending was clearly the last damage inflicted, as experience has shown that fighting with a bent sword is impossible (see Chapter 3.4.4). As evidently a lot of work and effort was put into repairing and maintaining the sword, yet the effort was abandoned once the sword was bent, it is possible that its owner was killed or incapacitated during their last fight.

Figure 5.184 – Sword ID 71 bend.

Figure 5.185 -- Filled and newly drilled rivet hole in the hilt of Sword ID 71.

Figure 5.187 -- Deformed and newly drilled rivet hole in the hilt of Sword ID 71.

Figure 5.186 Striation pattern on the flat of the blade near the bend on Sword ID 71.

Figure 5.188 Fissure on the flat side of the blade opposite the striation pattern on Sword ID 71.

Sword ID 8 – BM 1863,0122.119 (Figure 5.189)

Figure 5.189 – Sword ID 8 obverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

25	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Compression Curling	Rebound
Left	2	n/a	n/a	1	n/a	2	2	n/a	n/a
Right	4	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	1
Visibility	1								

This complete leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant C, was recovered from the River Thames in Kingston on Thames, Surrey, in 1863 (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 118, No. 718; Cowen 1967, 443 No. 177). There is a total of eleven rivet holes in the hilt, with nine rivets *in situ* (all but two in the terminal). Three rivets are in linear alignment in the tongue, and three in each shoulder (Figure 5.190). A modern saw was used to cut the blade in half at 247 mm from the tip, and a wedge, possibly for metallographic analysis, has been removed. Unfortunately, the wedge is no longer available. The sword was then reattached with glue, and the hole of the wedge was filled in. Bevel lines are present. The whole sword is covered in rough dark patina. Corrosion is frequent on the cutting edges, yet visibility was good enough to carry out the analysis on this sword. There is a large amount of small-scale compression curling along the cutting edge, which seems to be the result of poor storage (the sword was lying unsecured in a box with other objects), or possibly even deposition or recovery. This was not included in the analysis. The sword has a total length of 616 mm.

A total of 25 wear marks could be identified, displaying clear edge dominance with seven on the left and 18 on the right cutting edge. The marks consist of nearly equal amounts of various grazes, notches, and indentations. All marks on the left are located in the lower half of the blade. The marks on the right edge are fairly evenly spread.

Such clear edge dominance suggests that this sword was mostly held in the same way, and was therefore the property of a single owner. The amount of wear marks suggests that various high- and low-velocity clashing impacts with other bladed weapons have taken place, potentially in more than one combat scenario. It seems likely that the sword was used against a variety of other weapons, including those with wooden shafts and metal sockets, causing the formation of indentations (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 5.190 – Two rivets *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 8.

Sword ID 14 – BM WG.1238 (Figure 5.191)

Figure 5.191 – Sword ID 14 reverse. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

26	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Rebound
Left	2	1	3	1	1	n/a	1	n/a	n/a
Right	8	n/a	n/a	3	1	1	1	2	1
Visibility	1								

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant D, was found on a peat moss near Brechin, Angus (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 120 No. 740; Cowen 1967, 445 No. 205; Coles 1959-60, 82). There are six rivets *in situ* in the hilt, two in the tongue and two in each shoulder (Figure 5.192). The shoulders are straight and merge into slightly curved ricassi. Bevel lines are present. The sword is covered in rough dark brown and black patina. Total length of this sword is 669 mm.

A total of 26 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying clear edge dominance with nine on the left and 17 on the right. Otherwise evenly spread, there are no marks within 60 mm of the tip. The most common marks are indentations, which occur most frequently on the right cutting edge and appear in small clusters. The tip has been subject to pressure and is flattened (Figure 5.193).

The clear edge dominance indicates a single owner, who has consistently held the sword in the same manner. Whilst the marks are evenly spread along the cutting edges, the clustering of marks indicates that certain actions were carried out repeatedly, as can be expected from a skilled and trained swordsman. The indentations suggest that the sword was not only used

against other swords, but potentially also spears or other shafted weapons (see Chapter 3.5). This variety of opposing weaponry, and the high number of combat marks, suggest that the sword was likely used in more than one combat scenario.

Figure 5.192 – Rivet *in situ* in the left shoulder of Sword ID 14. Figure 5.193 – Slight tip pressure on Sword ID 14.

Sword ID 64 – NEWMA1886.33 (Figure 5.194)

Figure 5.194 – Sword ID 64 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

30	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Compression Curling	Bulge
Left	5	1	n/a	1	1	n/a	4
Right	5	2	4	n/a	1	4	2
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant C, was recovered from the River Tyne during dredging works near the Tyne Bridge in Newcastle, Tyne and Wear (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 118 No. 716; Cowen 1967, 444 No. 198; Brewis 1923, pl. 42 figs. 25, 25a, b; Evans 1881, 281 fig. 344). The sword is completely covered in black patina. There are three rivet holes in the tongue and two in each shoulder (Figure 5.195). Short, straight shoulders, straight ricassi and bevel lines are present. A large amount of corrosion holes is present throughout the sword (Figure 5.196). At a total length of 696 mm, the sword was cut in two at 463 mm from the tip, then reattached with glue. The tip has fractured (Figure 5.197).

A total of thirty wear marks could be identified on this sword, twelve on the left and 18 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations and bulges. On both sides, the marks are evenly distributed along the cutting edges, though there are no marks closer than 87 mm to the tip.

The marks suggest that this sword was used in combat, most likely on multiple occasions or against multiple opponents. A combination of indentations, and various notches and grazes suggests that the opposing weapons had both bladed and blunt sections (see Chapter 3.5). Binding and twisting motions were carried out as is evident through the bulges (see Chapter 4.4). The lack of marks near the tip suggests that forward-thrusting cuts were possibly not part of the combat style used by the sword bearer.

Figure 5.195 – Cast rivet hole in the right shoulder of Sword ID 64.

Figure 5.197 – Fractured tip of Sword ID 64.

Figure 5.196 – Corrosion holes on Sword ID 64.

Sword ID 60 – YORYM1948.1301 (Figure 5.198)

Figure 5.198 – Sword ID 60 obverse. Image courtesy of Adam Parker.

42	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Blow Mark	Rebound
Left	1	1	1	n/a	n/a	2	n/a
Right	6	11	10	1	1	2	6
Visibility	1						

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Gündlingen, Variant C, is of unknown provenance (Burgess & Colquhoun 1988, 119 No. 722), and completely covered in smooth dark brown patina. The hilt has fractured and was partially cut off with a modern saw. Slightly curved ricassi and bevel lines are present. There is a slight bend to the whole blade. Total length of this sword is 603 mm.

A total of 42 wear marks could be identified on this sword, displaying extremely clear edge dominance with five on the left and 37 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are sharp and round notches. The marks on the right are spread along the entire length of the cutting edge and appear in several clusters of two or three marks (Figure 5.199). On the left, the five marks are also spread along the entire length.

This sword displays the signs of repeated clashing impacts with other bladed weapons. However, such clear edge dominance in relation to the large overall number of marks on this sword, combined with the frequent clusters of marks, suggests that the sword could have been used in a training scenario, where distinct motions were repeated multiple times to practice a certain combat style.

Figure 5.199 – Cluster of Mark IDs 1425-8, right cutting edge, 273-8 mm from the tip of Sword ID 60.

5.6 Analysis

To create meaningful statistical analysis, only those swords with Visibility=1 were included in the data set, as it is imperative to analyse the entirety of the sword, lest marks may be missed which could bias the result. Being of unknown Irish provenance, Sword ID 53 was also not included. The remaining swords were split into four categories in accordance with their chronological metalworking stages, in order to highlight the differences and developments over time. Subsequently, 60 swords proved to be statistically relevant, six from the Penard Phase, twelve from the Wilburton Phase, 30 from the Ewart Park Phase, and twelve Hallstatt C (Llyn Fawr Phase). The analysis focuses on the four most common and distinctive marks, namely indentations, notches, bulges, and grazes, which are directly linked to specific combat actions. Different types of notches and grazes, such as round notches, sharp notches, curved grazes and straight grazes, have been merged into the general categories of notches and grazes. As O'Flaherty et al. (2011) have demonstrated, round notches and sharp notches are created during the same kind of combat action, and only differ in the way the swords are moving upon impact. Until further experiments confirm otherwise, it is therefore reasonable to assume that the different types of notches and grazes are most likely created by the same types of respective actions, and the slight differences in shape are only due to subtle variations in sword movement upon impact, or potentially rooted in differing alloy compositions (Gutiérrez-Sáez & Soriano-Llopis 2008). Two types of graphs are being used to visualize the data: box-and-whisker plots to show the location of marks along the swords, and bar charts to illustrate the absolute and relative frequency of the marks. The graphs were built with Microsoft Excel 2016 software.

5.6.1 Location of marks

To visualize where the main combat-related marks are located along the cutting edges, the data set had to be normalised. In order to compare 60 swords of different lengths, the formula $y=(d/D)*100$ (d =distance of mark from the tip, D =total length of sword) was used to express each mark's distance from the tip as a percentage of the entire length of each sword. The decision to calculate the distance as a percentage of the entire length of the sword, rather than of just the blade, had to be made due to the difficulty of establishing the exact limits of each sword blade. Unlike mediaeval swords, where the length of the blade can be expressed as the distance from sword tip to crossguard, the shapes of Bronze Age swords are highly varied, and in many cases, due to the lack of crossguards, no exact end point of the blade can be established. Other indicators such as the length of bevel lines, the start of a midrib, or the end of the ricassi, are also not uniformly present in the sword sample. In fact, many swords lack bevel lines, ricassi or shoulders, or the bevels are of different lengths, the ricassi are askew, or

the midrib starts from the hilt. The whole length of the sword was therefore determined to be the only reliable variable to consider for cross-comparison. Any possible deviations due to fractured tips or grip tongues were deemed small enough to be neglected.

Figure 5.200 – Box-and-whisker plot of normalised mark distances on British Penard Phase swords, illustrating the locations of Indentations, Notches, Grazes and Bulges.

	Indentations	Notches	Grazes	Bulges
Minimum	12	1	4	20
Q1	21	18	14	34
Median	67	41	40	55
Q2	78	63	70	75
Maximum	80	88	82	83
Mean	51	40	41	54
Range	57	45	56	42

Table 5.12 - Statistical values for normalised locations of marks on British Penard Phase swords.

The graph (Figure 5.200) shows that during the Penard Phase, the marks on British swords are fairly evenly distributed within almost 70 % of the length of the sword, whilst generally avoiding the 10 % closest to the tip. However, some outliers place notches and grazes almost directly onto the tip. Notches and bulges seem to be slightly more clustered within c. 45 % of the sword length. There are no bulges located within 20 % of the tip. Only 10 % of the analysed swords fall into this chronological category (six swords), and as such the data cannot be considered as conclusive.

Figure 5.201 – Box-and-whisker plot of normalised mark distances on British Wilburton Phase swords, illustrating the locations of Indentations, Notches, Grazes and Bulges.

	Indentations	Notches	Grazes	Bulges
Minimum	1	7	3	9
Q1	12	22	20	19
Median	32	32	35	30
Q2	60	49	59	45
Maximum	86	81	80	78
Mean	37	36	40	33
Range	48	27	39	26

Table 5.13 - Statistical values for normalised locations of marks on British Wilburton Phase swords.

During the Wilburton Phase, the marks are clustered more closely together within only 50 % of the sword, between c. 10 % and 60 %, with the exception of occasional outliers closer to the tip and hilt (Figure 5.201). There is a much tighter clustering of notches and bulges, with the first being mostly located within only 27 % percent between 22 % and 49 %, and the latter within 26 % between 19 % and 45 % (Table 5.13). The 10 % closest to the tip remain largely unmarked.

Figure 5.202 - Box-and-whisker plot of normalised mark distances on British Ewart Park Phase swords, illustrating the locations of Indentations, Notches, Grazes and Bulges.

	Indentations	Notches	Grazes	Bulges
Minimum	1	1	1	6
Q1	17	20	23	16
Median	35	32	40	27
Q2	61	55	64	43
Maximum	82	83	85	67
Mean	38	37	42	31
Range	44	35	42	27

Table 5.14 - Statistical values for normalised locations of marks on British Ewart Park Phase swords.

The majority of marks on British Ewart Park Phase swords are located within c. 45 % of the blade, though outliers can be found in close proximity to the tip and the hilt. Notches and bulges seem to appear in a slightly tighter cluster of around 30 %. However, in the case of notches there is a large number of outliers either side of the concentration (Figure 5.202).

Figure 5.203 - Box-and-whisker plot of normalised mark distances on British Hallstatt C swords, illustrating the locations of Indentations, Notches, Grazes and Bulges.

	Indentations	Notches	Grazes	Bulges
Minimum	1	3	1	20
Q1	24	34	11	23
Median	57	46	24	54
Q2	75	60	47	59
Maximum	90	92	93	74
Mean	51	46	32	45
Range	51	26	36	36

Table 5.15 - Statistical values for normalised locations of marks on British Ewart Park Phase swords.

The distribution of marks on British Hallstatt C swords is much less uniform than in the earlier periods. Whilst generally located along most of the blade, between 11 % and 75 % of the sword, the different types of marks are clustered in divergent locations and to unequal extents (Figure 5.203). Indentations display the largest spread, within over 50 % in the middle of the blade. Notches are clustered within only 26 % in the upper half of the blade. The grazes are almost exclusively located within 40 % in the lower half of the sword. There are no bulges within 20 % of the tip. Occasional outliers can be found closer to the tip and hilt.

Comparing the locations of marks from four succeeding British Bronze Age metalworking stages, several significant developments can be observed. During the earliest stage, the Penard Phase, the marks are not particularly clustered in any section of the blade. Instead, they are distributed fairly evenly along the entire sword. This lack of distinct clusters or patterns could

suggest that fighting styles had not yet completely developed. However, it must be noted that the small number of six swords in the sample could bias the interpretation.

The next stage, the Wilburton Phase, sees a drastic shift towards the tip, with the majority of marks being located between 10 % and 60 %. There are also some fairly dense clusters of notches and bulges in distinct locations just above the leaf-swelling of the blade. The shift in mark location and the denser clusters suggest that certain types of combat styles had been introduced at this stage, with specific actions that created distinct patterns through repeated execution.

During the Ewart Park Phase, this pattern of mark locations seems to have manifested itself, with all four mark types clustering in roughly the same area, despite an increased number of outliers. It can be suggested that by this point distinct fighting styles had been established. The ever-increasing amount of weaponry, and the associated greater number of weapon bearers, however, would simultaneously have resulted in an increased amount of exceptional circumstances, during which the fighters would have had to deviate from their trained fighting style in order to react accordingly to the opponent.

The following Bronze to Iron Age transition period during Hallstatt C seems to completely change the picture. Gone are the observed patterns created through previous fighting styles, and instead a completely different distribution of marks can be observed. This drastic shift could be the result of several factors: the introduction of iron, and therefore iron weaponry, makes it seem likely that the different materials came into contact with each other. Bronze and iron weapon clashes and their associated marks, however, have to date never been researched or reproduced experimentally. Due to the different material properties of iron swords, it is likely that new fighting styles had been developed, thus influencing the way copper-alloy swords were used in combat. An increased focus on equestrian warfare would also likely influence the mark patterns. Furthermore, a changing society could have developed different values, emphasising other areas of everyday life, resulting in a move away from swordsmanship, thus directly causing a loss of fighting styles and expertise.

5.6.2 Frequency of marks

Figure 5.204 – Bar chart displaying the total numbers of combat related marks on 60 British Bronze Age swords from four metalworking stages. The vastly greater number of marks on Ewart Park Phase swords is partially related to the sample size.

Figure 5.205 – Bar chart displaying the numbers of Indentations, Notches, Grazes and Bulges on 60 British Bronze Age swords from four metalworking stages.

There is a significantly higher amount of Ewart Park Phase marks than from any other British phase examined in this chapter (Figure 5.204). The other three phases display an almost equal amount of combat marks. Examining the individual mark types (Figure 5.205), it becomes apparent that Wilburton and Hallstatt C swords display similar numbers of marks. The charts, however, are biased due to the uneven numbers of swords from the four stages.

To compensate for the above-mentioned bias, the average numbers of each category were calculated using the formula $y = n_m/n_s$ (n_m =number of marks per category, n_s =total number of swords per stage). On average, Penard Phase swords display the highest number of marks,

whilst Wilburton Phase swords display less than half that amount. Ewart Park Phase and Hallstatt C swords rank between the two.

Figure 5.206 - Bar chart displaying the average numbers of combat related marks on 60 British Bronze Age swords from four metalworking stages.

The large average number of 32 marks per Penard Phase sword stands in stark contrast to the 14 marks per sword during the succeeding Wilburton Phase. That number then increases to 24 marks during the Ewart Park Phase, to finally decrease again to 18 marks during Hallstatt C (Figure 5.206). It can be suggested that the lack of sophisticated combat styles during the earliest phase could have resulted in a large amount of combat related edge damage. The introduction of training and fighting styles could then have resulted in the drastic decrease in edge damage. An increase in the amount of weaponry, and associated increased combat, could explain the accompanying higher number of wear marks. Finally, the proposed drastic change in combat and fighting styles during Hallstatt C seems to have resulted in a final decrease in the amount of wear created during that period.

Figure 5.207 - Bar chart displaying the average numbers of Indentations, Notches, Grazes and Bulges on 60 British Bronze Age swords from four metalworking stages.

Figure 5.208 – Bar chart displaying the average number of marks per sword by phase, as recorded on 60 British Bronze Age swords from four metalworking stages.

Evaluating the average numbers of the different mark types shows that the average numbers of indentations, grazes and bulges are fairly similar during the three later phases (Figure 5.207). Penard Phase swords have an outstandingly large number of notches. Wilburton Phase and Hallstatt C swords have near equal amounts of indentations, notches and grazes. Bulges are present during all four stages (Figure 5.208).

Whilst the average numbers of marks provide an insight into the development of sword usage through the stages, it must be noted that, in reality, the individual swords display largely varying numbers of marks and type. Really, there is no such thing as an average sword.

5.7 Conclusion

The metalwork wear analysis methodology described in Chapter 3.3.1 was successfully employed to analyse 70 Middle and Late Bronze Age swords from a variety of British Museums. These could be interpreted based on the reference collection created during the experiments discussed in Chapters 3 and 4. Following the descriptions of individual swords and their wear, the statistical analysis has revealed data which suggests that fighting styles became more specialised over time, before a sudden change during the Late Bronze Age to Early Iron Age transition period occurred. In order to compare the combat practices of different geographic regions within Europe, the next chapter will introduce and discuss the wear analysis of Italian swords.

Chapter 6. Wear analysis of Italian swords

6.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the metalwork wear analysis of 40 Italian swords dating to the Middle and Recent Bronze Age. After an introduction to the three main archaeological find contexts and the relevant chronologies, the chapter provides detailed descriptions of each individual sword and their wear marks. This is followed by some statistical analysis of the Italian sword sample as a whole.

6.2 Method

Two research trips were undertaken to Italy in order to analyse and collect data for a total of 40 Italian swords. In March 2016, I was given permission to analyse a number of swords at the Soprintendenza Archeologica per il Veneto in Verona. Only 30 swords were deemed in good enough condition to carry out wear analysis. Of these, 21 swords were recovered from the Olmo di Nogara cemetery, near Verona. Five swords were found as part of the Pila del Brancon hoard, discovered only 1.5 miles south of Olmo di Nogara. A further three swords were obtained from the Corte Lazise context, discovered in Lazise on the shores of Lake Garda. Both Pila del Brancon and Corte Lazise lie within an area that is known to contain deliberate wetland depositions of metalwork during the later Bronze Age (Pearce 2007, 100). Finally, a single sword without known context or affiliation was added to the sample, as it showed clear traces of a wooden scabbard *in situ* on the blade.

As 30 swords were deemed too small a number to carry out a meaningful comparison between British and Italian wear marks, permission was sought to access another collection elsewhere. In May 2017, permission was granted to examine a further 18 swords at the Museo Nazionale Preistorico Etnografico “Luigi Pigorini” in Rome, ten of which were suitable for analysis, thus boosting the total number of Italian swords analysed for this project to 40. The same comprehensive approach to wear analysis as described in Chapter 3 was used to record traces found on the entirety of the swords. Using an Access database, type, size, and location of each mark were recorded meticulously. In most cases, a GX-Cam 9 mounted on an optical stereo microscope and GX Capture software were used to take high-quality micrographs of each mark. Macrographs of the whole swords were also taken. Whilst travelling to Verona, however, the suitcase containing microscope and stand was left behind by the airline, and for two days it was necessary to switch to a handheld DinoLite digital microscope and DinoCapture software, which was carried as backup in the hand luggage. The same limitations regarding the DinoLite, as outlined in Chapter 5.2, applied, such as the lower quality of micrographs, and the slow and time-consuming process. However, the pictures and

data are overall comparable with those taken with the stereo microscope, and six swords were analysed this way. Once the lost luggage was delivered by the airline, much faster progress could be made. Location of marks on the sword is referred to as obverse or reverse, whereby the obverse is most commonly the side with the museum accession number painted on, and left or right cutting edge refers to the sword being held with the tip downwards. With this method, it was possible to identify and record over 850 wear marks. After processing the data, numerous patterns of wear marks could be identified. The following pages introduce the three main archaeological contexts, followed by descriptions of the swords and their marks, as well as an analysis of the patterns, and possible interpretations. All swords have been divided into categories, first chronologically, then by the number of marks detected on the cutting edges.

6.3 Archaeological contexts

Figure 6.1 – Map of Italy showing the provenance of the swords described in this chapter. The location of Olmo di Nogara is highlighted, as a large number of swords were recovered from this cemetery, which could not be displayed individually on the map.

The map (Figure 6.1) shows the locations from which the swords discussed in this chapter were recovered. Swords that were discovered in the same spot cannot be displayed individually, hence the relatively small number of provenance markers on the map.

6.3.1 *Olmo di Nogara*

Located c. 30 km south of the city of Verona, the cemetery of Olmo di Nogara sits on a plain surrounded by the rivers Adige, Mincio, and Po. The cemetery, dating to the Middle to Recent Bronze Age, is one of the most important late prehistoric burial sites in Italy. Bi-ritual funerary traditions have deposited at least 61 cremations and 456 inhumations between the first half of the 16th century and the second half of the 12th century BC, although some evidence in the form of small scattered pits with artefacts attributed to the Lagozza and Square-mouthed Vase Cultures suggests use of the site as early as the Late Neolithic. There is further evidence that the site continued to be in use during the Roman period and, much later, in the Middle Ages (Salzani 2005, 537).

Similar to other contemporary Bronze Age cemeteries in the region, such as Povegliano, Bovolone or Scalvinetto di Legnago, many of the inhumation burials at Olmo di Nogara are of so-called warrior elite male individuals, identified by accompanying grave goods such as swords, daggers, spears, or helmets (Cupitò et al. 2015, 333). In contrast to nearby cemeteries, however, at Olmo di Nogara, the number of inhumations with grave goods is comparatively high at 32.7 % (Salzani 2005, 537). Whilst the inhumations clearly depict an idealised individual hero ideology, the picture they paint is distorted. Arrowheads found lodged in the bodies of at least two individuals are evidence that bow and arrow were indeed still used in combat, although they were not deposited as grave goods associated with warriors. Similarly, axes are not part of the associated grave goods, which could mean that they were not used in combat, or not regarded as warrior items (Cupitò et al. 2015, 333). Inhumations associated with female individuals tend to contain a characteristic pair of pins and accompanying amber beads, positioned on the chest of the body. Alternatively, the pins could have been part of a costume or dress worn at the time of burial. Whilst serving the practical purpose of fastening the fabric, some theories suggest that the way pins were worn is closely related to age, gender, and identity of the individual (Stig Sørensen 1997). The majority of these burials are extended supine inhumations, although crouched, flexed, and extended inhumations are also present. It was suggested that the bodies would usually have been wrapped in a gown, although some evidence for wooden cases could be found. There are occasionally graves containing two individuals, usually an adult and a newborn infant. Evidence for ancient grave robbing has been found at Olmo di Nogara, indicating that the burial place and grave structures used to be prominent and visible in the landscape (Salzani 2005, 537-8).

The cremation graves contain single urns placed at the bottom of a small pit, usually covered by a stone, without accompanying grave goods. As the pits were generally shallow and close to the prehistoric ground surface, ploughing has seriously disrupted the record.

Chronologically, the Bronze Age burial ground can be divided into at least three major phases. Phase 1 and 2 are attributable to the Italian Middle Bronze Age (c. 1650-1350/1300 cal BC), the third phase to the Recent Bronze Age (c. 1350/1300-1200 cal BC; *ibid.*).

Osteological analysis of the human remains has produced evidence for direct interpersonal violence. In many cases, the trauma is directly comparable to the weaponry deposited with the individuals (Cupitò 2015, 333-4).

Figure 6.2 – Site plan of Olmo di Nogara Area B (Salzani 2005, 38), displaying the locations of graves TB 392 (Sword ID 97), TB 442 (Sword ID 75), TB 472 (Sword ID 86), TB 475 (Sword ID 98), TB 477 (Sword ID 82), TB 483 (Sword ID 72), TB 484 (Sword ID 80) and TB 500 (Sword ID 87).

Figure 6.3 – Site plan of Olmo di Nogara Area C (Salzani 2005, 113), displaying the locations of graves TB 28 (Sword ID 81), TB 31 (Sword ID 85), TB 33 (Sword ID 95), TB 34 (Sword ID 73), TB 48 (Sword ID 83), TB 50 (Sword ID 84), TB 54 (Sword ID 76), TB 63 (Sword ID 96), TB 113 (Sword ID 74), TB 115 (Sword ID 88), TB 153 (Sword ID 79), TB 163 (Sword ID 77) and TB 202 (Sword ID 89).

6.3.2 *Pila del Brancon*

Discovered by chance in 1993, the Pila del Brancon bronze hoard was recovered from the bank of the river Tartaro near Nogara, province of Verona. The hoard dates to the Recent to Final Bronze Age transition period around 1200 BC, and consists of a total of ten to 13 fragmentary swords, two daggers, 50 or so spearhead fragments, a bronze vessel, and a set of armour consisting of corselet and helmet. It has been suggested that the artefacts were deposited simultaneously in the water, following an outstanding ritual treatment of the weapons. The ritual is characterised by the partial or complete annihilation of the basic functionalities of the weaponry, whilst preserving their physical appearance and integrity. It was further suggested that the combination and number of weapons can be attributed to a group of armed men following a single leader. The weaponry is directly comparable to a contemporary group of grave goods from the nearby Olmo di Nogara cemetery (Sestieri et al. 2013, 155).

Although both swords and spearheads underwent similarly destructive treatments, the way the two types of weapons were treated is significantly different. The ritual destruction of the swords was carried out in a number of different stages. First, the hilt was manually bent until the handle faced a different direction to the blade, thus making the weapon uncontrollable. The second stage consisted of a hammering treatment of the cutting edges to create an undulated appearance, but was only carried out on two swords (none of which were examined for this research). Thirdly, the tip would be deformed, usually with the aid of fire, to bend, break, or melt the point. Finally, the whole sword would be bent into a u-shape, before the sword was deposited in the water. Whilst these steps were carried out to destroy the characteristic function of the swords, it is apparent that the intention was to preserve their intrinsic integrity and physical appearance (ibid., 159-161). The treatment of the spearheads is much less systematic, yet equally destructive. First, the wooden shafts were removed, as is evident through the complete lack of rivets or organic remains in the sockets. Then a combination of partial or complete fragmentation and mechanical deformation of the spearheads was carried out, the latter including partial removal of the cutting edges or disfiguration by hammering of the socket. To achieve both fragmentation and deformation, a combination of cold and hot working would have to be utilised. However, the temperatures never reached the melting point of the copper alloy, ostensibly to preserve the basic shape of a spearhead. Extent of treatment is inconsistent and varies, from the complete destruction to the near-complete preservation of individual spearheads (ibid., 161-2).

Different treatment of the two groups of weapons may suggest that different values were attributed to each. The swords appear to have been treated with a certain individual respect for

each item, and for the group as a whole. Whilst spearheads, however, could also be used as weapons, they have more general purposes than swords and were used in many aspects of everyday life, such as hunting, and were likely given to the great majority of able men. Spearheads can therefore be associated with the male identity as a whole, rather than a specific warrior identity (ibid., 162).

6.3.3 *Corte Lazise*

The Corte Lazise site context was first recognised after archaeological surveys were carried out in the area in 1990. Further campaigns were initiated in 1997 and 2004, alongside major agricultural improvement works in the area. Combined fieldwork and aerial photography have identified the archaeological context to stretch over an area of nearly 3,000 square feet (Salzani 2006, 25-6). Besides tens of thousands of ceramic fragments recovered from the entire area, over 50 individually deposited copper-alloy artefacts have been found, including numerous daggers, pins, discs, and ten swords (ibid., 26-31). Typological analysis has dated the site complex to the transition phase between Middle and Recent Bronze Age (c. 1400-1300 cal BC). Interpreted as a votive area, the site is located centrally between a number of settlement structures interpreted as contemporary villages, and it has been suggested that the site was not inhabited by one single community but was rather the political “central place” within the surrounding region. Whilst burial contexts containing grave goods, especially weaponry, seem to disappear during the Middle to Recent Bronze Age transition period, it has been suggested that instead of inhumation of individuals with their associated material culture, burial tradition shifted to cremation with deposition, and perhaps display, of the grave goods in a votive area (ibid., 33-4).

6.3.4 *Stray finds*

The remaining ten swords (Sword IDs 102-111) were analysed in the Museo Nazionale Preistorico Etnografico “Luigi Pigorini” in Rome, and consist mostly of stray finds without any known archaeological context. All but one sword date to the Recent Bronze Age (c. 1350/1300-1200 cal BC), with the exception being Sword ID 104 dating to the Middle Bronze Age (c. 1650-1350/1300 cal BC). If available, provenance and circumstances of discovery have been included in the individual descriptions for these swords.

6.4 Sword chronologies

The following table provides the relative and absolute chronologies of all Italian sword types examined as part of this research. Whilst the relative chronologies were taken from the referenced literature, the absolute chronology was determined through Nicolis’s summarized and integrated proposal for an Italian Bronze Age chronology (Nicolis 2013, 693-4).

Sword ID (Acc. No.)	Type	Relative Chronology	Absolute Chronology	Reference
75 (TB 442), 79 (TB 153)	Boiu IIb/Teòr	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 49
85 (TB 31), 76 (TB 54)	Boiu Ib	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 12
88 (TB 115)	Castiglione da Marano	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 27
95 (TB 33), 78 (VR 38733)	Boiu IIa / Castions di Strada	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 43
77 (TB 163), 83 (TB 48)	Boiu Ia / Wildon	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Salzani 2005, 536
87 (TB 500)	Chiese	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Salzani 2005, 536
96 (TB 63), 86 (TB 472)	Nogara	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Salzani 2005, 536
104 (15503)	Castione	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 17
84 (TB 50), 98 (TB 475)	Sauerbrunn	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 12
82 (TB 477)	Olmo	Middle Bronze Age	1650-1350/1300 cal BC	Salzani 2005, 536
97 (TB 392)	Spade a base trapezoidal	Middle Bronze Age	c. 1500 BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 14; Della Casa 2013, 712
73 (TB 34)	Asenkofen	Middle Bronze Age	c. 1550 – 1300 BC	Müller-Karpe 1974, 30; Della Casa 2013, 712; Jockenhövel 2013, 730
110 (23211), 94 (VR 40291), 93 (VR 40289), 92 (VR 40288)	Cetona	Recent Bronze Age	1350/1300-1200 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 64; Sestieri et al. 2013, 162
72 (TB 483)	Treviso	Recent Bronze Age	1350/1300-1200 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 61
102 (28634)	Montegiorgio	Recent Bronze Age	1350/1300-1200 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 61
107 (48137), 109 (32927), 108 (23210), 90 (VR 26487)	Allerona	Recent Bronze Age	1350/1300-1200 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 68; Sestieri et al. 2013, 162
111 (79477)	Monza	Recent Bronze Age	1350/1300-1200 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 31
99 (123571), 100 (147177), 101 (123570)	Terontola	Recent Bronze Age	1350-1300-1200 cal BC	Salzani 2006, 31 Bianco Peroni 1970, 35-6
80 (TB 484), 81 (TB 28), 74 (TB 113), 89 (TB 202), 103 (20997)	Bigarello	Advanced Middle Bronze Age	c. 1350 BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 19
91 (VR 26488)	Arco	Recent/Final Bronze Age	c. 1200 BC	Sestieri et al. 2013, 158
106 (85586)	Spade a pomo discoidale	Final Bronze Age	1200-900 cal BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 103
105 (23209)	Cuma	Early Iron Age	900-700 BC	Bianco Peroni 1970, 88

Table 6.1 - Relative and absolute chronologies of all Italian sword types examined.

6.5 Swords descriptions and figures

This section provides a detailed description of each Italian sword and their marks analysed for this research. The section is split into three categories in accordance with the chronological phases of Middle Bronze Age, Recent Bronze Age, and Early Iron Age. As in the previous chapter, the visibility of marks has been rated “1” to “3”, with “1” being excellent visibility, allowing a full assessment of the sword, “2” being poor visibility, where only parts of the blade could be examined due to corrosion or other factors, and “3” being extremely poor visibility, where the majority of the blade could not be examined.

6.5.1 Middle Bronze Age, c. 1650-1300 cal BC

Sword ID 78 - VR 38733 (Figure 6.4)

Figure 6.4 – Sword ID 78 reverse.

	Indentation	Round Notch	Irregular Graze
Left	1	1	n/a
Right	n/a	n/a	1
Visibility	3		

This slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword was identified as type Castions di Strada according to Bianco Peroni’s typology (Bianco Peroni 1970, 41). Provenance and circumstances of discovery are unknown. The entire sword is covered in black, brown, and green patina. Large amounts of corrosion are present on the blade. The accompanying information in the museum states that there are still traces of wood and leather present, originating from the scabbard the sword was buried in. The semi-circular grip plate has four rivets *in situ* in each shoulder. Curved ricassi, faint bevel lines and a midrib are also present. There are decorations on the grip plate and surrounding the upper part of the midrib. The sword remains at a total length of 759 mm.

Due to the heavy corrosion, it was only possible to record three prominent wear marks, two on the left cutting edge and one on the right. On the left, a mark can be found towards both the top and the bottom of the blade. The mark on the right (Figure 6.5) is situated in the middle of the cutting edge. Although the marks do suggest that blade on blade contact has happened, it looks more like a very deliberate use in very few strikes than actual combat damage. However, due to the corrosion, it is possible that there are further marks that remain undetectable.

Figure 6.5 – Mark ID 1947, irregular graze, right cutting edge, 389 mm from the tip of Sword ID 78.

Sword ID 104 – 15503 (Figure 6.6)

Figure 6.6 – Sword ID 104 obverse.

3	Sharp Notch	Irregular Graze
Left	1	n/a
Right	n/a	2
Visibility	1	

This copper-alloy sword of type Castione was discovered at Gambaloni Tomb 6 at Povegliano Veronese, Province of Verona, during the 19th century, without associated finds (Bianco Peroni 1970, 16-7). At only 290 mm total length this weapon is uncharacteristically short, and reminds of a modern dagger. The sword is covered in smooth green, brown and gold patina. Four rivet holes were drilled into the round grip plate. Very round shoulders turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines are not present. The blade thickens towards the middle, almost like a midrib, and is covered in striations which appear to be a rough attempt at polishing. It seems like the grip plate had a tongue attached which has fractured off.

Three marks could be identified, one on the left and two on the right cutting edge. All marks are located in the middle of the blade. The sharp notch and two irregular grazes (Figure 6.7) are few, but distinct, marks on an otherwise very short, peculiar blade.

Figure 6.7 – Mark ID 2612, irregular graze, right cutting edge, 111 mm from the tip of Sword ID 104.

Sword ID 84 - TB 50 (Figure 6.8)

Figure 6.8 – Sword ID 84 obverse.

3	Round Notch	Straight Graze
Left	1	1
Right	n/a	1
Visibility	1	

Tomb 50 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara contained a complete inhumation, extended lying on the back, with a sword lying on top of the skeleton. The sword hilt protruded over the right shoulder, and the tip was located on top of the pelvis. A cup was deposited to the right of the skull. The *post-mortem* deformed cranium prevented an accurate determination of the age. Based on size of the bones, however, the skeleton was estimated to be an adult male, 159.4 cm tall (Salzani 2005, 135-6). An indentation on the cranial vault can be interpreted as a healed perforation trauma. Due to the level of bone regrowth it is suggested that the injury was sustained more than one year prior to death (Canci et al. 2015, 775; Pulcini 2014, 140; Canci et al. 2009, 9).

The complete, slightly leaf shaped copper-alloy sword of type Sauerbrunn is completely covered in fairly smooth green and brown patina. The grip plate has five rivets remaining *in situ*. Curved, short ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is also present. Elaborate decorations can be found on the hilt plate (Figure 6.9) and the upper midrib (Figure 6.10). The sword has a length of 551 mm.

Only three marks were identified on this blade, two on the left and one on the right cutting edge. One round notch was found on the left near the tip, and two straight grazes were

identified directly opposite each other on either side of the blade in the upper third. Such an elaborately decorated sword with only three, very deliberate-looking marks, could indicate a ritual use rather than combat.

Figure 6.9 – Decorations on the hilt plate of Sword ID 84

Figure 6.10 – Decorations on the hilt plate and along the midrib of Sword ID 84.

Sword ID 82 - TB 477 (Figure 6.11)

Figure 6.11 – Sword ID 82 obverse.

5	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	2	n/a	n/a
Right	n/a	1	2
Visibility	1		

Tomb 477 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara contained a complete extended inhumation of an adult male, c. 40 years of age, lying on his back. A sword was placed on top of his right arm, with the hilt protruding over his shoulder. The male was 167.1 cm tall (Salzani 2005, 94-5).

The sword is a complete, slightly leaf-shaped, copper-alloy sword of type Olmo. It is covered in green, brown, and black patina. Large amounts of pock mark corrosion are present on the blade. The hilt retains all 13 rivets *in situ*, six in the tongue and seven in the grip plate (Figure 6.12). Slightly curved shoulders turn into straight ricassi. Bevel lines are not present. A prominent thick midrib extends the length of the blade. This sword is very elaborate and measures 649 mm in length.

Five marks were identified on this sword, two on the left and three on the right cutting edge. One mark is located very high on the cutting edge, one at around 200 mm on the left. The other marks all cluster around 70-100 mm from the tip.

The small amount of five marks suggests that this sword was only used for a small amount of fighting against other bladed weapons.

Figure 6.12 – Thirteen rivets *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 82.

Sword ID 97 - TB 392

8	Indentation	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze
Left	3	n/a	1	1	n/a
Right	1	1	n/a	n/a	1
Visibility	1				

Tomb 392 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara contained the extended inhumation of a 40-50-year-old male, buried lying on his back. Sixteen shell studs, each with a diameter of c. 15 mm, were arranged in a semicircle to the top right of his head. A sword of type Spade a Base Trapezoidale (sword with a trapezoidal hilt plate) was deposited on his body, the hilt over his torso, with the blade extending over his pelvis and further between his hips terminating at the knees. The male measured at a height of 163 cm (Salzani 2005, 49). Osteological evidence suggests that the male, along with a small percentage of his community, suffered from tuberculosis (Pulcini 2014, 97-8).

The straight bladed copper-alloy sword tapers towards a pointy tip (Figure 6.13). An almost square grip plate with two thick rivets *in situ* ends in a fractured tongue. Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A slight midrib is also present. The entire blade is covered in smooth green and brown patina. At a length of 666 mm, only a few tiny marks could be identified. Macroscopically, the sword appears entirely unused, bar some sharpening striations.

The total of eight microscopic marks, five on the left and three on the right cutting edge, are located in clusters. The three indentations on the left are located near the tip. On the right, the marks are clustered further up the blade. The most common marks are indentations.

Only a few very small marks have been found on this sword, and the blade seems almost new and unused. It appears that the sword was not used in heavy combat. Contacts likely occurred with other weapons such as swords and spears (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 6.13 – Tip of Sword ID 97.

Sword ID 87 - TB 500 (Figure 6.14)

Figure 6.14 – Sword ID 87 obverse.

12	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Elongated Graze
Left	2	1	n/a	n/a	n/a
Right	6	n/a	1	1	1
Visibility	1				

Tomb 500 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara contained the complete extended inhumation of a mature male in an oval pit aligned precisely West-East, with the feet located in the West. Although almost complete bar one missing vertebra, the male had been decapitated; his skull was buried around 30 cm NE of the body. Both arms were aligned fairly straight along the torso. A sword of type Chiese and a dagger of type Capurso were deposited on the male's left arm. Both weapons were aligned parallel, with the hilts towards the shoulder and tips towards the feet. The male was 163.7 cm tall (Salzani 2005, 108). Osteological examination has recorded an extensive neoformation of bone within the left sinus, usually associated with dental infections. However, no caries or abscesses could be recorded, indicating that an injury must have initiated the growth (Pulcini 2014, 103).

This complete copper-alloy sword has a total length of 823 mm, and is completely covered in rough green, brown, and black patina and pock mark corrosion. The trapezoidal grip plate with rounded shoulders terminates in a cylindrical grip tang. Four rivets remain *in situ*, two in each shoulder (Figure 6.15). Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A slightly rounded midrib is also present. The tip has fractured off (Figure 6.16).

A total of twelve marks could be identified, three on the left and nine on the right cutting edge, indicating a clear edge dominance. The majority of the marks are eight indentations, completed by two types of notches and two types of grazes. Despite the length of the blade, the marks tend to be clustered in the 300-400 mm section on the right cutting edge. The two indentations on the left cutting edge are located in direct proximity to each other at around 400 mm. On the right edge, the indentations also seem to be located in a cluster.

It seems possible that the male was a left-handed fighter, and, combined with the clear edge dominance, it is reasonable to assume that the sword was always held in the same way (see Chapter 4.4). Additionally, the sword displays an amount of marks that likely stems from at least one action of combat or battle. The dominant presence of indentations suggests that the opposing weapons were both blunt and bladed, such as a spear (see Chapter 3.5). Although the male possibly met his death during a combat encounter, he was most likely not

decapitated during a battle. Decapitation requires an enormous amount of repeated force to separate the ligaments, muscle tissue and bone structure in the neck, for which the fast pace of a battle would not allow enough time.

Figure 6.15 – Grip tang and four rivets *in situ* on Sword ID 87.

Figure 6.16 – Fractured tip on Sword ID 87.

Sword ID 80 - TB 484 (Figure 6.17)

Figure 6.17 – Sword ID 80 obverse.

14	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	3	n/a	n/a	1	1	1	n/a	n/a
Right	2	2	1	n/a	n/a	1	1	1
Visibility	1							

Tomb 484 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara is an oval pit aligned WSW-ENE, which contained the complete extended inhumation of an adult male buried on his back. He was 166.5 cm tall. The arms are aligned straight along the torso. A sword of type Bigarello was deposited on top of the male's left arm, the hilt resting over his shoulder and the tip of the sword aligned with the fingertips of his left hand (Salzani 2005, 98).

The complete copper-alloy sword has a total length of 605 mm. Its straight cutting edges taper towards a pointy tip. There is no tang present at the hilt, but a rounded grip plate with six thick rivets remaining *in situ* (Figure 6.19). Short, curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is not present. The entire sword is covered in fairly smooth green, brown and black patina.

A total of 14 wear marks could be identified on this sword, six on the left and eight on the right cutting edge. The marks on the left edge are all clustered in the lower part of the blade within 10 cm of each other, between 110-214 mm. On the right cutting edge, a clustering of

five marks appears within 40 mm of the tip. The most common marks are indentations (Figure 6.18) and grazes of various types.

It is likely that this sword was used in skilled combat. The amount of marks detected would coincide with at least one combat encounter. Mark clusters on each cutting edge suggest the skilled and precise use of the weapon, repeatedly using the same part of the blade to strike the target. The indentations and grazes suggest contacts with other bladed and blunt weapons (see Chapter 3.5). Deposition of the sword on the male's left arm could be linked to a certain handedness of the individual.

Figure 6.18 – Mark ID 2011, indentation, right cutting edge, 190 mm from the tip of Sword ID 80.

Figure 6.19 – Six rivets *in situ* in the shoulders of Sword ID 80.

Sword ID 96 - TB 63

15	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze
Left	4	1	n/a	1	1	1	n/a	n/a
Right	1	n/a	2	1	n/a	n/a	1	2
Visibility	1							

Tomb 63 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is an oval pit aligned N-S which contained the complete extended inhumation of an adult male, 173.5 cm tall. Buried with the arms extended and aligned next to the torso, a sword of type Nogara was deposited on top of the left arm. Whilst the hilt was placed over the shoulder, the sword was actually angled inwards and downwards so that the tip was located just below the left pelvis (Salzani 2005, 141-2).

The complete copper-alloy sword consists of a blade with straight edges, a triangular hilt plate with three rivets *in situ* in each slightly rounded shoulder (Figure 6.20), and a hilt tang. Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. The blade swells to a rounded midrib section. At a length of 665 mm, the sword is completely covered in smooth green, black, and brown patina.

A total of 15 marks could be identified, eight on the left and seven on the right cutting edge. No marks at all could be identified around the tip. Instead, the marks are spread fairly evenly along the entire length of the blade. Indentations are the most common marks, but there is no apparent pattern detectable. The other marks are a variety of notches and grazes.

Buried with the sword deposited on his left arm, it is possible that the male was left-handed. The sword appears to have been used in at least one fighting sequence, the grazes suggest several high-velocity impacts. Notches and grazes further indicate the use against other bladed weapons (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 6.20 – Rivets *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 96.

Sword ID 77 - TB 163 (Figure 6.21)

Figure 6.21 – Sword ID 77 obverse.

20	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	1	1	3	1	1	n/a
Right	7	n/a	1	1	3	1
Visibility	2					

Tomb 163 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit with rounded corners containing the almost complete inhumation of a mature adult male buried extended lying on his back, 162.7 cm tall. Seven decorative nails were placed in a semi-circle to the top right of his head. A sword of type Boiu Ia/Wildon was placed on top of his right arm, with the hilt positioned directly over his shoulder and the tip on his wrist (Salzani 2005, 186).

The slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword is completely covered in green and brown patina. Large amounts of pock mark corrosion have formed on the surface of the blade. Traces of the wooden scabbard can be found on the sword. The tongue has fractured at the set of rivet holes

closest to the hilt. There are two rivets *in situ* in each shoulder on the semi-circular hilt plate. Curved ricassi and a midrib are present. The sword measures a total length of 524 mm.

Due to the heavy corrosion, only 20 wear marks could be identified from the lower two thirds of the blade; the remaining sections are in too poor condition to be analysed. Of the 20 marks recorded, seven are located on the left, and 13 on the right cutting edge. Eight thereof are indentations.

Unfortunately, the corrosion prohibits a complete analysis of the blade, and any interpretation of the data would likely be incorrect.

Sword ID 73 - TB 34 (Figure 6.22)

Figure 6.22 – Sword ID 73 obverse.

20	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	3	n/a	1	n/a	2	1	1
Right	6	1	1	1	n/a	2	1
Visibility	1						

Tomb 34 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is an oval pit aligned W-E containing the complete extended inhumation of a mature adult male, no older than 40 years, with his feet pointing westwards. To the right of his head, 15 pin heads were arranged in a circular feature. A sword of type Asenkofen was positioned diagonally on top of the male’s torso, with the hilt placed over his left shoulder and the tip protruding over the body over his right hip. A sixteenth pin head was placed near the tip. Osteological analysis has estimated the male’s height as 160.9 cm (Salzani 2005, 126-7).

The complete copper-alloy sword of type Asenkofen is outstandingly long, as it measures a total length of 808 mm, which makes this sword half the length of the buried individual. Straight cutting edges taper towards a fractured tip. The entire sword is covered in patchy green and brown patina. Pock mark corrosion occurs frequently on the blade. A broad, flanged tongue (Figure 6.24), straight shoulders and slightly curved ricassi make up the hilt. Five very thick rivets remain *in situ* in the tongue, two smaller rivets remain in each shoulder (Figure 6.23). Bevel lines occur only in the lower third of the blade. A midrib is not present.

A total of 20 wear marks could be identified, eight on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge. Remarkably, given the length of the sword, all eight marks on the left cutting edge are clustered within 200 mm of each other, between 300-500 mm from the tip. The marks on the right cutting edge are more evenly distributed along the length of the blade. The most

common marks are nine indentations and seven grazes of various kinds. A double notch is also present.

The clustering of marks on the left cutting edge indicates skilled use of the blade, repeatedly hitting the target with the same mid blade section. Twenty marks is likely too high a number for one single course of fighting, and could stem from several violent encounters, or one extensive battle. The blade-to-body-length ratio indicates that the male was a strong individual, capable of handling such a long and heavy sword one-handed.

Figure 6.23 – Seven thick rivets *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 73.

Figure 6.24 – Side view of the hilt of Sword ID 73.

Sword ID 75 - TB 442 (Figure 6.25)

Figure 6.25 – Sword ID 75 obverse.

21	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Elongated Graze
Left	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	n/a
Right	3	n/a	3	n/a	n/a	n/a	4	1
Visibility	1							

Tomb 442 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit containing the incomplete, extended skeletal remains of a young adult male, 160.2 cm tall. Only the head, long bones of arms and legs, some hand and finger bones, and two vertebrae have been found in the pit. A sword of type Boiu IIb/Teòr was placed on top of the torso, with the hilt positioned on top of the right shoulder and the tip extending over the (missing) pelvis (Salzani 2005, 77). The male displays an injury on the endocranial side of the frontal bone, which was most likely the result of a tuberculosis infection (Pulcini 2014, 98).

The sword is a complete, slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword, completely covered in green and brown patina. Some sections are covered in pock mark corrosion. The hilt tongue retains three massive rivets *in situ*. There are four rivet holes in each semi-circular shoulder. Four rivets remain *in situ* in the right, two in the left shoulder (Figure 6.26). Short, curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is present. Elaborate hallmark decorations can be found on both sides on the hilt plate and along the upper quarter of the midrib. The left cutting edge is heavily corroded.

A total of 21 marks could be identified, ten on the left and eleven on the right cutting edge. On the left there, is a clustering of four marks near the tip, whilst the remaining six are located on the upper part of the blade. The marks on the right cutting edge are evenly distributed. Whilst the blade shows a collection of eight different kinds of marks, with none outstandingly frequent, it must be noted that the marks themselves are very small indeed.

The elaborateness of the sword could indicate a special meaning and function of the weapon. Whilst the clustering on the left cutting edge indicates that the blade was skilfully used for a certain purpose, there is no explanation for the spread on the right cutting edge. The small size of the marks could indicate that potentially only a small amount of force has been used to create them, indicating a very deliberate and considerate use of the weapon.

Figure 6.26 – Hilt with rivets and decorations of Sword ID 75.

Sword ID 85 - TB 31 (Figure 6.27)

Figure 6.27 – Sword ID 85 obverse.

26	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	9	n/a	n/a	1	1
Right	12	1	1	1	n/a
Visibility	1				

Tomb 31 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit with rounded corners containing the incomplete skeletal remains of a mature adult male, 162.3 cm tall, buried extended on his back in West-East alignment. A total of 22 shell studs were found in two semi-circular rings towards the top right of his head. These could have formed part of a headdress or a piece of clothing. A single copper-alloy arrowhead was positioned underneath his left forearm. A sword of type Boiu Ib was deposited on top of the male's torso, the hilt was placed in a central right position over his sternum, the tip protruded well over his left hip and upper thigh (Salzani 2005, 124-5). There is no conclusive osteological analysis, but it is likely that the arrowhead was embedded in the flesh of the forearm, instead of deliberately deposited as a grave good. If embedded, this was most likely a perimortal injury, as otherwise the male would have extracted the arrowhead from his arm. Similar arrowheads, in combination with associated lesions, have been found in Tomb 463 (Pulcini 2014, 137-8).

This complete, slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword measures a total length of 687 mm, and is completely covered in smooth, dark green and brown patina. The hilt consists of a short, wide tongue with two rivet holes next to each other; one rivet remains *in situ*. A further ten rivet holes are in the hilt plate, with three rivets *in situ*. Elaborate hallmark decorations can be found on the hilt plate and along the midrib (Figure 6.28). The shoulders are very round, creating an almost circular hilt plate. Curved ricassi turn into bevel lines.

A total of 26 marks could be identified, eleven on the left and 15 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are indentations. They frequently occur in clusters of two or three marks within immediate proximity to each other, such as Left 181-186 (3 marks), Left 250-253 (3 marks, Figure 6.29), Right 548-567 (4 marks), Right 491-495 (3 marks). There are no marks near the tip on the left cutting edge. The marks on the right cutting edge are evenly distributed.

Whilst this sword displays an unusually high amount of indentations, which are usually associated with impacts on dull or rounded weapons such as spear shafts (see Chapter 3.5), the marks on this sword are too small to be the result of such weapons. More research is

needed to find an explanation for such small indentations, especially in such high frequency and clustering.

Figure 6.28 – Remaining hilt with rivets and elaborate decorations extending along the midrib of Sword ID 85.

Figure 6.29 – Cluster of three marks (Mark IDs 2084-6), left cutting edge, 250-3 mm from the tip of Sword ID 85.

Sword ID 98 - TB 475

28	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	11	1	1	1	1	2	1
Right	6	n/a	2	n/a	1	1	n/a
Visibility	1						

Tomb 475 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit with rounded corners, containing the almost complete extended inhumation of an adult male, approximately 30-35 years old, buried on his back. The male was outstandingly tall for his time, standing 174.5 cm tall. Eleven round shell studs were found on his left arm and chest, which were likely ornamental accessories on a piece of organic material. A round ceramic jar with handle was placed on its side immediately to the left of the head, touching the skull. Whilst the head was resting on his chest, forcing the body to “look” towards his feet, the opening of the jug is pointing in the same direction. A sword of type Sauerbrunn was positioned on top of the male’s torso, with its hilt resting on the left collar bone and the tip positioned centrally over the groin (Salzani 2005, 92-3). Osteological analysis has identified two distinct cut lesions. The first is a deep incision into the left diaphysis of the left femur, likely the result of a strike to the knee executed with considerable force. Depth and angle of the cut suggest that the male might have been on horseback at the time. The second lesion is to the left ulna. It has been suggested that the injury was inflicted while the male was lying on the ground and had raised his arm for protection (Pulcini 2014, 134-5).

This slightly leaf-shaped, complete copper-alloy sword measures a total length of 628 mm, and is completely covered in smooth and rough green, brown, white, and grey patina. The hilt

consists of a semi-circular plate without tongue. Three rivets remain *in situ* in each shoulder (Figure 6.30). Curved ricassi merge into discontinuous bevel lines. Uneven decorations can be found on the hilt plate (Figure 6.31) and along the midrib in the upper part of the sword. The blade is slightly bent.

A total of 28 wear marks could be identified, 18 on the left and ten on the right cutting edge, indicating a clear edge dominance. By far the most prominent marks are indentations, of which eleven are located on the left cutting edge. The remaining marks consist of different grazes and notches. On the left edge, the marks are distributed along the entire length of the blade. Only the indentations appear to occur in a clustered pattern. On the right edge, no marks were identified anywhere near the tip. There is, however, a pattern of six indentations between 196-363 mm from the tip.

The large amount of marks indicates use in battle, possibly on more than one occasion. A combination of indentations, grazes, and notches suggests a variety of opposing weapons (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 6.30 – Rivets *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 98.

Figure 6.31 – Decorations on the hilt plate of Sword ID 98.

Sword ID 88 - TB 115 (Figure 6.32)

Figure 6.32 – Sword ID 88 obverse.

34	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	5	n/a	2	3	2	1	2	1	1
Right	5	1		1	2	1	2	3	2
Visibility	1								

Tomb 115 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is a nearly perfectly rectangular pit containing the extended inhumation of an adult male lying on his back, 163.1 cm tall. A sword of type

Castiglione di Marano was positioned in alignment on the torso. The hilt was placed centrally on the abdomen, with the blade and tip protruding over the male's hips and phallus (Salzani 2005, 166). Osteological analysis has revealed that the male suffered from severe arthritis in the right coxofemoral joint, which was likely the direct result of a previous traumatic event. The arthritis would have caused severe pain and limited the male's mobility (Pulcini 2014, 128).

This complete copper-alloy sword is slightly leaf-shaped, and covered in smooth brown and green patina and corrosion. The hilt consists of a short grip tang and an unusually formed trapezoidal hilt plate. Each straight shoulder preserves two rivets *in situ* (Figure 6.33). Curved ricassi and a rounded midrib complete the blade, while bevel lines are not present. Total length is 532 mm.

The total of 34 wear marks is split evenly between the two cutting edges, with 17 marks on either side. The most common marks are indentations, five on either side. There are also eleven grazes of various kinds. Although marks appear on the entirety of the blade, on the left edge there is a clear pattern of marks clustering between 323-82 mm. On the right cutting edge, there are also two areas of clustering, between 123-85 mm and 313-449 mm. The amount of marks could indicate possibly three or four fighting scenarios.

Figure 6.33 – Hilt tang and four rivets *in situ* on Sword ID 88.

Sword ID 76 - TB 54 (Figure 6.34)

Figure 6.34 – Sword ID 76 obverse.

47	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved graze	Irregular graze
Left	6	2	3	1	n/a	1	1	1
Right	11	1	6	1	1	2	5	5
Visibility	1							

Tomb 54 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is an oval pit containing the almost complete inhumation of a mature adult buried extended on his back, 163.8 cm tall. The pit is aligned SW – NE, with the male’s feet buried in the SW. One rivet and two capped studs were found on his right shoulder, which could be the remainder of organic material such as clothing. A sword of type Boiu Ib was positioned on his right arm, with the hilt placed on top of his shoulder and the tip just over his forearm (Salzani 2005, 137-8). The skull displays the signs of several injuries, including a deep, elliptical indentation on the left frontal bone, and three smaller dents on the back of the skull, two of which penetrate the bone. Such dents could be the result of a deliberate drilling operation into the bone. The formation of bone suggests that the male lived for at least one year after the intervention (Cupitò et al. 2015, 335; Canci et al. 2015, 773; Pulcini 2014, 138; Canci et al. 2009, 9).

The slightly leaf-shaped, almost complete copper-alloy sword has a fractured hilt tongue. At a total length of 550 mm, it has a weight of 334.3 g. The broad tongue has two remaining rivet holes next to each other, with one rivet *in situ*. Four rivets also remain *in situ* in the semi-circular hilt plate. Very round shoulders and short, curved ricassi complete the hilt. Bevel lines and a slight midrib are present. Very elaborate hallmark decorations start on the hilt plate (Figure 6.35) and run along the midrib for one third of the blade length (Figure 6.36).

A total of 47 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 15 on the left and 32 on the right cutting edge, indicating clear edge dominance. There is a diverse mix of marks along the entire length of the blade on both sides. A slight clustering of indentations could be observed on the right cutting edge near the top and near the tip. The most common marks are indentations, which make up one third of all marks on this sword, and round notches.

It appears as if the right cutting edge was the preferred forward, attacking edge. The large amount of marks indicates use on more than one occasion. To create the edge dominance, the sword would have had to deliberately been held in the same manner every time.

Figure 6.35 – Decorations on the hilt plate of Sword ID 76.

Figure 6.36 – Rivets and decorations on Sword ID 76.

Sword ID 79 - TB 153 (Figure 6.37)

Figure 6.37 – Sword ID 79 obverse.

55	Indentation	Round Notch	Wide Angled Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	5	1	1	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	6
Right	18	6	5	1	4	2	1	5
Visibility	1							

Tomb 153 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is an elongated trapezoidal pit with rounded corners, aligned W-E, and contained the almost complete inhumation of a mature adult male buried extended lying on his back, 167.1 cm tall. His grave goods consisted of a fractured pottery jug placed to the top left of his head, three round studs placed next to the head, a flint arrowhead that was discovered within his torso, a dagger of type Capurso placed centrally on his sternum, and a sword of type Boiu IIb/Teòr which was placed centrally on his torso, slightly left of his spine, with the hilt protruding over the left collar bone and the tip positioned over his groin (Salzani 2005, 182).

The complete, slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword measures a total length of 737 mm and is completely covered in green and brown patina. Small amounts of pock mark corrosion have formed on the sword. The long, broad, complete hilt tongue is rectangular in shape and displays two rivet holes, with one rivet remaining *in situ*. In the semi-circular hilt plate eight rivets remain *in situ*, four in each shoulder. Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is also present. Elaborate decorations have been hallmarked into the hilt plate (Figure 6.38) and along the midrib for c. one quarter of the length of the blade (Figure 6.39).

A large amount of wear marks could be identified, displaying clear edge dominance with 13 on the left and 42 on the right cutting edge. The most prominent marks are indentations, with 18 located on the right and seven on the left cutting edge. There are also 18 grazes of various kinds. The marks are evenly spread along the entire lengths of both cutting edges.

Displaying such clear edge dominance indicates that the blade was used very deliberately on numerous occasions, and was generally held in the same way (see Chapter 4.4). It is possible that the organic material of the hilt was shaped to accommodate for holding the sword correctly. The flint arrowhead discovered amongst the ribs could indicate that the male died as a result of being shot, or else was shot during an encounter at a previous stage of his life. Whichever it is, it is clear that this male was involved in violent combat encounters and used his sword frequently.

Figure 6.38 – Decorations on the hilt plate of Sword ID 79.

Figure 6.39 – Hilt with rivets and decorations on Sword ID 79.

Sword ID 95 - TB 33

62	Inden- tation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide- Angled Notch	Double Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	6	1	n/a	2	3	2	2	n/a	1	1
Right	24	n/a	2	4	2	n/a	4	6	1	1
Visibility	1									

Tomb 33 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is an oval pit containing the almost complete inhumation of an adult male of not further specified age, buried extended on his back, 168.3 cm tall. Along with eight studs and a dagger of type Pieve S. Giacomo, his grave contained a sword of type Boiu IIa/Castions di Strada which was placed on top of his left arm, with the hilt placed on top of his left shoulder and the tip protruding well over his left hip towards the middle of his left femur (Salzani 2005, 125-6). Osteological examination of the skeleton has revealed an incision just above the acetabular cavity on the left hip. The incision

is 30 mm long and 1 mm wide, and was most likely caused by a sharp metal implement, such as a sword or knife blade (Canci et al. 2009, 10).

The complete, slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword has a fractured tongue, and is completely covered in smooth brown, black, and green patina. It measures a total length of 819 mm. The remaining hilt tongue has one rivet *in situ*. A further eight rivets, four in each shoulder (Figure 6.40), remain *in situ* in the semi-circular hilt plate. Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is present. There are elaborate hallmark decorations on the hilt plate (Figure 6.41) and along the upper section of the midrib.

Displaying a clear edge dominance, a total of 62 marks could be identified, 18 on the left and 44 on the right cutting edge. Although the marks are spread along the entire lengths of the cutting edges, they seem to cluster in the upper half of the blade on both sides. Thirty indentations make up almost half of the marks, with 24 located on the right cutting edge. Three clusters of around five indentations each were identified on the right cutting edge, as well as some smaller clusters with only two or three, and some individual indentations. Despite the large number and distinct shape, the indentations are very small in size, only measuring around 1-2 mm in length. Whilst some of the indentations could in fact be rebound marks, the size makes it almost impossible to differentiate between initial and secondary impacts. There are also 16 grazes of various kinds, and numerous notches.

The large number of marks indicates use in multiple combat situations. Both definite edge dominance and the clustering of marks imply that the user was a skilled swordsman, who used the sword with deliberate consideration and precision. The small size of the marks could be due to material properties of the copper-alloy, or else the result of the deliberate fighting style with low force impacts to preserve the blade.

Figure 6.40 – Rivets *in situ* and decorations in the right shoulder of Sword ID 95.

Figure 6.41 – Decorations on the hilt plate of Sword ID 95.

Sword ID 86 - TB 472 (Figure 6.42)

Figure 6.42 – Sword ID 86 obverse.

96	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Flattening
Left	12	2	4	n/a	n/a	n/a	2	n/a
Right	48	4	4	5	2	3	8	2
Visibility	1							

Tomb 472 in Area B at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit with round corners containing the complete human remains of a mature adult male, estimated at least 50 years of age, who was buried extended lying on his back. The male was 168.2 cm tall. A sword of type Nogara was placed between his legs, with the hilt positioned on top of his groin and the tip terminating between his knees (Salzani 2005, 91).

The complete, straight copper-alloy sword measures a total length of 706 mm. A cylindrical tang is attached to a triangular hilt plate with six rivet holes, three in each shoulder (Figure 6.43). Three rivets remain *in situ* in the right, one in the left shoulder. The whole sword is covered in dark and light green, and brown patina, and occasional areas of pock mark corrosion.

The total of 96 wear marks identified on this sword display clear edge dominance with 20 on the left and 76 on the right cutting edge. By far the most common marks are indentations, twelve on the left and 48 on the right. The indentations are generally very small in size, yet precise in shape, and are unlikely to be as the result of an impact on a spear shaft or similar. On the right cutting edge the marks are evenly distributed along the entire length of the blade, whereas on the left there are no marks within 144 mm of the tip.

The large amount of marks and clear edge dominance indicate skilled and frequent combat use. As the indentations are too small to stem from impacts with rounded sections of other weapons, such as spear shafts, is it possible that they are the result of impacts on bone as suggested by O’Flaherty et al. (2011, 12).

Figure 6.43 – Hilt tang and three rivets *in situ* on Sword ID 86.

6.5.2 Recent Bronze Age, c. 1350-900 cal BC

Sword ID 107 – 48137 (Figure 6.44)

Figure 6.44 – Sword ID 107 obverse.

1	Striation
Reverse Shoulder	1
Visibility	1

This long and fairly straight-edged copper-alloy sword of type Allerona was recovered from a cremation burial at San Benedetto in Perillis, Colle Brignile, Province of L’Aquila, and is associated with a cremation urn of unknown typology (Bianco Peroni 1970, 66). The sword is complete with one fractured shoulder, and a fractured and bent tip (Figure 6.45). There are four rivet holes in the hilt tongue. Three rivet holes were drilled into each curved, elongated shoulder (Figure 6.46). The holes look extremely crude and poorly manufactured. A bending of the hilt can also be observed. Unusually, the ricassi are not regular, but curved on one side and straight on the other. The left shoulder is also longer than the right. Bevel lines and a rounded swelling instead of a midrib are present. The whole sword is covered in dark brown, grey, and black patina. It measures at a total length of 644 mm.

No combat marks could be identified on the blade of this sword. There is, however, one deep striation on the reverse shoulder (Figure 6.47).

This sword is peculiar, in that it was badly manufactured. It could possibly be the early work of an apprentice, and it is unsurprising that the sword was not used in combat.

Figure 6.45 – Bent tip on Sword ID 107.

Figure 6.46 – Hilt with ten rivet holes on Sword ID 107.

Figure 6.47 – Mark ID 2650, striations, reverse shoulder, 533-42 mm from the tip of Sword ID 107.

Sword ID 109 – 32927 (Figure 6.48)

Figure 6.48 – Sword ID 109 obverse.

1	Striation
Left Reverse	1
Visibility	1

This straight copper-alloy sword of type Allerona was recovered from an inhumation burial in Fucino, Province of L’Aquila, in 1886 (Bianco Peroni 1970, 68). It is complete with a fractured terminus. The hilt is flanged and has three rivet holes and a tear in the tongue. Each narrow, slightly curved shoulder has two rivet holes. There are no real ricassi, but wide bevel lines and a swollen, rounded midrib. The entire sword is covered in fairly smooth green patina. No macroscopic wear marks could be detected apart from one striation on the left reverse (Figure 6.49). Total length is 647 mm.

The striation is unlike any other created during combat. Instead, it appears to be the result of a deliberate strike, possibly with an axe or a chisel. Similar treatment was given to swords at Pila del Brancon as part of their ritual destruction prior to deposition (Sestieri et al. 2013, 159).

Figure 6.49 – Mark ID 2669, striation, reverse left cutting edge, 82-90 mm from the tip of Sword ID 109.

Sword ID 111 – 79477 (Figure 6.50)

Figure 6.50 – Sword ID 111 obverse.

4	Indentation
Left	2
Right	2
Visibility	1

This complete copper-alloy sword of type Monza was recovered from the bottom of the right bank of the river Adda at Cassano d’Adda, in the Province of Milan (Bianco Peroni 1970, 30). It is covered in glossy, dark green and brown patina. A small amount of pit corrosion is present. The hilt consists of a grip tongue. There are no shoulders, ricassi or bevel lines, only a slight swelling towards a midrib. At a total length of 529 mm, the sword has a distinct bend to the blade.

Only four marks could be identified, two on each cutting edge. All marks are indentations. The two indentations on the left are located in close proximity to each other near the tip. On the left, one indentation is also located near the tip, the other towards the middle of the blade. The indentations could be the result of impacts against a small round object. Considering the small amount of only four marks, however, it appears that the marks were either created during a very short fight, or not at all in a combat situation.

Sword ID 83 - TB 48 (Figure 6.51)

Figure 6.51 – Sword ID 83 obverse.

4	Indentation	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	1	1	n/a
Right	n/a	n/a	2
Visibility	3		

Tomb 48 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit containing the almost complete inhumation of a mature adult male, buried extended lying on his back, 161.3 cm tall. A sword of type Boiu Ia/Wildon was placed on top of his torso, with the hilt positioned centrally above his sternum and the blade at a slight angle running over his right hip with the tip on top of his right femur (Salzani 2005, 134).

The slightly leaf-shaped, complete copper-alloy sword is covered in green and brown patina. There is some surface corrosion, and heavy corrosion of the cutting edges. The hilt plate displays eight rivet holes, with seven rivets remaining *in situ*. Curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is present. Some basic hallmarking decoration has been added onto the hilt plate and upper midrib (Figure 6.52). Total length is 651 mm.

Due to the heavy corrosion only four marks could be identified, two on each cutting edge. One graze in close proximity to the tip on the right cutting edge could be the result of a thrust. The other marks are located in the middle of the cutting edge.

The heavily corroded cutting edges make further analysis or interpretation impossible.

Figure 6.52 – Hilt plate with rivets and decorations on Sword ID 83.

Sword ID 72 - TB 483 (Figure 6.53)

Figure 6.53 – Sword ID 72 obverse.

5	Indentation	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze
Left	1	n/a	1
Right	n/a	1	2
Visibility	3		

Tomb 483 in Area B contained the extended inhumation of a 45-50-year-old male lying on his back, 165.1 cm tall. The male was buried with a sword deposited centrally on his torso, with the hilt just below his chin and the tip ending below the pelvis (Salzani 2005, 97-8).

This complete copper-alloy sword from Tomba 483 is of type Treviso, and completely covered in patchy brown and green patina. The straight cutting edges taper towards a pointy tip. Pock mark corrosion has grown on the sword, especially on the lower part of the blade. The cast hilt has straight shoulders, which turn into curved ricassi. Bevel lines and a prominent midrib are present. One thick rivet remains *in situ* in the tongue, two rivets are *in situ* in each shoulder (Figure 6.54). The cutting edges are fairly corroded, so only the visible marks could be recorded. Total length of the sword is 613 mm.

Due to the corrosion, only five marks could be identified, two on the left and three on the right cutting edge. The two marks on the left are within 4 mm of each other. No clear handedness could be identified. Although it is possible that the sword was used in one single combat situation, the heavy corrosion prevents any further interpretation.

Figure 6.54 – Hilt with five rivets *in situ* and prominent midrib on Sword ID 72.

Sword ID 102 – 28634 (Figure 6.55)

Figure 6.55 – Sword ID 102 obverse.

6 (5 + midrib marks)	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	n/a	1	1	1
Right	1	n/a	1	n/a
Visibility	2			

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Montegiorgio was discovered at Montegiorgio, Province of Ascoli Piceno, under unknown circumstances during the 19th Century. It is fairly short at a total length of 526 mm. The sword has a cast, oval-shaped handle with flanges and fish tail at the terminus. There is one rivet hole in the handle, and two in each curved shoulder. The rivet holes are poorly made and only roughly circular in shape. Curved ricassi are present, but there is no clear differentiation between the end of the ricassi and the beginning of the cutting edges. There are no bevel lines except for a decorative line. A slight midrib is present. On the obverse, the sword is mostly covered in fairly smooth green patina, with small green and brown areas. The patina on the reverse is rough and patchy, especially in the upper half. Total length is 526 mm. Due to the general corrosion, only a few prominent marks could be recorded.

A total of six marks, five on the cutting edges and one on the midrib, could be identified, three on the left and two on the right cutting edge. There is one big striation mark across the midrib (Figure 6.56). On the cutting edges, rebound marks were identified in immediate proximity to the irregular graze. All but one mark are located in the middle of the blade. It

must be noted that these marks are very prominent. Due to the corrosion, any possible smaller marks could not be identified.

The prominent marks indicate combat usage. However, the extent of this remains unknown as the corrosion prevented full analysis.

Figure 6.56 – Mark ID 2587, striation, reverse midrib, 225 mm from the tip of Sword ID 102.

Sword ID 94 - VR 40291 (Figure 6.57)

Figure 6.57 – Sword ID 94.

7	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	1	n/a	4
Right	1	1	n/a
Visibility	1		

This short copper-alloy sword from Pila del Brancon of type Cetona has a straight blade, pointy tip, and is unusually light (Sestieri et al. 2013, 162). The blade was heavily bent into a semi-circle, then re-bent the other way to create a slight s-shape. The tongue fractured at the second rivet hole from the grip plate (Figure 6.58). One rivet hole remains in the tongue, three in each slightly curved shoulder. The curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A midrib is not present. The blade is covered in smooth, green, brown, black, and grey patina. Some pit corrosion is present. Total length is 463 mm.

Seven marks could be identified, five on the left and two on the right cutting edge. No apparent clusters could be detected, but the majority of the marks are located somewhere in the middle of the cutting edges. It appears as if some binding and some high velocity impacts occurred. The most common marks are four bulges.

The bulges and grazes indicate high velocity impacts and binding, all marks that are expected from actual combat (see Chapter 4.4). This sword can be interpreted as having been used in at least one fight. Bulging is distinctive for binding, which suggests the fighter was skilled and trained in sword combat.

Figure 6.58 – Distorted and fractured hilt on Sword ID 94.

Sword ID 90 - VR 26487 (Figure 6.59)

Figure 6.59 – Sword ID 90.

8	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	2	1	n/a	n/a
Right	3	n/a	1	1
Visibility	1			

This complete copper-alloy sword of type Allerona was found as part of the Pila del Brancon hoard, and has a straight blade which tapers towards a pointy tip (Sestieri et al. 2013, 162). It is very heavily bent into a semi-circle. The blade is covered in smooth, brown and black, patchy patina. Some pit corrosion is present. There are three rivet holes in the tongue and two in each slightly curved shoulder. One rivet remains *in situ* (Figure 6.60). The curved ricassi merge into bevel lines; a midrib is present. Total length is 692 mm. The tip is heavily bent (Figure 6.61).

Eight marks were identified on this blade in total, three on the left and five on the right. On the right cutting edge, one mark is located close to the tip, the other four are clustered between 309-70 mm. These four marks are all joined directly, either like a series of marks created during one heavy impact, or the result of a repeated action using this particular section of the cutting edge. On the left, two marks are located in close proximity to each other near the tip, the third mark is in the upper quarter at 528 mm. The most common marks are indentations.

It appears that this sword could have been used in combat; the number of marks may suggest one combat encounter. The cluster of four marks appears to be the result of a repeated impact with the same section of the cutting edge

Figure 6.60 – Hilt with one rivet *in situ* on Sword ID 90.

Figure 6.61 – Bent tip on Sword ID 90.

Sword ID 110 – 23211 (Figure 6.62)

Figure 6.62 – Sword ID 110 obverse,

9	Indentation	Round Notch	Bulge
Left	5	1	1
Right	2	n/a	n/a
Visibility	1		

This complete copper-alloy sword of type Cetona was discovered in Fucino, Province of L’Aquila, under unknown circumstances (Bianco Peroni 1970, 62). It has straight edges and a flanged hilt. There are no rivet holes in the tongue, but three in each shoulder. One rivet remains *in situ* (Figure 6.63). Slightly curved, narrow shoulders turn into short, round ricassi. There is only a faint trace of bevel lines, the midrib is only a slight swelling. The sword is completely covered in fairly smooth green and brown patina. Total length is 616 mm.

A total of nine, extremely tiny, marks were identified, seven on the left, two on the right cutting edge, indicating a clear edge dominance. The most common marks are indentations. The bulge could be the result of a binding contact. Six of the marks are clustered towards the tip. Although the indentations have the typical shape of marks caused by spear contacts, they are far too small to be the result of such. A different explanation is yet outstanding.

The sword bears the marks of combat, clear edge dominance, a bulge caused by binding, and indentations. However, these marks are so tiny that it appears unlikely that they were actually caused during a fight. Instead, extremely slow or low force impacts must have taken place.

Figure 6.63 – One rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 110.

Sword ID 93 - VR 40289 (Figure 6.64)

Figure 6.64 – Sword ID 93.

13	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Double Notch	Curved Graze	Bulge
Left	n/a	n/a	n/a	2	n/a	1	4
Right	1	1	1	n/a	1	1	1
Visibility	1						

This straight bladed copper-alloy sword of type Cetona from Pila del Brancon is complete with a fractured tongue, and measures a total length of 587 mm (Sestieri et al. 2013, 162). The blade has been heavily bent twice: once in the middle of the blade, then again further towards the tip. The tongue has fractured off at the rivet hole closest to the hilt plate. Two rivet holes are located in each slightly curved shoulder. Slightly curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. A rounded midrib is also present.

A total of 13 marks could be identified, seven on the left and six on the right cutting edge. There is some distribution of the marks along the cutting edges, but all marks are located in the lower half of the blade, from the tip up to 258 mm. The most common marks are bulges, of which four are located on the left cutting edge. The other marks are different kinds of indentations, notches, and grazes.

It is interesting to note that all marks on this sword are located in the lower half of the blade. Although there is no clear edge dominance detectable, the bulges on the left could indicate that this side was mostly used for binding and twisting, and was therefore possibly the forward-facing cutting edge (see Chapter 4.4).

Sword ID 106 – 85586 (Figure 6.65)

Figure 6.65 – Sword ID 106 obverse.

13	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	1	1	n/a	1	4	1
Right	n/a	n/a	1	1	3	n/a
Visibility	1					

This complete copper-alloy sword of type *Dreiwulstschwert mit Scheibenknauf* was discovered as an isolated stray find during construction works in Fumarogo, Commune Valdisotto, Province of Sondrio (Bianco Peroni 1970, 102). It has a complete cast hilt and is in very good condition. At a length of 650 mm, the sword is completely covered in smooth green and brown patina. The hilt consists of a disc-shaped terminus, round shoulders with a skeumorphic rivet in each, and rounded ricassi. Elaborate hallmarking decorations can be found on the grip and terminus (Figure 6.66). There are two fractures in the shoulders (Figure 6.67 & Figure 6.68). The blade is leaf-shaped with wide bevel lines and a midrib, creating a lozenge-shaped cross section.

A total of 13 marks could be identified, five on the right and eight on the left cutting edge. A further eleven rebound marks could also be identified. Rebound marks are not counted towards the number of combat marks as they are caused by a secondary impact after bouncing off the blade, and they do not provide information about the shape or size of the initial impact. On the right cutting edge, there is a long graze at 85-99 mm, surrounded by rebound marks. The other marks on this side are clustered between 171-95 mm. On the left cutting edge, the marks tend to be located in the upper part of the blade, also in some cases surrounded by some rebound marks.

This sword bears the definitive signs of combat, with high velocity impacts creating a high

Figure 6.66 – Cast hilt with decorations on Sword ID 106.

number of grazes and rebound marks (see Chapter 3.5). The clustering on the right cutting edge indicates the skilled use of the weapon, using the same part of the blade to strike the opponent.

Figure 6.67 – Fracture in the left shoulder of Sword ID 106.

Figure 6.68 – Fracture in the right shoulder of Sword ID 106.

Sword ID 108 – 23210 (Figure 6.69)

Figure 6.69 – Sword ID 108 obverse.

14	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Double Notch	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	2	1	3	1	1	3
Right	1	n/a	1	n/a	n/a	1
Visibility	1					

This straight-edged complete copper-alloy sword of type Allerona was discovered in Fucino, Province of L’Aquila, under unknown circumstances during the 19th century (Bianco Peroni 1970, 68). It has a flanged hilt tongue and a small terminal tang. There are two rivet holes in the tongue (Figure 6.70) and two in each shoulder. The narrow shoulders are slightly rounded, the ricassi are very short and only slightly curved. Thick, prominent bevel lines and a rounded midrib swelling are present. At a total length of 626 mm, the sword is covered in slightly rough golden, bronze, brown, grey, and black patina. Numerous pit corrosion holes are present.

A total of 14 extremely small marks could be identified, eleven on the left and three on the right cutting edge. The marks mostly consist of different types of notches and grazes. Despite the clear left-edge dominance, no marks have been found near the tip on this side. Instead, the marks are clustered towards the midsection of the cutting edge. On the right, there is one mark near the tip, the other two marks are located closer towards the middle.

The clear edge dominance indicates a preferred way of holding the sword. Whilst the marks are identical in shape and form to those created during combat, these marks are all tiny, measuring around 1 mm. The cause of this has yet to be investigated.

Figure 6.70 – Drilled rivet hole in the tongue of Sword ID 108.

Sword ID 81 - TB 28 (Figure 6.71)

Figure 6.71 – Sword ID 81 obverse.

20	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze	Elongated Graze
Left	1	n/a	1	1	3	2	n/a
Right	2	2	2	1	2	1	2
Visibility	1						

Tomb 28 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit containing the articulated extended inhumation of a very mature male buried lying on his back, feet in the West and head positioned in the East. A sword of type Bigarello was positioned on top of the deceased's right arm, the hilt above the shoulder and the tip positioned over the hand. The male's height was estimated as 168.8 cm (Salzani 2005, 122).

The complete copper-alloy sword is covered in green and brown patina with occasional sections of pock mark corrosion. Six rivets remain *in situ* in the angular grip plate (Figure 6.72 & Figure 6.73). Curved ricassi merge into faint bevel lines. A slight midrib is also present. Total length of the sword is 575 mm.

A total of 20 marks could be identified, eight on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge, indicating a slight edge dominance. The marks on the right cutting edge are clustered in the

upper quarter of the blade, close to the hilt. On the left cutting edge, the marks are clustered in the mid-section of the blade. The most common marks are grazes of various kinds.

Both the high number of grazes and the precise clustering of the marks suggest high-velocity clashing contacts of a skilled swordsman (see Chapter 3.5). The fairly large number of marks could also indicate that the sword was used successfully over a prolonged period of time and in many violent encounters, correlating with the old age of the deceased.

Figure 6.72 – Six rivets *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 81.

Figure 6.73 – Rivet *in situ* in the right shoulder of Sword ID 81.

Sword ID 91 - VR 26488 (Figure 6.74)

Figure 6.74 – Sword ID 91 side view.

20	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Bulge	Compression Curling
Left	3	n/a	1	1	4	1
Right	n/a	1	n/a	n/a	7	2
Visibility	1					

This complete, straight bladed copper-alloy sword from Pila del Brancon is in good condition, and completely covered in smooth bronze, black, and brown patina. The hilt consists of a cylindrical grip tang and hilt plate, with one rivet hole in each slightly curved, slim shoulder. There are no real ricassi present. Bevel lines and midrib run the length of the blade. The sword is heavily bent in the middle of the blade, and at the grip plate. Total length is 546 mm. A total of 20 wear marks could be identified, evenly split with ten on each cutting edge. The most common marks are bulges (Figure 6.75). On the left the marks are fairly evenly distributed along the cutting edge. The marks on the right are mostly clustered within 100 mm of each other between, 200-300 mm. Three cases of compression curling have also been identified. The large amount of bulges and the presence of compression curling indicate heavy binding and twisting motions, whilst the accompanying notches and grazes are likely the result of clashing impacts. All marks are distinctively deep and pronounced.

Whilst bulges are not uncommon, such a large amount is highly unusual and might indicate perhaps a unique fighting style of the individual. This could explain the lack of ricassi, as the additional hilt protection would not be needed if the sword blade was used to control the opponent's weapon (see Chapter 4.4). The depth of the marks suggests that there was enough friction to properly bind and control other blades.

Figure 6.75 – Mark ID 2293, bulge, right cutting edge, 256 mm from the tip of Sword ID 91.

Sword ID 92 - VR 40288 (Figure 6.76)

Figure 6.76 – Sword ID 92.

24	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Rectangular Graze	Bulge	Compression Curling
Left	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	n/a
Right	1	1	3	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	7	1
Visibility	1								

This complete, straight bladed copper-alloy sword from Pila del Brancon has been heavily bent repeatedly: once in the tongue, twice in the middle of the blade, and the tip was bent several times. Overall, the sword is fairly corroded, but in good enough condition to be examined. Green and brown patina covers the entire blade. There are three rivet holes in the tongue. A further three rivet holes can be found in each straight shoulder. Curved ricassi connect the hilt and the cutting edge. Bevel lines are not present. The midrib is rounded. Total length is approximately 643 mm.

A total of 24 wear marks could be identified, eleven on the left and 13 on the right cutting edge. On the left all marks are clustered in the two middle quarters of the blade, and consist of two bulges (Figure 6.77) and a multitude of notches and grazes. On the right cutting edge,

Figure 6.77 – Mark ID 2324, bulge, right cutting edge, 45-55 mm from the tip of Sword ID 92.

however, seven bulges, some compression curling, and four notches could be identified. A few marks are located near the tip, but the majority of marks are also located towards the middle of the blade. It seems that the edge was predominantly used for binding and twisting motions, which could indicate that this side was generally forward facing (see Chapter 4.4).

Sword ID 103 – 20997 (Figure 6.78)

Figure 6.78 – Sword ID 103 obverse.

21	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	1	1	n/a	1	1	2	3
Right	3	n/a	3	n/a	1	3	2
Visibility	1						

This slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Bigarello was recovered from Gambaloni Tomba 3 at Povegliano Veronese, Province of Verona, and is completely covered in corroded brown patina (Bianco Peroni 1970, 18). The hilt has fractured off at the rivet hole closest to the blade. There are three round rivet holes in each of the straight shoulders. The right shoulder has fractured at the last rivet hole. One rivet remains *in situ* (Figure 6.79). Curved ricassi and a slight midrib are present. Whilst the cutting edges are fairly corroded, the marks were prominent enough to be recorded. Total length is 541 mm.

A total of 21 wear marks could be identified, nine on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge. There is only one mark located near the tip, the other twenty being all at least 110 mm further up the blade, and otherwise evenly distributed. There is nothing particularly outstanding about the marks, and no type of mark is more common than another.

The sword displays the signs of combat use, probably in more than one case. However, no patterns could be identified, and no further interpretations can be made.

Figure 6.79 – Rivet in the hilt of Sword ID 103.

Sword ID 99 – 123571 (Figure 6.80)

Figure 6.80 – Sword ID 99 obverse.

26	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	2	2	n/a	1	2	3
Right	9	n/a	1	n/a	2	4
Visibility	1					

This leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Terontola measures a total length of 431 mm, and is completely covered in smooth brown patina. It was recovered from the Corte Lazise find context (Salzani 2006, 31). The hilt consists of just a tang, with no plate, shoulders or ricassi to speak of. Evidence of rivet holes is lacking, suggesting that an organic handle would have just been forced onto the cylindrical tang. Faint bevel lines and a midrib are present.

A total of 26 wear marks could be identified, ten on the left and 16 on the right cutting edge, possibly indicating right edge dominance. The most common marks are indentations, of which nine are located on the right cutting edge. In total there are also eleven grazes. Interestingly, the majority of the marks on the left cutting edge are located close to the tip, whereas on the right there are no marks near the tip at all. It must be said that all marks are very small in size, and although there is some spread, no marks are located further than 257 mm away from the tip.

The right edge dominance indicates that this side was primarily forward facing. The marks on the right edge, however, indicate that backhanded strikes were part of the individual's fighting style (see Chapter 4.4).

Sword ID 100 – 147177 (Figure 6.81)

Figure 6.81 – Sword ID 100 obverse.

26	Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Bulge	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Compression Curling
Left	2	1	5	1	3	2	n/a
Right	5	n/a	3	1	n/a	2	1
Visibility	1						

This complete, leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Terontola was discovered in the Corte Lazise find context (Salzani 2006, 31). It measures a total length of 477 mm, and is completely covered in smooth green, brown and grey patina. Although complete, the sword has been bent several times and looks badly battered. The hilt consists of just a grip tang that slightly thickens towards the blade before forming ricassi. Rivet holes are not present, indicating a crude grip fixing by forcing the organic material onto the tang. Bevel lines and a slight midrib are present.

A total of 26 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 14 on the left and twelve on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are round notches and indentations. On the left, the marks cluster in the lower quarter of the blade, close to the tip. All but one mark are located within 131 mm of the tip on this side. The marks on the right cutting edge are more evenly spread. It appears that the left cutting edge was frequently used for attacks with the most forward section of the blade. The two bulges indicate that some binding or twisting action took place.

Given the relative shortness of the blade with only 477 mm total length, it is perhaps not surprising that many of the marks are located close to the tip, as the fighter would have had to use the entire length of the blade to reach his opponent. The short blade could also have been used for “serpent-like” forward strikes with the blade around the opponent’s defence. Binding and twisting motions would have benefitted from the shortness of the sword, as there would have been less metal to turn to navigate around the other’s weapon.

Sword ID 74 – TB 113 (Figure 6.82)

Figure 6.82 – Sword ID 74 obverse.

31	Curved Graze	Double Notch	Elongated Graze	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Sharp Notch	Straight Graze	Wide-Angled Notch	Irregular Graze
Left	1	1	1	1	1	4	2	1	1	n/a
Right	4	n/a	1	3	n/a	7	1	1	n/a	1
Visibility	1									

Tomba 113 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is an oval pit containing the almost complete remains of an adult individual, no more than 30 years of age, who was buried extended on their back. The individual was 168.2 cm tall. A sword of type Bigarello was deposited on the individual’s torso, with the hilt positioned centrally on top of the sternum and the tip

protruding slightly over the left hip (Salzani 2005, 165). The individual displays bone regrowth on the tibia, likely caused by a tumor, or possibly by bone marrow as a result of an accidental fracture (Pulcini 2014, 85-6).

This complete copper-alloy sword has straight cutting edges tapering towards a pointy tip. The hilt consists of a semi-oval hilt plate without a tang. There are six rivets *in situ* in the plate, three in each shoulder (Figure 6.83). Very short, curved ricassi merge into bevel lines. The entire sword is covered in fairly smooth green and brown patina and infrequent spots of pock mark corrosion. Total length is 607 mm.

A total of 31 marks could be identified on this sword, 13 on the left and 18 on the right cutting edge. The marks on the left cutting edge are clustered on the lower half of the blade. On the right edge, the marks are distributed evenly. Some marks are exceptionally small, yet distinct in shape (Figure 6.84). An unusually high amount of round notches were recorded.

The amount and types of marks suggest heavy use in combat, most likely during several altercations.

Figure 6.83 – Six rivets *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 74.

Figure 6.84 – Mark ID 1824, extremely small round notch, right cutting edge, 535 mm from the tip of Sword ID 74.

Sword ID 89 – TB 202 (Figure 6.85)

Figure 6.85 – Sword ID 89 obverse.

4	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Sharp Notch	Round Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Irregular Graze
Left	11	1	3	1	2	n/a	1	1
Right	8	2	1	3	2	4	n/a	4
Visibility	1							

Tomb 202 in Area C at Olmo di Nogara is a rectangular pit containing the extended, almost complete inhumation of an adult of unspecified age or sex, 162.8 cm tall. The adult was buried on their back, with the arms in parallel alignment with the body. A sword of type Bigarello was placed on top of the deceased's right arm, with the hilt positioned directly on top of the shoulder, and the tip over the hand (Salzani 2005, 203-4).

The complete copper-alloy sword measures a total length of 616 mm. It is completely covered in green and brown patina with some spots of corrosion. The basic hilt consists of a trapezoidal hilt plate with six rivets *in situ*, three in each shoulder (Figure 6.86). Curved ricassi merge into cutting edges without bevel lines. A slight midrib is present.

The high number of wear marks is evenly split between the two sides, with 20 on the left and 24 on the right cutting edge. The most common marks are 19 indentations, twelve notches, and ten grazes of different kinds. All marks are very evenly distributed along the entire length of the cutting edges on both sides.

Whilst no clear patterns or edge dominance could be identified, this sword appears to bear the marks of heavy combat on multiple occasions, or else it could have been used extensively in combat training exercises. The marks are most likely the result of clashing impacts with other bladed and blunt weapons (see Chapter 3.5).

Figure 6.86 – Six rivets *in situ* in the hilt of Sword ID 89.

Sword ID 101 – 123570 (Figure 6.87)

Figure 6.87 – Sword ID 101 obverse.

43	Indentation	Rectangular Indentation	Round Notch	Double Notch	Wide-Angled Notch	Straight Graze	Curved Graze	Elongated Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge
Left	6	2	3	1	n/a	2	2	1	3	1
Right	9	1	4	n/a	2	2	1	n/a	3	n/a
Visibility	1									

This slightly leaf-shaped copper-alloy sword of type Terontola from Corte Lazise has a fractured grip tang and a fractured tip (Salzani 2006, 31). Whilst mostly covered in brown, black, and green patina, a large amount of pit corrosion is also present. There are no rivet holes in the hilt and no midrib, but bevel lines are present. The blade is heavily damaged. Total length is 423 mm.

A total of 43 wear marks could be identified on this sword, 21 on the left and 22 on the right. The most common marks are 15 indentations (Figure 6.88). All marks are evenly distributed along the entire length of the cutting edges, and no clear patterns could be identified. On a whole, however, the marks seem to concentrate in the mid-section of the blade on both cutting edges.

Whilst this sword was clearly used extensively in combat or training, the pit corrosion and fractured tang and tip indicate that the sword was of poor quality.

Figure 6.88 – Mark ID 2559, indentation, left cutting edge, 9-12 mm from the tip of Sword ID 101.

6.5.3 Early Iron Age, c. 900-700 cal BC

Sword ID 105 – 23209 (Figure 6.89)

Figure 6.89 – Sword ID 105 obverse.

5	Round Notch	Straight Graze	Irregular Graze	Bulge	Blow Mark
Left	1	1	1	n/a	n/a
Right	n/a	n/a	n/a	1	1
Visibility	1				

This sword of type Cuma was recovered from Celano, Province of L’Aquila, and dates to the 9th century BC (Bianco Peroni 1970, 88). It is a complete copper-alloy sword with a cast hilt plate and plate for the terminus, and completely covered in fairly smooth brown and green patina. One rivet remains *in situ* in the terminus. One rivet hole can be found in the grip plate, two rivet holes and one partial rivet hole in the shoulders. The straight, wide blade tapers towards a pointy tip. Linear decorations were added on the flat of the blade on both sides (Figure 6.90). The sword is bent in the lower quarter, where a deep striation can be found (Figure 6.91). Total length is 479 mm.

Five marks were identified on this sword, three on the left and two on the right cutting edge. The deep striation in close proximity to the bend of the sword indicates that the sword was hit on the flat side of the blade. This most likely happened during a fight, where the sword was either hit accidentally, and hence bent the blade, or a flat parry had to be carried out (see Chapter 3.4.2). The flat parry was likely the end of the use life of the sword, as once bent it became non-functional.

Figure 6.90 – Decorations on the flat of the blade of Sword ID 105.

Figure 6.91 – Mark IDs 2619-20, striation and bulge, reverse left cutting edge, 120 mm from the tip of Sword ID 105.

6.6 Analysis

As in the previous chapter, it was necessary to only include those swords with Visibility=1 in order to conduct meaningful statistical analysis. Including the data of swords that were not analysed in their entirety might bias the result. Dating to the Early Iron Age, Sword 105 was also not included. The remaining swords were split into the two chronological categories of Middle Bronze Age and Recent Bronze Age, to highlight the differences and changes between the two periods. A total of 34 swords was therefore statistically relevant, 20 from the Middle Bronze Age and 14 from the Recent Bronze Age. Again, the focus was laid on the four most common and distinctive mark types: indentations, notches, grazes, and bulges, as these are directly linked to specific combat actions. For the same reasons as outlined in Chapter 5.6, different types of notches and grazes have been included as general categories of notches and grazes. Two types of graphs are being used to visualize the data: box-and-whisker plots to illustrate the location of marks along the blades, and bar charts to show the absolute and relative frequency of the marks. All graphs were created using Microsoft Excel 2016 software.

6.6.1 Location of marks

As in the previous chapter, to visualize where the main combat-related marks are located along the cutting edges, the data set had to be normalised. The formula $y=(d/D)*100$ (d=distance of mark from the tip, D=total length of sword) was used to express the distance from the tip of every mark as a percentage of the entire length of each sword, so that 34 swords of different lengths could be compared. Again, the difficulty with determining the exact limits of each sword blade meant that the distance had to be calculated as a percentage of the entire length of the sword, instead of just the blade. Any possible deviations due to fractured tips or hilt tongues were deemed small enough to be neglected.

Figure 6.92 – Box-and-whisker plot of normalised mark distances on Middle Bronze Age Italian swords, illustrating the locations of Indentations, Notches and Grazes.

	Indentations	Notches	Grazes	Bulges
Minimum	2	4	1	0
Q1	23	25	32	0
Median	45	48	50	0
Q2	69	67	66	0
Maximum	90	91	87	0
Mean	44	47	48	0
Range	46	42	34	0

Table 6.2 - Statistical values for normalised locations of marks on Middle Bronze Age Italian swords.

The graph shows that, on Middle Bronze Age Italian swords, the indentations and notches are fairly evenly distributed over around half the length of the swords, roughly between 20 % and 70 %, with minima and maxima close to both tip and hilt (Figure 6.92). Grazes, however, are clustered much more centrally between 32 % and 67 %, but also with minimum and maximum located closely to the tip and the hilt. No bulges were detected.

Figure 6.93 – Box-and-whisker plot of normalised mark distances on Recent Bronze Age Italian swords, illustrating the locations of Indentations, Notches and Grazes.

	Indentations	Notches	Grazes	Bulges
Minimum	2	1	4	8
Q1	18	20	21	25
Median	40	33	40	43
Q2	53	53	53	51
Maximum	79	80	83	83
Mean	37	35	39	40
Range	34	33	32	26

Table 6.3 - Statistical values for normalised locations of marks on Recent Bronze Age Italian swords.

Despite occasional exceptions (expressed as outliers in the box-and-whisker diagrams), the majority of indentations, notches and grazes on swords from the Recent Bronze Age in Italy are clustered in just over 35 % of the sword, between c. 20 % and 55 % distance from the tip. Additionally, bulges are found on Recent Bronze Age swords, and are clustered in a similar area between 23 % and 52 %, with occasional deviations further towards the tip or the hilt (Figure 6.93).

Comparing Middle and Recent Bronze Age swords from Italy, two major developments in combat mark distribution can be observed. First, the clustering of marks becomes much denser during the Recent Bronze Age, with the three main categories of marks grouped within only 35 % of the blade, as opposed to over 50 % in the Middle Bronze Age. This increased clustering could be the result of more sophisticated fighting styles and increased training. The clustering also happens to be located in the area of the characteristic leaf-shaped swelling of

Recent Bronze Age swords, suggesting that this deliberate advancement in sword design was directly linked to combat styles.

Second, bulges first appear in the record. The absence of bulging on Middle Bronze Age swords does not necessarily mean that the marks did not occur during that period. However, it is significant to note that all bulges were recorded on only 14 Recent Bronze Age swords, and none on the larger set of 20 Middle Bronze Age blades. This suggests that bulging was almost certainly related to the evolution of combat styles in the Recent Bronze Age. The increasingly frequent occurrence of swords during the Middle to Recent Bronze Age transition might have caused this adaption in fighting styles, as the bulge-producing binding and twisting motion is most effective in sword vs. sword combat, and would potentially not have been needed earlier.

6.6.2 Frequency of marks

Figure 6.94 – Bar chart displaying the total numbers of combat related marks (left), which consist of indentations, notches, grazes and bulges (displayed) and other marks of lesser frequency, on Middle and Recent Bronze Age Italian swords.

The above bar chart (Figure 6.94) shows that Middle Bronze Age swords from Italy display a significantly higher amount of combat-related marks than their Recent Bronze Age successors. This is the case with all major mark categories, indentations, notches, and grazes, with the exception of bulges, which appear to be an exclusively Recent Bronze Age occurrence. The chart, however, is biased, due to the uneven number of swords from either time period.

To compensate for the above-mentioned bias, the average numbers of each category were calculated using the formula $y = n_m / n_s$ (n_m =number of marks per category, n_s =total number of swords per time period). On average, a Middle Bronze Age sword displays ten more marks

than its Recent Bronze Age successor. The biggest difference lies in the amounts of indentations, which are significantly lower in the Recent Bronze Age. On the other hand, bulges are completely amiss during the earlier period.

Figure 6.95 – Bar chart displaying the average numbers of combat related marks (left), which consist of indentations, notches, grazes and bulges (displayed) and other marks of lesser frequency, on Middle and Recent Bronze Age Italian swords.

Whilst the typical swords would statistically display 26 or 16 marks respectively, with indentations, notches, grazes, and bulges occurring in distinct frequencies (Figure 6.95), the reality is quite different. In fact, many swords appear to mostly display either one type or the other, and especially swords displaying mostly indentations are common. This is likely the result of the local or individual fighting style executed by the swordsman, or the answer to a trend in preferred weaponry by the opposition.

6.7 Conclusion

Similar to the previous chapter, the metalwork wear analysis methodology described in Chapter 3.3.1 was successfully employed to analyse 40 Middle and Recent Bronze Age swords from a number of Italian museums. The location and frequency of wear marks suggest that a development of fighting styles over time occurred. Interestingly, bulges, which are indicative of binding and twisting motions, did not occur during the Middle Bronze Age. The next chapter will combine all the data created and recorded for this research, from both experiments and wear analysis, with information from the literature to discuss and (re-)interpret Bronze Age combat, warfare, and warriorhood.

Chapter 7. Discussion

7.1 Introduction

This chapter combines all the data gathered during the experiments (Chapters 3 and 4) and wear analysis (Chapters 5 and 6), as well as the osteological data (Chapter 2) and information from the literature. This is used to discuss combat related wear marks, British and Italian fighting styles and their similarities and differences, the practicalities of sword fighting, as well as Bronze Age sword fighters in a wider context.

7.2 Evaluation of experiments

When studying and interpreting the ways prehistoric weapons were used, it is essential to do so from a practical as well as a theoretical perspective in order to draw firm conclusions. In the case of this research, two different experimental methodologies were chosen and developed. The first consisted of combat broken down into individual actions, which were executed and recorded one at a time (see Chapter 3.3.2). This made it possible to match wear marks with specific actions. The second, “actualistic” experiments consisted of actual combat broken into short plays with a few sword contacts each, and were based on historical fighting manuscripts. Conducting fluid combat, rather than individual actions, introduces the dynamics of an actual fight, whilst the plays were short enough to allow to match wear marks with their specific actions (see Chapter 4.2.3). To create meaningful data and validate the results, it was deemed imperative to conduct scientific field experiments under controlled conditions, which were repeatable and followed a strict protocol, rather than laboratory-based assessments (e.g. Bridgford 2000; O’Flaherty 2007) or experiential tests like the ones conducted by Molloy (2004; 2006; 2007; 2008) and Anderson (2011). Although fundamentally different, both experiments were designed to recreate the wear marks recorded on original Bronze Age swords, which in turn allowed for an interpretation of the actions that would have caused the original marks. Furthermore, handling the swords, and other weapons, in different manners provides experiential data in addition to the physical wear marks created, and the researcher can combine the two in their interpretation (see Chapters 3.5 and 4.4 for the experimental results in detail). The results from an experiment can only ever be as good as its design, and it is crucial to keep an open mind when doing so. Working in collaboration with other academics and non-academic participants provides an influx of different ideas which a single researcher is unlikely to develop on their own. Training and working with the enthusiastic *Hotspur School of Defence* members has produced some excellent experiential results, such as the idea of handling a sword with the thumb on the flat (see Chapter 4.4), which I would otherwise never have thought of. Most importantly, the actualistic experiments have made me

realise that there is no clear distinction between “attack” and “defence”. Instead, for a skilled fighter of any martial art, attack and defence become interchangeable, and potentially defensive motions act as a primer for the next offensive action. Moreover, the experiments have shown that deliberate contact is made to control the opponent and their weapon. This means that the wear marks observed on original Bronze Age swords are by no means the result of “accidental” contact (Horn 2013, 40; Molloy 2007, 109; 2011, 75), but rather an indicator of sophisticated fighting styles that deliberately sought contact with the opponent’s weapon. The popular culture idea of opposing fighters exchanging blows, taking it in turns to attack and defend, does not represent the reality of prehistoric (or indeed historic) combat by any means, and future research must no longer be grounded in this.

While theoretical interpretation based solely on analogy and imagination (e.g. Kristiansen 2002; Heath 2009; Mödlinger 2011) is extremely precarious, so is basing conclusions exclusively on experimental data. Instead, information from experiments, wear analysis, and the literature must be brought together for a final interpretation. The next sections will discuss the original and replica wear marks, their interpretations, and how this changes the picture of Bronze Age combat and warfare.

7.3 Type of marks, locations and patterns

The wear analysis of 110 Bronze Age swords from Britain and Italy, integrated by the literature (Bridgford 2000; Horn 2011; 2013; Molloy 2011; O’Flaherty et al. 2011; Uckelmann 2012), has revealed 23 different types of use-related wear marks (i.e. excluding manufacturing and post-depositional wear). It was deemed imperative to define different mark types with the highest precision to avoid an unintentional bias of the data by summarizing different marks under overly general terms. During the experiments, it was possible to recreate 14 different marks (Table 7.1). Some of these can securely be linked to specific combat actions (e.g. bulges and tip pressure) or weapons-combinations (e.g. wide-angled notches and indentations). Others were caused by a number of different actions (e.g. sharp notches, round notches, curved grazes, flattenings, mirconotching, striations, and bending). Blow marks, rectangular indentations and irregular grazes were each only recreated once, and are therefore not necessarily indicative of only one specific action. No marks could be identified as being related to specifically offensive or defensive motions.

Mark	Experiment	Cause
Bulge	✓	twist and bind
Tip Pressure	✓	thrusts
Blow Mark	✓	kinetic flat parry
Rectangular Indentation	✓	shoulder strike
Irregular Graze	✓	glancing blow (wooden shield)
Indentation	✓	spear socket or shaft
Wide-Angled Notch	✓	spear edge
Sharp Notch	✓	multiple causes
Round Notch	✓	multiple causes
Curved Graze	✓	multiple causes
Flattening	✓	multiple causes
Micronotching	✓	multiple causes
Striation	✓	multiple causes
Bending	✓	multiple causes
Twisting	✗	unknown
Toothed Notch	✗	unknown
Double Notch	✗	unknown
Straight Graze	✗	unknown
Elongated Graze	✗	unknown
Compression Curling	✗	unknown
Rippling	✗	unknown
Fissure	✗	unknown
Fracture	✗	unknown

Table 7.1 – Table of 23 use-related wear marks, of which 14 could be recreated during the combat experiments, showing single or multiple causes of each mark.

7.3.1 Action-specific marks

Figure 7.1 – Replica wide-angled notch from 31e.4.

Figure 7.2 – Mark ID 151, original wide-angled notch.

Wide-angled notches are distinctive in profile and were exclusively created when the sword cutting edge impacted on the cutting edge of a spearhead. Due to the difficulty of connecting with that particular part of the spear, these marks were only created twice during the experiments (Figure 7.1). This is reflected in the archaeological record; only 64 original wide-angled (Figure 7.2) notches were recorded, on 36 of the Bronze Age swords from both Britain and Italy.

Figure 7.3 – Replica indentation from 27g.

Figure 7.4 – Mark ID 106, original indentation.

Indentations are evidence of the cutting edge connecting with the round socket or wooden shaft of a spear, thus creating a distinctly shallow impact profile (Figure 7.3). During the experiments, it proved much more likely that contact with the socket or shaft was made than with the cutting edge of a spearhead. The archaeological record (Figure 7.4) reflects this, with 693 indentations on 91 swords.

Figure 7.5 – Replica bulge from 304b.

Figure 7.6 – Mark ID 127, original bulge.

Bulges (Figure 7.5) were exclusively created during binding and twisting motions to control the opponent's weapon. They occur on both the controlling and the controlled weapon, and no preference for either could be observed. A total of 111 bulges have been recorded on 39 swords (Figure 7.6).

Figure 7.7 – Replica tip pressure from 104b. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 7.8 – Sword ID 5, original tip pressure.

Unsurprisingly, tip pressure (Figure 7.7) was only created during thrusting impacts with the tip of the blade. As the swords proved extremely effective in piercing the leather shield (and no mark was created on them in the process), all tip pressures were the result of contact with the wooden or the bronze shield. The mark was recorded on 35 original Bronze Age swords (Figure 7.8).

Figure 7.9 – Replica bend from 1k.

Figure 7.10 - Sword ID 71, original bend.

Figure 7.11 – Replica striation pattern from 1k.

Figure 7.12 – Sword ID 71, original striation pattern.

The distinctive bend and striation pattern created during test reference 1k. (Figure 7.9 & Figure 7.11) are conclusive evidence of a flat parry. As the bend is so severe that it renders the sword non-functional, one can assume that this move was avoided as much as possible.

Nevertheless, the same bend and striation pattern were observed on four original swords (Sword IDs 11, 59, 71 (Figure 7.10 & Figure 7.12) and 105).

Figure 7.13 – Replica flattening from 201a. Image by RJ Crellin.

Figure 7.14 – Mark ID 2119, original flattening.

Flattenings (Figure 7.13) were mostly created as the result of glancing blows (an action simulating the defence against a slashing strike) across the rim or face of the wooden and bronze shields. Only 13 flattenings have been observed on the original swords (Figure 7.14).

7.3.2 Marks with multiple causes

Figure 7.15 – Replica sharp notch from 31c.

Figure 7.17 – Mark ID 270, original sharp notch.

Figure 7.16 – Replica round notch from 301a.

Figure 7.18 – Mark ID 211, original round notch.

Figure 7.19 – Replica curved graze from 304c.

Figure 7.20 – Mark ID 381, original curved graze.

Sharp notches (Figure 7.15) and round notches (Figure 7.16) were the most commonly created marks during the experiments. They were created during a variety of cutting edge contacts and are not indicative of any particular actions. Likewise, curved grazes (Figure 7.19) can be the result of various actions and are not action-specific. Although there was no exclusive trend, curved grazes were more likely created when both swords were moving quickly towards each other prior to the impact. Sharp and round notches tended to occur when lower velocity impacts took place. On the original swords, 442 round notches (Figure 7.18), 264 sharp notches (Figure 7.17) and 155 curved grazes (Figure 7.20) were recorded.

Figure 7.21 – Replica micronotch (right) from 36b.

Figure 7.22 – Original micronotching (red) on Sword ID 5.

Micronotches (Figure 7.21) were frequently created as the result of rebounding during an impact. Eighty-eight cases of micronotches could be recorded on the original swords (Figure 7.22), although this number may not be representative as the small size of the marks mean that even a small amount of corrosion eradicates their presence. Furthermore, it is almost impossible to match micronotches with their specific mark (unless a mark appears completely isolated surrounded by micronotches). In any case, micronotches were not found to be evident of any specific combat actions, speed (also occurring when the sword was held statically), or opposing weapon.

7.3.3 *Offensive vs. defensive marks*

In addition to the fact that no mark can exclusively be classed as offensive or defensive, the experiments have also shown that dividing the blade into “attacking” and “defending” sections (see Kristiansen 2002, 323; Molloy 2011, 75) is incorrect, as no trends regarding the formation of marks along the cutting edge could be detected during the experiment. There were no sections more likely to make contact during offensive nor defensive actions than another. This relates to the notion that no sword combat action can meaningfully be classified as solely attack or solely defence (see 7.2). Whilst no consideration was given to this during the first set of field tests, the actualistic experiments revealed that when a sword is repeatedly held in the same manner, a clear edge dominance will develop (see Chapter 4.4). The same edge dominance could be observed on 31 original swords. Marks created on the back cutting edge were the result of backhand strikes.

7.3.4 *Mark clusters and patterns*

Figure 7.23 – Cluster of four marks on the right cutting edge of Sword ID 60.

Whilst no patterns of marks resulted from the experiments on the replica weapons, the analysis has revealed that there are certain reoccurring patterns on the Bronze Age swords, though none of which are indicative of offensive or defensive motions. Instead, two different trends could be observed. Firstly, some swords display tight clusters of marks, which appear to be the result of repeated impacts with the same section of the sword. These clusters consist of two, three, four, or more marks located in immediate proximity to each other (Figure 7.23). Although the clustering could potentially be a chance occurrence, it is much more likely that it is the result of carrying out the same action numerous times. In turn, this suggests that the action must have been practised. These patterns occur on all sections of the blade. Secondly, when studying the mark locations statistically, the concentration of all marks increases in a

certain part of the sword over time (see Chapter 5.6; 6.6). In Britain, this increased concentration occurs from the Middle to the Late Bronze Age, until the pattern suddenly disperses with the emergence of the Hallstatt C phase. During the Penard Phase, the marks are generally evenly spread within almost 70 % of the length of the sword. In the next phase, the Wilburton Phase, these marks are clustered much tighter. Particularly, different types of notches and bulges are located within only around 26 %. Overall, the marks in the Wilburton Phase are clustered within only 50 % of the sword. Towards the end of the Bronze Age, during the Ewart Park Phase, the marks are clustered even tighter together within only 45 % of the blade. The emergence of the Hallstatt C phase sees a complete loss of these patterns. Instead, the marks are located across almost the entire length of the blade. Individual mark types display clustering in divergent locations and to unequal extents. As previously discussed (see Chapter 5.6.1), this increased clustering over time suggests the emergence of distinct fighting styles and traditions. The sudden dispersal of the patterns could be related to the introduction of iron during Hallstatt C, which made a change in fighting practices necessary, and potentially a change in society and the importance of swordsmanship.

In Italy, during the Middle Bronze Age, the marks are located roughly within 50 % of the blade. Notably, bulges are completely absent from the record for this time period. As such, it can be suggested that binding and twisting motions were not part of the fighting styles. In the Recent Bronze Age, bulges have been introduced and are a common occurrence. The marks became tightly clustered within only 35 % of the blade. Again, the increased clustering is indicative of the development of distinct fighting styles. The late development of bulges further suggests a sophistication of these fighting styles over time. Furthermore, the lack of bulges during the Middle Bronze Age may suggest that binding and twisting was not necessary during this period, perhaps due to a larger number of other weaponry such as spears, against which this technique cannot be used successfully.

7.3.5 Similarities and differences of British and Italian marks

Comparing British and Italian wear marks, a number of similarities and differences could be observed. Generally speaking, the types and shapes of the wear marks are identical. No distinctly British or Italian marks could be identified. Overall however, the Italian wear marks tend to be smaller than their British counterparts. As discussed in Chapter 3.6, the size of the marks is directly related to the amount and quality of work-hardening (Wang, in prep.). Furthermore, the alloy-composition can have an effect on the appearance of marks (Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martin-Lerma 2015, 175). Further research, including metallographic and compositional analyses, should be carried out to understand this fully. The development of

patterns, as discussed above, is similar in both geographic regions. Britain and Italy display an increasingly tight clustering of marks over time, suggesting that in both areas the fighting styles developed and became more sophisticated towards the end of the Bronze Age. Interestingly, during the Middle Bronze Age bulges appear only in Britain, not in Italy, which suggests that the fighting styles of the two regions were slightly different. Generally speaking, however, the similar development of fighting styles over time and the similarity of wear marks suggest that Bronze Age sword fighting was practiced in similar ways in Britain and in Italy.

7.4 Interpretation

This section discusses the practicalities of sword fighting and combat, their implementation in everyday life as well as deliberate destruction and handedness in Bronze Age sword fighters.

7.4.1 *Attack or defence – a thing of the past?*

The principle of simultaneous, interchangeable attack and defence is prevalent in most traditional and modern martial arts, such as Wing Chun (Cheng 1986) and Krav Maga (Ben Keren 2014), and was also present in the historical fighting manuscripts of the mediaeval and Renaissance period (e.g. Liechtenauer's MS Chart.A.558 from 1443). In the latter, certain common actions are referred to as *meisterhau* (master strike), which attack and defend simultaneously (wiktenauer.com). Instead of designated offensive strikes and defensive parries which are exchanged by the fighters in turn, all historic sources agree in suggesting that real combat consists of offensive actions that simultaneously defend or prime the weapon for the next attack. Rather than exchanging quick blows with clashing contacts from a distance, the relative shortness of Bronze Age swords suggests that the fight would have been conducted at close measure. Understanding that no meaningful distinction can be made between attacking and defending motions implies two things: firstly, there will be no distinctly offensive or defensive wear marks, and secondly, the blade is not divided into offensive or defensive sections as suggested by Kristiansen (2002, 323) and Molloy (2011, 75). Both inferences have been confirmed by the experiments (see Chapters 3.5; 4.4). There are, however, wear marks that can conclusively be linked to certain combat actions, which in turn allow for an interpretation of specific fighting techniques favoured by Bronze Age sword fighters.

7.4.2 Holding the sword

Figure 7.24 – Three ways of holding the sword: with the hand “locked” into place (left), “fingering” the hilt (middle), and with the thumb on the flat of the blade (right). Unscaled picture.

Figure 7.25 – Inverted sword grip. Unscaled picture.

Figure 7.26 – Pommel grip. Unscaled picture.

Before interpreting the specific ways in which Bronze Age swords could have been used, it should be considered how these weapons were held. The physical properties of these weapons, especially their short hilts, lack of crossguards and ricassi allow for different grips, three of which proved useful when experimenting with. As suggested by Kristiansen (2002, 321), the shortness of the hilt typical for all Bronze Age swords “locks” the hand into place (Figure 7.24 left), thus providing good control of the weapon. The unsharpened ricassi allow for the index finger to be placed over the shoulder (Figure 7.24 middle; Crellin et al. in press), which provides a different balance and feeling of the sword. Finally, the sword can be held with the thumb placed on the flat of the blade between the ricassi (Figure 7.24 right), which again changes the balance of the sword significantly and allows for quick changes of direction

as well as backhand strikes. My experiments suggest that there is no “correct” grip as such, but that these techniques can be used in combination depending on the situation and/or personal preferences. It must be noted that further grips could be afforded by the sword, for example with the sword inverted (Figure 7.25) for a downwards thrust, or with the hand around the pommel (Figure 7.26; see Clements 1998, 77-81, for a discussion of mediaeval sword grips). These grips, however, were not experimented with as part of my research.

7.4.3 Protection of the sword hand

Figure 7.27 – Two fighters using their *bucklers* to protect the sword hand. From Paulus Hector Mair’s *MSS Dresden C93 and C94*, 147r, c. 1542 AD. Image courtesy of SLUB Dresden.

Crossguards are bars of metal placed between the hilt and the blade of a sword, and occur on swords and rapiers from the 10th century AD (Clements 1998, 30). They were introduced to add extra protection to the sword hand but could also be used as a means of holding the sword in a different way, and could further be used offensively to strike the opponent with. Whilst early crossguards consisted of simple, straight metal bars, these protective measures developed over time into protective shield guards and full-metal gaskets (Clements 1997, 35). No such protection can be found on Bronze Age swords, and the sword hand had to be protected in a different way. The experiments discussed in Chapter 3.4.4 have shown the effectiveness of all types of Bronze Age shields, whilst the actualistic experiments have demonstrated the successful use of these shields in combat. The replica copper-alloy shield is most similar to the mediaeval *buckler*, a small, round metal shield measuring between 20 and 45 cm in diameter (Clements 1998, 105). The main purpose of the buckler was to protect the sword hand of otherwise unarmoured combatants (Figure 7.27). It was equally as effective as an offensive weapon as it could be used to punch or trap the opponent (*ibid.*). For the

actualistic experiments, which were based on historical sword and buckler manuals, we used replica shields made out of leather, which, although slightly larger in diameter than a typical buckler, proved to be extremely successful. From all this it can reasonably be suggested that Bronze Age shields could have been used in a similar manner to mediaeval bucklers, that is to protect the sword hand and offensively to attack the opponent.

7.4.4 Strikes and centre of percussion

Comparatively slow strikes and fast strikes, as are evident through the large number of sharp notches, round notches and curved grazes (see 7.3) likely formed a significant part of Bronze Age sword fighting styles. The evidence for “slow” strikes could in fact translate into short, yet quick and nimble movements, thus creating an overall lower impact force resulting in “low-speed” impact marks. Certainly “...long, slashing movements with a lot of weight and force behind...” as suggested by Kristiansen (2002, 320) seem unlikely, as they would leave the fighter open to the opponent at close measure, and because the potential of Bronze Age swords did not lie in penetration by percussion (Molloy 2010, 415). Instead, Molloy’s suggestion of the occurrence of slicing draw-cuts from the elbow and shoulder, as well as thrusts (2007, 100-1) seems likely. His suggestion that this would result in increased mark formation at the centre of percussion, c. two-thirds along the cutting edge towards the tip, is only partially confirmed by my wear analysis of the archaeological swords. The analyses in Chapters 5.6.1 and 6.6.1 indicate that a general increased clustering of marks in that area developed towards the end of the Bronze Age, suggesting that the centre of percussion could have developed as the preferred striking section. During the Middle Bronze Age, however, the marks were clustered less tightly and spread over a large area of the sword, suggesting that less focus was laid on striking with the centre of percussion.

7.4.5 Avoiding contact during combat

As described earlier (Section 7.3), bulges are conclusive evidence of binding and twisting motions. This technique is employed to connect with the opponent’s weapon in order to control it through friction between the blades. The regular occurrence of bulges in the archaeological record suggests that this technique was widely known and practised. Most importantly, binding and twisting implies that deliberate contact is made with the opponent’s weapon. Instead of avoiding contacts as much as possible to preserve the material of the sword (Molloy 2007, 109), Bronze Age swordfighters would have accepted a small amount of wear to their blades in order to bind and control the opponent. As such, the wear marks on original Bronze Age swords are by no means “accidental” (Horn 2013, 40), but rather the result of fighting styles that deliberately sought contact with the opponent’s weapon.

Furthermore, the binding and twisting technique requires initial guidance and practice to be employed successfully, suggesting that a certain degree of training had to take place.

7.4.6 *Sword and spear combat – a regular occurrence?*

The large presence of indentations and wide-angled notches on Bronze Age swords (adding up to 32 % of all combat marks recorded for this research), both of which are evidence of contacts with spear sockets, shafts, and spearhead cutting edges, suggests that these weapons were employed against each other on a regular basis. Unsurprisingly, the majority of these marks suggest that contact was most often made with the spear shaft, as this is the longest section of a spear. Clashing contacts with the cutting edges of a spearhead appear to have occurred less frequently, but the experiments have shown that these can also result in more common marks such as sharp notches. The frequent contact between swords and spears make a scenario in which short spears are employed in a fencing style as described by Molloy (2006) seem likely.

7.4.7 *Bent swords & target areas*

The major bend that occurred during the first set of experiments (Chapter 3.4.2) is direct evidence that flat parries, as suggested by Mödlinger (2011, 164), and more generally contacts with the flat of the blade, would have been avoided as much as possible as they render the sword unusable. Both the bend and its associated distinct striation pattern are present in the archaeological record though, suggesting that this particular type of contact occurred occasionally, either accidentally or as a last resort to save one's life.

Kristiansen claims that Bronze Age swords were frequently deliberately bent in order to point towards the opponent's heart. His inference is based upon a comparison with "modern" sword fighters who, he claims, would employ a similar technique (Kristiansen 2002, 320). There are several problems with this interpretation. Firstly, bending the blade to point at the opponent's heart implies that swords were exclusively used to thrust, as the bend becomes useless, and arguably counter-productive, for any other combat action. In

Figure 7.28 – Foil fencing target area in orange. (www.wikipedia.org).

fact, the experiments discussed in Chapter 3 have shown that the bending has a devastating effect on the handling and control of the weapon, as it makes it no longer possible to predict

where the blade would land. Secondly, although bent swords do exist in the record, the vast majority of surviving Bronze Age swords do not have a bent point (see Chapters 5 and 6). Thirdly, Kristiansen's validation through contemporary sword fighters is presumably based on conversation with a foil fencer. A foil is a weapon entirely different in shape, material, and handling to prehistoric copper-alloy swords. Foil blades consist of thin, wire-like steel bands which significantly bend under pressure and are exclusively used for thrusting (British Fencing 2017, 10). These blades are deliberately bent slightly downwards to prevent the tip from sliding under the opponent's mask. The target area in foil fencing is the upper body only (Figure 7.28), and the slight bend assists in reaching around the opponent's arms to hit the target. Bronze Age swords, however, are completely different in shape, material properties, and design, and contemporary foil fencing cannot be used as an analogy to interpret prehistoric combat styles. Fourthly, Kristiansen's theory suggests that the main target area would have been the chest. The osteological evidence described in Chapter 2, however, clearly shows that the preferred target area for cut and puncture lesions are the skull and the pelvis, with only two examples of trauma to the chest in the Bronze Age skeletal record. These data might be slightly biased, as devastating injuries can be inflicted without leaving osteological evidence, but any attempt to pierce an opponent's heart would invariably inflict detectable trauma to the rib cage or sternum. The chest area also has a high potential of trapping the attacking weapon, thus creating an unnecessary hazard for the attacker. Injuries to the abdomen, however, can result in severe incapacitation and death without creating too much risk of losing the weapon. If thrust at the wrong angle, however, the weapon can get stuck in the pelvis, as is evident from five cases from Britain, Denmark, and Hungary (see Chapter 2.3). Nevertheless, the abdomen would likely have been considered a prime target for sword attacks. There is only little evidence for sword strikes to the face and skull. Historically, the head was one of the main targets for sword attacks (Clements 1998, 201). The lack of evidence for this in the Bronze Age, however, could be due to the different mechanical properties of copper-alloy swords. As demonstrated during the experiments (see Chapter 3), copper-alloy swords are prone to bending. As such, the bony structure of the skull could have been deemed too risky to attack without damaging the weapon. Instead, the neck provides a better target, with several major arteries, the windpipe and the spine. On the other hand, the skull appears to be the main target area for blunt force attacks. Although these data could again be biased, as blunt force lesions are difficult to detect on the rest of the body, this focus on the skull seems logical. Whilst blunt force attacks to the limbs or torso could potentially result in broken bones and bruising, they are unlikely to prove fatal. Attacking the skull, however, is extremely likely to lead to devastating injuries and death. Whilst the

abdomen and neck were likely the main target areas of Bronze Age sword fighters, this does not mean that attacks to other body parts were not executed. Molloy's (2007; 2008) and Anderson's (2011) experiments have demonstrated the devastating effects of Bronze Age swords and spears on flesh and limbs when used correctly. They were able to easily slice through muscles and tendons, which would likely have incapacitated the opponent to such an extent that they could no longer participate in the fight. Osteological evidence of lesions to the arms and legs (see Chapter 2.3) suggests that these body parts were also targeted. The risk of infection and long-term disability aside, injuring rather than killing an opponent in a clash or melee fight has implications on the dynamics of the opposing faction, as the screams of a wounded person can be demoralizing for their comrades.

Figure 7.29 – Composite drawing of the Pylos Combat Agate showing two warriors in combat. The winning male on the left is stabbing his sword over the opponent's shield into his neck (Stocker and Davis 2017, 584).

In addition to the osteological evidence, information about preferred target areas can be gathered from warriors' depictions on Late Bronze Age Minoan and Mycenaean gem stones, such as the Pylos Combat Agate (Stocker and Davis 2017). These gem stones always depict a scene of one fighter stabbing over the opponent's shield into their neck (Figure 7.29; Molloy 2010, 411). The depictions frequently display a standard assembly of weapons for Aegean warriors consisting of sword, spear, and shield (ibid., 594). This highlights that different types of weapons were likely to meet in combat. Whilst these scenes clearly refer to Aegean contexts and depict an idealised image of a heroic warrior's final strike against the opponent, expressing the skill, courage, and strength of the victor, it is not impossible that such actions

did take place for real. Stabbing through the neck downwards into the rib cage would most likely result in the death of the opponent by piercing the heart or the lung, without necessarily impacting on the bones. Such a thrust would not leave any marks on the bones and, as such, cannot be proved archaeologically. The action appears unfeasible for fast-paced skirmishes between small groups (see below for a discussion about the types of combat encounters Bronze Age sword fighters were likely to experience), but could well have been executed as a final, dramatic move in a duel.

7.4.8 The development of fighting styles in Britain and Italy

The analysis of the location of combat marks on British and Italian swords (see Chapters 5.6.1 and 6.6.1) shows a clear development of fighting styles over the course of the Middle and Late/Recent Bronze Age. Beginning with the Penard Phase in Britain (1275-1140 cal BC), the earliest swords display an even distribution of marks along the entire cutting edge, without distinctive patterns or mark clusters which would be indicative of formalised fighting styles cultivated through repeated training and exercise. Acute stress situations, such as combat to the death, can result in a complete loss of cognitive and physical abilities. Being paralyzed by fear in a combat situation can potentially be lethal, but training and muscle memory through repetition can be used to overcome the shock and regain functionality under stress. Muscle memory ensures that actions are executed reliably under almost any circumstances (Molloy & Grossman 2007, 191-3), thus creating patterns of marks on the cutting edges. As swords and swordsmanship were a fairly new concept in the Penard Period, it is perhaps not unsurprising that no distinctive fighting styles had yet emerged. After over a century of sword fighting, however, the succeeding Wilburton Phase (1150-975 cal BC) sees not only a shift of mark location towards the tip, but also the emergence of dense clusters of marks, especially on the leaf-shaped swelling of the blade. Combined with a large number of outliers still present at this stage, this suggests that certain fighting styles had been introduced by this point. The Ewart Park Phase (925-800 cal BC) swords display a distinct clustering of marks, suggesting that, by this point, sophisticated fighting styles had developed, before a complete change in mark distribution occurred during the Bronze to Iron Age transition in Hallstatt C (800-600 cal BC). Bulges, which are evidence for binding and twisting motions that require training and practice, are present throughout the timeline.

In Italy, on the other hand, a slightly different picture emerges from the sword analysis. Here, bulges are completely absent from Middle Bronze Age (c. 1650-1300 cal BC) swords. The locations of other marks are similarly evenly spread as the marks on early British swords, and suggest that no major sword fighting traditions had developed yet. During the Recent Bronze Age (c. 1350-900 cal BC), however, the marks become noticeably concentrated within only

35 % of the blade around the swelling. Bulges now also occur frequently in the record. This demonstrates that a significant development and sophistication of sword fighting styles had occurred over the course of a few centuries.

Importantly, both Britain and Italy display similar developments in fighting styles over time. Starting with relatively scattered mark distributions, distinct concentrations, clusters and patterns emerged towards the end of the Bronze Age. When studying prehistoric combat styles, it is imperative to understand the length of time that passed. Time periods such as the Middle or Late Bronze Age are often regarded as one glimpse of time, and interpretations are made for the whole period, without considering how rapidly people, technologies, and traditions can change. Studying historical and modern military tactics highlights this rapid development. The use of mounted swordsmen, i.e. cavalry, has changed substantially over the course of several centuries between the Middle Ages and the First World War. Within merely a hundred years, the training and methods of the Royal Flying Corps have developed drastically to become the modern Royal Air Force. If studied from an archaeological perspective but with today's knowledge, one would not summarize these different tactics as the fighting styles of a single period. It is therefore crucial to consider the rapid development of humans and their methods when interpreting a prehistoric context.

7.4.9 Training and practice

Kristiansen has suggested that sword training was a regular occurrence in the Bronze Age. He further suggests that copper-alloy swords would have been too expensive for such purposes, and that wooden swords were used instead (2002, 325-6). As discussed above, the presence of bulges and clustered patterns of marks, as well as the development of combat styles over time, support his view. Whilst it is certainly possible that wooden swords were used for practising, there are some archaeological swords with such a large amount of wear marks and clusters (such as Sword IDs 16, 25, 56, 60, 65, 67, 95, 86 & 101) that their use in a training scenario can perhaps be suggested. The clear development of fighting styles as well as the importance of muscle memory outlined above, suggest that regular combat training was indeed very common. In turn, this poses the questions of how much training was necessary to be a successful swordfighter, who trained the fighters, and how this was integrated into everyday life. It has often been suggested that swords were the weapons of professional warriors (Kristiansen 2018, 28; 2002, 323; Kristiansen & Larsson 2005, 213; Randsborg 2006, 43; Harding 2007, 137; Vandkilde 2013, 40), male members of a Bronze Age social elite. This theory was generally founded in the presence of weaponry in graves, but has recently been challenged and the problems with this interpretation are becoming increasingly apparent (e.g. Thorpe 2013, 239; Brück & Fontijn 2013, 202). The notion of professional warriors further

suggests that the members of Bronze Age elites spent the majority of their time practising and engaging in combat, not unlike mediaeval knights and noblemen. However, one has to ask how much training is truly necessary to become a good swordsman, or indeed a good fighter with any type of weapon. Looking at modern “warriors”, i.e. soldiers or armed police officers, shows that the amount of time these people spend practising with their weapons ranges from only twice a year to around twice a month (Grossi 2011). Students of Asian martial arts are recommended to train between one and three hours, about three times per week (Kerr 2016). The members of the *Hotspur School of Defence*, some of whom are regarded as experts in Historical European Martial Arts and compete successfully in international tournaments, follow a similar training schedule of a few hours, twice or three times per week. It becomes apparent that it is not necessary to train all day, every day, to become a skilled and successful fighter, and it seems doubtful that a considerable amount of Bronze Age society members would have spent their time this way. Whilst combat training was undoubtedly necessary, the fact that fighting may only have had to be practised for a few hours per week further challenges the theory of professional warrior elites. Although it is possible that certain individuals acted as instructors, and therefore spent more time practising and teaching with weaponry, it can be suggested that, similar to contemporary football training, combat training could have started from an early age and was simply integrated into everyday life. Furthermore, fighting could have been conducted as a recreational activity, as was indeed the case with longsword and sword-and-buckler fighting during the Middle Ages (Clements 1998, 105).

7.4.10 Deliberate destruction

Deliberate destruction of copper-alloy objects is a regular occurrence in Bronze Age archaeology (Horn 2017a, 54; Sestieri et al. 2013, 157; Molloy 2010, 418; Bridgford 2000, 4). The destruction of swords can occur in different ways, from the bending and breaking of the hilt and blade to grinding or hammering of the cutting edges and melting. As such, the question whether we can differentiate between use-wear marks and marks originating from deliberate destruction is asked frequently. Before approaching this problem, we must clarify what deliberate destruction is, as the term is often used, yet rarely explained. In its most basic form, deliberate destruction is any action carried out which intends (or allows) the object to be turned into an unusable state. Here lies the first problem, as the definition of the usability of an object is highly objective. A pan with a broken handle can still be used for frying, yet it can no longer be picked up. Some people would therefore consider the pan as broken, whereas others would happily continue to use the object. Secondly, the definition of how an object is used can vary drastically. For example, the mechanism of an expensive watch can be broken

and no longer display the (right) time, yet the owner might still wear the watch for sentimental or display purposes. Although the watch is technically unusable, it may still retain important social uses as a memorabilia, status symbol, or display object. The second problem lies in the definition of deliberate. Is using an object in such a way that will knowingly damage it, such as deliberately seeking contact with the opponent's weapon, deliberate destruction? Or is it necessary to carry out a more specific, isolated action for it to be classified as deliberate? For the purpose of this research, the following parameters have been set: deliberate destruction is defined as any intentional action that renders a sword unsuitable for combat, excluding any damage that is sustained from fighting. The experiments have shown that combat-related wear marks are fairly standardized, and the same shapes, forms and sizes tend to occur repeatedly.

Figure 7.30 – Sword ID 94 from Pila del Brancon.

Figure 7.31 – Deformed hilt of Sword ID 94.

In some cases, such as the swords from Pila del Brancon (Sestieri et al. 2013; Chapter 6.5), the marks and deformations (the swords were majorly bent in several directions (Figure 7.30), burnt, the hilts were deformed or fractured (Figure 7.31), and the tips were distorted (Sestieri et al. 2013, 159-60)) are so significantly more pronounced that they cannot possibly be the result of combat. In fact, the swords have been treated in such a way that they became obviously unsuitable for combat.

Figure 7.32 – Sword ID 13 with clearly visible intentional damage. Image courtesy of the British Museum.

Figure 7.33 – Mark ID 85, “normal” round notch.

Figure 7.34 – Mark ID 280, significantly larger sharp notch.

Other swords, such as Sword ID 13 (Figure 7.32; see Chapter 5.5.3) display both “normal” (Figure 7.33) combat marks and significantly different marks (about five times larger than the normal marks; Figure 7.34) that have undoubtedly been created intentionally. It is not possible to propose a hard-and-fast rule to differentiate between the two. However, when studying an object as a whole (and with increased experience of object analysis), deliberate destruction becomes very apparent. If there is no indicator of deliberate destruction, the marks can reasonably be interpreted as resulting from use.

7.4.11 Handedness in Bronze Age sword fighters

The topic of handedness and its visibility in the wear marks of prehistoric tools has been discussed by others (e.g. Uomini 2009; Steele & Uomini 2005; Spenneman 1987) and a general right-hand dominance could be observed on human remains and prehistoric flint objects (Steele & Uomini 2005, 217). Both the wear analysis and combat experiments conducted for this research have shown that holding and using the sword in the same way creates an observable edge-dominance over time, which could be identified on over a quarter (31) of the 110 archaeological swords. From the wear marks it has not been possible, however, to determine which hand these swords were held in. The inhumations containing swords at Olmo di Nogara always place the weapons on top of the body, in many cases in direct alignment with an arm. Interestingly, there is an almost even side-related distribution, with 13 swords deposited on the left arm, 15 on the right, and twelve placed centrally on the body (Salzani 2005). Only one sword was positioned diagonally across the torso, with the hilt of the left shoulder and the tip over the right hip. Placing a sword on top of an arm is a very deliberate action carried out during the funerary process. A common notion amongst sword fighters is that through training and practice the sword becomes the extension of the arm (Yun 2009, 64), a concept which has been discussed for Bronze Age (albeit Aegean) swords at

length (see Malafouris 2008). Based on these considerations, it can perhaps be suggested that, in the case of the Olmo burials, the arm on which the blade was located was the sword arm. Burying an individual with a sword further implies a special relationship between the object and the deceased, such as the person being a particularly skilled fighter. With around 85 % right-handedness in any human population (Uomini 2009, 411), this almost equal split between left and right sword arms at Olmo seems surprising. A recent study by Loffing (2017), however, suggests that an above-average left-hand dominance can be observed amongst the top contestants in close-distance fighting disciplines. Contrary to common belief, this is not due to a perceived advantage related to the expectations of a right-handed combatant, but rooted in more complex, still undefined factors. Loffing further argues that the prevalence of successful left-handed prehistoric fighters has played an integral part in the survival of handedness polymorphism in humans (Loffing 2017, 1-4).

7.5 Bronze Age sword fighting in context: a warriors' society?

Following the interpretation of specific combat actions, changing combat styles and training and practice as per above, it is now time to assess their implications for our understanding of society and the exercise of sanctioned violence in the Bronze Age.

7.5.1 *The fighters and their tools of trade*

First of all, we must investigate the people who were actually using, and fighting with, swords and other weapons in the late 2nd millennium BC. Traditionally, those people were interpreted as aristocratic warrior elites, often called warrior chiefs, who held political and military power (Kristiansen 1999a, 177). These were identified by the presence of swords, axes, and gold ornaments in burial contexts. Popular theories suggest that these warrior elites lived a life dominated by certain warrior values and rituals, and combat training (ibid., 180-1). In contrast to the sword-bearing chiefly warriors stand the “ordinary” spearmen. A clear distinction between the two groups, the aristocratic warrior leaders and the rest, is made solely based on their equipment. These traditional interpretations, however, are no longer supported by the evidence found in recent literature and the results of this research. Instead, a different scenario of weapons bearers must be proposed. Immediately, two historical analogies spring to mind. In Viking Age society, *freemen* (i.e. all men who were not enslaved) had not only the right, but the duty to own and carry weapons. They also had the duty to train and practise their use in order to provide protection to themselves, their families, and their community (Roesdahl 1998, 142). Contrary to popular believe, during the Middle Ages, it was not just the knights and members of the feudal classes who owned and used swords. Instead, commoners were frequently armed and trained in the use of weapons, and had to employ these to protect

themselves as well as their communities (Clements 1998, 7). Even today, when looking at the people in the Middle East, a region that has been prone to violent conflicts to this day, it quickly becomes apparent that the vast majority of men own some sort of weapon for similar reasons. Reverting back to the Bronze Age, we can propose a similar system of weapon owners. It is reasonable to suggest that instead of designated warrior elites, virtually every able man (or woman, depending on the family circumstances and individual capabilities) possessed at least one weapon, and was trained in its use to offer protection to themselves and, if necessary, to their community. This is not to suggest that there was no system (or systems) of hierarchy or power amongst certain communities, only that these systems were not based on the ability to bear and use arms.

Having established who the weapon-bearing people were, we can now discuss how they would have been equipped. Harding suggests that from the Middle Bronze Age, the sword became the principal weapon with which warriors fought (Harding 2007, 137). Even when considering the word “warrior” in the newly defined context as any weapon-bearing person who engages in combat, rather than in its original definition as a member of an elite class, this statement is problematic. Whilst the wear marks on original swords demonstrate that these weapons were certainly used in combat, the sheer number of spears, the osteological data and the evidence of sword-spear interactions from wear analysis suggest that spears were likely the most common weapon at the time. It has often been suggested that swords were too expensive for common people, and thus only social elites could afford their ownership (e.g. Kristiansen 2002, 325). However, archaeometallurgists have long been claiming that the large number of swords from the archaeological record, as well as the amount of wear on them suggest that they were indeed rather common objects. The recent discovery of several swords in the Must Farm settlement context highlights the “normality” of these objects (Knight 2017), and suggests that they were by no means exclusively available to the rich and powerful. Reverting back to the *freemen* analogy, their equipment was often varied and consisted of several items including swords, spears, axes, shields and armour, and was solely dependent on personal preferences and what the individual could afford (Wolf 2004, 159). The same can perhaps be suggested for the Bronze Age. Although rare in the archaeological record, it can be suggested that wooden clubs, as found at Tollense Valley (Lidke et al. 2015, 338), were a common occurrence, as they provided a cheap and readily available alternative to metal weapons. The suggestion that within any group of people only the leader had a sword, whilst everybody else merely possessed a spear (Kristiansen 2018, 33; Sestieri et al. 2013; Randsborg 2006) no longer upholds. As discussed earlier, weapon training would have been a regular occurrence during Bronze Age life, and likely consisted of a few hours, a few

times a week, in addition to normal, everyday farming activities. The training could even have been conducted as an activity involving neighbours or the whole community. After all, it takes at least two people to practise fighting. Furthermore, fighting could have been conducted as a recreational activity, possibly including tournaments and prize plays. Studying Bronze Age metalworking traditions suggests that copper-alloy objects were produced at an almost industrial level (Huth 2000, 32-3). Whilst swords are generally similar in appearance, there is a great variety in length and individual features such as decorations. This could suggest that their manufacture was indeed commissioned, and that individual swords were custom-made in accordance with the physical properties and personal preferences of the commissioner.

7.5.2 *Combat in the wider context*

Having established who owned weapons and conducted fighting, we must now investigate the social dynamics of combat and violence in the Bronze Age. Again, different scenarios could be proposed. On the smallest scale, interpersonal and domestic violence were as likely to take place then as they are today. Individuals such as the Stillfried Girl (Breitinger 1976; see Chapter 2.3.3) could have been the victim of such small-scale, impromptu violence. The next level could be planned duelling between two individuals, both within or between different communities, to settle a feud or disagreement. A popular example of this is the fight between Hector and Achilles from the *Iliad*. Achilles challenged Hector to a fight to honourably avenge the death of his cousin Patroclus, killing Hector in the course of it (Murray & Wyatt 1924, 472-9, *Iliad* book 22 lines 295-360). Although poetry, similar scenarios of two fighting individuals are frequently depicted in Bronze Age rock art (Vandkilde 2013, 52). Both the depictions and the poetry hint at social practices that may have been common, and were certainly significant, in Bronze Age society. On a larger scale, warfare was likely conducted in small skirmishes involving tens, rather than hundreds, of individuals. There is evidence that raiding of hillforts or other settlements was the prevalent type of warfare in the Bronze Age (Harding 2007, 160). For this, small groups of people would invade another settlement to steal livestock and goods, or to kill the inhabitants in an act of revenge or frenzy. Evidence of defensive installations such as ramparts, ditches, and fences support this theory. For this to happen, individual communities would have to be organized and guided by one or several leaders (*ibid.*), although the nature of this leadership does not indicate a warrior elite status. Following the initial impact of the raid, it is likely that numerous individual fights then broke out rather than an organised battle. There is some limited evidence of large scale battles involving hundreds, if not thousands of combatants such as that at Tollense Valley (Curry

2016). However, these are not the norm, and their relevance and regularity in everyday Bronze Age life remains yet unknown.

Both size and organisation of these units have been theorized in the past. The number of weapons as well as the different levels of destruction of the contents of the Pila del Brancon hoard from Northern Italy have been used to interpret a hypothetical group of weapon bearers. A ratio of c. 50 spears to ten swords is interpreted as a group of ten sword bearers, each in charge of a group of five spear bearers, which would sum up to a hypothetical group size of 60 individuals. The article suggests that this number correlated to the size of a single kinship group of armed men. Furthermore, it is suggested that the physical appearance as well as the level of destruction of the swords could be directly related to the hierarchical organisation of the group. It is argued that the longest, heaviest, most elaborate sword was that of the main leader, and it was therefore treated with the greatest respect and destroyed the least (Sestieri et al. 2013., 162). This interpretation is problematic, as it implies that all weapons originated from only one group of people, with each individual bearing precisely one weapon. Archaeological evidence, however, suggests a different scenario. Rather than each person bearing just one weapon, Iberian Bronze Age rockart carvings show the equipment of warriors to always contain at least three items: a sword, a spear and a shield (Harrison 2004, 44). Some stelae further depict other items or pieces of weaponry, such as bow and arrow, armour, toiletry articles or chariots. This suggests that those involved in combat and warfare most likely possessed an array of weaponry rather than just one sword or one spear. Returning to Pila del Brancon, the interpretation further implies that the sword was a distinct status symbol for leaders, based solely on the different attention paid to their destruction. The difference in treatment, however, could equally be due to the sheer number of objects involved, making it highly likely that the destruction was carried out by more than one person. Varying degrees of destruction could therefore be the result of personal preferences or interpretations of the ritual. Similar interpretations of other hoards from Denmark (Randsborg 2006) and Hungary (Kristiansen 1999a) have been proposed. These range from complex hypothetical groups of around 40 warriors divided into eight platoons consisting of five soldiers and one commander, with an additional two senior commanders (Randsborg 2006, 42-3), to simple interpretations of sword-bearing officers and spear-bearing soldiers (Kristiansen 1999b, 103). Although tempting, such interpretations are highly problematic for several reasons. Firstly, evidence from hoards is not uniform, and thus Randsborg's interpretation can only ever be viable for that particular hoard (Harding 2007, 168). Secondly, as previously discussed, the interpretation of one sword-bearer in charge of several spear-bearers is not borne out by the evidence of weapon hoards. These units were not strictly

organised and equipped equally from an armoury as is the case with modern armies. Instead, it can be proposed that skirmishing units consisted of individuals in the low tens, armed with the weapons of their choice regardless of social status or ability, following the guidance of one or more individuals, depending on the circumstances.

7.6 Conclusion

Combining all the data gathered during the experiments and wear analysis with osteological data and the literature has allowed me to make original interpretations of Bronze Age sword fighting and combat. The experiments have shown that wear marks are likely the result of deliberate contacts with the opponent's blade to control their weapon. Combat does not consist of attacking and defending motions, instead offence and defence become interchangeable. Bronze Age sword fighters likely encountered spear-wielding opponents on a regular basis. In a wider context, swords should no longer be seen as the weapons exclusively belonging to an elite group of society. Instead, most able male members were likely in the possession of a variety of weaponry. Which particular weapons they owned was dependent on personal preference and availability rather than social status. The next chapter will provide a summary of the thesis, draw final conclusions and propose future research.

Chapter 8. Conclusion

8.1 Research problem

The renewed interest in Bronze Age combat and warfare since the late 1990s has triggered a wealth of research into this subject. Researching weaponry and other combat-related artefacts has been at the forefront of many studies, as these items preserve well in the archaeological record, resemble their well-known successors from the historical periods, and provide an opportunity to research poorly understood social practices from our prehistoric past. Amongst the array of weaponry available for the period, the study of swords has largely been favoured by scholars of the European Bronze Age. The interpretations of their uses are almost as numerous as their typology, and contrasting narratives have been put forward over time. For most of the 20th century, primarily theoretical studies were favoured; these suggested that swords were largely intended to be ceremonial or prestigious items, signifying wealth and social rank, but were used sparingly in combat, if at all (Mercer 2006, 147). Other studies, however, suggested that Bronze Age swords could be divided into either “slashing” or “thrusting” weapons, and were primarily used for either function based on their specific shapes (Kristiansen 2002, 320). The development of metalwork wear analysis studies, pioneered by Kienlin & Ottaway (1998), has further contributed to the debate, not only by proving that swords were frequently used in combat (e.g. Bridgford 2000), but also by showing that swords cannot simply be divided into “stab-only” or “cut-only” weapons (Molloy 2007; Horn 2017a, 58). Overall, these studies suggested that the individual sword fighter’s skills and training may be much more important than blade design in determining the uses of the weapons. Realizing that physical actions such as sword fighting could never be fully understood from an exclusively theoretical viewpoint, scholars such as Molloy (2007; 2008; 2009) have conducted combat experiments to test the capabilities of Bronze Age swords. Whilst producing interesting and indeed viable results, these tests lacked the repeatability and control required by truly scientific experiments. Furthermore, these experiments produced largely experiential results, which were mostly not supported by evidence from archaeological swords. In contrast stand wear analysis studies of Bronze Age swords (e.g. Bridgford, 2000; Horn 2013), which aim to interpret the marks resulting from clashing contacts with other weapons during combat. The problems with unrefined methodologies and insufficient terminologies aside (see Chapter 3.2.5 for discussion), these studies generally lacked reference to sophisticated reference data bases stemming from scientific combat experiments. It quickly transpired that the two different approaches were frequently employed in near complete ignorance of each other, which has led to an

inconclusive, and potentially misinformed narrative of how Bronze Age swords were used. Studying the literature, I realized that in order to understand how Bronze Age swords were really used, my research had to develop a metalwork wear analysis methodology that reliably recognized and recorded all traces of combat-related wear marks, and design scientific combat experiments to create a reference database to interpret the wear on original specimens. Combining the two approaches, and including information from osteological studies of violence-induced trauma, rock art depictions of combat, and further information from the literature, would allow me to propose informed interpretations about the specific actions Bronze Age sword fighters carried out, and thus identify any underlying combat styles that had emerged. For the first time, these interpretations would be grounded in scientific evidence from field experiments and wear analysis. In a second step, these data would allow me to propose original interpretations about the manifestation of sword fighting and combat in everyday life, and provide a new interpretation of the social role of weapon-bearing individuals at the time. Furthermore, my research has undertaken a previously unprecedented comparative approach between British and Italian swords, to counter the generalization of previous studies that interpreted combat in the European Bronze Age as a whole, and to understand the similarities and differences between individual, regional combat styles. The next section will address the specific aims and objectives identified for my research, outline how they were met, and recap the results.

8.1.1 Aim 1, results and interpretations

The first aim was to “Understand how Bronze Age sword combat was conducted and identify any specific (regional) combat styles”. To meet this aim, five significant objectives were identified. Firstly, an extensive review of osteological studies concerning violence-induced trauma during the European Bronze Age was undertaken (Chapter 2). The review has revealed that the neck and abdomen were likely the preferred target areas for sword and spear fighters. Unlike the skull or chest, where the large presence of underlying bone structures limits the effects of strikes or thrusts, and cause the potential risk of damaging the weapon, damaging the soft tissue of the abdomen which contains vital organs and arteries is comparatively easy and is likely fatal or, at the very least, severely incapacitating. Similarly, targeting the opponent’s neck is likely to damage vital arteries, the windpipe or the spine, all of which can prove fatal or severely incapacitating if injured. Unsurprisingly, the skull appears to be the main target area for blunt force trauma, as such attacks are most effective when aimed at the opponent’s head. Blunt attacks to other body parts are capable of fracturing bones, but are extremely unlikely to prove fatal, or even incapacitating.

The second objective was to conduct scientific combat experiments to create a reference collection of wear marks. This would also help me to gain a better understanding of sword fighting. The main aim was to recreate the types of marks that can be found on original Bronze Age swords. To achieve this, it was imperative to design an experiment that was controlled and repeatable, and allowed for precise recording of individual marks and their related actions. Furthermore, the setup had to resemble real combat as closely as possible. In the end, two different experimental approaches were designed. The first one (Chapter 3) consisted of an extensive protocol of offensive strikes and defensive parries, created based on my own sword fighting experience. These strikes and parries were carried out individually, and the swords were examined closely after each action. It was thus possible to directly link different marks with their specific actions. The experiment was hugely successful. It was possible to create a reference database that linked a number of different marks to specific combat actions. Most strikingly, the experiment revealed that parries with the flat of the sword are likely to result in severe bending of the blade, thus rendering the sword useless. Such actions were commonly carried out during the mediaeval period to preserve the cutting edge (Clements 1998, 211), and scholars of prehistoric combat have previously assumed that this was also the case during the Bronze Age (e.g. Mödlinger 2011, 164). My experiments, however, have demonstrated for the first time that such an action would have been avoided at all cost, as the risk of severely damaging the sword was great. Moreover, the tests have produced conclusive evidence for sword vs. spear combat, which creates distinctively unique marks that are frequently seen on the archaeological swords. Despite the excellent results from this experiment, the methodology was not without problems. The main criticism was that the fight was broken down into individual actions. At the time, this was deemed necessary to assure correct recording and cross-referencing of marks with their specific actions. This approach, however, lacked the dynamics of real combat. Another methodological flaw was that every action was designed to strike the opponent's blade, whereas in a real swordfight the opponent's body would obviously be the primary target. Furthermore, all strikes were carried out with full force, which led to significantly deeper and more pronounced marks than those usually seen on original Bronze Age swords. Overall, it was felt that more could be learned from a second set of experiments with a revised methodology. The second experimental methodology (Chapter 4) was designed to record real combat whilst still being able to accurately link individual wear marks with their respective actions. In order to create an "actualistic" experiment, and to avoid a simple repeat of the first set of tests, it was decided to test the hypothesis of interpreting prehistoric combat through the use of a historical fighting manual. Working closely with an internationally renowned expert

on Historical European Martial Arts, we identified a 15th century manuscript that describes combat with swords and shields similar to those available during the Bronze Age. This manuscript, known as *Commentary by Andre Lignitzer on Sword and Buckler* in *Codex 44.A.8* by Peter von Danzig (Farrell 2012), divides the basics of sword and shield fighting into six short plays, five of which were deemed suitable for the experiment. Each play consists of only a few sword contacts, thus allowing to match individual marks with their respective actions whilst conducting actual fighting. The experiment was another huge success and has produced invaluable results. First and foremost stands the realization that combat is not simply divided into offensive and defensive motions, but that attack and defence become interchangeable. This is highly significant, as it negates previously proposed theories about offensive and defensive sections on sword blades (e.g. Kristiansen 2002, 323; Molloy 2011, 75), and suggests that there is also no differentiation between offensive or defensive marks. The experiments have also shown that bulges, a previously unexplained type of mark, is the direct result of binding and twisting, an action that deliberately seeks contact with the opponent's blade to control their weapon. This led to the second ground-breaking realization, that wear marks are by no means the result of "accidental" contact (Horn 2013, 40; Molloy 2007, 109; 2011, 75). Instead, Bronze Age sword fighters would quite happily accept a small amount of "damage" to their cutting edges when they were fighting an opponent. Moreover, the actualistic experiment has increased the reference database of experimental combat marks, and has shown that different ways of holding the sword have a considerable impact on the handling, balance, and control of the weapon.

The third objective was to undertake metalwork wear analysis on a sample of British and Italian Bronze Age swords. Having studied the literature, it transpired that previous wear analysis studies were often methodologically problematic, summarised a range of different marks under generalized terms (e.g. Kienlin & Ottaway 1988; Bridgford 2000; Kristiansen 2002; Molloy 2011; Horn 2013), or did not examine objects with enough detail (e.g. Kristiansen 2002; O'Flaherty 2007; O'Flaherty et al. 2011). To conduct meaningful wear analysis, however, I deemed it imperative to measure and record the objects accurately and in detail, and to microscopically examine and record all wear marks. A list of wear marks and definitions, partially informed by the literature but mostly based on archaeological artefacts, was created to an unprecedented amount of detail. As such, at least 23 different types of wear marks could be identified to date. Equipped with a stereomicroscope, an attachable camera to take micrographs, recording equipment and a digital database, I travelled to various museums in Britain and Italy to analyse 110 Middle and Late/Recent Bronze Age swords. In total, over 2300 combat-related wear marks could be identified, photographed, and recorded in the

database. The analysis provided the archaeological evidence to make informed interpretations about Bronze Age sword fighting.

The fourth objective was to compare all gathered data, from the two different combat experiments, the metalwork wear analysis of British and Italian swords, and the review of the osteological data, to make original interpretations of Bronze Age sword fighting. Furthermore, the data was used to identify any specific combat styles. All marks recreated during the experiments resemble those marks present on original Bronze Age swords. The most commonly occurring marks are indentations, sharp and round notches, various types of grazes, and bulges. Studying the marks of each individual sword has shown that these weapons were subject to extremely varied degrees of use, from none or at most one combat encounter, to heavily marked swords that were used extensively and could have served as training weapons. It transpired that indentations and wide-angled notches, both of which are evidence of clashing contacts with spears, occur frequently. Sword vs. spear combat must therefore have taken place on a regular basis. Bulges, which indicate binding and twisting motions to control the opponent's blade, also occur regularly. Identifying specific combat styles has proved tricky. Statistical analysis of the locations of different types of wear marks has shown that different fighting styles did in fact exist, and that they changed over time (see Chapters 5.6 and 6.6). Whilst the marks on earlier swords are generally distributed fairly evenly along almost the entire length of the cutting edges, during the progress of the Middle and Late/Recent Bronze Age, these marks tend to cluster increasingly tightly around the characteristic leaf-shaped swelling c. one third blade-length from the tip. Whilst it is sometimes possible to determine which exact actions an individual sword has been used for, in most cases only general inferences about the different fighting styles can be made. Besides the styles becoming more sophisticated over time, that is until a sudden change with the emergence of the Early Iron Age, they likely comprised some key features. The swords would have been held with a variety of grips, providing different balance and control of the weapons, depending on situation and personal preference. Fighting would have been conducted against a number of different weapons, including swords, spears, and shields. Deliberate contact with the opponent's blade was often sought to control their weapon, thus accepting small amounts of wear forming on the cutting edge. Combat actions were not strictly divided into offensive and defensive motions, but instead comprised interchangeable actions which always seek to attack the opponent, or at the very least prime the blade for the next attack. Opposing weapons would not deliberately have been parried with the flat of the sword, as this would damage the weapon severely. Sword IDs 11, 59, 71 and 105, however, display the same bend and associated striation pattern resulting from a flat parry as recreated during the experiment,

suggesting that such actions did occur infrequently though. They could be the result of an accidental contact, or a last-resort effort to save the combatant's own life. Especially the later swords, which display a clustering of marks around the swelling of the sword, were likely used in a cut-and-draw fashion, as suggested by Molloy (2007, 100-1). Finally, sword fighters likely made use of a shield, made of organic material or copper-alloy, to protect themselves, especially their sword hand, and to use offensively as a secondary weapon.

The fifth objective was to identify differences between the fighting styles of Britain and Italy. Comparing the wear analysis data, it transpired that the types of marks present on the swords from both regions are identical in shape. Italian marks, however, have a tendency to be slightly smaller in dimension. This could be due to different alloy compositions (Gutiérrez-Sáez & Martín-Lerma 2015, 175) or different levels of work-hardening (Wang, in prep.). Comparing the statistical analysis that displays the development of fighting styles over time shows that a similar development can be observed in both regions. The major difference is the presence of bulges, which occurred on British swords from all four metalworking phases analysed for this research. In Italy, on the other hand, bulges exclusively occurred on Recent Bronze Age swords, thus indicating that binding and twisting motions played no part in the fighting styles of the Italian Middle Bronze Age. On a whole, however, the fighting styles in Britain and Italy would have been very similar.

8.1.2 Aim 2, results and interpretations

The second aim was to understand the role of combat and warfare in Bronze Age life. This was to be achieved through three different objectives. The first objective was to combine the new data created during this research with information from the existing literature to propose new and original interpretations about the combatants, and their role within society. Although the literature frequently proposes a scenario of professional, elite warriors, who were the only members of society to bear swords (e.g. Kristiansen 1999a, 117; Horn & Kristiansen 2018, 4), I propose an alternative interpretation. Combining the new evidence with historical analogies, it can be suggested that, similar to the Viking's *freemen* (Roesdahl 1998, 142), all able-bodied men, or maybe women, had the right, and perhaps duty, to bear arms, in order to protect themselves, their family, and the wider community. This would involve regular practice and training, which could even have occurred as a communal activity. These armed individuals would likely possess a number of different weapons, including sword, spear, and shield, depending on their personal preferences and availability rather than social status. The "normality" of swords has recently been highlighted by the discovery of several swords in the Must Farm settlement context (Knight 2017).

The second objective was to interpret how combat was integrated into everyday life. As mentioned above, being able to fight effectively, and ultimately survive, with any type of weapon requires training and practice. Contrary to the image of the professional warrior, who would spend the majority of their time practising and fighting, the amount of training required to become a good combatant is less than one often assumes. Considering the three training sessions a week recommended to students of Asian martial arts (Kerr 2016), and the at most two-weekly shooting practice of American police officers (Grossi 2011), suggests that a few hours of training each week were sufficient enough to turn people into skilful combatants. Similar to the mediaeval period (Clements 1998, 105), (sword) fighting could have established itself as a recreational activity.

The third objective was to propose a revised interpretation of social structure and military organisation amongst Bronze Age societies. As mentioned above, contrary to some scholars' beliefs, social status would not have been based on the ability to bear arms. Instead, weaponry may have been a common occurrence in most households, and their use was likely practised in a communal environment. Combat itself could have taken place on different levels. Small-scale interpersonal and domestic violence were as likely to take place then as they are today. Planned duels between two individuals could have occurred to settle a disagreement or a feud. Combat on a larger scale was likely conducted in small group skirmishes, consisting of tens of people (Harding 2007, 60). Large scale battles involving hundreds, or even thousands, of combatants were rare, but evidence from the Tollense Valley (e.g. Jantzen et al. 2011) suggests that they did occur occasionally.

8.2 Limitations of the research

My experimental methodologies and metalwork wear analysis approach have proven extremely successful, and significant, original results could be achieved. However, as is the case with any study, my research is not without its limitations. I was also able to identify specific results that my research *was not* able to achieve. The main limitations lie most likely within the experiments (see Chapters 3.6 and 4.6 for in-depth discussion), or within the notion of combat experiments itself. Recreating prehistoric fighting styles from a 21st century perspective will always bear its own problems, as any interpretations we make will necessarily be influenced by our very own, modern ideas. Any meaningful experiments researching the use of prehistoric objects are based on the assumption that the object would have been used in a similar manner through the ages. As such, when experimenting with axes, we fell trees and chop wood using the Bronze Age axe in a similar way as a modern axe. The problem with weapons and the complex embodied knowledge their use entails, however, is

that one cannot follow this assumption – hence the creation of the two different experiments, both of which are imperfect in their own right, and neither fully reflect the realities of Bronze Age combat. By combining the different approaches, however, working with different individuals from various backgrounds, and keeping an open mind, it is possible to create meaningful results. Conducting the experiments with replica weapons is also not entirely unproblematic, as the quality of the replica has a direct effect on the outcome. This could be seen with Coles’s shield experiments (1962), which were made of unauthentic material, and produced arguably false results (see Molloy 2009; Chapter 3.4). As the knowledge of prehistoric manufacturing techniques is lost, the quality of replicas must be assessed and accounted for. The single cycle of work-hardening, that was used for the manufacture of the replica swords used for this research, turned out to have limited influence on the hardness of the cutting edges (Wang, in prep.). Nevertheless, the replica marks are identical with those found on original swords, albeit deeper, thus still making them a reliable source for reference. Conducting combat in such a way that the replica wear marks can be accurately recorded has proven difficult, and it was deemed necessary to break the combat into individual actions. As this was perceived to be an unrealistic representation of combat, a different experimental methodology was developed, which eventually allowed me to conduct and record actual fighting in an experimental manner.

One of the main aims of this research was to identify different combat styles. The wear marks recorded on the original swords suggest that combat styles did exist, and that they changed over time. The combat experiments made it possible to link certain types of marks to specific combat actions. With the available data, however, it was not possible to fully identify all aspects of any individual combat style. Further research is needed to gain a fuller understanding of the different styles. Finally, the actualistic combat experiments have shown that edge dominance is the result of a (single) owner, who frequently held the sword in the same way (Chapter 4.4). In turn, this suggests that handedness has an effect on the creation of wear marks, as the wear on a sword that was always wielded with the right hand will likely display a different pattern of marks than that of a left-handed fighter. Whilst the same edge dominance could be identified on over a quarter of the original specimens, it was not possible to detect any distinctly right or left-handed patterns on the prehistoric swords.

8.3 Open problems/future research

As with the completion of any piece of research, working on the subject of Bronze Age sword fighting and combat has left some open problems and given ideas for future research. Whilst the combat experiments conducted for my research can safely be regarded as extensive, it

feels like they have only just started to scratch the surface. As Brandherm stated, only comprehensive experimental tests will allow us to form a definitive narrative of the specifics of Bronze Age combat (2011, 24-5). My research has shown that swords frequently encountered other weaponry, including spears and shields. There are also still a number of unexplained wear marks. Further experiments, if possible designed around real combat, involving various weapons combinations should be conducted, to create a reference database for *all* combat-related wear marks, and to gain an even better understanding of the reality of Bronze Age combat. Considering the likely changes occurring in combat styles during the Late Bronze to Early Iron Age transition phase in Hallstatt C (800-600 cal BC), and the emergence of iron weaponry during that phase, calls for an experimental study involving copper-alloy and iron weapons, to see whether a change in material coincides with different wear marks. Although not considered to be a common occurrence, the possibility of equestrian combat, or fighting from horseback, should also be considered. Whilst there is some evidence of horses in a combat-related context (e.g. at Tollense Valley (Curry 2016)), the general notion is that wide-spread use of horses in combat did not commence until the beginning of the Iron Age (Harding 2007, 174). However, with regards to the newest evidence from Bronze Age contexts, this theory might have to be revisited and also provides a basis for future experiments.

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Appendix B

Interview transcription for actualistic experiments. Conducted on 24. January 2018.

Interviewee:

- a. Name: Robert Brooks
- b. Age: 46 years old.
- c. How long have you been practising HEMA?

I have been practising HEMA since 1994. HEMA came about as an extension of sport fencing. I was a sport fencer specialising in sabre fencing from 1987 when I was 15 years old. Before that I started with karate as a kid (red belt). Then I did sport fencing until about 1994. HEMA didn't exist when we started. We actually pioneered or partially pioneered the initial movement in the early 1990s to look at the reconstruction of historical fencing methods. I think at the time in '94 we established what was called the Dawn Duellists Society at Napier University (Edinburgh). At that time, I believe there were maybe less than half a dozen clubs in the world who came from a number of different backgrounds whereas we largely formed from a sports fencing background. Other groups came from a re-enactment background and in the USA they came from what's known as Society for Creative Enactors (SCE). It really stemmed from the discovery and circulation of some fighting manuals which incidentally at that point had no translations to modern English. As far as we can gather the fight manuals began to circulate within the re-enactment community and the SCE. Arguably the earliest manuscript that was actually made and became common knowledge for the tiny number of people who were looking into these things was *Fiore Dei libris Flos Duellatorum*, and really there are two people who stand out as being the catalysts for the early community in HEMA terms. There are others in academic terms who I can name who were doing the *Fechtbuecher* research in Germany in the 1980s. Hans Peter Hills was one of them. In terms of the proto-HEMA community, Patrick Cugliese, an American-Italian, and Steve Higg. In the UK we know there was a chap called Terry Brown who was arguably the godfather of historical fencing on the British Isles, having done extensive research on English martial arts traditions. There were a number of people who made a formative venture into looking for all the methods, and for some reason it spread and people like myself, sport fencers, and history students. I can't even remember who was first to get wind but it created its own dynamic and managed to creep into these circles. The more manuscripts emerged the more desire there was to find more and so obviously with the community growing like that you then extend your list of contacts, and eventually you end up with people in contact with research fellows and university environments and with access to libraries and special connections. The community

started to grow from this point. It sprang up within about three or four years in several different locations. We weren't aware of the other groups because it was pre-internet. It was generally through meeting people in the sports fencing field, and in the late 1990s in the re-enactment field, that we learnt about the other groups. I was involved in a movement as the interest in historical fencing grew in the late 1990s to set up a British Federation, which we did in 1997. I acted as the secretary to the British Federation, being a journalist they wanted me for my short hand, so I was secretary from 1997-2004. Then in 2013 I was elected president.

[BECAUSE OF THE CONTEMPORARY YET INDEPENDENT DEVELOPMENT OF HEMA GROUPS, WAS THERE ANYTHING IN THE MEDIA OR WITHIN SOCIETY THAT MIGHT HAVE TRIGGERED THIS DEVELOPMENT? WAS THERE A SUDDEN INCREASE IN FENCING?] I don't think there was. Fencing still remains a niche activity in terms of interest. Interestingly, we have a good idea of the growth of the HEMA community. We can see that during the mid to late 1990s the internet was absolutely fundamental in putting people into touch. The earliest website dedicated to historical fencing was created by John Clines in the US who was in Texas at the time. By that point another interesting thing that happened was, being in the university environment at Napier, we had foreign students who were fencers and came to the fencing classes, only to find that there was a proto-HEMA scene, and then took that back to their own countries. So we have an example where myself and the club leader at Napier, Paul McDonald, were arguably the first in the world to look at the *Dusack* fencing of Joachim Mayer from this 1570 manuscript, where these very unusual training swords, they were made of wood and look like a banana shape. We had a student who came from the US called Jared Curby who is now one of the leading event organisers for historical fencing in the US, who came to Napier and joined our club, learned some *Dusack* and actually introduced the *Dusack* into the US and now we have a proliferation of *Dusack* clubs in the US, all because of one guy coming to the right place at the right time. And in return we have people saying "what on Earth is this?". There has pretty much the same thing happened in Italy, roundabout 1997 or '98. The Italians, who still have a living fencing heritage, looked at us with horror and said "what is this thing?" and it is now widespread across Europe as one of the most popular forms of historic fencing, in terms of being very accessible with the weapons being made of wood. These are a couple of examples of how the field spread.

In the beginning you have enthusiastic amateurs, but over time we've seen some fantastic academic research and now we're able to piece together entire biographies of men whose life

stories were forgotten, hundreds of years ago and time lost in history. There was a research interest in historical fencing at the end of the 19th century in Britain, but it was very short lived. Then probably driven by ex-military men, who were still instructed in the use of the sword, the like of Sir Richard Burton, Aggerton Castle, Sir Alfred Hutton, who were arguably the pioneers of HEMA, because they left books behind which again formed part of our library as we were building knowledge on the subject. There are multiple threads that come into this but at the same time we really did the first serious groundwork and in fact we revive things that hadn't been in some cases practiced for 500 years, which is the next best thing to having a time machine. HEMA really is the art of turning words, and in some cases illustrations, arguably the best manuscripts are the non-illustrated because they have more text, but it's the art of turning words into physical actions. It's very, very difficult, but if you know certain martial parameters [it is possible]. Next years marks my 25th anniversary in HEMA, a quarter of a century given to this study, purely as a labour of love for the first 18 years. Since I turned it into a profession in 2012, things got serious at that point. We can say that even with some of the more obscure manuscripts we would estimate that we are right on about 90-95% because we constantly have multiple peer review going on. You have people who you've never met in Australia or America who are studying the same manuscripts, and on those rare occasion that you meet up you cross reference and they come to the same conclusion. Some of the instructions are so obscure that even coming to a similar conclusion is generally an arrow in the right direction. We now have a worldwide HEMA scholarship award where there are actually prizes for academic scholarship, which are given by the key manufacturers, the sword makers, the authors, and I served on the jury of the first one. We have to sift through a lot of papers and see, much like an actual academic peer review, whether the material is good. That's the last 25 years in a nutshell.

[IS THERE A CONTINUOUS INCREASE VISIBLE OVER THE LAST 15 YEARS?] There is. I set my school up in 2003, so I had roughly 9 years of research and practicing. I'm very much a traditionalist so I like to do things properly, so I thought of it much like the apprentice journey and master journey, and that brings me into conflict today with some people who think they can be an instructor after six months of even hearing of HEMA. I set it up in 2003 with six of us in the school; we're now 70. We started with one class a fortnight, we're now four classes a week. That really gives an idea of just how popular it has become. I use popular as a relative term, because in the grand scheme of things it's minute. Within its own parameters it has grown massively. Similar growth has been experienced in other parts of the UK and Europe. We've seen some of the older clubs, by older I say any associations past the 15-year mark. If there wasn't the appetite for it, they definitely would have failed. Along with

that we've seen the emergence of lots and lots of new groups. I can't remember how many groups there are in the UK at the moment, the British Federation at the moment has about 26 under its umbrella, but that's not massively representative mainly because the British Federation has a particular set of standards that it adheres to. One key factor that I think certainly played a part in the last five years is what's being referred to as the Game of Thrones effect. We saw a boom after Lord of the Rings. With the hobbit as well. But GoT has particularly driven a lot of new people to take up what's being referred to as real sword fighting. Which to me means a completely different thing, but in terms of HEMA. The other thing is a vast increase in the representation of women. Lots and lots of women doing HEMA. At one point we hit our Zenith in 2014, roughly 40% of our members were female. We also find that the attrition rate for losing students is quite slow, but we tend to attract people who want to invest time. One thing that is happening at the moment, that's been slowly diverging over the last five or six years, is a split, and it's quite clear now, between those who want to focus more on the sporting side, entering tournaments and winning medals, and the academic side who want to research, understand and revive and preserve the martial traditions of Europe. One of the big gains in that period has been the number of tournaments. The number of tournament fencers is quite extraordinary. We now have major tournaments being held, a good example is swordfish, which is held in Sweden, regularly getting 150-160 competitors across multiple disciplines. Mediaeval longsword still seems to be the most popular, but we're talking about everything from rapier fencing, small sword, highland broadsword, sabre fencing, *messer*, poleaxes. The pole weapons don't seem to have made as big an impact, but bladed weapons certainly have. There is a growing interest in folk wrestling, the wrestling styles that we find in some of the manuscripts both in German and Italian traditions. It's ever evolving. At the moment the tournament organisers set the rules. There's not one governing organisation. At the moment there is actually a move which started in Scotland of all places, I say that with Scotland being one of the places where HEMA really took off at first in the British Isles, but again in Scotland there was a move started there that's now gathered pace in England, to have the government recognise HEMA as a sport. There is some resistance from the martial arts side who are saying "we don't want this recognised as a sport because of the connotations of it becoming like sports fencing". Or much the same as jujitsu developing into judo, where the cultural side and the martial side takes a second place to gaming in the rules and winning medals. There is some movement towards giving it a status where there could be some kind of unification. I think, like with everything there are always arguments of who is going to run because you can't please everybody. So that's really where it's at at the moment. It's taken 25 years to get to this point. I think one of the strengths of the HEMA community is

that there is diversity within the community because it's very much a pitch-in attitude. There's a lot of feeding into the community from lots of directions that wouldn't necessarily exist if there was a stratified regulated approach. Somebody can come in from the left field and introduce something completely out of the blue, but all of the sudden it changes everything. The fact that it's developed embryonically allows us to do things like the experiments that we did because it encourages out of the box thinking and a very hands-on practical approach to things. The final part of it is that in a sense the HEMA community made the academic community sit up and take notice because when we even look back at the textbooks from 30, 40 years ago, there are so many assumptions made in them by people who have arguably never handled a sword with anything like a martial mindset. They can handle the sword as an object and not actually understand it. It's taken "enthusiastic amateurs" to take up the reins. Curiously it seems to have developed in tandem to the idea of experimental archaeology. Again, that's a fairly newly emerging field. We see that the HEMA community arguably have been engaged in experimental archaeology, which hasn't really had a final objective in sight, whereas we're seeing experimental archaeology like we've done, which is looking to actually match up with evidence that we find. Two very different approaches. One is "let's see what we find out" and the other one is "whether we can actually make it concur with the evidence from different fields". [.....] As with the bronze sword experiment, where do you start?

d. What got you into HEMA (briefly)?

See above.

e. How would you assess your own HEMA knowledge, experience and expertise?

My HEMA knowledge in terms of the source material that I've chosen to focus on is expert. I know the manuscripts so well that I can recite passages from them. But more importantly, I can understand that the context that they're written in often lead to a deeper conclusion than you would get if you didn't know the subject. There are certain areas of HEMA that I would say my knowledge is non-existent. I've been lucky to have been involved in it for so long that I've practically tried everything there is to try. But in terms of things for example like rapier fencing from Italy from the 16th century, I have a passable knowledge, and I can demonstrate it, but if somebody asked me to quote from Giganti.. you know... My area specifically is manuscripts from 1389 and ending in 1487. They span German language and Italian. They are the ones I work from. I thought it was important when I was teaching it to keep what I was teaching contemporaneous, because we find that even with a particular weapon such as the

long sword, once the context of the longsword in society changes, from say the earliest longsword manuscript we have from 1389, to one of the later manuscripts for example Meier 1570, the longsword at that point is used more in a sporting context, as an expression of manly athleticism. We have the Fechtschule, which is not actually a school but gatherings of fencer to fight for prizes, where there are very strict rules of what you can do, what you're allowed to do, you can't thrust, you can strike the hands, you can only strike with the flat of the weapon. Even looking at a single weapon we even see the form of the weapon changes considerably between for example swords that we see in the period that we're interested in that could be termed lance longswords, which have distinct edge profile and distinctly tapering points, to the Federschwert of the 16th century, which is designed with no edges and no point. It has a spatulated tip and a broad shield, what the Italians would call a ricasso, at the head of the blade just below the crossguard, which the Germans refer to as the Schild. The Schild's designed to protect the thumb, which is placed flat on the flat of the blade. Even the use of the longsword and the use of the Federschwert, there are distinct differences between how the Federschwert was used and how a longsword in actual combat was used. [THAT DEVELOPMENT WAS REALLY JUST OVER A FEW CENTURIES] It is. What I often say to my students: "An analogy could be, it would be like training British army infantry soldiers today using Victorian methods. It's the same time frame. There is roughly a hundred and ninety years between the MS3227A, often referred to as the *Nuremberg Hausbuch*, from 1389 and Meier's work in 1570, so roughly about 190 years, so we could arguably use that as an analogy". [WE ALWAYS ASSUME THAT THINGS DON'T CHANGE QUICKLY, BUT THINGS CAN CHANGE DRASTICALLY OVER A SHORT PERIOD OF TIME] Or for example a fighter pilot today being taught in the style of the royal flying corps from 1970, and that's even more recent. In terms of warfare and the development of warfare, also the development of warlike activities within a social context, you find for example with the neo-classicism, which arrives in Germany with the neo-renaissance, even the illustrations in the manuscript radically changed, because now there was an aesthetic quality to the human body, whereas if you look at the fight manuscripts of the 15th century, particularly of the early part of the 15th century, in the illustrations the men are all pot-bellied, they've got skinny legs. There wasn't any reference in there to "this helps keep your body beautiful and makes you ripped". But when you look at Meier, rippling muscles, bulging calves, you know, and some even say at this point that fencing is an expression of manliness, but in an aesthetic way rather than in a warlike aggressive manner. This is one of the importance with HEMA, that I think a lot of the good scholar have heavily looked into the context of the societies to which the arts belong, so you see society actually changing attitudes as well. You see things that normally

would be preserved for the military classes in 16th century Germany, becoming a kind of blowing off steam or the *Buerger* class, who were the middle-class merchants who decided that they wanted to blow some steam on a Saturday afternoon by hitting each other with dusacks. Certainly in Germany in the earlier period that we stud, and this is something I'm very, very interested in, I'm made a point in researching and trying to understand more, is the distinction, the delineation between the martial classes, so the *Edelfrei*, free noblemen, from the bottom end of the aristocratic rank, up to the knights, the kings, the princes. The delineation between that strata of society, because we know now, that there is a very strong culture of martial activity within the lowest classes of society. We knew of the wrestling culture in Germany which really lights it up. When we look at the *messer* culture within German society in the 14th and 15th centuries, that there is a recognisable pattern of fighting style in that period. And then it becomes codified and it finds its way into fight manuscripts but only after a certain period. You tend to find that the biggest *messer* work from 1482, there's two version, 1478 and 1482, by a German priest, so not a member of the aristocracy but a priest called Johannes Lechkuechner, who writes two versions of the manuscript, and he puts the *messer* in the context of the traditional Johannes Lichtenauer, the we believe 14th century grandmaster of fencing who spawned a series of masters. We have a roll of masters recorded in a manuscript from 1460, but we find that before Lechkuechner, before 1478, all of the *messer* manuscripts are very, very simple. And then all of the sudden we've got Lechkuechner. 600 pages of *messer*, which is a phenomenal amount of data. Before Lechkuechner very little. You tend to find that in some manuscripts, it makes maybe three for you. Glasgow manuscript, for example you find it's twentyfive verse, twentyfive rector, twentysix verse, and that's it. That's the *messer*, eleven items on how we use the *messer*. Because we're dealing with a system for peasant fencing it has to be quickly taught, easily remembered and then you improvise the rest. But curiously it contains information which is relevant again to the Bronze Age study of how you deal with certain situations. Glasgow contains for example two emergency stands, for example what to do in an emergency, how to fight a man in armour, how to grabble and how to disarm them, all contained within eleven plays, which is pretty incredible really the way it's written. But that brings us directly to the next question which is Lignitzer. [HOW WOULD YOU ASSESS YOURSELF IN TERMS OF THE SPORTING SIDE?] Yhe actual fencing is critically important. Providing that the manuscripts, or what we find in the manuscripts, is adhered to. Once you start throwing out the advice that, if you look at Lichtenauer, and the lessons that Lichtenauer gives via his students who record Lichtenauer's words, you'll find that once you throw out the advice in a sporting context it doesn't really matter. Because sporting eventually boils down to

athleticism, reflexes, a lack of risk. In a real fight this completely changes. This is why the fidelity of the manuscripts and maintaining that is really important for me personally. The only way we can understand what the manuscripts are telling us is right is a pressure test. So pressure testing in a free and open environment is important because you need to know whether you can perform this under stress. When you have the adrenal dock, when there is an element of risk. You still have to take all the necessary precautions of proper fencing mask, jackets etc. The sporting side, if it's done properly, it has its merits, and a lot of my students enter tournaments and do very well in them, but the approach is important. Once you forgo the approach and win at all costs, and ignore the advice the manuscripts give, and there is one critical example of this that I'm constantly flagging up with those who are more tournament orientated, is: the first lesson Lichtenauer gives us is if you are right handed, strive to enter the combat with your left foot forwards, because if you do not pass behind your strive with your right foot, that's a step forwards with your right foot, after you've initiated the motion of the strike, it is a false, an incorrect strike. And we know this from pressure testing that if you don't do this the geometry is wrong. We can read in many manuscripts from that period that fencing is born of time and distance and geometry. My argument, and I constantly see it in the sporting side of HEMA, if you watch any youtube videos of tournaments, you will see them constantly fencing right foot forwards, and this is against the first lesson. My argument is, if you can't adhere to the first lesson Lichtenauer gives, why bother with the rest? That's my feeling on the sporting side. I think it's very important, but I think we need to be honest with ourselves. It needs to be less about the ego and about medals and more about the validation of the systems that we're reporting to spend [...time on]. I tend to be very methodical. Certainly, on the sporting side it's human nature that people want to achieve things quickly. But if we look at the context of the arts that we're studying from the 14th and 15th centuries, the military classes would arguably spend the best part of their childhood and into their early adulthood, squiring and practicing these arts on a daily basis. I'm fond of an analogy, I use the analogy of if you imagine a child who shows a talent for football at the age of 5 or 6 years old, joins a junior football team, by the age of 9 or 10 years old if they are very, very good they may have made it to a higher league side or even a schools county team, by the age of 11 or 12 they may have been talent spotted by the ages or 15 or 16 you may be about to become a premier league player, by 17 or 18 you could actually be playing for England, you could be playing for the National team and that perfectly fits the medieval mantra. You look at Harry Hotspur leading armies into battle at the age of 22 years old and so these people are essentially we're talking about the military classes who have to practice not just the full panoply of armour on horseback, but we know this from the manuscripts we studied that there is a regimen of they

must learn to wrestle, use the rondel dagger, sword in one hand, sword in two hands, the poleaxe, the spear, in armour out of armour, on horseback, so that effectively they can fight under any circumstances, these were the elite warriors of this period and again this is one of the reasons, harking back to the methodology of the bronze age is that if you have professional warriors within society they require training and so when we look at the professional warriors of any period of antiquity there must be a training regime otherwise it doesn't differentiate them from everybody else. There is even a human pragmatism that nobody in their right mind would voluntarily enter a battlefield without any training, especially if you are looking to seek personal glory and survival.

So you see a similar thing with the longswords. They get longer and longer until eventually you end up with the great swords of the 16th century. You end up with these *zweihander* or the *bidenhander* and then they stop, they are gone. It's the same with the pike, it renders the two-handed sword pretty much useless.

2. Liegnitzer Sword and Buckler

a. Why was this manuscript chosen?

The Liegnitzer is a 15th century manuscript. The key reason is that it is short but it is comprehensive. The second is that it is within the Lichtenauer tradition where we have comparables, obviously we have comparable data from other sources, we know this isn't an isolated case, an isolated manuscript which somehow has massive variances with what else is out there. It is important because you are able to interpret it correctly. The third reason is because as opposed to for example 133, it is very unique, there is very little out there that actually can be compared in any depth with ms 133, it stands alone whereas with Liegnitzer you see the same plays appearing multiple times in different manuscripts. The principles importantly in Liegnitzer are recorded in other manuscripts. The other interesting point with Liegnitzer is it's not the only weapon Liegnitzer writes about, he writes about the longsword and he also writes about wrestling so we can see that as a source of date Liegnitzer is knowledgeable about fighting. We know he is knowledgeable as he is recorded in the role of masters, he is one of Lichtenauer's students so we know this. So that's why Liegnitzer's method of sword and buckler is part of a tradition and that suggests lineage. [IS THERE A DIRECT CORRELATION BETWEEN *MESSER* AND EWART PARK SWORDS?] The reason Liegnitzer stands out is, in terms of the use of the Bronze Age buckler and the Ewart Park type sword, is that the Liegnitzer plays are played at a very close measure. There are no funny strikes. And so, if we imagine a typical image of sword fighting where they're standing at a comfortable distance from each other, and they're simply using the weapon to strike and

ward off blows with the shield. Lignitzer doesn't have this, and neither does any of the supporting evidence of the sword and buckler tradition that Lignitzer is part of, that this is the measure with which the fight was conducted. Because of the length of the bronze sword, we have to get close. So Lignitzer brings us to the measure that really we want to be fighting at. Even though the Ewart Park sword is considerably shorter than a *messer*, we know that even with a weapon this short it is within the correct measure to be effective. That's why Lignitzer worked well. One of the reasons why for example MS1.33 would be difficult to work with is because the measure is further apart. You have to get so much closer. Lignitzer brings you within that very close measure, while there are things in 1.33 that simply wouldn't work with a bronze sword. [NB negative evidence would be that standing at a distance and repeatedly hitting the shield would damage the bronze swords and it would show up on the marks!] The tradition Lignitzer belongs to uses the principle of *versetzen* (displacement). Not parries. So we know from the manuscripts the types of actions that are being performed with the blade. So Lignitzer uses the idea of displacement. The displacement does not unduly stress the material. It's making the most efficient use of the strong and weak points of the swords. In terms of a martial context, *versetzen* makes excellent sense. It not only displaces the incoming attack, it also primes your blade in an offensive position so that you can follow with a thrust or a slice of your own. So attack as defence and defence as attack, they actually become interchangeable. Ultimately any martial art seeks to do this. We can look at any martial art, at the highest level, attack and defence become simultaneous.

- b. How did the manuscript develop? Where does it stand within the history of combat manuscripts?

Lignitzer was a student of Lichtenauer and was instructed with a traditional Lichtenauer lineage. How far back the lineage stretches we don't know. The manuscripts in terms of how to use them we don't see them before around 1300. [PREDECESSOR MANUSCRIPT?] The first Lichtenauer manuscript we know of is the MS3227a from Nuremberg, which is believed to date from 1389. This is the first manuscript in the Lichtenauer tradition. Before that, in Germany there is nothing. Between 3227A and MS.1.33 that we've found so far.

c. Why were only certain parts of the manuscript chosen for the experiment?

There are only six plays in the Lignitzer sword and buckler section. The one was a disarming technique that wouldn't have produced any data on the blade, and that's why we left that one out.

d. What are the similarities of BA and MA swords, and what are the differences?

In terms of the similarities, Lichtenauer tells us that there are three types of attacks that can be made with a blade. The strike, the slice and the thrust. The BA blade type is capable of all three. The key differences are obviously the length, the metallurgy, lack of a cross. However, that leads us to the similarity between the bronze sword and the use of the buckler. Sword and buckler in the mediaeval tradition tends to be the weapon for a lower class in society, who are not necessarily going to be wearing armour of the kind that we begin seeing in the period whether it's composite steel and leather or chain, or later plate armour and then the full harnesses, so the types of protection that the fencers are using would be similar to the types of protection available to a Bronze age person. This made it a good choice. Even though maybe the social context of who is using it changed, the fact that they would be fairly lightly armoured by MA standard is good. The sword and buckler has very limited uses against a very heavily armoured person. The idea of covering the hand with the buckler is still heavily evident in the medieval period, and we think this is predominantly the need for the buckler. The weapon is so short you have to be close to the opponent to strike, which means that your buckler is going to be close as well. That brings us again to the connection between the MA and BA which is fairly evident from the measure of fighting, and that the buckler also has an offensive use. It's used not just to ward off blows but also to trap your opponent in a position that they can't fight from. The buckler plays an important part in protecting the hand and the forearm.

3. How did the BA swords perform?

They did far better than I thought. I thought they would pick up more damage than they did, but with the parameters we were using according to the method that Lignitzer reports certainly the displacements from the feel of the blade the displacements were very strong. Naturally the displacement is a very strong action when you are performing it with steel, when you change that to something that is malleable you really have to trust them and in fact the fear that it wouldn't hold up to the *versetzen* as well was gone after the first exchange. You could tell that the blade really had an innate quality along the lateral portion where with the oval centre you had almost the perfect surface for being able to push the opponents blade

off the line of attack. One thing that became apparent though is that the idea of entering with a blow with the bronze sword from a self-preservation point of view didn't seem to be a good idea because you had to get so close that if you messed it up just aiming a wild blow at the opponent and they managed to displace you quite simply at that point the fight is finished and so the blade leant itself perfectly to fighting at that measure because it's almost like a large knife. You are so close providing that you can control the opponents weapon or even their shield at that point there are certain automatic drilled responses, so the weapons handle beautifully within that particular method and so really they are just as good as the steel ones.

4. In your opinion, how were BA swords used?

I think that drawing on conclusions, one thing that you become aware of having spent the best part of 3 decades fighting with swords is that you become attuned to the feel of a sword, the way a sword wants to move and if you're moving that sword in a way that really doesn't match its personality, you know there are things that sword wants to do naturally and things that it can do counter intuitively. It's hard to quantify, even looking at the shape of a sword, taking into consideration its dimensions and the material its constructed from gives someone with experience a certain set of parameters of how that's going to be used. Like any tool you are going to know that a sledgehammer is not used for knocking nails in so the tool to an extent dictates its use but with knowledge there are some things that are counter intuitive that the weapon is perfectly capable of doing such as the *versetzen* which is a very unnatural movement, that is something that needs to be trained, that is given to you because it isn't something that immediately springs to mind. What I would call downright blows from outside the measure, a downright blow is when I swing the word and step in to strike that the Ewart Park doesn't want to do that for a couple of reasons – it's too short so if it goes wrong I haven't got the time to correct myself so, the sword didn't have the properties that I would associate with being designed for that purpose, where it was exemplary was in being able to position the point and I think thanks to the slightly anthropomorphic hilt shape, with the indentation in the wood, the U shape between the two arms of the wooden grip perfectly fit the thumb and something happened where I kept instinctively finding my thumb in that groove which allowed me to turn the blade very quickly and very neatly. Again I'm a believer that there are things designed for stylistic purposes but form fits function and so while it could be stylised it has a function and I think that when you are talking about arts that involve potentially your death nothing is extraneous, it's there for a reason and I think that this is the reason why we see these shapes, that this is designed especially with the form of the blade being broad towards the tip the thumb helps counterbalance the point of the blade otherwise

it's quite a point heavy weapon but when you sit with it comfortably in your hand in that position you grip it like that it becomes an extension of the arm. So, I find that with the thumb sitting in that notch the weapon begins to move in a far more natural fashion rather than being swung like an axe. The other thing I would say about the shape of the sword is that the shape of that sword in particular with its leaf shaped blade and point lends itself perfectly to slicing because the length of the weapon, while it's short the edges are longer than the length of the weapon so you have more edge contact so for slicing at an opponent who is lightly armoured, whose face or neck or forearms are unprotected its ideal. You can slice really comfortably with it and the point of the weapon is incredibly fine for a broad sword. Again, the fine point tells us that this sword is optimised for thrusting. One advantage of the leaf shaped blade and the edges being as sharp and pronounced as they are, and having an increased length over the actual length of the sword is that when you thrust with a blade like that the penetration is far more severe rather than if it was a needle shaped point although a needle shaped point thrust in the right place will burst an organ, but with a blade form like that and a thrust to the body with a blade of that width that's going to cause horrendous damage to the human body, you've actually got an increased chance of hitting something and so I think that the design of the blade lends itself to being stabbed into the human body and being drawn but blows from an open measure not to say that it can't be used to chop from a short measure however a chop is of limited use. Is it going to sever a limb, is it going to sever fingers, is it going to disrupt the face? We see a lot of maxillofacial blows from the archaeological records is that necessarily going to deter or stop an opponent? The mass of the weapon might not dictate that it will however slices and thrusts at that kind of measure are far more dangerous and so to me it's more knifelike than sword like.

5. Retrospectively, was this the right manuscript? What would you have done differently?

We've known of Ligtizer now for nearly 20 years nothing has come out of the woodwork even in recent years, even in the last 6 months that I would say replaces Ligtizer as an option for studying BA swords, for the reasons I mentioned before. Ligtizer really ticks so many of the boxes that really we can extrapolate the best results from, it's got the potential to give the most data.

6. What other manuscripts could be used in future experiments?

Depending if we were looking at incorporating Buckler, potentially looking at some of, there isn't a lot of variation within the mediaeval period for the Sword and Buckler work other than

133, so perhaps looking at 133 and some of the plays that happen where the shields are literally in contact with each other, but again we would be limited as we are only taking really part of the system there.

I think if we were looking at broader studies for example in the different BA weapons, there is certainly work that could be done with BA halberds and I also think that with the types of hewing spears that we see like the Yetholm spear, there are spear manuscripts from Italy and Germany where we are looking at really the same dimensions. The Yetholm spear is an interesting one because it is of similar dimensions to a weapon we find in Italy in the 14th and 15th century called the *chiavarina* which is specifically a spear designed for fighting horsemen, but also certain types of hewing spears, spears with a cutting edge that we see in both Italian and German manuscripts.

7. What other experiments should be carried out?

I think other experiments I'd certainly like would be big carcass experiments using a recognised cutting mechanic that we have evidence for example from Lichtenauer's manuscript where he tells us how to move and how we perform that. I think we can certainly show that thrusts and slices at close measure could cause devastating injury.

Appendix C

Codex 44.A.8: Commentary by Andre Lignitzer on Sword and Buckler (Farrell 2012)

Original German Transcription: Dierk Hagedorn

English Translation: Keith Farrell

Transcription of original text

Hie heben sich an die stuck mit dem pucklär Die maister Andre lignitzer gesetzt hat her nach geschriben

Das erst stuck mit dem pucklär aus dem oberhaw Merck wenn dw den oberhaw treibst zw dem mann So setz mit dem knopf dein swert Inwendig auf deinen pucklär zw deinem daumen vnd stich Im von vnden auf zu^o einem gesicht vnd wind gegen seinem swert und la vber schnappen ~

Das annder stuck

Item aus dem vnderhaw wenn er dir oben zw^ohaut So wind gegen ym auf dein lincke seitten gegen deinem schilt So stestu yn zwaien schilten So wind denn auf dein rechte seitt plos vnd greif ym nach dem maul Wert er dir das vnd hebt den schilt auff So nm das linck pain das get zw^o paiden seitten ~

Das dritt stuck

Item aus dem pucklär aus dem wechelhaw streich von der lincken seitten aus dein pucklär vast vbersich in sein swert vnd haw Im den von der lincken seitt zu^o dem haupt vnd wind plos vnd stos ym nach dem maul Hebt er mit schilt vnd mit swert vnd wert das So haw mit der langen schneid Im nach dem rechten pain das get auch zw paiden seitten ~

Das vierd stuck

Item aus dem mittelhaw mach die twer zw paiden seitten vnd den schaitlär mit der langen schneid vnd stich ym vnden zw seinem gemächt

Das fünft stuck

Item aus dem sturzhaw tu^oe sam dw Im zu^o der lincken seitten vber sein schilt wilt stechen vnd var mit dein ort vnden durch vnd stich ym Inwendig seines schildes vnd wind Inndes auf dein lincke seitten wert er dir das So nym sein rechtes pain mit der langen schneid ~

Das sechst stuck

Item nym dein kling zw dem pucklar in dein lincke hant vnd wind gegen ym als mit dem halben swert Haut er oder sticht er dir oben zw dem gesicht oder unden nach dem pain So la dein rechte hant var von dem pint vnd vorsetz ym das mit schilt vnd mit swert vnd greiff denn mit deiner rechten hant auf sein rechte seitten nach dem schilt wol vndersich vnd dr in auf dein rechte seitten So hastu ym den schilt genomen

English translation

Here start the plays with the buckler as written by the master Andre Lignitzer.

The first play with the buckler from the Oberhaw (over strike / strike from above). Mark when you drive the Oberhaw to the man: with the pommel go inwards, your sword close to the buckler and your thumb, and thrust in from beneath to his face. Wind against his sword and then go with a snap over and around.

The second play.

From the Underhaw (under strike / strike from below), when he strikes from above. Wind against him to your left side, [with his sword] against your shield. Thus you stand in two shields. So wind to the right side opening and strike in at the mouth. See if he deals with this by raising his shield, and if so then take the left leg. This works on both sides.

The third play.

From the buckler, from the Wechselhaw (changing strike), sweep from the left side. From your buckler sweep clearly above with your sword then cut into his head from the left side; wind [to the] opening and thrust into his mouth. If he lifts with the shield and with the sword and defends against this then cut with the long edge in at his right leg. This works on both sides.

The fourth play.

From the Mittelhaw (middle strike) make the Twer (cross strike) to both sides and the Schaitlär (skull strike) with the long edge, then make a thrust in underneath.

The fifth play.

From the Sturzthaw (plunging strike) make as if to go to [his] left side over his shield with a thrust then with the point change under and thrust swiftly inside his shield. Wind immediately to your left side and if he defends against this then take his right leg with your long edge.

The sixth play.

Take the blade and the buckler in your left hand and wind against him in the half sword. If he strikes or thrusts at you from above to the face or from beneath to the legs, then set him aside with the shield and with the sword, and go with your right hand from the grip of your sword. Shoot with your right hand towards his right side, grasp his shield from underneath and twist to your own right side. So you will take the shield from him.